

Territory, power, and Scotland:
a review of UK statecraft towards
Scotland's secessionist impulse

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Abstract

Statecraft theory can be found within a narrow body of literature and one of a type that also pays scant regards to Scotland or its secessionist impulse. This thesis helps addresses that gap in the literature. The United Kingdom, by design, is built on a space that has as an inherent feature, competing ideas on sovereignty, national identity, governance, and statehood. These features acquire political potency when a secessionist impulse emerges and starts to dominate the socio-political discourse. Specifically looking at Scotland, its post-1707 history tells of a country often restless at its political settlement, a position that has again taken precedence over recent decades. In the 1960s the country started to record incremental increases in support for independence. This secessionist impulse was sustained sufficiently for Scotland to reach the precipitancy in 2014. Recent decades also indicate a trend for secessionist impulses to be tested by referendums. However, as electoral vehicles referendums and their administration are vulnerable to politically expedient change. There have been three referendums in Scotland, each testing its political relationship with the UK, two focusing on devolution (1979; 1997), and the most recent being the 2014 independence referendum. This thesis reviews how statecraft was employed and engaged with at these points.

This thesis investigates how Scottish secessionism has been influenced by internal and external statecraft and for their analysis a combination of process tracing and grid analysis is used. In line with the realist foundation, this thesis posits that the closer a secessionist impulse progresses towards the precipitancy stage, the more likely the state will respond with hard line realist tactics. By definition, the same should apply to the Scotland impulse. TO the end, Scotland's secessionist impulse is viewed in line with Wood's (1981) comparative framework of secession and focus on three parliamentary debates that took place in 1978, 1997, and, 2013. In each case, the referendum franchise was targeted in one way or other, out of political expediency. Added, to gain a wider context, newspaper reportage of each of the debates were also interrogated and similarly reviewed via a statecraft lens.

This thesis contributes to ongoing debates in five ways. **Firstly**, this thesis offers evidence that in its preparation for the 2014 independence referendum, the Scottish government backed an electoral strategy that served only to undermine its chances of victory. **Secondly**, this research found very limited evidence of newspapers being in favour of any change to the status quo - either through Scottish devolution or independence. Instead, this thesis provides further evidence to support arguments that through Whiggism, the state and newspapers are ideologically aligned. **Thirdly**, an effect of devolution is the emergence of 'opposition craft' where statecraft is practiced contrary to the national interest. The overall effect is that Bulpitt's (1983) idea on the dual polity may no longer be relevant as an explainer for UK territorial politics and instead, it may be more appropriate to talk of a multi-polity. **Fourthly**, the Bulpittian perspective is Westminster-centric and does little to explain Scottish politics or politics in Scotland. As such, this thesis also identifies a need for a specifically Scottish perspective on statecraft. **Fifth and finally**, this thesis used criminalistics to create a model for interrogating multi-person transcripts.

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Abbreviations

ASA	Advertising Standards Authority
BBC	British Broadcasting Corporation
CA1	Cunningham Amendment
CA2	Cash Amendment
CAP	Committee of Advertising Practice
CBI	Confederation of British Industry
CGS	Chief of General Staff
DSMA	Defence and Security Media Advisory Committee
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
EEC	European Economic Community
ERO/s	Electoral Registration Officers
EU	European Union
EVEL	English votes for English Laws
FT	Financial Times
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HPE	Hewlett Packard Enterprise
ICJ	International Courts of Justice
IMF	International Monetary Fund
IPSO	Independent Press Standards Organisation
MP/s	Member of Parliament
MRC	Media Reform Coalition
MSP/s	Member of the Scottish Parliament
PCC	Press Complaints Commission
PIRA	Provisional Irish Republican Army
rUK	Remainder UK
RIC	Radical Independence Campaign
RBS	Royal Bank of Scotland
SAP	Scottish Analysis Papers
SIRFA	Scottish Independence Referendum (Franchise) Act (2013)
SLP	Scottish Labour Party ¹
SNP	Scottish National Party
SCVO	Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations
TAA	Target Audience Analysis
UDI	Unilateral declaration of independence
UK	United Kingdom
UKIP	United Kingdom Independence Party
UN	United Nations
UNSC	United Nations Security Council
USA	United States of America
USSR	Soviet Union
WoS	Wings over Scotland
WW1	World War One
WW2	World War Two

¹ The SLP was a short-lived venture that formed out of a split in the Labour Party when three of its Scottish MPs became dissatisfied with the lack of progress towards Scottish devolution (Sillars, 2021).

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Introduction

There is a tradition in the UK to put blue plaques on buildings. Their purpose is to highlight the significance of a building or other location and their association to an important person or event from history (English Heritage, 2023; Historical Environment Scotland, 2023). Determining whether a plaque should be awarded or not is a regulated process and it features some notable omissions. One historically important place that does not boast a blue plaque is in Edinburgh, specifically the building on the corner of North Bridge and the Royal Mile. For it is there where, on the 16th of January 1707, that Scotland's Act of Union was signed (Smith, 2007). Given that a number of political petitions had been presented to the parliament and not one had been in favour of Union (Grant, 1882; Devine, 2012), it is fair to say that Union with England had not been popular. The Kirk campaigned against Union and its opposition culminated with church bells chiming out sombre tunes on the day that Scotland ceased to be an independent country (Grant, 1882). Riots had already taken place in towns across Scotland, including in Edinburgh where martial law had been declared and troops had been ordered to open fire. Professor Richard Finlay says that on January 16, 1707, the politicians went on a procession to the old Parliament House to ratify the 1706 Treaty of Union with England (Smith, 2007). But the ongoing riots forced the elites to take shelter in the building on the corner of North Bridge and the Royal Mile. They hid in the basement and duly signed off on the Act of Union (Smith, 2007). As was said, this building still exists but there is no blue plaque to help commemorate the historic event that took place there or encourage the circumstance to become folklore. Instead, the events in 1707 have been quietly forgotten, almost as though there are some aspects of history best left in the past. It is also fair to say that the likelihood of the building acquiring a blue plaque any time in the future is low because although the basement in question also still exists, it has since been converted into a toilet (Smith, 2007).

That there is a strict selection process for granting a blue plaque implies an in-play set of value-laden criteria, including politics, and are intended to frame a particular view of the past. Miller argues that communities exist because of "mutual recognition" (1995: 22). This recognition is created for us and forms part of a politically constructed sense of belonging between peoples who are bound by a common identity (Anderson, 1983; Miller, 1995). History forms a part of that social construction, and the blue plaques offer meaning to and a relationship with, an inherited past, and one that has been shaped for us (Zinn, 2012).

However, maintaining a manufactured sense of belonging becomes more difficult in the presence of competing ideas of mutual recognition or communal belonging. Ultimately, suppressing those ideas become part of a political agenda (Zinn, 2012) and indeed, this perspective may offer relevance given the lack of a blue plaque on the corner of North Bridge and the Royal Mile.

Research context

The United Kingdom, by design, is built on a space that has as an inherent feature, competing ideas on sovereignty, national identity, governance, and statehood. These features acquire political potency when a secessionist impulse emerges and starts to dominate the socio-political discourse. Specifically looking at Scotland, the status quo has been challenged on and off and in numerous ways over the lifetime of the Union (Devine, 2012). More recently in the 1960s, Scotland started to record incremental increases in support for independence. For Nairn, the catalyst was a set of small but significant Westminster victories for the independence-supporting Scottish National Party (SNP). This sentiment, he says, was so strong that within a decade it had replaced class struggle as “the principal factor” for altering the political status quo and social contract (Nairn, 1977: 79). Two devolution referendums were held, one in 1979 and under controversial circumstances, and the other in 1997. In 2014 a referendum was held on Scottish independence and recorded a ten percent margin in favour of the status quo. This result was recorded against a backdrop of claims that the media were inherently biased against Scottish independence (Robertson, 2014; Blain, Hutchison, and Hassan, 2016). However, the impulse has not subsided and today opinion pollsters continue to report high levels of support for independence and majorities in favour are not uncommon (Institute for Government, 2021). This thesis seeks to explain this secessionist impulse offering insights on how UK statecraft played out across the impulse and the approach includes assessing the, who, where, how, and the rationale for doing so, and in terms of wider world context.

Research drivers

This thesis has as a foundation, Wood’s (1981) comparative framework of secession. There, a secessionist impulse is deemed to typically go through several evolutionary stages including the preconditions; rise of the secessionist movement; and, the precipitancy. His framework was applied to the Scottish case and at three specific points in the impulse; (1) the devolution referendums held in 1979 (preconditions) and 1997 (rise/movement), and the 2014

independence referendum (precipitancy). Wood's framework also offers insight on how government was expected to respond to the impulse and it is via there where statecraft theory gains relevance to both concept and case. It is also noted that the trend in recent decades has been for secessionist impulses to be tested by referendums (Sorens, 2012; Griffiths, 2016 (b)). Statecraft theory in that electoral and referendum administration is vulnerable to politically expedient change (Qvortrup, 2000; James. 2014; 2016). To this end, this thesis identified three parliamentary debates, one in each of 1978; 1997; and, 2013 which, as preparation for the then upcoming referendums, sought to alter the franchise for political expedient purposes. The debate transcripts were interrogated via process traced hoop tests, with the results informing on how statecraft played out at the culmination of each of the three stages of the impulse, in line with the conceptual framework. Newspaper reportage of each of the debates were also interrogated and reviewed via grid analysis. This approach provided for an assessment in regards of what was debated versus what was reported, and through a statecraft lens.

Gaps in the literature

Statecraft is the collective term for the machineries of state that are used for combating challenges to the governing party, the state and/or the status quo (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a). The problem is however, it is a narrow body of literature that pays scant regards to Scotland or its impulse. Statecraft theory is also parochial and focuses mostly on the domestic scene, more so given the recent focus of statecraft theorists on media and public image as a facet of statecraft. By consequence this internal form of statecraft largely ignores the external variant practiced in international relations and the effect it has on the potential for achieving statecraft either at home or abroad. As for secession, the literatures there are more likely to be found in international relations theory. As an approach, it creates the conditions for an internal v. external statecraft scenario, the effect of which is that whilst there is a wealth of literature on Scottish independence, it is a rare event when the impulse is viewed through a secessionist lens. Similarly, whilst the media is increasingly important to statecraft theorists, reportage is yet to be reviewed through a statecraft lens.

Fundamentally, the difference between statecraft and secession is that the former is geared to preserve the status quo whilst the latter seeks to destroy it. Yet, there is nothing in either the literatures on statecraft or secession that can explain how this interaction has played out.

What that does mean is that in respect of Scottish secessionism, our understanding in terms of statecraft is skewed.

Research question

How has Scotland's secessionist impulse been influenced by internal and external statecraft?

Hypothesis

The contemporary literature on statecraft is heavily influenced by a set of codes for government that were devised in the late eighteenth century by Lord Salisbury (Marsh, 1978; Bulpitt, 1983). Those codes were sought to create a strategy for perpetuating the status quo both at home and abroad and are inherently realist. Schmitt says that the state governs through "compulsion" (1996: 36). It is a point that became apparent in 2017 when the Catalan unilateral declaration of independence (UDI) resulted in violence. The UK is not immune to such practices, particularly given the British Army's deployment in Northern Ireland in the late twentieth century. Indeed, when this type of activity does occur, be it malign or benign, they are referred to as 'acting in the national interest'. Such practices are defined in law as being in the interests of the government of the day (Ponting, 1987). They have also been incorporated into statecraft theory, and benefit from the much gentler sounding 'bending the rules' (James, 2016; 2018). The point being, that the UK already possesses the supporting infrastructure to take a hard-line realist posture when the need arises. To this end, this thesis posits that the closer a secessionist event progresses towards the precipitancy, the more likely the state will respond with hard line realist tactics, with the expectation that a similar eventuality could be found in the Scottish impulse.

Contributions to current debates

I: this thesis sought to help address evident limitations in the literatures on statecraft; secession; referendums; process tracing; and on Scotland's recent political past. Focusing on the legislative preparations for the referendums held in 1979, 1997, and 2014, this thesis offers a range of insights that help explain how UK statecraft has influenced Scottish secessionism over the length of the impulse. A most evident example lies with this thesis' finding that the Scottish government, as preparation for the 2014 independence referendum, backed an electoral strategy that served only to undermine its chances of victory.

2: this thesis reports newspapers being consistent in their opposition to any change to the status quo, either via Scottish devolution or independence. Indeed, it was a rarity for newspapers to offer something favourable in respect of either Scottish devolution or independence. The outcomes also add further evidence to support claims that newspapers are aligned to the state via Whiggism.

3: this thesis identifies an emergent opposition craft. Premised on its being an act of statecraft that is contrary to the national interest, opposition craft has traditionally been practiced in the House of Commons via rebellions, cabals, and the ilk. However, and consequent to the numerous devolution settlements currently in situ across the UK space, this thesis offers evidence of the same practice playing out across the UK space, The overall effect is that Bulpitt's (1983) ideas on the dual polity may no longer be relevant as an explainer for UK territorial politics and instead, we may be better served talking about a multi-polity.

4: the Bulpittian perspective is Westminster-centric and focuses in the main on the party in government, though there are some notable exceptions. As such, it does not easily translate to the Scottish parliament, given its being a parliament in the round and based on the participatory model. As such, thesis identifies a need for a Scottish perspective on statecraft.

5: this thesis used criminalistics to investigate how statecraft strategies were deployed during the legislative preparations for the referendums held in 1979, 1997, and 2014. In doing so, it create a model for interrogating multi-person transcripts.

Chapter one: secession

A secessionist event occurs when a part of an existing territory breaks away and forms its own state, or joins with another already existing state (known as irredentism) (Pavkovic and Radan, 2011: 2). It is a political event that has shaped political communities and relations between them for over four thousand years, dating back to Akkad (Foster, 2015; Chase-Dunn and Lerro, 2016; Coggins, 2016). Akkad was the first Empire, a form of governance that persisted from two thousand BC up until its dismantling in the years following World War Two (WW2) (Baylis and Smith, 2001; van de Mierop, 2016). The overall effect is that consequent to this chapter's observations on the post-1945 world, secession has played a major role in shaping today's geopolitical geography. The effect is that this first chapter notes that it is only in the past forty years or so that secession has developed as a formal concept with a developed line of academic enquiry. It notes a number of causes and influences of a secessionist event - UDI, or an agreed settlement (commonly via an electoral event - usually referendums) (Buchheit, 1978; Wood, 1981; Buchanan, 1997; Crawford, 2006; Sorens, 2012; Qvortrup, 2000). Each of these causes can be further catalysed through war, state collapse, and further still by a rebalance of the global system (Hechter, 1992; Buchanan, 1997; Buzan and Waever, 2003; Brooke, Strauss, and Anderson, 2018; Heraclides, 2002; Crawford, 2006; Ker-Lindsay, 2012; Kohen, 2012; Coggins, 2016). To this end, this chapter intends identifying, outlining, and defining those fundamentals or dynamics that underpin a secessionist impulse and event and it begins with an outline of how secession has helped shape the world since 1945.

Secession post-1945

This section looks at the trends in secession since 1945 up to the present day. The dismantling of Empire led to an almost fourfold increase in the number of states. The effect is that the majority of states in existence today are under the age of seventy years old, with secession being a major causation.

The global rebalance that occurred post-1945 resulted in power being drawn away from Europe to the benefit of Washington and Moscow. This meant that for the first time since the industrial revolution, Western European powers were not in control of the international arena (Leffler and Arne, 2010). This global rebalancing also impacted the political geography of the global south - of Asia, Africa, and the Middle East. An integral part of that evolution was

the sweeping away of those structures of the past, as well as the reformation and rethinking of a number of established ideas, including the potential of democratic governance acting as a fundament of state legitimacy as part of a truly global international system (Baylis and Smith, 2001). Kissinger (2014) added that this new international system was purposeful insofar that it offered a stability that had been missing in previous eras. It is through these new structures Kissinger (2014) claimed, states would experience peaceful co-existence. Kissinger’s (2014) claim premises on the idea that revolution in the international system was necessary. WW2, he argued, had exposed a structural weakness at the heart of the international system (2014: 6). The major European industrial powers had become exhausted by war and it is the fallout of this situation that the emerging powers of the United States of America (USA) and the Soviet Union (USSR) had inherited as they took up primary positions on the international stage. Indeed, Kennedy (1987) also assessed that post-1945 neither the United Kingdom (UK) nor France could afford to maintain their Imperial endeavours. Similarly, they also experienced armed insurgencies in parts of their Empires (Rapoport, 2004). These outcomes, when considered in conjunction with the creation of a single, inclusive, law-based international system from the creation of the United Nations (UN), led to the inevitable diminution of Empire (Kennedy, 1987). Of those new states that have emerged in the years since 1945, the UN became the centre of gravity for international diplomacy; and it provided much of the normative architecture of the new international system. Indeed, as Figure 1 outlines, UN membership has increased exponentially, resulting in nearly a fourfold increase in membership since inception to 2020.

Figure 1: UN membership: 1945-2020

Wood (1981) had argued that secession can be characterised as an internal or domestic issue which only concerns the international community towards the point of the end game. But secession clearly has attributes of an international hue and to ignore external factors in this way is to discount the routes available to secessionists as they strategize their political action.

Here, it is noted that secessionist impulses that push for independence through war or violent conflict are likely to draw in third-parties and other forms of direct intervention (Baylis and Smith, 2001). In such cases, a potential solution has been to partition the affected space and create new states (Baylis and Smith, 2001). As a process, partition led to more powerful states interfering in the administration of sovereign territories, including India, Korea, Vietnam, Pakistan, and Cyprus, albeit with limited success. Post 1990s interventions, however, have pursued other approaches have premised on realising conflict resolution and as with partition, the level of success has not been high. It also hasn't helped that states use any first-amongst-equal positions in international relations to maximise their foreign policies. For example, Kosovo, which unilaterally declared its independence from Yugoslavia in 1991, is still to be accepted into the UN and is still classed in terms of its de facto status (HM Government, 2009). The causation was Russia which used its veto at the UN Security Council (UNSC) to deny UN membership to the Kosovans. Similar stories can also be told regarding Taiwan and China (UN, 2007; HM Government, 2009). Nonetheless, the dissolution of Yugoslavia also lends credence to Wood's (1981) observation that international actors are likely to become involved in violent secessionist cases.

Figure 2 (overleaf) shows us that the world has experienced two distinct secessionist waves. The first was caused by the dismantling of Empire and discrediting of colonialism. The process ostensibly, was instigated in 1945 and by the 1980s, had run its course with the effect being the emergence of over eighty new independent states. The USSR's collapse in 1990 resulted in a second wave. The effect of which led to the creation of roughly thirty new states. Included in the second wave is the decision by Czech politicians to begin the peaceful dismantling of the Czechoslovakian state. The result was the creation of two new states, the Czech Republic and Slovakia (Sorens, 2012). The Czech case is indicative of the reality that not all secessionist cases use violence to further their cause. Overall, the effect is that secession having been a shaper of geopolitics can now be considered to be a political outlier. Figure 2 indicates that trends in the post-Cold War era indicate that the numbers of successful secessionist acts have tailed away to become a mere fraction of that experienced between the 1950s and 1990s.

Figure 2: Secessionist events: 1950-2020

(Fabry, 2010: chapters 5 and 6)

At the time of writing, the geopolitical geography has been at its most stable for decades (Fabry, 2010). Whilst this trend is viewed from a systemic perspective, if we drill down to the domestic and sub-state arenas, it can be seen that numerous states continue to experience secessionist impulses (Griffiths (a), 2016). Included in their number is Scotland which in 2014 turned down the opportunity of independent statehood. Additionally, there is both Catalonia and Kurdistan which both failed to build on their 2017 UDI and create viable states. The most recent example can be found in Papua New Guinea where, in 2019, the territory of Bougainville voted overwhelmingly in favour of independence (Regan, 2019). The referendum there was a culmination of a textbook third-party intervention that sought a peaceful settlement to a decade long civil war between the Papua new Guinean state and Bougainville Revolutionary Army (Regan, 2019). Yet at the time of writing Bougainville is yet to realise its independence and may also be the only case of a territory that current resides within the secessionist precipitancy. And depending on when, and if, a settlement is reached, Bougainville may well have bucked the downward trend in secessionist activity experienced in recent decades. However, whilst there are countless active secessionist movements to be found across the globe (Sorens, 2012; Griffiths (a), 2016), thus far, none have realised their political ambitions.

This section has outlined a number of causal factors in relation to secessionist events. As was the case with the historical cases outlined earlier in this chapter, war, conflict, and third-party interests continued to be factors in secessionist cases, post-1945. The recognition that state collapse also catalyses secessionist events has also not gone unnoticed. What is new is the potential for states to administratively agree to or accept the diminution of their territories via a secessionist event within its governed space, any potential unwillingness to do so being a pre-requisite. That this phenomenon occurred in the first place may in itself, be symptomatic

of the global rebalancing that took place in the aftermath of WW2. The potential for a change in the international balance of power being a catalyst for secessionist waves as per Buchanan (1997) has been reinforced by the ongoing effects following the end of the Cold War. As such, whilst secession has since drifted from being a mainstay of the international system to a political outlier, its potency as a shaper in a new global future should not be forgotten. This may be less likely the case within academic where it has only really been in the past thirty years or so that secession has benefitted from a developed line of academic enquiry. The irony there being that whilst secession is clearly not a new political phenomenon at least in terms of its fundamental principles for action (Coggins, 2016; Brooke et al, 2018), academics have only really paid attention to secession in a time of relative geopolitical stability. To this end the next section reviews the literature on secession.

The literatures on secession

Academic interest in secession evolved out of the post-WW2 discussions on self-determination and decolonisation. The traces of what is now a separate and distinct strain of academic practice only really began to take shape from the mid-1970s, with early scholars being Buchheit (1978) and Wood (1981). Today, this area of research has expanded somewhat and now boasts the likes of Sustein (1991), Hechter (1992), Buchanan (1997), Haverland (2000), Altman and Wellman (2009), and Pavkovic and Radan (2011). Additionally, the area also boasts a wealth of talent that specialises in increasing our understanding of specific secessionist cases. That said, it is noted that recent years have seen a shift away from a research approach that premised on historical institutionalism as a philosophical foundation. Instead, the recent popularity of meso-led research feeds into what is now “a growing number of positions on the justification for and scope of, the right to secede” (Buchanan, 1997: 31).

In his (1978) work, Buchheit asserts the idea that secession should be considered as an act of revolution by a people against the state. This perspective is particularly relevant where state policies are exclusionary and cause tyranny, injustice, and discrimination against a people that boast a communal identity distinct from the one advocated by the state. In such cases, secession has “moral appeal” and can be regarded as a case of self-determination (Buchheit, 1978: 2). Buchheit’s work is typical of research into secession found during the late 1970s in that his focus was less about secession *per se* and more concerned with the processes of self-determination which generally preceded it. Brilmayer’s (1991) work follows a similar theme

to Buchheit's, albeit from an ethno-nationalist perspective. However, interest in this emerging field of study was sufficiently slow that Buchanan (1997) had to rely on literature from outside of core secessionism studies to advance his theories of primary and remedial rights⁹. The result was a developing philosophy on rights-based secession that helped inform our understanding of the dynamics of a secessionist impulse in overlapping areas such as nationalism, ethnicity, law, and a host of other areas, as energies for both fundamentalist and gradualist secessionist politics.

Buchanan (1997) also argued that academics and scholars had missed several opportunities to develop their knowledge of secession. One of the results is a complete failure of the academic community to agree upon the meaning of even the most basic of terms. There is an obvious lack of consistency across the literature (Cohen, 1961; Buchanan, 1997). For example, Crawford asserts that "the use or threat of force without the consent of the former sovereign" is the most central aspect of a secessionist event (2006: 375). The meaning here is that violence is an essential ingredient for any secessionist endeavour. When applied to the real world this means that even though the world have experienced over a hundred secessionist events since 1945, Crawford (2006) would argue that only one - the 1971 secession of East Pakistan - counts as secessionist. Crawford's beliefs are obviously shaped by a very narrow interpretation of what secession is and how it is practiced but he is not alone in holding narrow postures. Sustain (1991), for example, believes that secessionist events need to be legal, and by this, he means having the full agreement of the former parent state - thereby undermining a UDI¹⁰ as a route to independence. By definition, Sustain would have difficulty agreeing that the Catalan event of 2017 but would agree Croatian independence from Yugoslavia and the disintegration of Czechoslovakia as acts of secession, but not East Pakistan. Another option, offered by Hechter (1992), would preclude the demise of Czechoslovakia because in that case, the masses were not given a choice in the matter. The moral here is that strict definitions offer limited applicability. They teach us that it is difficult to employ them in a way that offers an accommodation of varied contemporary examples. This leads to a theoretical impasse and a weakness sufficient that for Buchanan (1997) the literature on secession will find difficulty evolving into a more coherent body of work.

⁹ For example, he used Margalit and Raz' (1990) paper on self-determination and Beran's (1987) ideas on political obligation to advance his work.

¹⁰ Muro defines a unilateral declaration of independence to be an alternative to a negotiated secession and has been associated with remedial right theories which invoke the rights of nations for unilateral secession in cases of serious violations of human rights, unjust annexation of territories, and systematic violations of agreements on self-government (2018: 22).

Indeed, the terminological development on secession has also seen conflation of secessionism with separatism, itself a wholly different outcome.

Separatism is not secession and as a process it is geared less towards full independence and instead seeks some form of territorial autonomy as equilibrium (i.e., devolution and federalism) within the existing state structure for its aims to be achieved (Wood, 1981; Baylis and Smith, 2001). To this end, separatism can be regarded as a third way, one that helps de-pressurise secessionist impulses whilst at the same time recognising historical differences within the governed population, all the while ensuring the integrity of the state (Wood, 1981). Indeed, this same settlement prevails in Denmark where both the Faroe Islands and Greenland benefit from considerable autonomy (Jensen, 2003). An outcome of this nature is distinct from secession given the latter's explicit goal of creating a new and independent state. As a scenario, however, it can be further complicated by the reality that not all secessionists work toward the swift and complete fulfilment of their aims. A secessionist movement that is led by gradualists will behave not dissimilar to those promoting separatism, but only insofar that the action is a steppingstone to independence. By contrast, a fundamentalist approach furthers UDI as an acceptable end-game, as per Catalonia in 2017. Sorens (2012) also suggests that it is common for secessionist movements to flit between these two positions. In Wales, for example, Plaid Cymru has only recently abandoned its separatist platform in favour of a secessionist one (Elias, 2009). Given these dynamics it is perhaps, understandable that academics might conflate the two concepts the development of which has also involved using the terms in conflicting ways. For example, Haverland argues that secession is the "separation of part of the territory of a state carried out by the resident population with the aim of creating a new independent state or ceding to another existing state" (2000: 254). As for Sorens, his ideas on secession premise more on increased autonomy than on outright independence (2012: 6). Still, these works are an improvement on Alesina and Spolaore (1997) where terminological conflation between secession and separatism is routine. Wood, however, has an advantage over his peers. He offers a distinct definition: for him, separatism is a process that leads to "the reduction of control by a central authority in a specific area" (1981: 110). For clarity, 'area' here means territory.

There is one last point to note. With its purpose of taking the state head-on in pursuit of a change in the political status quo, secession may sound like a form of revolution, but it is not (Buchheit, 1978). Table 1 indicates that the purpose of revolution is the complete overthrow

of the political status quo and the installation of a new leadership with new ideas for how to advance government and society (Tilly, 1995). On the contrary, there is nothing of significance in the literature on secession to suggest the overall toppling of the state as a political end-game. Secession instead, is concerned merely with the departure from the status quo of a territory and its population intent on forming an independent state. In legal terms, sovereignty over the affected territory transfers from one political institution to another and the immediate geopolitical geography is redrawn to suit the new arrangement (Buchheit, 1978; Wood, 1981; Sustain, 1991; Pavkovic and Radan, 2011; Sorens, 2012). By consequence, secessionists are not anti-state they're just anti-status quo.

Table 1: key difference of concepts

	Separatism	Autonomy	Secession	Independence	Revolution
Local control	X (aim)	X (outcome)			
Sovereign control			X (aim)	X (outcome)	X (aim)
Overthrow					X (Outcome)

It is also important to note that secession is also a process and not just an event (Kohen, 2012: 14). For Novic and Urs (2016), secessionist impulses do not just simply happen. To progress to a secessionist event, sufficient political momentum is needed if a supportive movement is to catalyse an affected population, sufficient for them to believe in then strive towards creating their own independent state. Here, Wood (1981) and his comparative framework of secession allows us to more easily compartmentalise the dynamics and stages of a secessionist impulse. Through his comparative framework of secession, Wood (1981) created for the first time a cohesive theory that covers the various stages of secession. He views secession as a process of political disintegration which in turn results in the territorial dismemberment of the parent state. It is a model that helps political scientists bring some objectivity and consistency that can be brought to bear on the dynamics, energies, and processes of specific case studies.

Wood's (1981) comparative framework of secession

Wood (1981) was one of the first scholars to outline the multi-faceted and multi-layered nature of secession. His framework was intended to develop insights into the journey of secession, sufficient that academics could employ it to assess individual case studies.

Pavkovic and Radan consider that Wood's centrepiece work to offer "*universal*" validity to any secessionist event, regardless of the "*size or ideological type*" of the concerned polity or territory (2011: 175). The result is a five-stage model that caters for the conditions and collective actions of secessionist impulses through to their conclusion - the preconditions of secession; the rise of secessionist movements; the response of central government; the direct precipitants of secession; and resolution of secessionist crises by armed conflict.

The preconditions of secession: Wood depicts the preconditions to be replete with competing and differing agendas and opinions and primarily of a type that is contrary to the status quo and in favour of territorial independence. The most fundamental pre-condition of secession is that any affected territory needs to be distinct and separable from the host state and boast cleavages such as a fixed border or other demarcation (Wood, 1981). These cleavages are likely to be found across a wealth of areas, including geography; social and psychological attitudes; and in the existence of alternative economic and political policy and practices. Economics is deemed to be an important aspect for fomenting social attitudes towards secession (Wood, 1981). Similarly, the affected population will claim to feel the brunt of economic inequality (Shanks, 1963; Hechter, 1972; Pinderhughes, 2011; Sorens, 2012; Twining, 1980; Wood, 1981). Where this is the case, the potential for different socio-political agendas and attitudes in the affected territory is reinforced^{11 12} (Wood, 1981; Sorens, 2012).

However, the secessionist movement is unlikely to possess insufficient political clout to force through change in order to balance out these inequalities. Even so, Wood adds that dynamics such as these can help catalyse a romanticised idea of an independent homeland. This same theme is furthered in later works by Heraclides (2002) and Pavkovic and Radan who also note the potential for envy and grievance acting as constituent elements of a prevailing romanticism (2013: 177). It is at this juncture that nationalism is likely to be used as an "aggregative device meaning all things to all alienated people" (Pavkovic and Radan, 2011: 123). This shift towards an independence-supporting ideology is deemed to underpin a subsequent groundswell of opinion, or impulse. It is this same approach that helps to

¹¹ What can result is an internal core and periphery, and a scenario that Hechter labelled as "internal colonialism", and an "unequal exchange between the territories of a given state that occurs either as a result of the free play of market forces, or of the economic distribution of the centre state that have intended or unintended consequences for regions" (1972: xiv).

¹² Wood also leaned on Gurr's (1970) perspective on relative deprivation.

reinforce and perpetuate not only difference but ultimately, helps erode the idea of an established political order and status quo (Pavkovic and Radan, 2011).

The rise of secessionist movements: Wood argues that a crossover occurs between disparate social and political campaigns once the idea of a separate homeland is concretised in the public consciousness¹³. This move helps provide the foundations for the establishment of a distinct political movement that is mandated to advance political action in support of a secessionist impulse (Buchheit, 1978; Wood, 1981; Sorens, 2012). Out of it comes an emergent leadership whose job is threefold: (1) present a public face to the movement (2) mobilise and convince the population that their futures are best served as an independent state (3) create further cleavages between the affected territory and the state (4) bring to life the socio-political aspirations that underpin the impulse (Wood, 1981; Sorens, 2012). Subsequent agitation is undertaken is intended to concretise difference in the mindsets of the affected population, sufficient to encourage progression towards independence (Hroch, 1985; Buchheit, 1978; Wood, 1981; Maxwell, 2010; Sorens, 2012). Ultimately, a mass movement emerges that spans both the political spectrum and the social classes (Maxwell, 2010). And as a part of that process, the movement and its leadership need to create an effective organisational structure. Without it, Wood (1981) argues, any impulse is likely to have only a limited and short-term impact on the political status quo.

Responses from central government: when faced with calls for secession, central government has three specific choices in front of it: suppress, accommodate, or equilibrium - a combination of both (Wood, 1981; Cetra and Harvey, 2019). Suppression can include a range of actions and can include both passive resistance and actual violence (Buchheit, 1978; Wood, 1981; Buchanan, 1997). One example offered by Wood (1981) involves the mobilisation of the 'home' focussed population within the affected territory who can be utilised to advocate for the status quo. This suppressor approach can also be called counter-secessionism (Ker-Lindsay, 2012). Ker-Lindsay leans on international relations for his theory on counter-secession and in doing so, offers a four-pronged governmental policy response.

¹³ Wood's (1981) also suggests that a secessionist movement is necessary as a precursor to independence. Tilly's (1977) resource mobilisation theory has relevance here in that a central feature for success is the availability of resources - human, equipment, skills - necessary for creating and advancing a movement (Tilly, 1977). The idea is that mobilisation is a task best suited to institutions rather than through individual or other autonomous action. However, movements and the organisations that comprise them still have some control over the political opportunities that are presented to them. Early risers are important here (Tarrow, 2011). Early risers are pace setters and who define early on the nature and style of a campaign. However, an expectation is that whilst more sections of society could be actively drawn into the movement, the more it drags on without resolution the more likely entrepreneurs will disengage and move onto other contentious topics (Tilly, 1977; Tarrow, 2011).

First, maintain a claim to the disputed territory; second, pursue legal avenues to maintain sovereignty over the disputed territory. The third is to undermine the perceived legitimacy of the secessionist movement; and the fourth, to prevent recognition of secessionist movements by international actors (Ker-Lindsay, 2012). The latter tactic can include pursuing a claim through the International Courts of Justice (Ker-Lindsay, 2012). Nevertheless, Wood (1981) warns that suppression can embolden the secessionist opponents. Buchanan's (1997) paper echoes the same view, where actual violence against the secession- supporting population can cause a claim of remedial rights.

A state that decides to accommodate secessionist demands tends to result in their being tested via a referendum (Qvortrup, 2000; Sorens, 2012; Griffiths (b), 2016). A strategy of this type is often deemed more useful when a secessionist impulse has not reached the stage of criticality - that is, when there has been no attempt at outright secession (Qvortrup, 2000). Even so, they can be a high-risk strategy for governments to undertake and there is no guarantee it will win (Qvortrup, 2000). Government can also fall back to a negotiated solution that can include the transfer of decision-making responsibility to the affected territory via devolution or other form of autonomy (Wood, 1981). Wood asserts that an approach of this type can act as equilibrium, the effect of which puts the brakes on attempts at outright secession. Overall, and regardless of the strategy employed by the state, the primacy intent is to re-legitimise the political status quo; and for Wood it is only through such actions that the state is able to compete and maintain its integrity (1981: 127).

Direct precipitants of secession: the direct precipitants of secession are those events that drive secessionism towards the tipping point, Here, there is a distinct possibility that either the state will fracture and an independent state is created, or it fend off the impulse and maintain its integrity. Typically, both sides will use security as a rationale for action (Wood, 1981). Even so, it is extremely difficult to predict the outcome of this stage (Wood, 1981). However, it is also possible for there to be a pause in proceedings in the immediate aftermath of UDI (Ker-Lindsay, 2012). In such cases, it is likely that the parent state will assess international recognitions of the new state before it decides to reclaim the territory, by force if necessary (Wood, 1981; Rapoport, 2004; Crawford, 2006). The fewer the acts of recognition (and their quality) that the embryonic state acquires the more likely the parent state will activate its plans for direct intervention.

Resolution of secessionist crises by armed conflict: Not all acts of secession are likely to end in armed conflict; and not all secessionist movements possess an armed wing (Sorens, 2012; Griffiths (a), 2016). Where a secessionist impulse does progress to violence or armed conflict the likely modus operandi will comprise terrorism, insurgency, or guerrilla warfare (Crawford: 2006; Rapoport, 2004). Pacification tends to come via interested third parties who will broker a settlement (Wood, 1981) Wood (1981) adds the likelihood that these third parties will invariably pick a side and broker accommodations between the conflicting parties. Another option is for third parties to undermine the parent state, enable entrepreneurs, and assist in the creation of a new state (Wood, 1981). Either way, every case, Wood argues, will eventually lead to a peaceful co-existence with the former parent state. It is merely a question of time.

Chapter summary

The purpose of this chapter has been to define secession by way of outlining the fundamentals and dynamics of its occurrence as an impulse or event, as well as review how scholars have attempted to explain the phenomenon. As with any social or political science, that there is disagreement between scholars is to be expected. As a generic overview, however, what is clear is that secession helps the international system evolve whilst a change in the international balance of power presents as a causal factor for the increased likelihood of a secessionist event.

Figure 3: secessionist outcomes

Regardless, there are four basic outcomes from any secessionist event, as is observed in Figure 3. Outcome 1 presents two states, A and B, viewed in terms of international relations and geopolitical geography. State B in this case acts as an interested third party. Outcome 2

drills down to the sub-state level and indicates the existence of a secessionist impulse within State A (shaded area). Outcome 3 presents the effect is irredentism via the expansion of state B's border at the expense of State A, and involves the transfer of sovereignty over a specific territory and its population from one state to another. Outcome 4 is the creation of a new independent state, State C. Where a secessionist impulse fails, the status quo outlined in outcome 1 will perpetuate.

Wood's (1981) comparative framework of secession is beneficial for helping understand and compartmentalise the various stages of a secessionist impulse. However, his fifth conflict stage presents as a bolt-on that has less relevance today as it had when he first developed his ideas. Looking specifically at real-world secessionist trends it has become increasingly clear that secessionists now routinely opting for the democratic route (Sorens, 2012; Griffiths, 2016; Qvortrup, 2000). This shift from a modus operandi based on violence to a more pacific type has occurred in the same timeframe from within which secession has become a political outlier. Whether there is a link there remains to be seen. However, it is also noted that by opting for a less violent route to independence, secessionist movements are arbitrarily reducing their room for manoeuvre given that interested third parties are more focused on intervening in violent cases (Wood, 1981; Griffiths (a), 2016; Sorens, 2012; Regan, 2019). To this end, this chapter has also noted a further trend in the testing of secessionist sentiment via referendums (Qvortrup, 2000). This same trend is also found where states have adopted separatism and some form of autonomy for affected territories. This response can be viewed as a form of containment, the effect of which involves reform of the domestic infrastructure to placate or ward off a secessionist impulse whilst also maintaining the integrity of state borders.

That these trends are expressing themselves at a time when secession is a rarity appears indicative of some form of trap that tilts the outcome of a precipitancy to the state's favour. Even so, the death of the state and the birth of a new one is an event that can be felt not only in the immediate region, but on occasion also in the wider world. Certainly this was the case with the dismantling of Empire and the latter collapse of the USSR, both of which provided for two complete secessionist waves, post-1945. Any further secessionist wave can be assumed to come via a similar route and either by a change in the international balance of power or the collapse of a multi-ethnic, multi-nation, or large federal state, A hypothetical collapse of the USA could cause the emergence over fifty new state actors; a Spanish

collapse could create nearly twenty whilst the UK offers the same potential outcome. Comprised of four home countries, and a series of overseas territories, the UK is not immune to secessionist impulses and, indeed, continues to face down concerted claims to both outright independence (Scotland) and irredentism (Northern Ireland). The UK is no stranger to secession, particularly given that the bulk of states that emerged onto the international stage in the post-1945 years were former UK colonies. To this end, the UK's experience of secession is unrivalled. This next chapter looks at the UK in more detail. It looks at how the state has responded to its relative diminution post-1945.

NB: Appendix 2 provides an overview of early events that today would be classed as secessionist.

Chapter two: statecraft

No state is immune from internal stresses or external threats and challenges. It is the job of statecraft to mitigate these threats and make for more effective governance (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; 1986b; 1996; Buller and James, 2012a; 2012b; James, 2016; 2018). Statecraft is used by states to respond to real-world events and at the heart of the theory are two things. First, the dual polity - or the separation of high and low politics (Bulpitt, 1983); and second, a set of inter-changeable levers are relied upon for furthering state interests, as conceived by the political party in power (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; 1986b; 1996; Buller and James, 2012a; 2012b; James, 2016; 2018). However, as this chapter notes, since 1945 the UK has struggled to achieve statecraft, consequent to a drifting foreign policy that has impacted the state both externally and internally. The effect is a relative long-term declinism that has negatively impacted the infrastructure necessary for the state to function effectively, a trend that has been further concretised given the recent shift towards deglobalisation (Tomlinson, 1996; 2009; Bello, 2013; Bordo, 2017; van Bergeijk, 2019; Witt, 2019; Kornprobst and Paul, 2021). The effect has led to short-termism creeping into political decision-making causing decisions to be made with one eye on the next election (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; 1986b; 1996; Buller and James, 2012a; 2012b; James, 2016; 2018). The overall effect is that UK statecraft now revolves simply around winning elections (Bulpitt, 1986a: 21). This posture is far removed from the original statecraft, a set of strategic codes for perpetuating the Victorian status quo in both the domestic and international realm.

The UK post-1945

The late 1800s are widely considered to be halcyon years for the UK (Pollard, 1989; Tomlinson, 2009; Bordo, 2017). Empire was reaping the material benefits of the second industrial revolution. Rail and other technological advancements helped bolster communications across the Imperial space, extending and facilitating the reach of governance (Abernethy, 2000; Hopkins, 2000). For Tomlinson, the years immediately after, however, saw the UK begin to experience regular “relative decline” (2009: 227). A first squeeze occurred towards the turn of the twentieth century, caused by more competitive markets in the USA and the emergent Germany, whereas the second occurred in the inter-war years (Tomlinson, 2009; Bordo, 2017). This section is about a third, more protracted, decline that has appears to have taken hold since 1945 and focuses on the UK and its struggle to find a place in this new world. This section is in three parts - drift; decline and stability; and,

deglobalisation. This section assesses that the UK is yet to recover from the loss of primacy and stature in the international arena.

Drift

Prior to the outbreak of WW2 the UK had already faced numerous sustained secessionist impulses within a number of its colonies, from India through to Nigeria (Rapoport, 2004). The evidence suggests that at the ground level the appetite for Empire had been waning and that by 1943 the UK government had already entered formal discussion with various secessionist leaders regarding future political arrangements (Hansard, 1943; Curtis, 1995). The immediate response from the UK in the early years of this new world was to attempt to retain some influence in its Imperial space via establishing a Commonwealth (Hansard, 1943). However, by 1948 it was becoming clearer that the UK's political grip was loosening. India and Pakistan had seceded from the Empire and Israel's UDI collapsed the British Mandate in Palestine (Reynolds, 2015). By the 1950s UK politicians were openly speaking about the importance of retaining what was left particularly in order to bolster the UK standard of living¹⁴ (Hyam, 2008). UK political attention subsequently changed to Africa in the 1950s, the intention being to capitalise upon resource extraction. Africa was ripe for "intensive exploitation" and plans were developed for local infrastructural builds in order to ease extraction (Hyam, 2008: 140), the determination being that Africa would replace India as the primary source of UK wealth. This policy did not last long because by the 1960s the Winds of Change¹⁵ had swept across the African continent leaving the UK's presence around the world further diminished, and with it a further loss of income.

The overall effect, for Tomlinson (2009) was that the UK, unsure of its position in the world, was experiencing foreign policy drift which is defined simply as the outcome of policies that fail to adapt to a new set of circumstances (Falleti and Lynch, 2009; Galvin and Hacker, 2020). Galvin and Hacker reinforce their perspective by asserting not only that "policies are not simply the product of politics, but they can also have significant causal effects on politics" (2020: 1). They add that the impact can be limited policy development and political inertia but, they note, drift can also be an energiser for change through which policies are

¹⁴ The extraction of wealth from India had provided the UK with direct benefit in terms of its strategic commercial, political, and military goals (Abernethy, 2000). Yet under the Raj, Indian produce served only to provide the UK with material benefit while at the same time the country had faced regular famine despite its being rich in natural resources. Indeed, the country recorded a nugatory average Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth of 0.5% for the century or so leading up to its independence in 1947 (Abernethy, 2000).

¹⁵ In a speech to the South African Parliament in 1960 the former UK Prime Minister Harold MacMillan referred to the 'Winds of Change' as a descriptor for the increase in secessionist impulses spreading across Africa (BBC, 2022).

developed that otherwise may not have been considered Galvin and Hacker, 2020). The British Empire officially ended in 1997 when Hong Kong was handed back to China. That said, the UK still retains a number of overseas territories, and acts on the international stage for three Crown Dependencies.

Figure 4: colonies of the British Empire: 1945-2000

(Source: Taylor, 2015)

Tomlinson (2009) asserts that in the 1960s the UK started to display structural weaknesses in its political, social and other, spheres, the result leaving the UK in decay (Tomlinson, 2009). This period is what he called a “post-war declinist moment whereby the impact of UK being usurped by the USA and the USSR was a causal factor in a vastly reduced international standing and a lack of economic stability (2009: 232). The post-WW2 restructuring of the global economy and the eradication of Empire left the UK increasingly boxed in by events outside its control (Reynolds, 2015; Kegley and Wittkopf, 2001). An array of forces - geopolitical, domestic party-political, combined with increased competition from Western European states, served to have a negative impact on the UK’s socio-political performance (Shanks, 1963; Hyam, 2008; Tomlinson, 2009). A side effect of the changed balance of power was the prospect of former powers watching the new ones picking over assets. This was certainly the case with Egypt which, via Nasser fell under the influence of the USSR, had embarked on a programme of industrial nationalisation, including taking the Suez Canal into public ownership (Reynolds, 2015; Hall, 2016). The UK responded by sending a military expedition to Suez with the objective of capturing the Canal. The USSR responded by threatening a nuclear strike on the UK if it did not withdraw its forces (Smolansky, 1965). As for the USA, it tabled a series of economic sanctions, sufficient that within months the UK experienced the ignominy of being the first state to receive a financial bail-out from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) (Kunz, 1991; Tomlinson, 1996; Keohane and Nye, 1987; Dieter, 2004; Hall, 2016). Ultimately, the Suez expedition left the UK financially and

militarily diminished on the international stage and if any doubt had still existed, it could no longer claim to be first amongst equals in international relations.

Decline and stability

By the late 1960s, the UK had resided long-term over an incrementally poorer economic performance, and some in the elites were convinced that the Wilson government had been lying about the extent of the UK national debt (Assinder, 1999; Hamilton, 2005; Curtis, 2011; O'Hara, 2012). In 1968, the press baron, Cecil King, thearistocrats who ran the Bank of England, the higher echelons of the military, and the Monarch's cousin, Lord Mountbatten, were in the process of plotting a military coup d'etat against Wilson (Hamilton, 2005; Curtis, 2011; O'Hara, 2012). When it learned of the coup attempt, Wilson's inner circle drew up their deterrence, called 'Operation Brutus' (Hamilton, 2005; Curtis, 2011). The plan there was to seize all foreign assets held by banks registered in the UK and all foreign direct investments into the UK (BBC, 1999; Hamilton, 2005; Curtis, 2011; O'Hara, 2012), and in effect, the nationalisation of the entire UK financial system. At the same time the border was to be closed stopping both people and money from leaving the UK. Had Brutus gone live, the expectation was of a catastrophic collapse of Pound Sterling, state bankruptcy, and mass civil unrest (Assinder, 1999; Curtis, 2011). However, whilst the coup quickly fell apart the message from the central government to the plotters was a simple one - "you try and overthrow us, and we will pull the house down around all of us" (Curtis, 2011: n.p.). This may sound like institutional suicide but with Brutus not going live there is no way of knowing if the exercise was mere bluff.

Regardless, the UK was jolted into action because in the 1970s it finally began addressing its foreign policy drift by joining the European Economic Community (EEC). Buzan and Waever (2003) argue that institutions such as the EEC were a product of the new international system being built to replace Empire. They presented as a second-generation system for inter-state collective action that not only helped to diffuse tension and power between states but also resulted in their no longer the sole actors in international relations (Baylis and Smith, 2001). Consequentially, the interests of states could be managed through negotiation and co-operation instead of on the battlefield, as was the 'old' practice. Institutions such as these, Nicholson (2002) argued, furthered the potential that through working together, Western Europe had been able to bring to an end hundreds of years of war and conflict whereas for Kissinger (2014), the potential existed for a level of stability in

international relations that had previously not existed. Nonetheless, for the UK the 1970s were dominated by regular mass industrial actions that resulted in shortages and a three-day working week. This decade also records the third in a row in which UK had requested a bailout from the IMF (Coyle, 2017). By contrast the UK's neighbours in Western Europe were already recording faster growth rates and were more competitive (Shanks, 1963; Smith, 2001). Reform eventually came to the UK domestic arena in the 1980s when concurrent political change on the international front, particularly in respect of the IMF and World Bank (Mavroudeas and Papadatos, 2007). Out of it came a set of best-practice interventionist policies to help address structural weaknesses in failing and underdeveloped states (Williamson, 2000). As is seen in Table 2, a number of the policies had already been rolled out in the UK and catalysed at the outset by monetarism (Tomlinson, 1996; 2009; Baylis and Smith, 2001).

Table 2: UK/Washington Consensus policy parallel

Decade	Prime Minister	Washington Consensus	UK policy
1980s	Thatcher	fiscal discipline	monetarism
1980s	Thatcher	redirecting public expenditure	public sector internal markets
1980s	Thatcher	privatisation	market floatation and other selloffs
1980s	Thatcher	deregulation	stock market reform
1990s	Major	trade liberalisation	membership of the EU single market
1990s	Major	liberalised foreign direct investment	membership of the EU single market
1990s	Major	competitive exchange rate	EU single currency exchange rate mechanism
1990s	Blair	liberalised interest rates	devolved to the central bank
1990s	Blair	tax reform	tax credits
1990s	Blair	redirecting public expenditure	redefining poverty

(Minikin, 1993; Alcock, 1997; Williamson, 2000; Baylis and Smith, 2001; Smith, 2001; Mavroudeas and Papadatos, 2007; Frazer, 2009; Conaghan, 2012)

UK reliance on Keynesian economics was replaced by a two-decade long programme that involved the dismantling of the mixed economy and the privatisation of large state-owned monopolistic corporations, and which resulted in numerous communities across the UK were impacted with poverty and mass unemployment (McInnes, 1995; Alcock, 1997; Beckett, 2009; Lister, 2010; Gray, 2014; Gibbs, 2016). The effects of decades of policy drift had depreciated the domestic space to such an extent that an argument could be made for the UK

being a model for the shock therapies that have been applied latterly around the world¹⁶. Nonetheless, the UK was embarking on a prolonged period of relative stability, albeit of a type that left the domestic economy exposed to international events - as indicated by the financial crisis of 2008/09. The consequence there was a run on its banks and the forcing of the UK government to re-adopt a policy of nationalisation, this time to take a number of banks into public ownership. To pay for this endeavour, the UK entered into a period of austerity (Financial Services Authority, 2011; Blyth, 2015), which as a policy, arguably remains in place. The experience brought to an end the longest period of stability in the UK in its post-1945 history. In the time since, the UK has entered into a new foreign policy era, one that coalesces around a policy of deglobalisation.

Deglobalisation

The literature on deglobalisation has grown in recent years and largely focuses on the dynamics of international trade in the post-financial crisis era (Bordo, 2017; van Bergeijk, 2019; Witt, 2019; Kornprobst and Paul, 2021). Deglobalisation has since been adopted by states that intend limiting their exposure to the international system (Bordo, 2017; van Bergeijk, 2019; Kornprobst and Paul, 2021). The rationale behind deglobalisation concerns not just limiting state exposure to another financial or other crisis but is a response also to the primacy of institutions such as the EU and the rise of China as an economic powerhouse (García-Herrero and Tan, 2020). Deglobalising states develop mercantilist and other protectionist policies, specifically in three areas - international trade, capital flows, and migration, intent on regaining their sovereign power (van Bergeijk, 2019; Kornprobst and Paul, 2021). It is into this world the UK stepped when in 2016 when its electorate voted in a referendum to leave the EU.

Bello (2013) posits that the 2008/09 banking and financial crises were a catalyst for states plumping for a deglobalised policy platform. Witt (2019) says the policy is indicative of the cyclical nature of international relations and based on a presumption that ‘we’ve been here before’, particularly in the aftermath of the Wall Street Crash which contributed to the declinist UK experience in the years between WW1 and WW2 (Tomlinson, 1996; 2009). Even so, the argument is that deglobalisation has resulted in “simultaneous growth and decline of worldwide interconnectedness” (Bordo, 2017: 1), and acts as a form “levelling off”

¹⁶ Devised in 1989 the Washington Consensus led to case specific policies that in the extreme included an intervention into Bolivia that resulted in the privatisation of rainwater (Bonnardeaux, 2009).

(Kornprobst and Paul, 2021: 1305). For the UK, the real-world effects of its departure from the EU were not immediately noticeable, but more recently clear problems can be cited across the economic base - infrastructure, logistics, utilities, food supplies, manpower, with an inevitable impact on the public purse (Springford and Portes, 2023; Islam, 2024; Emmerson, Johnson, Mitchell, et al, 2016). These outcomes have persisted despite a pre-arranged transition framework. The effect is that deglobalisation has not proven to be the panacea that proponents of the policy had intended and given that the UK is now on its sixth Prime Minister since the UK voted to leave the EU in 2016. Pandemic didn't help either. The effects of that, combined with EU departure, led the UK to record its worst economic performance in its history (Szalay, 2020). GDP to debt ratio resides at around 100%; Pound Sterling has been known to perform in line with emerging market status (Giles, 2020; Giles and Sampson, 2020; Szalay, 2020). And at the same time, the average wage has barely increased above pre-2008 levels whilst inflation has been recorded to have risen to its highest levels for thirty years. As for taxation, it resides at its highest level since the end of WW2 (Corlett and Try, 2022; Plummer, 2022). The culmination is the UK boasting the lowest GDP per capita in Northern Europe (Bindman, 2021; Weldon, 2022). This insight resonates with Aldrick (2022) who argues that UK economic sustainability has been at its lowest compared with thirty-six major competitor economies. The result is a state currently weakened in a number of areas - economic, fiscal, and structural, with the public health crisis placing further pressures on the state, including compounding manpower shortages caused initially by deglobalised migration controls (Springford and Portes, 2023). These events have also led the central government to rely on emergency legislation. More recently, it has been commonplace for military personnel to carry out duties normally undertaken by the civilian population¹⁷, and in an era when the UK military has been degraded over the long term and where it can no longer boast a tier-one capability (Ashcroft and Oakeshott, 2018).

Overall, these insights note that the seventy years after WW2 the UK continues to adjust its new international diminution and the new international environments that have emerged concurrently. Even so, it would be wrong to suggest that the UK has failed to maximise the domestic and international opportunities presented to it during this time (Bulpitt 1996: 1097). This is where statecraft has relevance, and it is to there where this chapter now turns its attention.

¹⁷ Military service provision include undertaking logistical duties, i.e., delivering fuel and assisting the health service (UK Government, 2021),

UK statecraft

This section begins with an outline of five early codes for government that were intended to perpetuate the status quo in the Victorian era. It then discusses Bulpitt's (1983) ideas on the dual polity, then latterly, five statecraft levers.

On the surface the UK in the late nineteenth century remained economically sound but underneath there were “signs of weakness, of mistaken policies and false assumptions, of snobbery in the schools and short-sightedness in the City” (Pollard, 1989: 271). There was also an institutional tilt towards the land-owning aristocratic elites who absorbed and then directed political power and influence (Peters, 1967; Roberts, 2012). One of them was Lord Salisbury, a hereditary peer in the UK's unelected House of Lords. He served as UK Prime Minister at the turn of the twentieth century and he was the last in the post to be seated in the Lords as opposed to the House of Commons as has been the recent custom (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a). And when in office, he loaded his cabinet with Lords-based aristocrats who were presented to the people as the protectors of “every silver fork in the country” which, in layman terms, meant the middle classes (James, 2009: 337). He also viewed Empire through a Christian Imperialist lens and further believed the Lords to be superior to the Commons (Marsh, 1978; Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; James, 2009). He further believed that a function of the Lords was to veto Bills thought damaging to the interests of the state regardless of whether or not they were backed by an electoral mandate (Dymond and Deadman, 2006). To this end, Salisbury had previously been against electoral reform and was against widening the franchise, was against legislation geared towards reducing corruption and bribery, and to support the introduction of the secret ballot (HM Government, 1872; HM Government, 1883). Such reforms, he argued, would undermine the primacy of the aristocracy (Bulpitt, 1983).

This worldview premised on the suppression the then emergent “aggressive democracy” that was pushing for socio-political change in the UK (Bulpitt, 1983: 114). Bulpitt adds that Salisbury's intention was to “delay and weaken” the Labour and Suffragette movements (1983: 114). That aside, Salisbury is best remembered for his codes for government (Marsh, 1978). They comprised a continuance of the primacy of the Aristocracy and a trade-off on Home Rule (specifically concerning Ireland); an English predominance that determined that England spoke for Scotland; a system for party management called the Middleton machine;

and a foreign policy referred to as ‘splendid isolation’ (Marsh, 1978; Steele, 2002; Roberts, 2012). Each of these codes has endured and has continued to influence decision-making in central government. Salisbury’s intention was to create a system that managed efficiently, UK responses of the state to events both at home and abroad (Bulpitt 1996: 1097). To be successful, political leaders needed to be both rational and self-interested, or as political scientists would call it, realist, so to ensure the status quo (Bulpitt, 1983: 114).

Aristocratic primacy: Steele (2002) portrays Salisbury as a natural pessimist who was inclined to recognise the gradual weakening of the aristocracy. But, Salisbury’s underpinning response was to seek the continuance of the establishment, particularly the aristocracy, as the guiding force for the state (Marsh, 1978). He had intended to protect the Lords “as a bulwark against demotic liberalism, militant trade unionism, and the politics of envy” (James, 2009: 337). However, he had to capitulate to the forces for social change which meant making strategic choices. What social reform he oversaw had been chosen specifically to ensure a class-as-regime survival programme. For example, his involvement in the earliest UK welfare system helped lead to the creation of a system type that ideologically equated to Bismarck’s “welfare monarchy” and which considered rudimentary services and handouts as a necessary evil (Esping Andersen, 1996: 66).

The Middleton machine: named after Captain Richard Middleton who had been tasked with developing an efficient and effective party-political machine that ironed out friction and infighting in the Conservative party (Marsh, 1978). What resulted was a system for party management that supervised relations between the centre and the territories it administered (Marsh, 1978; Bulpitt, 1986b). These reformations are also considered to have helped lay the foundations for the later absorption of the Unionist party into the Conservative structure (Marsh, 1978; Roberts, 2012; Torrance, 2017).

Home Rule trade-off: Salisbury offered unwavering support for the Union, albeit overseen via a London-centric state (Bulpitt, 1983; James, 2016). He also feared an Ancien Regime- or an act of unilateral secession, such as that which had occurred in the USA (Bulpitt, 1983; James, 2016). At the time, Irish separatism was a main political issue. For Salisbury, the consequence of some form of Irish autonomy should be a reduction in Irish representation in the Commons, and with Irish members being restricted to votes on country specific and ‘Imperial’ matters only (Hansard, 1894; Dymond and Deadman, 2006). Whilst Salisbury

successfully held off an Irish political advance, he also made separate arrangements to stave off any similar moves from Scotland. These include his re-establishing of the Scottish Office through which the UK could “redress the wounded dignities of the Scotch people” (Hanham, 1969: 23). The result led the UK to become less centralised and offered a tacit acknowledgement to the existence of Scotland as a distinct political, cultural, and administrative entity when set against rest of the UK state space (Torrance, 2017).

English predominance: an overlap with the Home Rule trade-off, this relates to a politico-legal hierarchy in the UK within which it was for the English representatives to decide the conclusion of the Irish Home Rule debate and that this took precedence over any opposing view from Scotland¹⁸ (Hansard, 1894: c-22-23).

Splendid isolation: when in office, Salisbury intended advancing a UK exceptionalism that limited state exposure to international interference in the state’s imperial and colonial endeavours (Marsh, 1978). The intention was to help protect state interests on a case-by-case basis from what was an explicitly realist disposition (Marsh, 1978; Orgill, 2018: 1-6). The underlying belief was that in operating in this way the UK could tip the European balance of power in its favour, thereby furthering protecting state interests (Orgill, 2018).

In the century and a half since Salisbury first espoused his ideas for government, they have endured and evolved to form part of a wider approach that includes not just the perpetuation of the state, but also the party of government and, indeed, whoever is positioned as UK Prime Minister. Satisfying these three interests means ostensibly that statecraft has been achieved (Marsh, 1978; Bulpitt, 1983; James, 2016; 2018; Roberts, 2012). A contemporary understanding of statecraft practice emerged in the 1980s and has evolved in the years since. The works, headed by Bulpitt (1983; 1986a; 1986b; 1988; 1996), present a departure from prior publications that focused on the roles and functions of the establishment as the drivers of the state. These include Hennessey (1986) and Sampson’s (1962-2004) series on the *Anatomy of Britain*. There, the establishment is portrayed as a cohort that resides at the helm of the socio-political hierarchy and who provide oversight of the arms of the state. Added is the pre-requisite that the establishment is also responsible for collectively advancing the

¹⁸ Salisbury argued in the Lords that “Everybody is aware that if England is willing to accept Home Rule, the resistance of its antagonists will not prevail. I freely admit that if Scotland had as strong an aversion to Home Rule as England has that would be a bar to its adoption; but, dealing with the matter as we stand, the opinion of England for or against is the deciding judge in this issue of Home Rule” (Hansard, 1894: c-22-23).

status quo through claiming legal and moral legitimacy (Bulpitt, 1983; Hennessey, 1986). Party politicians are also to be found in this cohort (Wolff, 1990: 20; Schmitt, 1996; Boitani and Torti, 1999; Baylis and Smith, 2001; Mearsheimer, 2001; Lake, 2003; Oppenheim et al, 2008). Ultimately, Bulpitt's contributions shifted understanding of UK statecraft from the 'whom' of the state to the 'what' and the 'how' (1977; 1983; 1986a; 1986b; 1988; 1996). The result is politicians having at their disposal a "set of relatively coherent principles or rules" that help determine the policies that government relies on to advance its political platform (Bulpitt, 1996: 1097). In its totality, Bulpitt's work tracks state change over time, in line with historical institutionalist perspectives (Rhodes 1996; Parsons, 1997; Evans and Davies, 1999; Della Porta and Keating, 2008; James 2016). Using historical institutionalism in this way allows the work on statecraft to analyse continuity and change in central governmental activity - past, present, and prospective (Fioretos, Falleti, and Sheingate, 2016). Bulpitt (1996) also argues that political science research had been captured by the present and lacks historical context. For him, "the 1190s ... are as interesting and as important as the 1990s" and "how we got here" is just as important as "being here" (Bulpitt, 1996: 1094).

In its totality, the core thrust of the contemporary literature on statecraft concerns how the state responds to real-world events in a way that perpetuates the electoral status quo. The theory covers a range of socio-political topic areas at both macro and meso levels: party-political strategies, economic policy; race relations; urban policy; party politics; electoral reform; and foreign policy development (Bulpitt, 1986b; Bulpitt and Burnham 1999; Savitch and Osgood, 2010; James, 2016; Ayres, Flinders, and Sandford, 2018). Many of these studies are undertaken at the meso level where the focus has been on small particulars, the result helping cause a compartmentalisation of the research (James, 2016). For Richardson (2012), this outcome may not necessarily be a bad thing. He argued that these types of studies help facilitate institutional change rather than simply monitor and explain it (Richardson, 2012). The dual polity is a core aspect of this Bulpittian perspective on statecraft. It is a facet of statecraft theory dedicated to explaining how the UK central government manages territorial relations within its space, and it is the subject of the following subsection.

The dual polity

Bulpitt (1983: 61) argued that the central government is where "the locus of actual political power" is found. The literature on statecraft typically demarcates high and low politics, with its emphasis being a necessity for the central government to remain aloof from the small

particulars of low politics and instead concentrating on international affairs and the like. This is what Bulpitt (1983) calls the dual polity and it is a central plank in explaining how the UK government deploys statecraft to the benefit of the status quo. Central government, as such, is the nucleus of the state and its preferred operating domain is within high politics - central policy, exchequer, foreign affairs - everything outside that zone is deemed to be low politics (Bulpitt, 1983). The suggestion is that by remaining focused on high politics, political leaders are able to present themselves in a strong, positive light (Foley, 2004; James, 2018). As for low politics, these are deemed to be parochial and can be messy and unrewarding” and, as such, a main priority is to maintain distance (Ayres et al, 2018). For Bulpitt, this stance allows politicians to act autonomously and independently of its territorial and political periphery (1983: 96). The argument is that with each emergent problem an assessment is made regarding the potential damage to the status quo and then categorised as either high or low politics (Ayres et al, 2018). From there, supporting policy is drawn up and executed.

Relations between the ‘centre’ and the ‘periphery’ are a core consideration for operating a successful dual polity. The periphery comprises the lower rungs of the state ladder, i.e., local councils and those other agencies of state that interact directly with the people, and it is to there where emergent ‘low’ problems are assigned (Bulpitt, 1983). Models have been developed that explain the approaches that the centre might take in developing its peripheral relations (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986b; Ayres et al, 2018; Keating, 2018). Each of them coalesces around central government and its formal relations with the various bodies, institutions, and the elites that make up the UK state infrastructure. The first is the central authority model which premises itself on the acceptance and co-operation of the periphery as way for enhancing centre-led governance (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986b; Ayres et al, 2018). The capital city bargaining model premises on communication between the centre and periphery in line with pre-existing institutional arrangements. The coercive power model is regarded as authoritarian given its reliance on threat to maintain the status quo (Ayres et al, 2018). The last model is what Bulpitt (1983) believes the UK uses for managing the dual polity, what he calls the central autonomy model which offers limited freedom of institutional movement at the local level (Ayres et al, 2018). This model is deemed to be the only viable option available for developing effective relations between the centre and the periphery, and as a means for ensuring the status quo (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986b; Bradbury and John, 2010).

For Bulpitt (1983; 1986a), the centre autonomy model is central to Salisbury’s legacy, developed primarily as a response to the rise of popular government, the widening of the franchise, and the emergence of the Labour Party as a political force. Bradbury and John (2010) also argue that through this model the central government is able to retain focus on high politics via using foreign policy as a way for bolstering party-political support in the domestic space. And this is the main point: that through the centre autonomy model, local problems can be assigned to local authorities and other arms-length public bodies and institutions to deal with, as long as the periphery does not interfere in high politics (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; 1986b; Bevir, 2010; Ayres, et al, 2018). Bradbury and John (2010) add further that whilst post-1945 declinism left the state vulnerable to peripheral challenge, lessons learnt from the dismantling of Empire have since been applied to the domestic space (Bradbury and John, 2010). For Ayres et al (2018), the dual polity, in terms of its operation, is merely a system for territorial management - one that is intended to help further bolster support and legitimacy from the people to a state that relies on arms-length public institutions to do its bidding for it (Bradbury and John, 2010; Convery, 2013; Ayres et al, 2018). Lastly, all five models used in conjunction could produce an outcome in which an arms-length state cares only about ensuring tax receipts and that law and order is maintained (Ayres et al, 2018: 856). That said, using one managerial approach in isolation of the others cannot be ruled out.

Nonetheless, being successful here can also mean the employment of local elites for specific duties, as well as peripheral bodies and, at times, the citizenry also (Ayres et al, 2018). The totality of the exercise is outlined in Table 3.

Table 3: territorial management

Central penetration	The minimum necessary to maintain law and order.
Local elite assimilation	Peripheral leaders govern on behalf of the central government and do so via a clear policy platform.
Central control of local governments	Imposing policy by legal means onto local authorities and other arms-length public bodies.
Organisation mobilisation	Central government mobilises local authorities and arms-length public bodies to govern local affairs.
Citizen mobilisation	The mobilisation of the peripheral citizenry so as to provide active support for central government policy and its objectives.

(Source: Ayres et al, 2018: 586)

The five levers

To assist in the management of the dual polity, government has at its disposal five levers to develop and further its statecraft strategy as applied in the domestic space. Collectively, they have been called “internal statecraft” (Hopkins, 2011: 93), and comprise those machineries that are under the direct control of the central government: argument hegemony; governing competence; party management; electoral strategy; and, bending the rules (Bulpitt, 1983; James, 2016; 2018).

Argument hegemony

Argument hegemony is concerned with winning the battle of ideas (James, 2016; 2018). In essence, the message a politician promotes may be subject to change, in terms of maintaining the status quo the underlying meaning will always be the same.

Argument hegemony is defined as “the party achieving an easy predominance in elite debate regarding political problems, policies and the general stance of government”, and it can be won and lost, at any time, in a number of arenas in both governmental, and/or social spheres (Bulpitt, 1986: 21; Hopkins, 2011). This section outlines two types of argument hegemony. The first is specific to the party of government and consists of how ideas are used to dominate the party-political discourse. The second type is state symbolism which can be converted into actionable practices that reinforce the state-centric status quo.

Bulpitt says that argument hegemony is underpinned by the need to create a winning rhetoric in variety of locations (1986: 21)¹⁹. Argument hegemony is central to exercising power and is achieved through the effective projection of political ideas on to the people (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986; Kissinger, 2014; James, 2016). It is through being successful in argument hegemony that the party in power can claim ongoing legitimacy in government (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; James, 2016). Bulpitt sees this requirement to be simply “the politics of governing” (1996: 515), and for Buller (1999), it is evidence that it is political parties that frame the political agenda. Leys further adds that ideology is vital here but, he argues, argument hegemony does not need to be loved, “it is merely necessary that it have no serious rival” (1990: 127). Indeed, for Gamble (1993) and Heffernan (1998), argument hegemony is the reason behind

¹⁹ Winning either because the framework of the party’s arguments becomes generally acceptable, or because solutions to a particularly important political problem is seen to be more plausible than offered by opponents (Bulpitt, 1986: 21).

the success of Thatcherism as a political idea, itself bolstered by a Conservative party that has been more successful at achieving argument hegemony than the Labour party (Gamble, 1993: 38). Thatcher's legacy is considered to remain relevant even though by the mid-1990s the Conservatives were a "busted flush"(Gamble, 1993: 24). A core success, for Heffernan (1998), was the creation and success of an effective argument that is premised on specific and clearly communicated political, economic, and electoral objectives that offer more than mere rhetoric but which were also communicated effectively (Heffernan, 1998). Thatcherism was successful in this endeavour, and it is for this reason, he adds, that the Conservatives could feed from it well into the twenty-first century if they so wished.

Argument hegemony however, is not merely a matter for the mind or its conquest via competing political ideals; some aspects are tangible and are in-built into the state. Here, it is of note that Nairn (1977) acknowledges the existence of an in-built argument hegemony that resides at a higher level, one that revolves around the aristocracy, the culture of the ruling classes, and the establishment. He adds that the UK has never really addressed this practice:

This state, consolidated in England by 1688, and, by extension, in Scotland after the Union of 1707, was therefore pre-modern in structure: Although not, of course, an absolutist state, the Anglo-British state remains a product of the general transition from absolutism to modern constitutionalism: it led the way out of the former but never genuinely arrived at the latter (1977: 75).

Through ceremonials, speeches, and status, the symbolism of the state has its part to play here in the perpetuation of the status quo. The Mace, for example, has traditionally been the symbol of Royal sovereign patronage that allows the UK Parliament to make legislation of on behalf of the Monarch (UK Parliament, 2021). Two Maces are in situ when the House of Commons is sitting - one via Cromwell and the other consequent to William of Orange²⁰. However, distinct, and separate, arrangements exist in the devolved institutions. There is a Mace in both the Welsh Assembly and the Scottish parliament, the Scottish Mace being distinguished by a caveat inscribed upon it, "Scotland Act 1998" (Scottish Parliament, 2021), in effect, reinforcing the reality that sovereignty over Scotland lies elsewhere (McDonald and Hazell, 2007). By contrast the Northern Irish Assembly sits without a Mace being present.

²⁰ Nenner argues that the Glorious Revolution began when William, Prince of Orange, invaded England to oppose the "twin demons of Popery and tyranny" (1988: 283). In layman terms this meant opposing a Catholic on the English throne and installing a constitutional Monarchy (Goldie, 1980). Whiggism emerged out of the events that followed and as a set of founding principles, the ideology advanced a system of constitutional Monarchy in which Parliament is supreme (Womersley et al, 2005). Whiggism was supported by the English middle and capitalist classes already opposed to governance via Tory squirearchy (Womersley et al, 2005).

On the whole, argument hegemony is a constant and is never out of play, regardless of the origin (idea or symbolism) (Wood, 1981; Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; Morgenthau, 1978; Mearsheimer, 2001; Kissinger, 2014; James, 2016). This next subsection looks specifically at central government and discusses the role of state machinery and structures in creating a perception of competent government.

Governing competence

Bulpitt has argued that the “principal aim” of the Thatcher government was to recreate the “traditional centre autonomy enjoyed by British governments prior to the 1960s” (1986: 34). This was the basis for the dual polity. Beforehand, the central government had made a habit of becoming involved in low politics, with the resultant blame for failure being levied at government (Bulpitt 1983: 192; Buller 1999: 698).

Competent government is not just about policy or its implementation but also how it is perceived - and that can mean deciding to do nothing, dealing with problems directly, or devolving responsibility to other areas of the state, as per the dual polity (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; Buller and James, 2012a). Effective policy rejection when in government is as necessary a requirement as policy adoption (Bulpitt, 1986: 21; Hopkins, 2011). There are numerous reasons why a policy is adopted or not - for example, the primacy of ideology in the party of government; pressures from lobbyists and other interest groups; the difficulty of implementation; and the reputation of the party in government (Bulpitt, 1986; James, 2018). Ultimately, however, competent governance is as about “the economy, stupid” (James, 2018: 564) - perception matters “and not necessarily reality” in determining competence in government (James, 2018: 565). To this end, economic growth and real improvements in standards of living, the type of international disputes that government finds itself involved in, and the length of time the party of government has spent in office are core components on competence (Bulpitt, 1986; James, 2018). It is also possible that the party of government could face an engrained, negative socio-political attitude and these factors indicate that there is more to competent government than just policies (Bulpitt, 1986; James, 2018). Overall, however, competent governance is heavily dependent on the abilities of the person making the final decisions for a future course of action (Bulpitt, 1983; Stevens, 2002; Buller and James, 2012a; 2012b; James, 2016; 2018). Indeed, a premise such as that one is reminiscent of Morgenthau’s (1978) assertion that it is the politicians that are ultimately responsible for whether statecraft is achieved or not.

Where government lacks competence, the expectation is that the dual polity will collapse and the central government will become “overwhelmed” (Bulpitt, 1983; Buller 1999: 698; Convery, 2013). For Bulpitt, this was what happened to the Heath government in the 1970s when Heath allowed himself to become absorbed by policies that served only to embolden the Labour opposition (1983: 161). Thatcherism addressed this weakness through ruthlessly applying the dual polity to a point that the UK government became an “absentee landlord” in its own space (Bulpitt, 1983: 161). This form of ‘hands-off’ government, for Bulpitt (1983), played well with the electorate and enhanced the image of competent governance. The effect reinforced a perception of competence in Thatcher’s government but in reality, it meant off-loading damaging policies to the periphery and to the mostly Labour run local authorities, (Bulpitt, 1983; Stevens, 2002; Convery, 2013; Ayres et al, 2018). However, Thatcher’s monetarist ideology is considered to have left her boxed in and eventually offered her little room for manoeuvre when she attempted to move towards her next stage in the UK’s economic recovery (Bulpitt, 1983).

Essentially, decision making in the central government is only successful where it helps create or maintain a favourable political operating environment and, by definition, the status quo. The next section looks at how the party of government manages its internal affairs so that the central government can not only continue the appearance of competence, but also offer a unified front to the electorate, and it is to this area where this section now turns.

Party management

Party management is an internal, perpetual affair (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; 1986b). Evolving straight from Salisbury and the Middleton Machine (Marsh, 1978), the contemporary party management system today acts as a lever of statecraft and is intended to encourage the party-political machinery to create, preserve, and/or portray a unified party, regardless of the rank or purpose of any official or member (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; Buller and James, 2012a; James, 2016; 2018). Party management can also overlap with argument hegemony, as part of an attempt to instil confidence within the party of the leadership (James, 2016; 2018).

Bulpitt (1986) assumes that party leaders will seek to maintain calm relations within the party. Nevertheless, there are times when a more aggressive stance is considered necessary. Similarly, managing Members of Parliament is made easier because of the institutional constraints in the Westminster system (Foster, 2006; Shapiro, Skowronek, and Galvin, 2006;

James, 2016). Westminster offers MPs long-term high-end employment for those that have been successfully elected and whose party is in government (Digby-Jones, 2011). Consequentially, it is believed that most elected representatives are unlikely to rock the boat, out of both a personal and collective need to avoid electoral defeat. The need to maintain an effective system of party management, however, is ongoing, regardless of whether or not in government or not (Hopkins, 2011). For this purpose, the Whip system is designed to retain member loyalty and helps enforce attitudinal alignment between MPs and the Ministerial cohort and in a way that assists in repressing rebellions when they arise. The need is to avoid or dampen the potential for rebellions in order to retain the ability to exercise statecraft (Buller and James, 2012a).

Electoral strategy

Electoral strategy is the product of the other three above levers - argument hegemony, governing competence, and party management. Those three 'levers' can be combined to form a system for encouraging perpetual electioneering. A successful electoral strategy is a major step to achieving statecraft (James, 2016: 2). To this end, party leaders make winning general elections their uppermost consideration and will rely on a successful platform, a united party, and a reputation for competence (Bulpitt, 1983).

No government ever wants to increase taxes in an election year so a successful electoral strategy could include bringing in unpopular policies earlier in the term (James, 2016; 2018). Since the central government is in control of the timetable in the House of Commons it is also capable of countering obstructions in the governmental policy-electoral cycle. For example, the now-repealed fixed term parliament, which had been in operation for around a decade largely nullified this latter consideration but as was the case in 2019, a simple vote in the Commons caused an early general election (UK Government, 2019). As for success at the polls, this eventuality is further facilitated through the first past the post electoral system. An outcome of this system makes it entirely normal for a political party to win a landslide victory yet at the same time receive little over forty percent of the vote (Stephens, 2002; Buller and James, 2012a; 2012b).

However, it must also be noted that governing parties have reduced room for manoeuvre to practice electoral/economic manipulation, given that interest rates haven't been under central government control since 1997 (Conaghan, 2012; Shapiro et al, 2006). Even so, the winner-

takes-all approach to UK elections not only facilitates a form of elective dictatorship but reinforces the old adage that general elections are for governing parties to lose (Bogdanor, 2009). Essentially, there are a multitude of factors - procedural or political response to real-world events - that need to be incorporated into central government decision-making when in the process of developing its electoral strategy to achieve statecraft. Another is turnout because recent decades have seen a downturn in voting numbers across the UK and, for Armstrong (2015) such a reality has led to calls for compulsory voting. At the same time, Armstrong argues, government appears to be content with a lack of voters as opposed to seeing a problem with voters who are “ill-informed or have no wish to support the existing system” (Armstrong, 2015: 4)²¹. A similar set of calculations can be found when the central government sanctions the use of referendums to address political problems (Qvortrup, 2019).

Referendums have been a fixture of political systems for over three centuries and “have been called to address constitutional, territorial, moral or other issues” (Boyd, 2010: 2). However, their efficacy as a tool for testing voter opinions remains open to question. Boyd, for example, argues that referendums are used by dictatorships and “ruthless governments, such as Nazi Germany or Communist Romania” (2010: 2). For reasons such as these, Oakeshott argues, a referendum provides government with “unlimited authority”²² (1991: 380). For Dicey, referendums are akin to a ‘people's veto’ that resulted in arguments that they were a machine for “Tory democracy” and needed to be used only in a “Conservative sense” (Atkinson, Blick, and Qvortrup, 2020: 6). The result, for Lijphart (1984), is that “when governments control the referendum ... they will tend to use it only when they expect to win” (Lijphart, 1984: 203). For Lijphart, referendums are “controlled” and designed to be “pro-hegemonic” in that they serve to reinforce the status quo (1984: 203). Consequentially, Boyd (2010) questions whether or not referendums are as democratic a tool they are purported to be. Even so, the potential that referendums are capable of holding power to account cannot be understated (Qvortrup, 2019; Atkinson et al, 2020).

Qvortrup also offers the potential that referendums can be used to help address party-political purposes, including to confirm government policy and address problems in-party. He cites

²¹ Armstrong also noted empirical research where voters called for a ‘none of the above’ voting option (2015: 5).

²² “Is not a method by which ‘mass man’ imposes his choices upon his rulers; it is a method for generating a government with unlimited authority to make choices on his behalf. In the plebiscite the ‘mass man’ achieved release from the burden of individuality he was told emphatically what to choose” (Oakeshott, 1991: 380).

three examples; the EEC referendum in 1975; the 2011 referendum on electoral reform; and, the 2016 referendum on EU membership. In each case, Qvortrup (2000), there was a need to address unity in the party of government or, in respect of the 2011 referendum, maintain unity in the Coalition government. Nonetheless, as an argument for promoting the Western system of democracy, Atkinson et al also argue that “governments have been unsuccessful in their attempts to control the referendum” (2020: 1). As Table 4 outlines, this has not been the UK experience in that government policy has prevailed in the majority of cases.

Table 4: UK referendums

Year	Election	PM	Government result
1973	NI irredentism	Heath	Win
1975	EEC membership	Wilson	Win
1979	Scottish devolution	Callaghan	Win (Threshold loss ¹⁴)
1979	Welsh devolution	Callaghan	Lose
1997	Scottish devolution	Blair	Win
1997	Welsh devolution	Blair	Win
1998	English regional devolution	Blair	Win
1998	Northern Ireland devolution	Blair	Win
2004	English regional devolution	Blair	Lose
2011	Welsh separatism	Cameron	Neutral
2011	Proportional representation	Cameron	Win
2014	Scottish independence	Cameron	Win
2016	EU membership	Cameron	Lose

(Sources: Ark, 2002a; Ark, 2002b; Atkinson et al, 2020; Bochel, Denver, and Mitchell, 2013; Callaghan, 1987; Osmond, 2011)

The referendums held in the 1970s premised on objective framework that had been drawn up by government and which could be campaigned on. Since 1997, referendums have been held on a pre-legislative basis (Winetrobe, 1997; Bochel, Denver, Mitchell, and Pattie, 2013). The meaning here is that the electorate have been asked to vote on an abstract idea, with the frameworks being developed latterly and consequent to the result of the vote.

To sum up, in a system where the purpose is to win elections and keep on winning all governmental decisions, policies, and actions will be undertaken with one eye on the next election. The result is a statecraft practice that encourages perpetual electioneering and short-termism. This section now turns to the last and most recently developed of the five levers.

Bending the rules

James argues simply that statecraft is achieved “because” of the rules (2012: 284). He furthers that “statecraft occurred in the UK because of the institutional rules of the game” and that, as a criticism of the Bulpittian perspective, “how elites changed the rules was not considered within the model” (James, 2012: 284). For James (2012; 2018) this insight represented a limitation in the theory that assesses institutional change in that the ‘rules of the game’ have never been explained in any real way, or indeed why a need for them to change in the first place. Consequentially, he argues that there exists a fifth statecraft lever which he calls ‘bending the rules’.

James (2012; 2016) came from a neo-statecraft perspective, one that built on and updated Bulpitt’s (1983; 1986) work and which posits that political leaders need to alter the institutions of state so to achieve statecraft. James adds that the democratic process requires by design a need for politicians to act in a self-interested way, with the need for winning elections as the main driver. As such, he limited his work on rule bending to elections, of which the “institutional architecture” is vulnerable to being manipulated so to make winning elections easier and, thus, achieve statecraft (James, 2012: 105). But, as both James (2012; 2016) and Bulpitt note, the party of government “will prefer to pursue their own interests and ... these may not be the same as the national interest or the interests of powerful domestic and external groups” (1983; 1986a: 184). Perspectives such as these further entrench statecraft theory and practice to realism. Morgenthau (1978), for example, argues that when there are problems between state and society it is the politicians that are responsible for addressing them. For Morgenthau, politicians need to think in terms of power. The meaning here is a simple one in that governing parties will still seek re-election even if it is to the potential detriment of the state. The result is the placing of the interests and needs of a select few over those of the masses and in principle is no different to the old idea of the Divine Rights of Kings (Philpott, 2016). However, given real-world dynamics it is fair to say that state crises come in many guises and often without warning; and the potential for secondary crises cannot be ruled out (Sheffer and Barak, 2009). Buzan, Waeber, and de Wilde (1998) argue that crises become existential threats to the state when they are not addressed. ‘Threat’ in this context equates to being a direct threat to the sovereignty or identity of the state which, by definition, includes a secessionist impulse. Where occasions such as these emerge, James argues, central government will change the “rules of the game” to suit (2012: 105). Where the

central government acts this way, it does so out of necessity. When this is the case, the indication is that central government has found itself in a position that it has to alter rules and regulations to suit, and so achieve statecraft.

Critiques of the literature

When developing his works, Bulpitt had asked how the Conservative Party sought to gain office and then govern satisfactorily so to retain office, and do so within the structures of British politics (1986: 21). The effect, however, is that much of his work on statecraft revolves around the Conservative party and the non-political elites (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; 1996; Hennessey, 1986; Sampson, 2004; Buller and James, 2012a; James, 2016; 2018). This section offers a critique of this perspective and in doing so, considers the nuances of theory and their application to the real-world as well as the contending explanatory approaches to long and short-term politicking as factors in preserving the status quo.

A primary criticism of statecraft theory is the difficulty of using the theory to weigh statecraft levers in terms of their importance in any one case. A similar point comes from Bradbury and John who complain that the dual polity is vague and has “no fixed meaning” (2010: 300). Ayres et al concluded something similar when they suggested that statecraft theory is undermined by a “rhetoric-reality gap” (2018: 853). Continuing this line, Bevir argues that Bulpitt “explicitly rejects” the languages of “constitutional designs” and “formal powers and functions” because they “neglect political processes” (2010: 11). For him, statecraft acts as a substitute for the legal limitations of the state - the tendency being that the elites will also act outside of any “formally defined roles and relationships” (Bevir, 2010: 11). Bevir furthers that actions such as these risk debate over the centre/periphery becoming a distinguishing feature of UK territorial politics (Bevir, 2010). The result, he asserts, is self-defeating in that it undermines the notion of a unitary state, and instead promotes the idea that the UK is dominated by “a complex matrix of diverse and negotiated patterns of rule” (Bevir, 2010: 12). Bevir’s (2010) works indicate a need for statecraft theory to be updated, and regularly. His work reflects the structural constraints placed on statecraft consequent to a more-diffuse state, one that has within it devolutionary systems of various styles, design, and importance. Buller (1999) offers an alternative perspective in that the purpose and focus of statecraft should be on political ideas and how they are put into practice. Hopkins (2011) believes the theory to be a guidebook for statehood, with statecraft being a one-stop-shop for aiding our understanding of both theory and practice. James (2016; 2018) however, believes

statecraft theory should focus on the recent trend toward personality politics and the implications for the UK system of a presidential style of politics. Regardless, the general consensus is that a primary objective of statecraft theory should be to assess how perpetuation can occur in a system where politicians are held to account, democracy. This includes political responses to the necessity of winning an election then keep on winning, as way for securing the status quo (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; Foley, 2004; Buller and James, 2012a; Hayton, 2014; James, 2016; 2018).

A further criticism of the literature is the position of the Conservative Party as a central player in the theory. Compared with the Conservatives, Labour may have spent far less time in power, but its legacy is unrivalled in terms of social reform. But for Nairn (1977), a traditional weakness of the Labour party has been its habit for considering the public sector as neutral which is a non-sequitur, given the inherent interest of the wider state system in preserving the status quo. The upshot is that for the Conservatives, power comes first and foremost in all governmental decision-making, whereas the same cannot necessarily be said about Labour (Gamble, 1998; 4). Thatcher, for example, is still considered to have been an “exceptionally forceful leader” who focused on whether or not her colleagues were “enemies or friends”, meaning that in practice there was no middle ground (Gamble, 1993: 117). She is also considered to have been “driven by political expediency, making short-term tactical moves to win elections rather than being a leader driven by an ideological *raison d’être*” (Bulpitt, 1996: 1097; Stevens, 2002; Hayton, 2014). That said, Stephens (2002) notes that whilst politicians have a limited shelf life and sell-by date, so too do ideas. The argument there is intellectual denial by the Conservative membership that Thatcher’s ‘brand’ “had played itself out” by the 1990s (Stephens, 2002: 122). The totality of these dynamics, for Marsh, Smith, and Richards, is a narrow expression of democracy, one where more credence is given to institutions than to “ideas and culture” (Marsh et al, 2003: 310). For them, the long-term impact of this style of governance has resulted in a “conservative notion ... [in which] government knows best” and a system that has an “obsession with strong, decisive, necessary action with limited scrutiny” (Marsh et al, 2003: 310-312). The consequence is that voters are canvassed on their opinions only on relatively rare occasions and only when any vote is likely to take place when the central government has judged that its position will prevail, the recent fixed-term Parliament arrangement aside. Although this situation does not necessarily create diminished accountability, there is a direct impact to be had on the social contracts operating across the UK space. The overall effect, for Bradbury and John, is that

Bulpitt's work relied heavily on Conservative "continuity and tradition" and is "self-referential" - and is based on opinion rather than a testable hypothesis (2010: 200). The result is that, for James (2016), Bulpitt's work doubles up as a history of the Conservative Party. Indeed, it is for this reason that Bradbury and John labelled him a "tory" (2010: 305). In fairness to the Conservatives, however, that they form a central position in the literature is to a considerable degree reflective of their success at the polls. Particularly since Salisbury developed his codes for government, the UK been twice has been twice as likely to be governed by a Conservative administration as opposed to one from any other party.

There is one further criticism of the literature, and it comes from Bulpitt himself (Marquand and Seldon, 1996). It is the idea that "in any period [structure will] grind out or deliver, a natural rate of governability" (Marquand and Seldon, 1996: 1096). The natural rate of governability, or the decaying capacity to govern effectively over time, presents as a departure from his earlier works in that a "purely structuralist explanation of political behaviour is either possible or on offer" (Marquand and Seldon, 1996: 1095). Further to this, Rawnsley (2010) posits symmetry between the natural rate of governability and economic stability: the more difficult the economic conditions, the lower the governability of the central government, and the more its political leaders become boxed in by events. Added is the reality of a tired government, the challenge of which is exposed when confronted by real-world, a weak or ineffective response indicates the natural rate of governability. In reality, this is Bulpitt recognising the effects of post-1945 declinism on the UK, the economic fallout and the effects on governing. However, whilst governments remain fixated on winning elections, every politician has their own professional life expectancies to manage. The inevitability, however, is that the political party in power will become fatigued, with the result being an electoral loss and a period in opposition.

Chapter summary

The Bulpittian perspective built on earlier literatures that focused largely on the elites and the establishment (Hennessey, 1986; Sampson, 2004). Developed over one hundred and fifty years ago, the codes were intended to enable a Victorian Britain to be capable of recapturing the halcyon years of Empire. What Bulpitt did was to move the narrative away from the 'who' to the 'what' and 'how', and his works have since been built on by James (2012; 2016; 2018) and his neo- arguments on rule bending. Today, statecraft is multi-faceted and a machinery available to the state to help it achieve its political and institutional objectives

(Bulpitt, 1983; Morgenthau, 1978; James, 2012; 2018; Kissinger, 2014). For the politicians, however, what this insight means is that every action or decision taken by the central government needs to be tested against whether or not statecraft is being achieved. In layman terms, this means evaluating policy action against the electoral effect (Bulpitt, 1983). The result is that today in the UK, the primary purpose of statecraft is as a tool for aiding the party of government stay in power (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986b; James, 2012). This is the status quo that today, and the machinery of statecraft is geared towards its preservation. Nonetheless, there is a complex mix at play here. Nonetheless, as an exercise, statecraft entails a managed adjustment to the routine of government. These often extend beyond survivalist considerations and employ both established and sometimes novel initiatives intended to satisfy an array of personal, party (including broader establishment), or national interests, each always at play. The real world effect is Conservative party predominance over the long term. Indeed, since Salisbury, the UK has been twice as likely to be governed by a Conservative Prime Minister as of one from any other party. That is clearly a factor in why statecraft theory has been described as a history of the Conservative party (James, 2016; 2018).

Party colours aside, the ‘art’ of statecraft is founded on a deep understanding of two things. First, how policy impacts and limits central government manoeuvrability; and second, how to mitigate those impacts and limits. But, if we take into consideration the UK’s record post-1945 it informs of a greatly diminished state compared to its zenith years of the late nineteenth century. Pointon (1980) argues that Salisbury’s ideas for government were premised on four policy pillars: Empire, Imperialism, Christianity, and capitalism. However in the time since, Empire has been dismantled and Imperialism is no longer practiced. And with Christianity no longer having the pull of yesteryear, all that remains is capitalism. At the time of writing the state may be intact but its diminution, and the associated state performance record, must factor into a weakened statecraft practice, and one that not only lacks strategic direction but is determined through short-termism. The overall effect for this thesis is that contrary to the Bulpittian idea that statecraft is about winning elections, instead, statecraft is defined to be those machineries available to the UK elites whilst they respond to real-world events as they seek to perpetuate the status quo. This change in emphasis indicates that that established definition tells only a bit of the story.

As is outlined in the next chapter, statecraft practice has evolved in a way that seeks to portray politicians in a presidential image, having a profound effect on how the media covers politics. The discussion there forms part of a wider discussion on the seeming fragmentation of the UK space where the constituent countries of the UK and its populations are pulling in different directions.

Chapter three: the fragmenting space

Chapter two outlined that the years since WW2 have not been kind to the UK. Being on the victorious side in 1945 has proven to be a pyrrhic victory. War left it exhausted, weakened, diminished, and largely helpless to avoid the dismantling of its Empire (Kissinger, 2014). The long-term effects have left the state weakened both internally and externally, Increased infrastructural demands have only added to state strain and at a time when the public finances have been impacted by a faltering economy, itself compounded by inflated debt, reductions in trade, and a reduced and unstable workforce (Emmerson et al, 2016; Springford and Portes, 2023; Islam, 2024). Nonetheless, the endless reconfigurations and interactions that take place between human groups in the socio-cultural, political, legal, and economic spheres sometimes manifest through competing identities tied to a defined territory. It is a reality that most states must live with even though the majority of them wrongly consider themselves to be nation-states (Farley, 1986; Smith, 1991). The result is that most of them have experienced some level of secessionist impulse meaning that the cohesive national image that states project into the world are rarely reflective of reality.

Jessop (2018) suggests that the state is not a single institution. It does not exercise power per se and the actualisation of power is manifested through a collective that hold office across the infrastructure of the state and to this end, the state is the sum of its parts (Jessop, 2018). This perspective is relevant to the UK given that in the late 1990s the state reformed itself to include devolution in its make-up, specifically for Scotland, Northern Ireland and Wales, with England being the exception. For Leith, the effect was that UK was no longer alone in its space (2006: 11). However, as is noted in this chapter, these structural reforms have not quashed or dented any aspiration for secession in the respective countries and, instead, have served only to embolden them. What is now clear is that in the UK numerous bodies and institutions are present, with each of them practicing statecraft in their own jurisdictions and domains, and the practice there may not be congruent to the aspirations of central government. To this end, this chapter notes the potential that government now has to compete with an array of second-tier actors so to achieve statecraft. This proliferation means that statecraft is more multifaceted than the literature suggests and that UK statecraft is no longer practiced solely by the central government or state elites. At the same time, politicians continue to present the aforementioned idea of a cohesive nation-state, and are increasingly reliant on the media to achieve not just this outcome, but to show politicians operating in high

politics (Buller and James, 2012a, 2012b; Griffiths, 2016 (b); James, 2018). Today, image and spin, as well as other aspects of news management, are now considered to be an integral management component with much of it designed to reinforce a political class firmly positioned within the realm of high politics (Buller and James, 2012a, 2012b; James, 2018). It is to this emerging aspect of statecraft that this chapter first turns its attention to.

UK statecraft and the media

Recent years have seen statecraft theorists take a greater interest in the relationship between politicians and the media (Buller and James, 2012a, 2012b; Griffiths (b), 2016; James, 2018). This section looks at the evolution of this trend, its underlying theories, the resultant presidentialism that now forms a part of the UK's political landscape, and the potential consequences.

Over the past thirty years or so, broadcast media has experienced a post-deregulation revolution, primarily via satellite television, and dedicated channels including twenty-four-hour rolling news (Hopkins, 2011; Turow, 2016). Added, the past two decades have also experienced an explosion in the numbers of social media platforms that help inform citizens about events both locally and globally. This is a world-wide phenomenon to which the UK is not immune, the result of which has led to social media now playing a major role in informing content output in both the broadcast and print media (Sterrett, Malato, Benz et al, 2019). Of all forms of media, it is the print media that despite its decreasing circulations has been largely consistent in its operating model across the time period of interest to this thesis - included in this premise is the assertion that the print media has recently been acting as an echo chamber for social media. The result is an easily consumable stream of information that flits between 'lies' and 'bullshit' (Frankfurt, 2005; Hughes, 2016) within which, governmental news management is a pre-requisite to achieving statecraft. This insight is particularly important given the shift away from statecraft as a strategic driver to a short-term approach that centres on winning the next election (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986; James 2012; 2016; 2018).

Political news management has emerged as a major feature of statecraft strategizing, particularly since the late 1990s and is a role that is commonly overseen by spin doctors (Foley, 2004). Found at the heart of government, spin doctors work as facilitators of the central government message. Their functions are twofold - to maintain dominance in the

public discourse, as per argument hegemony, and to strategize selling the message on offer, as part of electoral strategy, so to win elections (Bernays, 1928; Bulpitt, 1983; 1986; Osborne, 1999; 2004; James, 2012; 2014; 2016; Tatham, 2015). Spin doctors have emerged at a time when the overall ownership of the media is being monopolized, with ownership now held in a very limited number of hands (Farrell and Cupito, 2010; Haywood, 2013; Chomsky, 2016). With spin doctors are directly employed by the politicians meaning that neither civil servants nor elected officials have limited say in party-political and governmental news management processes (Haywood, 2013). Haywood adds that although there is a code of conduct that regulates these special advisors, concern remains regards their accountability. This concern is not misplaced when it is remembered that Andy Coulson, a spin doctor working for David Cameron, was simultaneously in the pay of both the UK government and News International (BBC, 2011).

Insights such as these led to accusations that the UK media was being sequestered as an external tool of statecraft. Philo (2013), for example, argues that UK Border Agency reality television programmes had been financed by central government. These developments are not a legacy of Cameron's time as Prime Minister. Indeed, the practice has deep roots within UK governance dating back over decades. Indeed, Osborne (2004) has argued that the Blair government was actively involved in news management. He claims that the Sun newspaper ran a number of stories critical of the government's position on immigration. The existence of a Downing Street media matrix that mapped out the Sun's reportage - story, narrative, and angles - had been planned weeks in advance as part of a strategy for controlling the news agenda (Osborne, 2004). Thomas (1998) also notes similar suppressive tactics during the both the Falklands War in 1982 and the thirty year insurgency in Northern Ireland. In both cases, the news had been subject to governmental interference, including suppression and slanting of stories to suit government policy. Insights such as these serve only to reinforce the theories of news management outlined by Herman and Chomsky (1988), particularly their theory on fear ideology. This practice is not new, similar manipulative practices can be traced back over a hundred years to the work undertaken by the likes of Edward Bernays and Walter Lipmann at the US Committee on Public Information when a sceptical public was convinced through a concerted media campaign to support US involvement in World War One (WW1) (Bernays,

1928; Tye, 1999)²³. The hint is that these types of practices are not new. What is new, however, is the associated manufacturing of public personas that equate image and personality with competence (Buller and James, 2012a, 2012b; James, 2018). This insight is particularly relevant given that from time to time, government will face crises or loses control of events (Bulpitt, 1983; Gonzalez-Herrero and Smith, 2010). Where this is the case, government moves into fire-fighting mode and the short-termism mentioned in chapter two can become further entrenched (Bulpitt, 1983). However, there is also the potential that how a crisis is managed and/or sold to the public can itself become a story, particularly if the crisis is fast moving and government is unable to keep up with events or the spreading of alternate narratives (Gonzalez-Herrero and Smith, 2010).

Nonetheless, as a trend, this personalisation and presidentialist approach to statecraft had been weaponised by Tony Blair (Foley, 2004). Foley adds that Blair successfully “elevated the role of individual leadership into a defining value of New Labour” (2004: 293). This Blair ‘brand’ led to his taking ownership of the Labour party, its leadership, its manifesto, and its action in government (Foley, 2004). Price (2006) suggests that the Blair era was dominated by vain politicians who focused mostly on image, especially with respect to perceived competence. Adopting a presidentialist persona is deemed to help portray the “status, role and meaning of a prime minister’s position” that fits into this new media environment (Foley, 2004: 292). This tactic tends to be bent towards a positive image that revolves around the perception of “strong executive authority” (Foley, 2004: 292). Foley further argues that what is essentially a personalised approach to statecraft is now concretised in the political system “to an unprecedented degree” (2004: 295). The result is a form of personality politics that has acquired a life of its own with the result being a mutually beneficial arrangement between the political classes and the media (Buller and James, 2012a; James, 2016; 2018; Hayton, 2014). That said, James (2016; 2018) sees Blair in a positive light and argues that he had a sense of both conscience and cunning, with both aiding his successfully communicating personal ideals through the media to the electorate. Through routes like these, it is claimed, the public are offered direct access to politicians and are better informed as a consequence (Zaller, 1999). Bolted onto this presidentialist approach is the idea that party leaders will play along in this environment and partake in the ‘promotion of the personal’ (Bulpitt, 1986b; Foley,

²³ Bernays is considered to be the ‘father of Public Relations’ (Tye, 1999). His ideas revolved around what has since been called public relations, so-called because ‘propaganda’ had acquired a negative connotation consequent to the First World War (Bernays, 1928; Tye, 1999). Bernays was involved in the CIA-led overthrow of the democratically elected government of Guatemala (Tye, 1999).

2004; Buller and James, 2012a; James, 2016; 2018). Frankfurt (2005) adds that in environments such as this one, there will be an expectation for politicians to have an answer for everything despite their having a lack of knowledge on the subject. The intention is to develop a sense of governing competence but as an approach it is not always successful but the end result is at one extreme “banality” and at the other, power without responsibility (Curran and Seaton, 1997; Torrance, 2017: 20). However, practicing politics in this way is deemed to do little for those politicians that do not want to play along or participate in a media practice that promotes style over substance (Bulpitt, 1988; Foley, 2004).

Overall, the final result causes “the Prime Minister’s position no longer to be even nominally reducible to a construction of parliamentary accountability, nor to being a pure derivative of party democracy” (Foley, 2004: 295). And with news ownership being held in the hands of a small number of the elites, what passes as news is increasingly based on narrower interpretations of events. And this point brings us to news consumers, or the UK audience which, it is argued, are treated like a “national ‘community’” (Torrance, 2017: 92), and where nationhood is subject to “continual flagging” so to provide a backdrop to the UK “political discourses” (Bilig, 1995: 8). However, as the next section outlines, the UK is little more than a jigsaw state that governs over countries and territories, each with their distinct social, historical, political, and nationalistic ideals.

Delineating the UK

As was noted earlier, most states see themselves as nation-states but few actually are (Farley, 1986; Smith, 1991; Kymlicka, 1995). Included in this cohort is the UK, which this section looks at in greater detail.

The UK’s current formation comes about as a consequence of historical legal Acts of Law - Union between England and Scotland (1707); Ireland (1800); and latterly, Northern Ireland (1922). The result sees the state governing over four²⁴ constituent countries, each with their own histories, identities, geographic boundaries, social contracts, and legal systems, Wales aside. Keating says that the UK is an ‘intellectual puzzle’ and goes on to label it as a state of nations (2021: 1-3). This is a small departure from his earlier works where he labels the UK as “a plurinational union” (Keating, 2018: 171). Even so, the assertion is a common one. For

²⁴ Wales was annexed by England in the 1500s and under executive laws created by Henry VIII (which are still on the statute books), Wales no longer has an independent legal system and has been subsumed into the English legal framework (Jenkins, 2014).

example, Rokkan and Unwin call the UK a “union state” (1983: 187), for Morgan (2006: 84) it is a “multi-nation state”, and for Leith and Soule it is a political system where nations have been “subsumed within a larger UK state” (2012: 41). Linguistic subtleties aside, the real-world effect is the existence of a state that governs over a series of competing ideas about sovereignty, territory, population, history, culture, identity, and order. In addition, the lack of a codified constitution has aided endless reconfigurations of both the structure and shape of the state, and of the social contracts in play within the UK space. As such, the holistic social contract in the UK is neither fixed nor unitary. Instead, it is found across a wealth of traditions, laws, statutory instruments, and judicial rulings, some of which date back centuries and, in some cases, remain specific to the originating country (Berlin, 1969; Devine, 2012; Allen and Thompson, 2002; Foster, 2006). Thus, the state appears able to shape-shift in response to the prevailing winds in the social-political sphere. In reality, however, the central government is not bound by a constitutional court and is free to conceptualise and draft changes to the social contract, and then embed them in law (Allen, 2014; UK Parliament, 2019; Institute for Government, 2020; Landmark Chambers, 2020; Miles, 2020; Storey, 2020)²⁵.

As for power, this resides in the hands of this close-knit cohort that has within it both competing and collective interests, and these may be fundamentally different to the interests of the UK’s constituent countries (Hennessey, 1986; Sampson, 2004). This practice remains ongoing, as though a willingness for central government to tilt the tables to accommodate elite interests when necessary is a permanent feature of UK politics (Allen, 2014; UK Parliament, 2019; Institute for Government, 2020; Landmark Chambers, 2020; Miles, 2020; Storey, 2020). Yet what is also clear here is that if we look at the level of accountability central government is beholden to, it is actually far less rigorous than we initially anticipate.

The Judicial Review and Courts Act (2022), for example, reduces the right of UK citizens to attempt a redress of grievance against prior state actions, meaning that the UK central government is now able to place its actions beyond legal scrutiny (Williams, 2022). At the same time, the central government also stands accused of undermining the various Acts of

²⁵ “The UK does not have a codified constitution. There is no single document that describes, establishes, or regulates the structures of the state and the way in which these relate to the people. Instead, the constitutional order has evolved over time and continues to do so. It consists of various institutions, statutes, judicial decisions, principles, and practices that are commonly understood as ‘constitutional’. The UK does not have a constitutional court to rule on the implications of a codified constitution, and the sovereignty of Parliament is therefore unrestrained by such a court” (UK Government, 2011: 2).

Union, including through the aforementioned Internal Markets Act (UK Government, 2020). Here, a direct correlation exists between departure from the EU and the deglobalised platform currently in play. Similarly, further evidence exists of the potential for dismantling of human rights legislation, the potential for juryless tries and the slow erosion of habeus corpus (Hansard, 2023). Added is the erecting of electoral barriers - for example, voter identification, as ways for undermining universal suffrage (Uberoi and Johnston, 2022). Here, it must also be recognised that the uncodified constitutional allows the UK to respond to pressure from below, resulting in some form of renewed social contract (Allen and Thompson, 2002; Foster, 2006). Indeed, this same flexibility aided the creation of the Scottish parliament and the other devolved institutions. One last point lies within the drafting of the first Cabinet Manual for Government (2011) which provided an updated delineation of the UK. There, the 'UK' is now a collective of four sovereign institutions - the London parliament, the Monarch, judiciary, and the executive (UK Government, 2011: 3). The four countries that make up the UK - Scotland, England, Wales, and Northern Ireland, are conspicuous by their absence and are not afforded sovereign power. Instead, their needs or requirements are addressed via political management of the dual polity, as discussed in chapter two.

Bulpitt argued a need for politicians to clearly differentiate high and low politics so to help the central government act autonomously and independently of its territorial and political periphery (1983: 96). His argument was that Thatcher had intended insulating the central government from peripheral issues that had dogged previous administrations and, he says, she had been successful in this regard and to a point that her government's role was limited to that of an "absentee landlord" (Bulpitt, 1983: 161). This insight suggests that the dual polity operated at the time combined with the aid of local authorities, central penetration and central control to maintain order and collect taxes. Simultaneously, Ayres et al add, to also "impose policy by legal means onto local authorities and other arms-length public bodies" (2018: 856). That, however, was in the era before devolution of which, Sandford, Ayres, and Flinders (2017) argue, whilst central government remains limited in their peripheral interventions, as a whole the state is more interventionist than it used to be. They add further than despite structural changes, government remains firmly fixed on the centre autonomy

model that Bulpitt (1983) had earlier identified and promoted. Even so, the dual polity appears to be guided by a new territorial management cod that centres on devolution²⁶.

State of the 'nations'

Chapter one outlined the potential that the UK possesses sufficient territories that if it were to collapse could cause a small secessionist wave that leads to near-on twenty new states emerge onto the international arena. As is indicated in Table 5, some of the UK overseas territories have already shown signs of secessionist impulses, though it is too early to assess the extent or sustainability of their respective impulses.

Whilst the overseas territories benefit from levels of autonomy not afforded to the four 'home' countries, recent developments have seen these four benefitting from enhanced local controls via devolution. For Ayres et al, devolution has created space for another model of territorial management via some form of local elite assimilation where "peripheral leaders govern on behalf of the central government and do so via a clear policy platform" (2019: 856). By the time Kilbrandon had²⁷ been published the UK had already enacted reforms intended to promote limited Welsh local decision making, and further legislation intended to protect and promote the Welsh language (Forman, 2002). For this reason, Forman (2002) argues, Welsh political manoeuvres tended to coalesce around socio-cultural autonomy rather than full blown political independence or, indeed, self-governance (Forman, 2002). Despite this position, Nairn (1977) has argued that Wales presents as an emerging country and for Forman (2002), the country has the potential to be simply more than a cultural antiquity. Nonetheless, an effect of Welsh political dynamics has resulted in Welsh support for independence lagging behind that recorded elsewhere in the UK. Indeed, current estimates indicate although backing for Welsh independence is growing, support still resides at around the thirty percent level (Paun and Hall, 2021).

For England, Kilbrandon also recommended a set of regional bodies so to enhance regional voices (HM Government, 1973). Nine bodies were suggested, with London benefitting from region-city status (HM Government, 1973). For Morrison (2013) progress towards devolved

²⁶ Sandford et al say that "localities are required to develop business cases for the handling of devolved powers, and to evaluate them against the terms of the 'devolution deal'. Through the terms and conditions of devolution, central autonomy is retained in place. Even when some devolution deals collapsed following stakeholder and public disquiet, the government did not deviate from this approach" (2017: n.p.).

²⁷ In the late 1960s and as a response to an increase in support for Scottish independence and reinforced by an upswing in electoral victories for the SNP, the UK government convened a Royal Commission on the Constitution (Kilbrandon Report) which went on to recommend a devolved Scottish parliament (outright independence was not in the Commission's remit) (UK Government, 1973; Wilson, 2017).

legislatures across England was extremely slow, to the point of being nugatory. In 1998 voters in the English North-East voted against its own dedicated assembly whereas in London, a referendum there led to the creation of the London assembly and a separately elected Mayor (Morrison, 2013; Tomaney, 2010; Sandford, 2013). The 2010s heralded an era of elected Mayors for English cities, with large local councils also being mandated to hold local referendums on the establishing of a Mayoral office (Sandford, 2013). More recently UK Parliamentary reform made space for a new England-only system of legislation. English Votes for English Laws (EVEL) had been intended to address a political paradox at the UK Parliament in which elected members from the three other constituent countries had been able to vote on matters that pertained only to England (UK Parliament, 2021). EVEL has since been repealed but, nonetheless, the effect was England temporarily having its own de-facto parliament, albeit one that sat on a part-time basis (Elliott and Thomas, 2020). Indeed, by default of devolution being installed elsewhere in the UK space, the UK Prime Minister and Cabinet at times, oversee and discuss England-only policies. Only recently have opinion pollsters began to ask questions on English independence. The results have reported near 50/50 returns (Business for Scotland, 2020). A similar polling record can be found when assessing Northern Irish irredentism.

Following the Irish secession from the British Empire and resultant partition of the Island in 1921, Northern Irish affairs had been overseen by a Governor, of a type found elsewhere in the colonial space up until 1973 (Bell, 2008). The Irish Catholic communities had experienced ongoing structural discrimination across the social, political, and economic, spheres (Lipset, 1959; Galtung, 1969; Honderich, 1973; Nairn, 1977; Derrida, 2002; Bell, 2008; Della Porta, 2008; Mansfield, 2011; Taylor, 2014). Resultant civil unrest led to the UK military being deployed to the country in 1969 as an attempt to maintain law and order. It was an event that coincided with the initial convening of Kilbrandon and which, ultimately, offered nothing of substance for addressing the situation in the country (HM Government, 1973; Wilson, 2017). For Taylor (2014), the reason lay with the parallel bilateral - UK/Irish - Sunningdale Agreement which mandated a number of cross-border initiatives and a referendum on irredentist secessionism. An irredentist referendum was held in 1973 but was boycotted by the Catholic communities, leading to a result heavily in favour of the status quo. By this time Northern Ireland was in the early years of the 'Troubles' which saw the proscribed Provisional Irish Republican Army (PIRA) emerge as a paramilitary force, and with this, Northern Ireland descended into insurgency. PIRA boasted sufficient numbers to

sustain an almost three decade long paramilitary campaign in support of Irish irredentism (Townshend, 1984; CGS, 2007; English, 2008; Taylor 2014). In the 1990s PIRA called two ceasefires so to allow the conclusion of peace talks that had been brokered by both the EU and the USA. In 2007, and after some thirty-eight years of ongoing operations, UK military deployment to Northern Ireland came to an end (CGS, 2006). As it stands the UK government is now committed to Irish reunification should it be supported by a majority of its electorate (HM Government, 2008). However, arrangement lacks an objective mechanism to test or advance local opinion sufficient that irredentism occurs.

Table 5: overseas territories

Referendums	Political settlement	Support for irredentism
Falkland Isles, 2013 sovereignty referendum: No	Overseas territory; Crown Dependency; British Antarctic	Impulses in Bermuda; Cayman Isles
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The UK retains remnants of its Imperial past. Fourteen overseas territories including three Crown dependencies and territory on Antarctica are represented by the UK in international relations, and also acts on behalf of the City of London. • Each individual territory offers the potential to become micro-states. • Many are tax havens and are hard-wired into the international financial system, and act as subsidiary bases to the UK whilst simultaneously benefitting from a level of autonomy and self-governance historically denied to the countries of the UK. • In 2013, the Falkland Islands held a sovereignty referendum and more recently there have been calls for independence referendums in Bermuda and the Cayman Islands. 		
Sources: Monbiot, 2011; Watts, 2013; McWhirter, 2019; CNS, 2020; Commonwealth Parliamentary Association UK, 2021		

Table 6: Wales

Referendums	Political settlement	Support for independence
1979: No 1997: Yes 2011: Yes	Devolution since 1999	65/35 against
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Having been annexed by England in the 1200s and fully assimilated into it in the 1500s, Wales traditionally has lacked a differentiated legal system.• In the 1960s the UK government enacted reforms intended to promote limited Welsh local decision making, and protect and promote the Welsh language.• Kilbrandon had recommended a distinct Welsh Assembly even though at the time there was little appetite across the country for self-governance, and indeed in 1979, the Welsh voted against having their own Assembly.• That position was reversed in 1997 when Wales voted narrowly in favour of an Assembly which was created a year later.• In a third referendum in 2011 Wales voted in numbers not previously recorded for their Assembly, increasing its responsibilities, including additional rights to change the law in Wales.• Plaid Cymru which, as was indicated in chapter one, has traditionally been the main driver for Welsh separatism; and it is only recently that the party has shifted its policy to advocate a more proactive policy on Welsh secessionism.• Current estimates indicate a one-third support for Welsh independence		
Sources: HM Government, 1973; Forman, 2002; Elias, 2009; BBC, 2011; Paun and Hall, 2021		

Table 7: England

Referendums	Political settlement	Support for independence
nil	Piecemeal devolution	50/50
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • England it does not have a devolved parliament, nor has its electorate been asked whether it should have one or not. • Kilbrandon recommended a set of regional bodies that could enhance the English regional voice. Nine bodies were suggested, with London benefitting from region-city status. • In 1998 voters in the English North-East voted against its own dedicated assembly whereas in London, a referendum there led to the creation of the London assembly and a separately elected Mayor. • By the 2010s a new policy was adopted that heralded an era of elected Mayors for English cities, with large local councils also being mandated to hold local referendums on the establishing of a Mayoral office. • UK Parliamentary reform made space for a new England-only system of legislation. EVEL had been intended to address a political paradox at the UK Parliament in which elected members from the three other constituent countries had been able to vote on matters that pertained only to England. EVEL has since been repealed but, nonetheless, the effect was England temporarily having its own de-facto parliament, albeit one that sat on a part-time basis. • Today, England is littered with regional and locally devolved systems of varying degrees of autonomy, in line with a piecemeal approach to political reform. • Only recently have opinion pollsters began to ask questions on English independence. The results have reported near 50/50 returns. However, there is no political outlet to advance this aspiration, nor is there any indication of an emergent impulse. 		
<p>Sources: HM Government, 1973; Morrison, 2013; Tomaney, 2010; Sandford, 2013; Business for Scotland, 2020; Elliott and Thomas, 2020; UK Parliament, 2021.</p>		

Table 8: Northern Ireland

Referendums	Political settlement	Support for irredentism
Irredentism 1973: No Devolution 1998: Yes	Devolution since 1999	50/50
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Following the Irish secession from the British Empire and resultant partition of the Island in 1921, Northern Irish affairs had been overseen by a Governor. • The Irish Catholic communities had experienced ongoing structural discrimination across the social, political, and economic, spheres. • Ongoing civil unrest resulted in the UK deploying its military to the country in 1969 as an attempt to maintain law and order. It was an event that coincided with the initiation of Kilbrandon and which, ultimately, offered nothing of substance for addressing the political situation in the country. • The parallel bilateral - UK/Irish - Sunningdale Agreement which mandated a number of cross-border initiatives and a referendum on irredentist secessionism. • The ‘Troubles’ saw the proscribed PIRA emerge as a paramilitary force. PIRA boasted sufficient numbers to sustain an almost three decade long paramilitary campaign in support of Irish irredentism. • PIRA was capable of operating on a number of fronts - not only in Northern Ireland or wider UK but also as far afield as Germany and Gibraltar. Its ‘England Department’ was created to take the war direct to the heart of the UK government, inflict economic damage sufficient that the UK presence in Northern Ireland unaffordable. • The 1993 Downing Street Declaration committed the UK and Irish states to peaceful irredentism should there be sufficient popular support. In response, PIRA suspended its military operations so further negotiations took place. However in 1996, after two years of stagnation, PIRA resumed its campaign. A second ceasefire was brokered in 1998, this time aided via EU and US support. The Good Friday Agreement catalysed a reformation of the Northern Irish political system, as well as lever the disarmament, demobilisation, and reintegration initiative. • In 1998 the electorate in Northern Ireland voted via referendums in favour of a devolved Assembly with equal representation between communities. • In 2007, and after some thirty-eight years of ongoing operations, UK military deployment to Northern Ireland came to an end. As it stands the UK government is now committed to Irish reunification should it be supported by a majority of its electorate. 		
<p>Sources: Galtung, 1969; HM Government, 1973; Townshend, 1984; CGS, 2006; Bell, 2008; Della Porta, 2008; English, 2008; HM Government, 2008; Mansfield, 2011; Taylor, 2014; Coniam, 2021; Review Panel in Northern Ireland, 2022.</p>		

Similar to England and Northern Ireland, Scotland is another UK constituent country to record 50/50 polling records on independence. In 2014 an independence referendum was held on independence from the UK. This next section considers events leading up to the referendum, starting with an explanation of Scottish politics, post-1945.

NB: a more in-depth explanation on secession and separatism in England, Overseas territories, Northern Ireland, and Wales can be found in Appendix 3.

Scotland post-1945

The SNP was formed in the 1930s and won its first Parliamentary seat in 1945 a few months later in a general election (Douglas, 1996; Lynch, 2002; Finlay, 2016). Latterly, the campaign for independence shifted into territory that today would be referred to as direct action. For example, in 1950 Westminster Abbey in London was broken into and the Stone of Destiny taken and returned to Scotland.²⁸ SNP activists also set up Radio Free Scotland, an illegal broadcast service that broke into the BBC's analogue television frequency to broadcast pro-Scottish propaganda; and a Covenant calling for independence was signed by almost a half of the Scottish population (Hamilton, 2008; Lynch, 2016). Adding to the wider debate at the time was the 1953 case of *MacCormick v Lord Advocate* where there, it was adjudged that “the principle of unlimited sovereignty of Parliament is a distinctively English principle and has no counterpart in Scottish constitutional law” (1953 SC 396).

Indian administration

Nairn (1977) argues that the Irish secessionism in the 1920s had been a catalyst for the burgeoning secessionist impulse emanating out of Scotland. However, his assertion regards the influence of Irish secessionism may not offer the full picture for the shift in mood in Scotland he says it did. Consequent to decolonisation and the dismantling of Empire, it is clear that Scottish secessionists had more than one case to refer to when attempting to advance their cause. As an issue, it is a point that Sorens (2012) picked up on when arguing that a national identity is insufficient as a secessionist catalyst in its own right. He argues that “only when identity is coupled with interest does a popular desire for independence come about” (Sorens, 2012: 6), and that appears to be the case with Scotland. Regardless, what is evident is that by the 1960s Scotland had begun to display the signs of a sustained secessionist impulse and in 1967 the SNP recorded its second UK Parliamentary electoral victory, taking nearly half the vote (Leith, 2006; Dalyell, 2016). Bulpitt also notes that in the

²⁸ The 1320 Treaty of Arbroath claims that Scots came from Scythia, a space located roughly to the north of where we would have found the Fertile Crescent (Ellis, 2006). The story goes that Scotland's ancestors were nomads having been forced out from their homeland. They travelled westwards and would soon be joined by others, including two sisters, Scota and Scotia, who are said to have been daughters of an Egyptian Pharaoh. It is via them from where Scotland is said to get its name (Society of Antiquaries of Scotland, 1871; Ferguson, 1998; Ellis, 2006; Steinberg, 2019), and the daughters are said to have brought with them the Stone of Destiny. And in the 500s BC these nomads are said to have settled in what is now Scotland (Ferguson, 1998; Steinberg, 2019). Scottish Kings had previously sat on the Stone during their coronation but during the Wars of Independence around seven hundred years ago. The Stone was recovered and returned to London (Hamilton, 2008).

same year the SNP won over a hundred seats in the Scottish local council elections (1983: 195). The consequence for Bulpitt was that there had been some acceptance within the central government that "some degree of governmental autonomy was required" as a concession to Scotland (1983: 141). However, whatever the changes government proposed to Scotland, they served only to further distinguish Scotland administratively from the rest of the UK.

Nonetheless, the Conservatives appeared to be caving in the electoral pressures emanating out of Scotland. In 1968, Conservative leader Ted Heath made what became known as his 'Perth Declaration'. This was a surprise announcement committing the Conservatives to an elected Scottish Assembly (Bulpitt, 1983). And whilst the UK government remained "hostile" to Scottish devolution, it responded in 1969 with a Royal Commission on the Constitution (Kilbrandon) (UK Government, 1973; Bulpitt, 1983: 183; Wilson, 2017).

Heath became Prime Minister in 1970 and in 1973, Kilbrandon was published. It recommended a dedicated parliament for Scotland, with law-raising powers, and the closure of the Scotland Office (HM Government, 1973; Wilson, 2017). Despite his earlier rhetoric, Heath did nothing. A year later in 1974 the Labour Party returned to power. There were two general elections that year and in both, the SNP increased its representation in the House of Commons, from two to seven in the February general election, then eleven in a further general election which took place in the October (Lynch, 2002; Mitchell and Hassan, 2016). Overall, the party came second in near-on half of the Scottish constituencies and recorded the support of a third of the Scottish electorate (Bulpitt, 1983: 182; Lynch, 2002). It is in this time frame where we see the emergence of an early and alternate political leadership, as per Wood (1981), and it was their job to give institutional expression to the secessionist impulse. As for a governmental response to Kilbrandon, this took a further five years to develop and progress the legislation through which a referendum on Scottish devolution could be held.

For Bulpitt, the advent of Scottish devolution meant that Westminster needed to alter the dual polity. Of devolution, he said that it:

Was not meant to represent a radical break with the traditional territorial order, but rather a reconstruction of much of the old system of hived-off territorial administration via the indirect rule of local or regional collaborators, albeit within a new institutional and constitutional straitjacket (1983: 190).

The straitjacket that Bulpitt talks of was in keeping with the idea that states will not countenance a political change that would “result in their dismemberment” (Sorens, 2012: 14). As it turned out, the Labour government found it difficult getting the legislation through the UK Parliament. Government lost control of its legislation and watched as a series of backbench Amendments served to undermine its manifesto pledge on establishing a Scottish parliament, including one instructing the government to hold a referendum to test Scottish opinion. From there, “wrecking” Amendments were tabled (Leith and Soule, 2012: 8), one of which required an additional forty percent threshold of the total Scottish electorate to vote in favour of a parliament before government was obliged to act (Drucker and Drucker, 1980; Callaghan, 1987; Leith and Soule, 2012; Mitchell and Hassan, 2016). The referendum was eventually held in 1979 and whilst a majority voted in favour of a Scottish parliament, failure to meet the threshold rendered the result irrelevant (Dalyell, 2016; Mitchell and Hassan, 2016). The consequence was Scotland continuing its being subject to “Indian administration” (Bulpitt, 1983: 97).

Labour lost the 1979 general election, heralding in the Thatcher government which initiated a programme of economic and financial reform (see chapter two, Table 2). The result was the winding down of the large monopolistic nationalised industries many of which dominated a host of communities, including Scotland’s central belt (McInnes, 1995; Gibbs, 2016). Change caused Scotland to experience the fastest decline in the industrial world, with unemployment more than doubling, compared to 1970s levels, leaving whole communities reduced to poverty (McInnes, 1995; Gibbs, 2016). By this time Scotland had also become an oil-producing country but the revenues went to the UK exchequer, so direct material benefit to Scotland was limited (Gray, 2014). For Gray, Scotland became something of a milch cow. Resultant social inequalities and a lack of an equitable settlement prevailed, as did a hint of grievance, which in turn helped foment social attitudes in favour of independence. However, it was the Labour party and not the SNP that capitalised on these conditions (Sorens, 2012; Gibbs, 2016).

A third Thatcher election victory coincided with a Conservative rout in Scotland where, by comparison, Labour recorded a landslide victory (Sorens, 2012; Gibbs, 2016). The results helped radicalise Labour’s Scottish contingent (Hassan, 2004), some of whom called for Scottish MPs to not return to Westminster and instead, set up base in Edinburgh. This did not happen and instead, in what was largely a performative gesture the bloc staged a one-day

walk-out of the House of Commons (Alexander, 2005). Labour was also central to the convening of the Scottish Constitutional Convention in 1988 and a redrafting of the 1689 Claim of Right²⁹. The SNP's only capitalisation from this era was a by-election victory in Govan, Glasgow in 1988 (Mitchell and Hassan, 2016).

The 1992 general election saw the Conservatives win its fourth election a row. In Scotland, Labour continued its by-now long-term stranglehold of Scottish politics. As for the SNP, it recorded a modest improvement in its vote share (Rallings and Thrasher, 1993). In the same year John Smith became Labour leader and his short tenure³⁰ helped see in an era, albeit a brief one, when Scots dominated the highest offices of the land (Devine, 2012). This cohort included a number of leading Scots-born politicians, all from the Labour party - Brown, Cook, Darling, Dewar, and Robertson, and to this cohort we can add John Reid, and Lord Irvine of Lairg who, collectively, were pledged again to create a parliament for Scotland with law-making and tax-raising powers (Labour Party, 1997). These, and their party colleagues, won the 1997 general election. Within a month of taking power, the new Labour government introduced legislation for a second referendum on Scottish devolution to be held later in the year (HM Government, 1997). Unlike in 1979, this referendum was to be decided solely on the simple majority principle.

The 1997 referendum saw Scotland voting overwhelmingly for a parliament with tax-raising responsibilities (Devine, 2012; Dalyell, 2016; Leith and Sim, 2020), and in 1999 a Scottish parliament convened for the first time in three hundred years (BBC, 2009). However, Kilbrandon had also recommended the closure of the Scotland Office and all oversight for Scotland transferred to this parliament and that did not happen. The Scotland Office has remained in situ, affording central government a continuance in its oversight of Scotland. Ultimately, London would retain for itself a series of reserved powers, all of them strategically important to achieving statecraft in both the domestic and international spheres (HM Government, 1998). This was no standalone legislative body: the Scottish parliament served as an arm of the state. The legislative sanction is inscribed on the Scottish parliament Mace. "There shall be a Scottish Parliament", it says, with the caveat being "Scotland Act 1998" (Dewar, 1999: n.p.; Scottish Parliament, 2021). The limitations of the Scotland Act were tested one month later when the UK central government unilaterally moved the

²⁹ Many of the modern-day signatories included a number of Labour's leading Scottish figures (Priddy, 2016).

³⁰ Smith died in office in 1994

maritime boundary between Scotland and England and annexed around 6,000 miles sq. of Scottish waters to the benefit of the English jurisdiction (HM Government, 1999; Murray, 2012). The Scottish parliament was powerless to block the move, and with this the “straitjacket” that Bulpitt had talked about was there for all to see (1983: 190).

What this episode informs is that parliament or not, sovereignty over Scotland continued to reside elsewhere (McDonald and Hazell, 2007). In the next section considers events in the timeframe of the Scottish parliament and in doing so, Scotland offers as a textbook case of secessionist parties ending up running devolved governments.

To a third referendum

The Labour party topped the first Scottish election in 1999 and formed an administration (Alexander, 2005). The SNP took second spot, ahead of the Conservatives and the Liberals. Eight years later in 2007, the SNP replaced Labour as the largest party and formed a government (Mitchell and Hassan, 2016). One of the first acts of this new administration in 2007 was to change its name, from the Scottish ‘executive’ to ‘government’. Upon assuming the role of governing party, the SNP’s Salmond administration, made preparations for state formation (Brooke et al, 2018). Included here was a series of infrastructural builds - roads, railways, hospitals, as well as numerous reforms to social policy (Borders Railway 2021; NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde, 2021; The Forth Bridges, 2021; Unger, 2013). However, the SNP government did not have it all its own way. The Calman Commission was an example of how the secessionist political sphere can be counterbalanced by opposing political forces.

Legislated for by a combination of the Conservatives, Labour, and LibDem Members of the Scottish Parliament (MSP/s) in the Scottish parliament, Calman intended reviewing Scotland’s devolution settlement (Holden, 2010; Wilson, 2017). On the surface, any additional transfer of responsibilities from the central government to a devolved institution represents further travel in the direction towards independence - all the while further concretising the Scottish cleavage within the UK space (Wood, 1981; Sorens, 2012). However, in Calman, the dual polity was again in action. The result was the offloading of some of the more administratively cumbersome tax responsibilities overseen by the UK, for example, aviation and landfill. But again, Calman also failed to adhere to Kilbrandon and fell short of suggesting either full fiscal autonomy for Scotland or the closure of the Scottish

office (Holden, 2010; Wilson, 2017). Congruent with Kilbrandon, Calman did not entertain the potential of independence. In some respects, however, this decision would prove irrelevant because in 2011 the SNP retained office at the Scottish election, this time achieving a seemingly impossible overall majority (Leith and Sim, 2020).

Subsequent negotiations between the Scottish and UK governments led to the 2012 Edinburgh Agreement on an independence referendum, to be held in September 2014 (UK Government, 2012). The question was a simple one: should Scotland be an independent country? At the time opinion polling indicated that around a third of the Scottish electorate would vote 'Yes' to independence (UK Polling Report, 2014). At the same time it was discovered that, unbeknown to the UK government, a part of the British Antarctic Territory had accidentally been devolved to Scotland, including the granting to the Scottish government a veto over any alterations (Hansard, 2012). The SNP was concerned that central government would use the issue as an excuse to review the devolution settlement (Hansard, 2012). But in reality, the uppermost concern in Westminster was the potential of an independent Scotland having ready access to a rich wealth of natural minerals and deposits (Hansard, 2012). Nonetheless, a referendum on Scottish independence was on the horizon and all sides needed to organise.

The lead-up to the referendum also saw a tendency for the media to interview establishment grandees and invite their opinion to the Scots electorate (Graham, 2014). And although the Monarch is traditionally viewed as being above politics and apparently does not comment on it, it is a legal fallacy - the Monarch is an inherently political role, s/he is merely above party politics. Yet, it cannot simply be coincidence that when the Monarch has made subtle commentary it has happened only in times of political tension, including in the run up to the 1979 and 2014 referendums (BBC, 2013; Ashcroft, 2015). Indeed, a similar occurrence took place in the lead-up to the 2016 referendum on UK membership of the EU (Woodcock, 2016). Robertson (2014) adds that a typical media tactic to frame the binary referendum question as a party-political one - the effect being that reportage would include commentary from Conservative, Labour, and LibDem representatives and only one representative from the SNP or wider Yes movement, thereby providing a reportage equating to a three-to-one bias against independence. He adds further that media reportage during the precipitancy tended to focus heavily on the perceived effects of independence on the Scottish economy (Robertson, 2014). As an approach, it is commensurate that resonated with Wood's (1981) assertion

concerning the importance of economics to the precipitancy. Arguably, however, these tactics had not worked because as the referendum date neared, the polls continued to narrow and for a brief period, recorded a majority in favour of independence. The response from the three main UK party political leaders was to publish, with the help of the *Scottish Daily Record*, a last minute ‘vow’ offering an enhanced devolution settlement if Scotland voted to retain the status quo (Pike, 2015; McHarg, McMullen, Page, and Walker, 2016; Keating, 2020). The vow was drafted amidst a backdrop of claims that the media had been biased against the independence campaign (Robertson, 2014; Blain et al, 2016; Schlesinger, 2000). This perception was catalysed, in part, by misleading reporting on the BBC of a press conference hosted by First Minister Alex Salmond, and led to a mass demonstration outside the BBC studios in Glasgow (BBC, 2014). A few days later, Scotland voted fifty-five to forty-five in favour of remaining in the UK.

Chapter summary

The UK is legally distinct from the four countries and other territories over which it governs (UK Government, 2011). Constitutional reformation, the UK occurs less from a cataclysmic or revolutionary event and, instead, take place when “cracks” appear in the system (Wright, 2004: 870). Indeed, the rationale for Kilbrandon was to perpetuate the unitary model of the state and do so in such a way that it accommodated local and regional governance (HM Government, 1973). However, given the slippage of state responsibilities from the centre to the periphery in the devolution era, it may be fair to refer to the UK as is today as a “regionalised unitary state” (Alder, 2010: 117). The result is a myriad of sub-state parliaments, assemblies, Mayoralities, et al, each with their own distinct set of responsibilities, each of which was overseen by a form of local elite assimilation where local elites undertake state functions within distinct jurisdictional and geographical areas (Ayres et al, 2018). To this end, the state merely wallpapers over them and as an approach, it has been sufficient to address changes in the social discourse without the integrity of the state being overly threatened (Farley, 1986; Blackburn, 2016). As an approach, however, may not be sufficient in the future because whilst chapter two noted the UK’s decline on the international stage and in international relations, it also recorded a comparatively similar performance in the domestic space. There, a gradual splintering of the collective sense of unity has left UK politicians fire-fighting in a number of fronts - economic, fiscal, infrastructural, political, and social (Emmerson et al, 2016; Ashcroft and Oakeshott, 2018; UK Government, 2021; Springford and Portes, 2023; Islam, 2024). The culmination has resulted in UK economic

indices recording their worst in state history (Romei and Giles, 2021). The domestic effect, as has been outlined in this chapter, is four constituent countries pulling in different directions. That said, previously, there is a strain in the literature noting that devolution helps catalyse further rises in support for secessionist-supporting political parties, leading to their practicing government, albeit at the devolved level (Wood, 1981; Sorens, 2012; Griffiths (a), 2016). England boasts fifty percent support for independence but with no party-political or devolved vehicle to advance this aspiration, the indication is of a large untapped political market. As for Scotland, at the time of writing it continues to be governed by a secessionist supporting party, as does Northern Ireland where there, the irredentist Sinn Fein topped the elections held in 2022 (Burton, 2022). Arguably, and with a clear majority in favour of the status quo, Wales appears the most loyal of all four home countries. This trend has persisted in spite of an expansive statecraft practice that now provides a polished and managed news media campaign. Any inherent message to encourage mass unity is not working, with only the Welsh being most susceptible to this message.

Nonetheless, Scotland is the focus of the next chapter and there, a question is raised in respect of how Scotland's secessionist impulse has been influenced by internal and external statecraft. Included in the next chapter is a conceptual framework that will guide this thesis towards offering a response.

Chapter four: counter-leveraging Scottish secessionism

Sovereignty is intangible and is nothing more than an idea perpetuated through laws and arms and has implications for both the domestic and international arenas. In reality, it is a mere set of cognitive conditions sufficiently coherent that it provides the state a level of authority to govern over a population and territory and do so with legal and moral legitimacy (Kantorowicz, 1957). To this end, theory states that consolidated power does not readily yield to argument. Indeed, the roots of this practice are not new and are traceable back over four thousand years, dating back to Akkad (Grayson, 2000; Coggins, 2016; Podany, 2018a; Podany, 2018b). As such, it is also not a new observation that states seek power and having acquired sovereignty, the state will expect obedience (Wolff, 1990: 20; Boitani and Torti, 1999; Baylis and Smith, 2001; Mearsheimer, 2001; Lake, 2003; Oppenheim et al, 2008). To this end, this chapter is concerned with the status quo and its preservation. To this end, this chapter is about realism, and about how power is wielded, particularly in an environment where the state has arbitrary control over the laws that are intended to constrain its actions.

This chapter seeks to outline the legal vacuum that underpins the political rather than the legal dynamics that underpin both the UK and Scottish independence. From there, secession is explained through the lenses of constructivism, liberalism, and realism, the result being an indication for the potential that external statecraft, traditionally a mainstay of international relations, is now playing out in the domestic setting consequent to amongst others, devolution. The culmination is a conceptual framework that outlines how the literature portrays the political response of the state to Scottish secessionism as it passed through the preconditions, rise/movements, and into the precipitancy. The conceptual framework feeds into an attempt to help address evident limitations in the literature on statecraft, particularly in respect of how Scottish secessionism has been influenced by internal and external statecraft.

Legal vacuum

This section looks at the legal framework for secession both in international relations in respect of Kosovo and comparatively in the UK, regards Scotland. This section notes that, given the lack of lack of legal guidance in either realm, Scottish secessionism resides in a legal vacuum. There is nothing in the UK constitution for either retaining the status quo nor is there stopping Scotland from leaving. With the same applying to international relations,

Scotland resides in a legal vacuum. There is, however, political pressure, and of a type capable of undermining an independent Scotland not recognised by a remainder UK (rUK).

Kosovo first unilaterally declared its independence in 1992 (Bieber and Daskalovski, 2004), with very limited success in terms of international recognition. This first attempt at independence led to war with Serbia and a later international intervention. A second attempt in 2008 was more successful in terms of recognition but the matter ended up being heard in the ICJ (ICJ, 2022). The case had been brought by the UN General Assembly which had asked whether or not was “the unilateral declaration of independence by the Provisional Institutions of Self-Government of Kosovo in accordance with international law” (ICJ, 2022). The ICJ concluded that “the declaration of independence of Kosovo adopted on 17 February 2008 did not violate international law” (2022: n.p.), with the consequence being that via Kosovar independence “international law contained no prohibition of declarations of independence” and that consequentially international law did not preclude unilateral declarations. (ICJ, 2022: n.p.). As such, for the ICJ “the scope of the principle of territorial integrity is confined to the sphere of relations between States” (2022: n.p.), and that by consequence, secession is a domestic matter.

Several dozen states submitted advisory opinions to the ICJ, including the UK which argued that the Kosovar UDI did not breach international law (HM Government, 2009). The UK’s favourable argument premised on the potential that acts of secession are not “excluded” from international law. Consequentially, it argues, the Kosovar UDI “did not violate international law” (HM Government, 2009: 5.7). In terms of the need for secessionists to adhere to domestic law the UK argued further than:

In most if not all cases, provincial or regional authorities will lack the constitutional authority to secede... the conditions do not include compliance with the internal legal requirements of the predecessor State. Otherwise, the international legality of a secession [sic] would be predetermined by the very system of internal law called in question by the circumstances in which the secession is occurring In most cases of secession, of course, the Predecessor State’s law will not have been complied with that is true almost as a matter of definition (HM Government, 2009: 5.5-5.8).

These comments have since been seized upon by supporters of Scottish independence when arguing for a Scottish UDI, particularly in the years immediately following the UK’s departure from the EU (Murray, 2018; 2019; 2021). The Former Diplomat Craig Murray, for example, quite correctly stated that as a consequence of the ICJ/Kosovo case, “the domestic

law of the larger state cannot constrain the right to self-determination of the nation or people wishing to leave” (2021: n.p.), and he notes the UK not being immune to this legal loophole. Murray also adds, however, that “if the state seceded from could simply forbid it, a great deal of decolonisation would never have happened” (Murray, 2021: n.p.), and that “Latvia, Lithuania, and Estonia, would still be in the Soviet Union”. His posture here, however, may not be quite an accurate one because the Soviet constitution did include the right to secession; it merely lacked a mechanism or legal instruments for achieving it (Lenin, 1929; Unger, 1982). Indeed, this is the same position that Northern Ireland is in. As for Scotland, it has no similar mechanism for advancing its independence. That aside, it is evident that there is nothing in international law that precludes Scotland from seceding from the UK and, as is further indicated, the same applies in the domestic setting.

Tierney (2017) says that Scottish secessionism resides in a legal vacuum where the issue is more to be addressed by politicians and not the lawyers or barristers. He asserted his position in regards the ability of the Scottish parliament in unilaterally holding an advisory referendum on independence. At the time he wrote “as a legal scholar whose disciplinary inclination is to identify a legal problem and think about a legal answer. But what we are confronted with here is a political problem which demands a political answer” (Tierney, 2017: n.p.), and this is an important point of note because in 2021 a case brought to the Scottish Court of Session in Edinburgh requested:

A declarator of the Court, that the Scottish Parliament has the power to legislate for the holding of a referendum on whether Scotland should be an independent country, without requiring the consent of the UK government or any further amendment of the Scotland Act 1998” (Forward as One, 2021: n.p.).

The case revolved around the issuing of a Sec. 30 Order, an instrument of the Scotland Act (1998) that had been used in 2014 to facilitate the transfer of authority from the UK government to the Scottish parliament so it could administer the independence referendum. The case was brought by a collective called ‘Forward as One’ which argued that the Scottish parliament did not need to adhere to the Scotland Act (1998) in this respect. The Court dismissed the case on the grounds that its purpose was not to adjudge hypothetical scenarios saying, in effect, that the matter was a decision for the politicians³¹. The Court did say,

³¹ A Bill may or may not be introduced, depending upon the Government formed as a consequence of the election if introduced, a Bill may or may not be passed by the Parliament, depending upon that institution’s composition ... The UK Government may or may not be prepared to obtain an Order in Council under section 30 of the 1998 Act, which would, in any event, allow the Bill to proceed to Royal Assent (Judiciary of Scotland, 2021: n.p.).

however that “if the Bill were passed without such an Order, it is highly probable that the UK Government’s law officers would refer the Bill for scrutiny by the UK Supreme Court” (Judiciary of Scotland, 2021: n.p.). This is what happened in 2022 when the Scottish government drafted but had not as yet tabled a Bill on holding a referendum on independence without the benefit of a Sec. 30 Order (Torrance, 2022). The matter went to the UK Supreme Court which unanimously concluded that through holding a referendum that questioned the UK constitution the Scottish government will have breached UK reserved powers. It then said that outwith a Sec. 30 Order “the Scottish Parliament does not have the power to legislate for a referendum on Scottish independence” (Torrance, 2022: n.p.). This position, however, is not the same as denying Scotland the ability to achieve independence because outwith the Supreme Court case the vacuum that Tierney talked about is alive and well. At no point has this thesis detected in the court cases or indeed, the academic literature, commentary on the existence of either an objective a route to independence or for preserving the status quo. Simply put, they don’t exist. As such, a barrister could argue that a Scottish UDI would not violate UK law - an easy task given that very same outcome was achieved at the ICJ (2022) in respect of Kosovo. To this end, this section considers the enhanced importance to the issuing of a Sec. 30 Order.

This thesis insists that Sec. 20 offers a dual purpose: primarily it is concerned with the transfer of authority to hold a referendum on independence to Holyrood; but secondly, in doing so, a Sec. 30 Order facilitates a rUK policy on recognising an independent Scotland but the same outcome should not be expected in the event of a Scottish UDI. And to this extent, a Sec. 30 Order is merely a tool for conferring constitutive recognition from a future rUK Government to an independent Scotland. Without it, rUK can be expected to withhold recognition of an independent Scotland. An action of this nature would leave Scotland in no different a position to Kosovo or for that matter, Taiwan. In short, Scottish secessionism resides in a legal vacuum that is present in both the domestic and international arenas. A Sec. 30 Order does little to deny Scottish independence. Instead it is a tool for limiting the routes to independence whilst preparing the ground for a lack of rUK recognition of an independent Scottish state in the event of UDI. Through this lens, a Sec. 30 Order is a political instrument and not a legal one, thereby reinforcing Tierney’s (2017) legal vacuum.

Political power comes via the acquisition of sovereignty over a people and a territory and having acquired sovereignty, the state will act to preserve the status quo (Morgenthau, 1978;

Wolff, 1990; Baylis and Smith, 2001; Mearsheimer, 2001). Consequentially, were rUK to act as described when faced with a Scottish UDI it would be deemed to have adopted a realist posture. To do otherwise, realists argue, would be acting against the best interests of the state. This next section explains theories of international relations and their association to statecraft.

Internal and external statecraft

As was noted in chapter one, medieval scholars viewed man to be “asocial” and willing to “trample on reason and logic in order to secure for himself immediate, momentary advantage” (Schmitt, 1996: 36). Schmitt added that “the more dangerously this asocial individualism asserts itself, the stronger the rational necessity for reaching a general peace” (1996: 36). Here, Schmitt is replicating a very limited Hobbesian view of humanity where each and every one of us is considered at heart to be primal - regardless of wealth or strength (Wolff, 1990; Boitani and Torti, 1999; Mearsheimer, 2001). This perspective ends up promoting a socio-political hierarchy that has a sovereign at the helm, one backed by law which is used to promote fear in the populous as opposed to affection (Wolff, 1990; Boitani and Torti, 1999). This position is a necessary prerequisite for any sovereign which, from a Machiavellian (2017) perspective, means the drafting of good laws that themselves need to be backed by good arms. To this extent, sovereignty is practiced through incontestable authority of a kind not unlike the Divine Rights of Kings (Philpott, 2016). Where a state is not successful in this endeavour, there can be no ultimate authority and thus, sovereignty is open to contestation. Schmitt says equilibrium is vital here. However, he defines ‘equilibrium’ as “compulsion”, aided by a hierarchy that pressurises the population to conform and submit to the status quo in perpetuity (Schmitt, 1996: 36). Perspectives such as these are more likely to be found in realist schools of international relations and the political sciences.

Whilst Westphalia formed the basis for relations between states and helped create the idea of the ‘international’ as a way of explaining relations and interactions between states (Ozkirimli, 2000: 58), the fundament on which it rests is territory. In essence, it means the exercise of political authority in four areas - territory, autonomy, control, and mutual recognition. Control in these four areas form the basis for Westphalian sovereignty (Elrod, 1976; Kegley and Wittkopf, 1981; Krasner, 1999; 2001; Kissinger, 2014). To this end, realists argue that sovereignty holds the international system together (Baylis and Smith, 2001; Walt, 1998; Krishna-Hensel, 2013). Realists also argue that states are the authors of their own destiny. They can never rely on no-one but themselves for their existence (Baylis and Smith, 2001;

Mearsheimer, 2001). Realists also argue that anarchy in the international system ensures that there is no higher authority than the state and there is nothing to stop states simultaneously holding or advancing policies that are completely contradictory to one another. For example, the UK holds different positions on the secessionist events in both Kosovo and Crimea (HM Government, 2009; UK Government, 2018). The associating issue is Russia and the intention of the UK to act out of self-interest through seeking to undermine the international standing of the Russians. At the same time, Russia's refusal to recognise an independent Kosovo means that UN and, consequentially, European Union (EU) membership remain out of reach. Kosovar UDI is unique in that it has been adjudged legal under international law, as per a recent ICJ ruling (HM Government, 2009). Whether the (parent) state survives or not should be irrelevant. This is realism, and it is perfectly legal. However, the effect of the secessionist precipitancy is that the state becomes wholly reliant on its peers for its existence, and this is an occasion where realism is yet to account for any meaningful way. Clearly, as an explanatory framework for international relations, realism has its limitations and this is an important insight given the endless reconfigurations and interactions that take place between human groups. These can be found across the socio-cultural, political, legal, and economic spheres and at times sometimes manifest as identity differences tied to a defined territory. It is a reality that most states must live with (Farley, 1986; Smith, 1991). The effect, for Kantorowicz (1957) is that the existence of an overt sovereign authority does not mean an end to domestic contestation, to the extent that the majority of citizens and/or other states conform to it.

Moravcsik (1997) asserts that liberalism has helped to create and maintain the social contract through offering a direct link between society, state, and the international arena. Society, and the individuals within, does not have a contract with government, so it is for the people to decide the depth of their freedom, the width of their liberty, and how much power is granted to government (Rousseau, 1973; 1998: 99). This position acts as the original premise of the social contract which Rousseau argued, "the human species, is divided into so many herds of cattle, each with its ruler, who keeps guard over them for the purpose of devouring them ... man is born free but everywhere he is in chains" (1998: 5). These understandings owe much to the politics of US President Woodrow Wilson and the work of Norman Angell. Angell's (1910) paper on war as a false economy argues that there is little benefit of conquering new territories, as was the business of Empire. The liberalist frameworks reviewed here grew out of the elevation of self-determination as a political ideal. Woodrow Wilson that placed human

rights at the forefront of an international commitment to reform the social contract but it was after WW2 when the frameworks were developed. Here, there is little doubt that the imperial mindset was a factor in industrial-scale murder during WW2, combined with the idea that international regulation could have prevented such gross excesses, contributed to the drafting of the UN Charter (Hopkins, 2000; Zimmerman, 2006; Blatman, 2014). Charters such as this are considered by liberalists to encourage a peaceful co-existence across the international system (Evans, 1998; Baylis and Smith, 2001; Kegley and Wittkopf, 2001; Brecher and Harvey, 2002; Pugh 2005; Kalkman, 2011). As an influence, the UN Charter was not lost on Buchanan (1997) who had asserted reforming the international legal system offered strength to the idea of self-determination as a remedial right. However, the evolution of the post 1945 international legal system has not been perfect. Starkey (1965) noted early on the potential for loopholes being built into the system that allowed states to usurp or bend international law to their favour. The basis for that claim is one that Buchanan (1997) had also touched upon. He stated that Article 1 of the UN Charter (1945) had been written as a narrow interpretation of international practice. This was problematic he argued, because what it meant was that international law had arbitrarily limited self-determination to the colonial context. He continued that “international law does not recognise a right to secede in other circumstances, but that it does not unequivocally prohibit it either” (Buchanan, 1997: 33).

At this juncture it is worth recalling that the core thrust of constructivist theory is the advancement of ethnic or nationalist identities through geographic or local associations (Bookman, 1994). Situations such as these are particularly relevant where these same identities act as competition to that which is promoted by the state. Disgruntled peoples also frequently question whether they are likely to become more prosperous or not as an independent state than under the status quo (Bookman, 1994)³². Constructivist explanations are, in the main, focussed on the idea that society, historical memory, ethnicity, felt nationality, and a host of other, essentially non-political factors impact the international arena (Onuf, 1989; Chandra, 2001a; 2001b; Checkel, 2008). Onuf (1989) contends that whilst states continue to operate out of self-interest they do so not because they are of an inherently realist hue but, instead, they seek out other states that possess similar ideologies and seek to form alliances with them. This approach to geopolitics serves to support, and sustain partnerships

³² This issue has already been highlighted in respect of Catalonia, but the same could also have been said for Yugoslavia which had adopted a more centralised economic system where the impact of reform was felt on its richer territories, namely, Croatia and Slovenia (Bookman, 1994).

between states (Checkel, 2008). Checkel (2008) also notes, however, that these same decision processes help fuel inter-state rivalry. As a perspective, it is reminiscent of Waltz's (1959) premise that inter-state rivalries are themselves, influenced by history and culture to an extent that they play a part in the form of anarchy that persists in the international system. The result is any limitations placed on states by the international community can only really go so far because international law is made by states for states, and to this end, and again, realism remains a powerful explanatory theory for many of the larger dynamics in international relations. Indeed, this position, in essence, is the default position for all states regardless of their rationality or validity of political contestation (Morgenthau, 1978; Philpott, 2016). However, given the presence of the liberalist Kantian Triangle (consolidated democracy, liberal practices and policies, and peaceful co-existence) in domestic spaces in the West, there are in fact two types of sovereignty in play, external and internal (Krasner, 1999; 2000; Gilady, 2017). External sovereignty is deemed to insulate the state from the realities of international anarchy whilst internal sovereignty dominates the domestic arena (Krasner, 1999; 2001; Lake, 2003). Explanations such as these, Adler (1997) argues, creates space for a middle ground where competing explanations of international relations can co-exist and offer validity simultaneously in the same case studies.

Nonetheless, regardless of the social contract in place, what is also evident is that states are becoming more adept at repelling secessionist impulses, as per recent trends (see chapter one, Figure 2) (Sorens, 2012; Keating and Wilson, 2014). One possible cause is another recent trend, namely the imposition of some form of autonomy through devolution - having previously been tested via a confirmatory plebiscite (Wood, 1981; Sorens, 2012; Griffiths (a), 2016; Qvortrup, 2019). The combination of devolution referendums, the devolution experience, and latterly, another referendum on independence, as per the Scottish case, hints at the potential of referendums acting as tools of a counter-secessionist statecraft strategy (Keating and Wilson, 2014). Whilst there have been a number of independence referendums in the past decade, not one has resulted in a viable secessionist event³³. If this is an accurate

³³ Disputed Ukrainian/Russian irredentist events aside (Donetsk and Luhansk), the last territory to experience a secessionist event and subsequently receive international recognition was in 2011 via the creation of the independent state of South Sudan (Thomas, 2015; BBC, 2022). The results of similar referenda in 2017 in both Catalonia and Kurdistan were not recognised by either the state or via international relations and in both cases the status quo has prevailed. Recent cases where territories have reached the precipitant stage of secession but have stepped back include French Caledonia which has held two referenda in the past few years (Carine and David, 2020). Bougainville, an autonomous region of Papua New Guinea, bucks this trend (Regan, 2019). Its people voted for independence in an internationally brokered referendum that was held in 2019. However, at the time of writing the Papua New Guinean state is yet to honour the result (Regan, 2019).

interpretation then regardless of equilibrium or the quality of the Kantian triangle, the domestic space is dominated by realism.

Statecraft is geared towards perpetuating the status quo. As such, it is an inherently realist tool explained through five levers - argument hegemony; governing competence; party management; electoral strategy; and bending the rules (see chapter two). These five represent a set of abstract concepts for grouping together sets of political actions. Theory describes how statecraft is deployed and used by those in power, together with wider, often non-political elites. Together, they comprise as “internal statecraft” (Hopkins, 2011: 93). However, the advent of presidentialism and overlaps with the media, as well as devolution, hint at the existence of an external quality to statecraft in the UK’s domestic setting. Sequestration is another external control that the state possesses and there, it is not beyond reason to consider that government will guide or determine the policies of a third-party for political means (Boyer, 2000). This same practice was noted in chapter three in respect of the role of the Royal Bank of Scotland (RBS) in shaping the UK governmental policy towards the finances of an independent Scotland (McWhirter, 2014; Pike, 2015). If, as Hopkins (2011) says, Bulpittian statecraft is ‘internal’ then, by definition, actions such as sequestration are ‘external’ and in terms of statecraft, represents levers that are not under the direct control of central government or wider elites. To this end, external statecraft is accomplished by employing those levers outside the immediate control of government. As a theory, statecraft remains subject to changes brought about by everyday events and it is entirely feasible that the literature is unable to keep up with the evolution of the real world. Secession represents an existential threat to the state but it has been offered scant regard by the literature. Where statecraft and secession meet, a heady mix will be found that draw in a series of secondary topics: devolution; elections; banking and finance; franchise administration; governing policy; journalism; legislation; nationalism; party policy; primordialism; rebellions; referendums; social class; social movements; and, zealotry.

Overall, the effect is that there is nothing of value in the literature on statecraft that can assist in reviewing how the elites respond to Scottish secessionism while they seek to perpetuate the status quo. Taylor (2019) offers relevance here. The assertion there is that where a structure for analysis does not exist, one needs to be created. This is the purpose of the next section.

From accommodation to suppression

Easton argues that the “study of politics is concerned with understanding how authoritative decisions are made and executed for society” (1957: 383). He adds that political theory can be used to create conceptual frameworks that, by consequence, serve to inform political theory. The purpose of this section is to create a conceptual framework that monitors the ebb and flow in the intensity of the UK statecraft response towards Scotland’s secessionist impulse over its lifetime, and in a structured way.

Easton further commented that as a requirement, differentiating political systems from their contexts and that viewing political systems in isolation allows them to be viewed as a “self-contained entity” that is distinguishable from the operational environment (1957: 385). Wood’s (1981) comparative framework of secession, as outlined in chapter one, has a part to play here. The framework offers a secessionist trajectory as one side of a binary environment that contains not just the evolutionary stages of a secessionist impulse but also the state-centric counter pressures. Given this insight, there are two points to be noted about Wood’s (1981) conceptual framework and its relevance to this thesis. The first is that the campaign for Scottish independence has, apart from isolated low-level incidents, been wholly engaged with the democratic process. Therefore, Wood’s (1981) fifth stage concerning armed conflict can be ignored. The second point concerns the third stage of the framework, which he labelled as the response from central government (Wood, 1981). It is within this third stage that this thesis is located and for this reason, is focused on understanding the response from central government and how internal and external statecraft have influenced Scotland’s secessionist impulse. To do this, and in line with Easton (1957), a counter-secession feedback loop was created which by definition, must exist if the state is to preserve its integrity from secessionist pressures.

In effect, and whilst the potential is there to map out the evolution of Scotland’s secessionist impulse over time, this thesis is more concerned with the response of the UK government and elites to Scottish secessionism, in terms of internal and external statecraft, and in the same time frame. The result is a review of three of Wood’s (1981) five stages of his conceptual framework of secession, viewed as a continuum - the preconditions, rise/movement, and the precipitant stages of secession - and investigate how the UK has employed its statecraft levers at those times (Easton, 1965; Kaplan, 1957). In effect, this thesis is offering a unique

explanatory framework for helping to understand how Scottish secessionism is influenced by internal and external statecraft which, in doing so, will help address a weakness in the literatures on statecraft in respect of secession in general, and based on the UK response to Scottish secessionism.

UK statecraft in the preconditions

At the outset it is worth noting that that the earlier discussion on constructivism has relevance here. Bookman (1994) argues that a core component of constructivist theory is the linkage of a multitude of ethnic, nationalist, historical, and other influences that offer some form of geographic association (Bookman, 1994) (see chapter one). Within this scenario is deep-rooted competition over the national identity that is promoted by the state versus the one promoted locally (Onuf, 1989; Chandra, 2001a; 2001b; Checkel, 2008). This is the typical experience for most states given that most face some form of nationalistic, ethnic, or religious cleavage that causes them to face or experience a secessionist impulse to some degree or other (Farley, 1986; Smith, 1991). However, whilst there may be social disgruntlement, secessionist impulses during the preconditions stage remain relatively low-level, but it may have sufficient prowess to damage the governing party in elections (Wood, 1981; Bookman, 1994; Sorens, 2012). The consequence is that politicians remain focused on winning elections and appearing to present as competent in government (Bulpitt, 1986a; Hopkins, 2011).

The party of government has at its disposal argument hegemony to project political ideas on to the people sufficient to dominate the party-political discourse and reinforce the state-centric status quo so to recreate a sense of enduring legitimacy (Easton, 1965; Wood, 1981; Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; Morgenthau, 1978; Mearsheimer, 2001; Kissinger, 2014; James, 2016). The overall effect is that in this early secessionist stage a main driver of the response from government is to retain a focus on a “winning rhetoric” and in a variety of locations (Bulpitt, 1986a: 21). In all but-name this means a party-political focus and essentially, ‘business as usual’. The implication here is that popular culture can influence the local discourse, resulting in secession being “presented as the solution to the challenge of peaceful coexistence between distinct peoples” (Collier and Hoeffler, 2002: 37). Nonetheless, for secessionist movements and states alike, the competition for meaning to peoples’ lives is the embodiment of Stanton Rowe’s (1897) need for national unity. It is through here, it is argued, where people acquire a sense of belonging (O’Donnell, 1997: 11; Barker, 2005).

Figure 5: statecraft in the preconditions

Overall, however, the literature on secession asserts that in the preconditions stage, the response from government will revolve around argument hegemony, governing competence, and electoral strategy (Wood, 1981; Bulpitt, 1983), as indicated in Figure 5, and these insights make up the first stage in the conceptual framework.

UK statecraft and the rise/movement

The evolution from the preconditions includes occasions when a movement is consolidated in the public consciousness, and the arrival of a leadership team, It is their job to front the campaign and act as the main ideologues for sovereign change (Wood, 1981). Ostensibly, their job is to mobilise the affected population, convince them that their futures are best served as an independent state, and create cleavages between them and the wider masses (Buchheit, 1978; Wood, 1981; Sorens, 2012). This is a much easier task where the movement and leadership are emerging within a state that practices democracy, a central component being an overlapping liberalist agenda for shaping the social contract (Moravcsik, 1997; Gilady, 2017). As a part of that process, the movement and its leadership will need to create an effective organisational structure. Without it, Wood (1981) argues, any impulse is likely to have only a limited and short-term impact on the political status quo. Viewed through a Bulpittian statecraft lens, any state intervention at this time should be focused on retaining legitimacy in the status quo which, again, is reinforced predominately through continued success at the ballot box (Bulpitt, 1983; Hopkins, 2011; James, 2016).

The advent of devolution has served only to increase the numbers of elections that political parties now fight. This is the case in Scotland, the wider UK, and across the globe where devolution is used as a tool for accommodating and suppressing secessionist impulses. The effect, as Sorens (2012) has noted, is the creation for a system of second class sovereignty which, in doing so, reinforces the liberalist ideal that states are not the only actors in international relations (Baylis and Smith, 2001; Wolfrum, 2007). Nonetheless, this sub-state

evolution can cause status quo supporting parties problems in that they become vulnerable to defections to the benefit of the secessionist movement. To do nothing at this stage could have a detrimental impact on the party and various personal interests, as well as feed into the complex world of statecraft, via inflating the potential of counter statecraft forces which also play out a realist agenda.

Figure 6: statecraft and the rise/movement

Even so, central government is still unlikely to face a secessionist crisis. As indicated in Figure 6, above, as support for secession grows, leaders emerge, and the wider campaign becomes an active, consistent political force, the deployed statecraft levers are the same as in the preconditions period but with one difference - that party management needs to be strengthened in order to avoid the aforementioned defections.

UK statecraft in the precipitancy

This work now reaches the eventual zero-sum when there is a distinct possibility that the state might fracture, leading to a newly independent state (Wood, 1981). As such, this stage is shaped through realism. The primary argument of realists is that once having acquired sovereignty political actors operate in a way that helps ensure the perpetuation of the status quo. This practice in the extreme is not unlike the compulsion that Schmitt (1996) when talking of society begin compelled by the state. Realists argue that states are the authors of their own destiny and are unable to rely on any other state or actor for their existence (Baylis and Smith, 2001; Mearsheimer, 2001). The result is an international system that is populated by self-interest and competition (Baylis and Smith, 2001; Mearsheimer, 2001; Lake, 2003; Kissinger, 2014). Theorists also argue that the state would rather fight than pass on power (Kaplan, 1957; Easton, 1965; Morgenthau, 1978; James, 2016; 2018). This insight is particularly relevant to the secessionist precipitancy where it is acknowledged that the outcome is unknown and unpredictable (Wood, 1981; Sorens, 2012; Griffiths (a), 2016).

Realists expect the state to operate under conditions that in the UK is referred to as acting in the national interest (see chapter two), and this means rule bending (Wood, 1981; Ponting, 1987; James, 2016; 2018). This practice, however, is not restricted to the UK and as was evidenced in 2017 in Catalonia where the Spanish government, despite signing up to international agreements on human rights, exacted violence on local citizens seeking to vote in a referendum on independence (Ponsati, 2020). In more general terms, however, rule bending offers several possibilities in respect of tilting the electoral system in favour of the government of the day. And insights such as these offer relevance where secessionist impulses are more commonly tested via referendum (Sorens, 2012; Atkinson et al, 2020). That said, James (2016; 2018) argues that the institutional architecture is vulnerable to politically expedient manipulation so to make winning easier and, thus, achieve statecraft. In addition, a below-the-belt election campaign cannot be ruled out (Lijphart, 1984; Qvortrup, 2000; James, 2016; 2018). Overall, the anticipation from the conceptual framework is that rule bending takes precedence, legitimated through concentrated and directed argument hegemony which, it was noted in chapter two, is a constant (James, 2016; 2018). The result is visualised in Figure 7.

Figure 7: statecraft in the precipitancy

To this end, this thesis has noted the scant attention paid to Scottish secessionism in the literatures on statecraft. As such, and even though Scotland has already experienced the precipitancy, it remains unknown how Scottish secessionism has been influenced by internal and external statecraft. Nonetheless, given the state’s disposition towards survival, the expectation is that the closer a secessionist movement progresses towards independent statehood the state will move towards a hardened realist position intent on maintaining the status quo (Kaplan, 1957; Easton, 1965; Morgenthau, 1978; Wood, 1981; James, 2016; 2018). If, as Pavkovic and Radan claim, Wood’s (1981) works offer “*universal*” validity the same should apply to Scotland (2011: 175).

Chapter summary

Ker-Lindsay (2012) argues that when faced with a secessionist event, the state will pursue legal and political routes available to it in international relations so to maintain its integrity. This includes undermining the viability of the secessionist state through not recognising it, encouraging others to act similarly, whilst also considering legal routes. In essence, this means drafting support from its peers, including friendly or allied states, as well as those other states with a third-party interest in ensuring the geopolitical status quo (Easton, 1957; Krasner, 1999; 2001; Baylis and Smith, 2001; Mearsheimer, 2001; Lake, 2003; Oppenheim et al, 2008). That this is the case presents a problem for scholars of realism given that theory explains that the state has nothing but itself to rely on for its own survival (Morgenthau, 1978; Krasner, 1999; 2001; Baylis and Smith, 2001; Mearsheimer, 2001). At the secessionist precipitancy, however, and by co-opting other states in affirming their recognition of the status quo, the state becomes wholly reliant on its peers for its existence. As such, recognition of a secessionist event comes down simply to a constructivist political decision; one-by-one and case-by-case. At the same time international law will offer nugatory advice and guidance (HM Government, 2009; ICJ, 2022). To this end, the secessionist precipitancy is a point in time that the literatures on realism are yet to account for in any meaningful way. That said, realism also dictates that the state should be prepared to use force so to maintain its integrity (O'Brien, 1999; Tushnet and Khosla, 2015; Morgenthau, 1978; Baylis and Smith, 2001). Ultimately, when push comes to shove, the state will exist for no other reason than to simply ensure its own survival.

Acting out of necessity, or the national interest as it is called in the UK (see chapter two), effectively places the interests of the state over those of the people (Ponting, 1987). This basic premise for action lies in the practice of Parliamentary sovereignty, which along with necessity and the monopoly on the use of force, have spread across the globe and now form as a basic condition of the contemporary state (Morgenthau, 1978; Mearsheimer, 2001; Kissinger, 2014). To this end, Spanish action in 2017 can be deemed to be an act of necessity, the same in respect of prior UK military activity in Northern Ireland. These were also acts of statecraft, specifically rule bending (James, 2012; 2016; 2018). Rule bending forms a part of an increasingly complex domestic operating environment where multiple actors compete and co-operate dependent on the issues at hand.

The difficulty for scholars of statecraft lies in keeping up with developments, this thesis' compartmentalising of statecraft into their domestic-facing internal and external qualities being a casing point. Another is devolution which, until recently, been paid scant regards by a literature that remains largely Westminster-centric. Presidentialism is another, and so too is the centrality of Scotland to the status quo. The result of this literature review is the exposure of numerous limitations in the literature on statecraft, with the reality that despite its being an existential threat to the state, coverage of Scottish secessionism remains extremely limited. Via the subsequent investigations, this thesis seeks to help address this gap in our knowledge by reviewing how Scottish secessionism has been influenced by internal and external statecraft. And as has been stated, the expectation is that the closer a secessionist movement progresses towards the precipitancy the more likely the state will respond with hard-line realist tactics, in line with the conceptual framework. The next chapter explains how criminalistics can be helpful in this regard.

Chapter five: method

This chapter explains the method for investigating how Scotland's secessionist impulse has been influenced by internal and external statecraft. As is explained, the investigations relies on a qualitative approach that centres on grounded theory as an approach for developing new explanations and theories, itself borne of an evidence-based standpoint (Glaser, 1978; Charmaz and Thornberg, 2020). Three cases were selected for investigation. They emerge out of the narratives outlined in the literature review and focus specifically on the correlations between statecraft, secession, separatism, and referendums. The primary focus is three parliamentary debates and their content - two of which took place in the UK House of Commons (1978 and 1997) and the other in the Scottish parliament (2013), and the newspaper reporting thereof. All three had been convened to discuss electoral legislation to hold referendums on both devolution (1979 and 1997) and outright independence (2014). The debate investigations involved interrogating Hansard transcripts and were undertaken via process tracing and relied on hoop tests for identifying the causal mechanisms and eventual causal inferences to each of the three investigations (Beach, 2012).

Newspapers published at the time act as a second set of archival sources. This debate reportage was also interrogated and analysed, this time using grid analysis. The empirical basis for claims and findings are outlined and discussed across chapters six, seven, nine, and ten. As is explained in this chapter, the exercises produced over one hundred and eighty codes that manifest as in-text strings and which form the basis for the responses to the hoop test questions that were developed for this thesis. Ultimately, the methods used for this investigation confirm that this thesis is premised on a piece of inductive research that interprets qualitative data numerically.

A qualitative study

This section outlines the philosophical and theoretical influences that shape the investigations undertaken for this thesis. This section asserts the usefulness of qualitative research in investigating under-explored areas of the political sciences (Corbin and Strauss, 2015). As is also explained in this section, grounded theory is central to the success of this approach.

Gill, Stewart, Treasure, and Chadwick (2008) suggest that qualitative approaches help with gaining a deeper understanding of academic areas that have been overlooked, as is relevant to

this thesis. For Beach (2012), the qualitative approach is also an efficient way for extracting real-world events and applying causal meaning to them. In support, Hay (2002) argues that events are a product of social dynamics that offer inferences, sufficient that meaning can be applied to them. However, these same sets of dynamics can be blurred, misleading, and in some cases, are not immediately observable (Marsh and Furlong, 2002; Kerr, 2003). Added, Marsh and Furlong say that “positing their existence gives us the best explanation of social action” (2002: 30). And this implies interpretivism as way for offering real-world explanations. Unlike positivist research, interpretivism can argue the existence of multiple realities, and they are all relative (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988). One approach is to employ a model based on historical research, a route that Snyder (2010) says can assist in helping understand past events and interpret what occurred, so to help explain the circumstance and facts of the case. Given that this thesis is investigating how internal and external statecraft has influenced Scotland’s secessionist influence, it is observing and investigating events that occurred in the past. To this end, this thesis resides comfortably within a historical perspective. In arriving at the position of historical perspectives, this research could have used a naturalistic approach which offers the potential to observe, describe, and interpret events in the social world and discuss their cultural contextualisation (Armstrong, 2010; Snyder, 2010). Similarly, phenomenological research could also have been employed. Ultimately, and as will be explained, grounded theory was considered beneficial in furthering the research towards a viable response to the research question.

Grounded theory is deemed to assist in identifying new explanations or theories about a particular phenomenon from an evidence-based standpoint (Glaser, 1978; Charmaz and Thornberg, 2020). Charmaz and Thornberg add further that grounded theory helps researchers in their attempts to synthesise data in a way that helps them “move beyond description through constructing new concepts that explicate what is happening” (2020: 307). However, a tension with grounded theory is the potential that pre-existing theories are able to influence the direction a research project takes and how the data is interpreted (Glaser, 1978). But as has been noted elsewhere in this thesis, statecraft theory offers little in the way of offering insights into Scotland’s secessionist impulse. The effect is that there is an evident dearth in the literature for explaining the response to Scotland’s secessionist impulse through a statecraft lens. With the literature on secession also having similar limited influence, the overall meaning here is that there is nothing of relevance in the literature of secession or statecraft that has unduly influenced the shape or direction of this research. It is also

important to note that the themes (statecraft levers) that underpin the thesis investigations were borrowed directly from the literature on statecraft. So, it is important to recognise that incorporating the five levers of statecraft into the investigations boasts influence at some level or other in proceedings (Glaser, 1978). The overall effect is that other than a guide, the literature offers limited impact in unduly influencing the direction of the investigations being undertaken for this thesis. Where a potential influence can be found lies in the creation of the causal frameworks that have guided the investigations. This issue is discussed later in this chapter.

Lastly, it should be noted that the approach taken for this research correlated with inductive reasoning and theory-building (Corbin, 2016; Charmaz and Thornberg, 2020). For this reason, rather than looking for solid evidence of one explanation being dominant over the alternatives, this research seeks only to infer the probability and causality. Prior to this, however, this chapter turns its attention to explaining the relevance of a case study approach.

Case study approach

This section explains the employment of case studies in this thesis and, latterly, offers a discussion on the pros and cons of case studies.

Political case studies, for Connolly (2009), are beneficial for exploring a real-world event. However, as Yin argues, case studies, as an aspect of research design, are yet to be “codified in an objective way” (2009: 254). Yin (2013) adds further that there are implicit and explicit elements to research design whereas Cohen Mannion, and Morrison (2013) argue that studies that employ a case study approach leads to collecting insights and information of contextual relevance. The consequence is ongoing arguments between academics over the merits and applications of case studies to research. For Snape and Spencer (2013) a central contestation is the relationship between ontological and epistemological explanations of the world around us, and how it ‘works’. External reality is important here, particularly in respect of the separation of individual beliefs to our understanding of the wider world (Snape and Spencer, 2013). That said, However, Clarke and Primo (2007) also argue that researchers cannot truly know the world that exists around them. For them, this means that researchers operate from a position of imperfect knowledge. The effect is that it is difficult for social scientists to achieve a high level of accuracy in their research and findings (Clarke and Primo, 2007).

However, for Yin, a case-within-case approach, or “multiple cases”, can be beneficial in addressing this issue by way of strengthening any case-related findings (2009: 254).

Chapter one noted the trend in recent decades for secessionist and separatist impulses to be tested in a pacific way via the ballot box (Sorens, 2012; Griffiths (a), 2016). This political preference has come parallel to a real-world collapse in the numbers of secessionist events the effect of which has resulted in secession becoming a political outlier in international relations (Sorens, 2012; Griffiths (a), 2016). Building on these insights, chapter two considered the scholarly view that whilst referendums are used for “constitutional, territorial, moral or other issues”, as per Boyd (2010: 2), they are also considered to be used in a “conservative sense” and only when government thinks its chances of victory are high (Atkinson et al, 2020: 6). The effect is that referendums, for Atkinson et al, represent a “Tory democracy” (2020: 6), and for Boyd, a tool of “ruthless governments” (2010: 2), that are intent on securing the status quo. For this reason Lijphart considered referendums to be “controlled” and “pro-hegemonic” (1984: 203). The whole effect, Qvortrup (2019) argues, leads to referendums being vulnerable to manipulation. He adds that the referendums held in 1975; 2011; and, 2016 acted as decoys so to address party-political problems (Qvortrup, 2019). As such, it can be of no coincidence that electoral strategy and rule bending take precedence during referendum preparations (James, 2012; 2014; 2016; 2018; 2019). The message from these insights is that that whilst elections are political, and so too is the legislation that shapes and directs them.

A limitation in the literature on statecraft is that it is very much Westminster-centric. It is a point recognised by Sandford (2013), Sandford et al (2017), and, Ayres et al (2018) recognise and of whom, their work on policy towards English devolution helps map out an increasingly complex operational environment. Similarly, Hopkins (2011) also notes that via devolution, a host of statecraft actors have emerged, each with their own political agendas. Each of these works can be located in what this thesis refers to as the domestic external statecraft setting, as outlined in chapter four. Traditionally, however, statecraft opposition has in the main, been located in the House of Commons, specifically on the opposition benches and, at times, the governing backbenches and during times of rebellion and is a matter that the literature on statecraft covers as aspects of party management. However, the advent of devolution has meant that the numbers of elected forces challenging the status quo has increased, and they all reside outside of the immediate Westminster circle or bubble. All three scenarios can be

found influencing Scotland's secessionist impulse. They are, in effect, standalone cases the totality of which helps inform on a grander scale, in line with the multiple case approaches, and in a way that helps investigate how internal and external statecraft has influenced Scotland's secessionist impulse.

Case 1: the legislative arrangements for the 1979 Scottish devolution referendum, which, thesis asserts, took place within the Scottish preconditions stage, as per the conceptual framework (see chapter four). The focus is in-party.

Case 2: the legislative arrangements for the 1997 Scottish devolution referendum, which, thesis asserts, took place within the Scottish rise/movements stage, as per the conceptual framework (see chapter four). The focus is the official opposition.

Case 3: the legislative arrangements for the 2014 Scottish independence referendum, which, thesis asserts, took place within the Scottish precipitancy stage, as per the conceptual framework (see chapter four). The focus is the devolved Scottish parliament.

Pros and cons of case studies

All approaches to social science research methods have their strengths, weaknesses, benefits, and drawbacks. Case studies are no different. A first notable point to consider comes from Diamond who argues that a drawback of case studies is their inability to apply what he calls "scientific methods" (1996: 6). Added, Cohen et al (2013) argue that case studies are inherently biased towards the achievement of a pre-conceived doctrinal or academic position, the result being a narrowly defined piece of research. Flyberg further adds that whilst case studies are beneficial in offering "practical knowledge", they can also have a "black swan" effect that offers little of substance to any debate (2006: 8). The result is a lack of theoretical development and generalised findings (Flyvberg, 2006: 8).

However, Flyberg also says that a well executed case study can provide a rich source of data that further informs the real world through offering genuine insights and explanations (2006: 21). George and Bennett add that case studies can assist with identifying the causal relationships between seemingly unrelated phenomena or events (2005: 10). It is also noted that Kuper and Kuper also add that "more discoveries have arisen from intense observation than from statistics applied to large groups" (1985: 95). Added, Baxter and Jack (2008)

suggest that case studies can act as a springboard for secondary research strands, albeit ones in the same field of interest. Nonetheless, to be effective, case studies need to address four key questions - what questions to investigate; what data is relevant; what data to collect; how to analyse the results (Yin, 2013: 360). To this end, Cohen et al (2013) believe that case study research assists with the identification of core principles, and in a way that helps inform further the area of research under investigation in line with Baxter and Jack's (2008) ideas on secondary research. This posture is particularly relevant where the intent concerns gaining insights into how internal and external statecraft have influenced Scotland's secessionist impulse, as is the case here. This thesis relied on archival sources to help satisfy these considerations.

Archival sources

This section begins by explaining the choice of archival sources over other types of data collection, specifically interviews. Subsequently, this section provides a rationale for using both Hansard and newspapers as archival sources.

The use of archival sources comes at the expense of using interviews to help add to the literature on statecraft, specifically in respect of how it has influenced Scotland's secessionist impulse. Cohen et al (2013) argue that interviews allow for insights that have been sourced through, for example, anonymous personal remembrances. These outcomes can be achieved through using unstructured, semi-structured, or structured styles of interviews. Each of these three types equate to a different forms of interaction as a way of debriefing participants that partake in the interview process (Minichiello, Aroni, Timewell, and Alexander, 1990). Semi-structured interviews balance out the effects of structured or unstructured interviews - the former can be too rigid whilst the latter is prone to drift (Miles and Huberman, 1994; Morse and Field, 1996; Ajjawi and Higgs, 2007; Cohen et al, 2013). Regardless of the approach, to be successful all three rely on effective interpersonal skills - rapport building, strategies for questioning and interviewing, body language, and emotional intelligence, if the initial aims of the interviews are to be met (Bodenhamer and Hall, 2007; Whitling, 2008). Where a gap exists in a researcher's skill set, new competences need to be learned, and this can be time-consuming (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2007; Flick, 2021). Saunders et al (2007) add another potential weakness in the choice of suitable interviewees, especially given that any commentaries cannot be truly verified. Another important point they raise is that interviewers ask participants to retrospectively tell on something which could be distorted, because of time

passed (Saunders et al, 2007). Where an elected politician is being interviewed, as could have been the case here, the potential remains for the interview being reduced to sound bites, of a type not dissimilar to the content politicians publish on social media platforms. The upshot here is that full and open responsiveness can never be guaranteed, and any probing might need to be handled delicately (Flick, 2021).

To avoid these issues, this thesis relied on archival document interrogation. Archival research has been a staple of academic research for many years and is deemed to be beneficial in gaining a greater understanding of organisations and institutions, particularly in relation to how they operate (Bowen, 2009; Cohen et al, 2013). The evidential documents collected for this thesis might not hold equal weight but, collectively, offer potential relevance in respect of responding to the conceptual framework (George and Bennett, 2004; Kay and Baker, 2015). This is a point that Kippen (2019) supports and who argues that archival material is highly suitable for research of the type undertaken here. Hansard is used as the first of two archival sources.

Hansard

Hansard is the official record of the spoken word in both UK and devolved parliaments and it is via there where the legislative arrangements for the three Scottish referendums will be investigated. There, debate transcripts offer up as the foundations for the investigation into how internal and external statecraft has influenced Scotland's secessionist impulse.

Three specific legislative debates were chosen for the investigations; the Cunningham Amendment to the Scotland Bill (1977); the Cash Amendment to the Scotland (Referendum) Bill (1997); and, the Scottish Independence Referendum (Franchise) Bill (2013). All three had been tabled contrary to the UK stance in each of the referendums. Each offers congruence to the case study approach in two ways. Firstly, each offer up as examples of opposing statecraft. Secondly, all three debates premise on the primacy of electoral strategy and rule bending to referendums, in perception at least.

Case 1: the Cunningham Amendment to the Scotland Bill (1977). This transcript forms the basis for an investigation into how opposition statecraft practice played out during the preconditions. The intention of the Amendment was to redefine the meaning of victory in the

upcoming referendum deemed to have taken place in the Scottish preconditions stage. The opposition craft here is viewed from an in-party lens.

Case 2: the Cash Amendment to the Scotland (Referendum) Bill (1997). This transcript forms the basis for an investigation into how opposition craft played out during the rise/movement stage. The intention of Cash' Amendment was to widen the franchise from a Scotland-only to a UK-wide referendum deemed to have taken place in the rise/movements stage. Opposition craft is viewed from an official opposition lens.

Case 3: the Scottish Independence Referendum (Franchise) Bill (2013). This transcript forms the basis for an investigation into how opposition craft played out during the Scottish precipitancy. The intention of the Bill was to reduce the age of franchise from eighteen to sixteen in the then upcoming independence referendum deemed to have taken place in the Scottish precipitancy. Opposition craft is viewed from a devolution lens.

All three opposition craft cases reside within the realms of domestic external statecraft.

Newspapers

Newspapers are, for Anderson, “an extreme form of book, a book sold on a colossal scale” (1983: 35). For him, they are ‘one day best-sellers’ that act as a “substitute for morning prayers” and which contribute to a meditated “silent privacy, in the lair of the skull” (Anderson, 1983: 35). Anderson adds that newspapers contribute to the formation of national identities, and for Torrance newspapers are practiced in “treating their readers as a national ‘community’ (2017: 92). For Billig, this approach involves a “continual flagging, or reminding, of nationhood, which provides ‘a continual background for their political discourses, for cultural products, and even for the structuring of newspapers” (1995: 8). To this end, a predetermined governmental or other agenda causes stories to be slanted towards a particular angle (Thomas, 1998). It is a point that for Grix (2004), results in proprietary and editorial influencing the shape and direction of the final publishable article or commentary. The upshot is that newspaper coverage of events is subject to bias and, indeed, this point is emphasised in Figure 8 which plots the generic influences on the sources of media bias.

Figure 8: sources of media bias

(Source: Park, Kang, Chung, et al, 2009: 2)

However, the “continual flagging” of nationhood by the press that Billig talks about, has been unsuccessful in achieving a holistic UK press sector (1995: 8). Alongside the London-based UK market sits a “distinctly Scottish” media sector that has its own political and nationalistic positions on Scottish politics and, specifically, on the subject of independence (Seawright; 1996: Torrance, 2017: 157). The *Daily Record*, the Scottish sister paper to the English *Daily Mirror*, promotes ‘Scottishness’ as an extension of Labour values (Torrance, 2017). Other Scottish publications promote a “nationalist-unionist ideology” onto a “broad (and influential) readership” (Torrance, 2017: 64), with the *Scotsman* and *Glasgow Herald* being chief protagonists. Here it is worth pointing out that Bulpitt had argued that newspapers (and the wider media) “provided the form, but not the substance, of a homogenous, nationalised society” and where “local and regional loyalties would decline in strength” (1983: 106; 112). However, whilst this eventuality is yet to materialise, Bulpitt (1983) stated that the emergent Scottish secessionist impulse in the 1970s provoked an inevitable reaction from a media that had a collective interest in maintaining the status quo. Indeed, for Monbiot (2014), that is what happened during the 2014 referendum campaign. He says that “there is no newspaper - local, regional or national, English or Scottish - that supports independence except the Sunday Herald. The Scots who will vote yes have been almost without representation in the media” (2014: n.p.). More recently, Dekavalla has suggested that the London-based newspapers were opposed to independence whilst their Scottish counterparts were more “nuanced” (2018: 51). To this end, and with these insights in mind, newspaper reports on the three Hansard debates were interrogated as part of this research. They are listed in Table 9 and offer a cross section of UK/England and Scottish broadsheet and ‘red top’ tabloids, from

1978, 1997, and 2013. The relevant articles were assessed in terms of the journalistic focal points from the debate, and the editorial positions on the legislation, and viewed via an external statecraft lens so to help determine proximity to opposition craft.

Table 9: publications

Publication dates	Publications
26 th January 1978 4 th June 1997 15 th May 2013	UK/England: The Guardian; Daily Telegraph; The Times; The Sun; The Mirror. Scotland: Glasgow Herald; The Scotsman; Daily Record.
29 th January 1978 8 th June 1997 19 th May 2013	UK/England: Sunday Telegraph; Sunday Times; The Observer; News of the World/The Sun on Sunday; Sunday Mirror. Scotland: Sunday Herald; Sunday Post; Sunday Mail.

This next section explains how process tracing was deployed to assist in the investigations.

Process tracing

Process tracing is a method for undertaking qualitative research analysis (Collier, 2011). Its purpose is to help identify the connections and relations between sets of independent variables in retrospective single case studies where an outcome is evident, but the causation is not readily discerned (Van Evra, 1997; Collier, 2011). This section explains process tracing, its utility as a method, and its centrality in creating a causal framework. Beach argues that process tracing is “a research method for tracing causal mechanisms using detailed, within-case empirical analysis of how a causal process plays out in an actual case” (2017: n.p.). Process tracing revolves around the identification of causal processes and the relationships with what they call the causal chain (in our case, the causal framework) (George and Bennett, 2004: 206-207). Process tracing also helps identify both events and the paths between them (Kay and Baker, 2015). These pathways to change, they argue allows for “a rich account of ‘how’ a complex phenomenon ... emerges” (Kay and Baker, 2015: 2). The point is that process tracing helps in our understanding of the “strategic interaction” that exists between different policies (Kay and Baker. 2015: 2). In essence, process tracing is an investigative tool that is closely associated with trace analysis, and is a mainstay of criminalistics (Collier, 2010; Collier, 2011; Beach and Pedersen, 2013). The strategy also offers contemporary association to the gathering of fingerprints, hair fibres etc that are uncovered during forensic crime scene investigations³⁴. However, process tracing has its origins in cognitive psychology

³⁴ Beach and Pedersen (2013) also note how process tracing was used as the strategy for the investigation in the Sherlock Holmes story, *Silver Blaze*.

when in the 1970s it was used to examine human decision making (Bennett and Checkel, 2012).

Process tracing made the jump to the political sciences in the late 1970s when it was used to make inferences and provide explanations to case studies (Bennett and Checkel, 2012: 8), as is also the case here. Bennett and Checkel also note a convergence between “social and institutional structure and context with individual agency and decision-making” (Bennett and Checkel, 2012: 5). As a method, process tracing is encouraged in the social and political sciences because of the potential it offers in both furthering qualitative research, it also improves the quality of case analyses, and aids the identification of connections and relations between them (Van Evra, 1997; Collier, 2011). The consequence is the political sciences boasting more “emphasis on causal explanation via reference to hypothesized causal mechanisms” (Bennett and Checkel, 2012: 5). Underpinning these are identifiable “empirical fingerprints”, in line with trace analysis (Beach, 2016: 468). Beach also states that these fingerprints enhance research capabilities through identifying and reviewing “predicted and actually found evidence for each part of the mechanism” (Beach, 2016: 468). With these insights in mind, the core aim of process tracing remains the application of “histories, archival documents, interview transcripts, and other sources to see whether the causal process a theory hypothesizes or implies in a case is in fact evident in the sequence and values of the intervening variables in that case” (George and Bennett, 2004: 6). In other words, does the theory stand up to scrutiny? To this end, process tracing is concerned less with machinery and instead, more focused on the nuts and bolts that help produce an end product (Mahoney, 2010). And to help explain what this means for this thesis, attention now turns to the moveable parts, or the ‘doing’ of process tracing.

X, Y, and the black box

Beach sees causal mechanisms as a system that “allows us to flesh out the causal process between X and Y” (2016: 464). For him, the ‘X to Y’ depiction is the simplest way of explaining the causal process. And as an approach, it centres not on the potential that a change has taken place (X has become Y) but the unknown idea how, or why, it happened (Beach, 2012). This is the black box of causality and it lies at the heart of process tracing (Beach, 2012). The journey from X to Y is considered to have been catalysed by the interactions between independent variables, themselves divided into smaller components. For Beach and Pedersen, they represent a set of “descriptive and causal inferences” that provide

insights into events and the sequences and other phenomena that emerge from them (2013: 154). Central to the approach is an evidence gathering process (Hall, 2006: 28), the focus of which should concentrate on the actions necessary to inform the investigations, sufficient to support the causal framework. The result is a set of observable manifestations, or causal mechanisms (Collier, 2011).

To this end, Beach argues that causal mechanisms comprise a “theory of a system of interlocking parts that transmits causal forces from X to Y” (2012: 7). Observable empirical manifestations allow for the creation of a causal framework which is then subjected to investigation and from which a causal inference can be posited. It is this process that helps develop a theory for how X became Y (Van Evra, 1997; Collier, 2010; Beach, 2012), as outlined in Figure 9.

Figure 9: theory building process tracing

(Source: Beach, 2012: 21)

Process traced investigations should be separated into three parts: meta-theoretical, contextual, and methodological (Bennett, 2010; Checkel, 2008; Bennett and Checkel, 2012: 25). In layman terms, once the necessary empirical data has been collected it should be broken down to the lowest common denominator, prior to beginning any analysis (Beach, 2012). Bennett and Checkel (2012) also argue that despite process tracing offering a realist standpoint, the importance of ontology cannot be underestimated. There, an element of the real-world experience needs to be incorporated into research for it to have meaning (Bennett and Checkel, 2012). Process tracing involves the identification of closely aligned pieces of

evidence whilst at the same time, ruling out the alternatives (Collier, 2011; Beach, 2012; Beach and Pedersen, 2013). This outcome is not guaranteed; and effective due diligence can uncover new information as well as identify a faulty causal framework. On this issue, McNabb (2015) argues that a common problem with political science research is the potential for organisations and institutions to ‘hide’ their true motives as to why they behaved in a particular way. Due diligence is important here because process tracing also assists in helping undermine potential biases through in-built and on testing, bolstering, or eliminating potential explanations for a causal framework (Mahoney, 2012; Beach and Pedersen, 2013). The result can be unpredictable and at times, unwanted. Indeed, it is for this same reason that Christian Aid, whilst recommending process tracing for in-the-field evaluation reports, actively discourages its use when doing donor value-for-money reports (Talcott and Scholz, 2015: 4).

One further point to note is that process tracing can be used for document or content analysis (Bowen, 2009: 27; Krippendorff, 2018). Interrogating documents has been a staple of academic research for many years and as a method it is deemed to be beneficial for improving our understanding of organisations and institutions (Bowen, 2009; Cohen et al, 2013). However, whilst document analysis is considered as useful for identifying patterns in data, the process itself requires skill and knowledge to ensure the efficacy of the initial set-up and for managing the overall project (Cohen et al, 2013). Consequently, this approach must be prone to human error and if this is the case, then bias might also be present.

Testing the evidence

Beach and Pedersen (2013) argue that evidence bases need to comprise more than a simple log of empirical events that led from X to Y. Instead, a need exists to measure the activities that helped form the causal mechanism in the first place, and in a way that takes account of the underpinning causal forces (Beach and Pedersen, 2013). Process tracing satisfies this need given its in-built ability for due diligence via evidential testing and analysing for congruence to the causal frameworks (Collier, 2010; Beach and Pedersen, 2013). Four types of tests are offered - straw in the wind; smoking gun; doubly decisive; and, hoop tests.

Straw in the wind: as empirical investigations go, the straw in the wind is the weakest of the four tests (Beach and Pedersen, 2013). These tests are unable to confirm the assumption under question and serve only to show which way the wind is blowing (Collier, 2010).

Smoking gun: these offer high uniqueness but low certainty outcomes (Beach and Pedersen, 2013). Success in passing a smoking gun case may confirm an original assumption but it is a rare occurrence and any attempt at claiming universality of meaning would be futile (Collier, 2010).

Doubly decisive: these tests help positively confirm one assumption at the direct expense of all others (Collier, 2011). However, they can be biased in favour of the original assumption regardless of the strength of a counter argument (Collier, 2010).

Hoop tests

One way of bypassing the weaknesses of the other test types is to use hoop tests (Collier, 2010; Beach and Pedersen, 2013; Kay and Parker, 2015). Hoop tests involve asking a series of questions that are designed to support an assumption. They are, by definition, ‘loaded’. But, the evidence base has to exist for the assumption to pass and “remain under consideration” (Collier, 2010: 6). Consequent to the question sets, the assumption is tested again and again, causing “a more demanding inference” until it is eliminated (2010: 5).

With process tracing being derived from criminalistics, its usage in intelligence gathering, policing, and court room cross-examinations where, there, the simplest way to explain hoop tests is the use the well-worn question styles written into the court room television dramas. There, the following four questions would not look out of place:

Were you in the town the day of the murder?

Is this sale receipt for the weapon yours?

Is this you on the CCTV?

Witness A, is this the man you saw?

These four questions are an example of hoop tests, their usage, their structure and intent. The intention is to present a case beyond reasonable doubt, though the test could also fail at any point.

Figure 10: hoop tests

A final analytical stage is intended to give confidence in the quality of the evidence that has been gathered for the hoop tests (Kay and Baker, 2015). This means, in effect, applying due diligence to the evidence, which is done through identifying the potential explanations for why X became Y (Beach and Pedersen, 2013). This practice is the basis for what Collier calls the ‘Holmes variant’ (2010: 7)³⁵ and through which, ‘truth’ can only ever be inferred. Regardless, at this point, the black box can now be understood in theoretical terms (Collier, 2010; Mahoney, 2012). This research involved a final analysis stage that used nine sets - three per case - with each asking four questions (Collier, 2010). The sets are outlined in Tables 10, 11, and 12.

Table 10: 1978 hoop tests

Case 1	1: CA1 precipitated a failure of all five statecraft levers	1: CA1 required MPs to work together 2: CA1 was a response to weakened Government 3: MPs did not consider a Scottish parliament to be in the interests of the Commons 4: MPs bent the rules
	2: CA1 acted as a check on the creeping influence of referendums on the Commons and on Scottish devolution	5: MPs attempted to limit the impact of referendums on Commons supremacy 6: MPs tried to suppress turnout 7: MPs attempted to justify a change from simple majority 8: MPs cited previous practice in support of CA1
	3: CA1 presents as an indicator of an inward-looking political class	9: CA1 was designed to help perpetuate the legislative status quo 10: CA1 attempted to undermine the concept of a Scotland-only referendum 11: MPs attempted to sell the threshold to the Scottish electorate 12: Cunningham acted in the national interest

³⁵ “When you have eliminated the impossible, whatever remains, however improbable, must be the truth” (Collier, 2010: 7).

Table 11: 1997 hoop tests

Case 2	4: CA2 was directed at the Commons and not the Conservative party	13: there was a consensus amongst Conservatives that devolution should come at a cost 14: Cash attempted to find consensus across the Commons 15: Cash was focused on promoting a UK-wide vote 16: Conservatives were focused on promoting a UK-wide vote?
	5: CA2 was the consequence of problems within the Conservative party	17: the Conservative leadership supported CA2 18: Conservative speakers offered alternatives to CA2 19: Conservatives MPs were critical of CA2 20: the Conservative leadership offered an alternative to CA2
	6: CA2 was an attempt to preserve the status quo	21: CA2 challenged Conservative policy 22: Conservatives were concerned with the irrevocability of a Scottish parliament 23: Cash attempted to undermine referendums as electoral events 24: CA2 was an act of necessity

Table 12: 2013 hoop tests

Case 3	7: the Scottish government fully exploited the autonomy provided via Cameronian statecraft	25: redefining the franchise meant more responsibilities for the Scottish government 26: the Edinburgh Agreement bound the Scottish government 27: redefining the franchise meant the Scottish government breaking the rules 28: the Scottish government maximised the potential offered by redefinition
	8: SIRFA was premised towards citizen mobilisation	29: SIRFA facilitated the involvement of third parties in preparations for the referendum 30: SIRFA facilitated a new class of political entrepreneur 31: the involvement of third parties was entirely related to votes for sixteen-year-olds 32: the Scottish government controlled the activities of third parties
	9: SIRFA encouraged the mobilisation of Scottish society	33: MSPs considered raising the awareness of the referendum within Scottish society 34: the Scottish government offered specific arrangements to involve hard-to-reach voters 35: civic Scotland was fully representative of the Scottish electorate 36: the Scottish government maximised the opportunities for movement building

This next section explains the coding system that has been created for the investigations and offers an explanation of how they are expressed in the investigative narratives in chapters five, six, seven, and eight.

Coding

This section explains the organisation and application of codes to the research, both in terms of employing multiple coding schemes and strings, as part of an exercise in inductive reasoning. Here, and though others exist in political science research, it is problematic that statecraft theory does not offer up a system for organising and coding data. Indeed, the literature on statecraft is mostly devoid of any coding system for classifying political activities or arguments, rudimentary or otherwise. Instead, the preference is for concepts and frameworks, James' (2019) 'PROSeS framework for evaluating electoral management' being one such example. A similar picture is to be found in the works on secession where Sorens (2012) aside, much of the work again revolves around comparative frameworks, as per Wood (1981). The result was this thesis creating its own coding system, and in a way that caters for the potential of process tracing creating a mass of data (Beach, 2012).

Each of the three debates under consideration comprise as standalone investigations. They were deconstructed to their lowest common denominator; in this case the individuals that contributed to their respective debates. This exercise was repeated for every contributor and complete until the debate(s) had been completely deconstructed with the resultant individualised contributions being coded (Leith, 2006), one by one and in isolation of the wider debate. In all, this exercise produced over one hundred and eighty codes.

Coding selections were determined by the contributions beyond the control of the researcher and instead were determined by the content of the debates (Bailey, 2007). Specifically, the coding focused only on interpreting debate talking points, phraseology, arguments, ideological, and philosophical positions, and in relation to the five levers (Klingemann, Volkens, Bara et al, 2006). NVivo 12 software was used for these tasks, with the analysis being undertaken twice for each individual contributor. The first logged and coded the political arguments and the second looked for relevance or meaning to the five levers. The results meant the debate contents being assessed via "objective, systematic, and quantitative description" (Klingemann, et al, 2006: 165).

Multiple coding schemes

The investigations undertaken for this thesis resulted in the creation of separate and multiple coding sets, each complimenting one another in some way or other (Burnett, Sargent, and

Badzinski, 2010). Codes were grouped and provided with one of eight labels, as per Table 13. Table 14 outlines the codes for the five levers and an accumulative insight into the coded talking points across the three debates. NVivo 12 was also used for investigating and answering the hoop test questions that act as due diligence for the exercises. The complete data sets can be found in appendices 3 (1978), 4 (1997), and 5 (2013).

The activities underpinning these codes reinforce the inductive approach to this thesis (Goddard and Melville, 2004). The debate codes derived from the three case studies can be found in Tables 13, 14, and 15, and the evidence base outlined across Tables 16, 17, and 18. The newspapers that had been accessed for this study were also subjected to coding. As is explained later in this chapter, only the publications were coded, as per Table 19.

Table 13: labels

A	levers
B	1978 debate
C	1997 debate
D	2013 debate
E	evidence base
F-H	newspapers

Table 14: levers

A1	argument hegemony
A2	governing competence
A3	party management
A4	electoral strategy
A5	bending the rules

Table 15: debate codes

	Case 1		Case 2		Case 3
B1	referendum rules	C1	cost	D1	Votes for 16-year-olds
B2	previous elections	C2	English nationalism	D2	Prisoner voting rights
B3	irrevocability	C3	Europe	D3	Civic Scotland
B4	threshold	C4	EVEL	D4	16 year-olds political awareness
B5	parliamentary supremacy	C5	GERS	D5	Electoral awareness
B6	other state's experiences	C6	Kilbrandon	D6	Turnout
B7	Scotland v. UK-wide vote	C7	parliamentary supremacy	D7	Scotland/UK co-ordination
B8	Scottish independence	C8	previous elections	D8	ECHR
B9	turnout predictions	C9	Scotland-only vote	D9	Consultative referendums
		C10	Scottish nationalism	D10	Safeguarding
		C11	Scottish independence	D11	other state's experiences
		C12	Service personnel	D12	Service personnel
		C13	threshold	D13	Previous elections
		C14	UK-wide vote	D14	SEN
				D15	Scotland v. UK-wide vote
				D16	Finance
				D17	Education
				D18	Scottish society
				D19	Edinburgh Agreement
				D20	Third sector
				D21	Political entrepreneurs
				D22	Hard to reach voters
				D23	Scottish independence
				D24	Franchise legislation

Table 16: 1978 evidence codes

E1	backbench contributors
E2	backbencher statecraft
E3	pro-government statecraft
E4	Backbench debating points
E5	pro-government debating points
E6	government statecraft
E7	ringleader statecraft
E8	government debating points
E9	ringleader debating points
E10	statecraft (whole debate)
E11	basic rules
E12	turnout
E13	Scotland v. UK vote
E14	influence of previous elections
E15	merits of threshold
E16	backbench electioneering
E17	pro-government electioneering
E18	ringleader electioneering
E19	government electioneering
E20	electioneering
E21	merits v. basic rules
E22	backbenchers
E23	pro-government
E24	ringleaders
E25	John Smith
E26	experience of other states
E27	Scottish independence/ irrevocability
E28	Scottish independence
E29	irrevocability

Table 17: 1997 evidence codes

E30	whole debate (statecraft)
E31	whole debate (by topic)
E32	Conservatives (share by Member)
E33	Conservative statecraft
E34	English nationalism
E35	Cash
E36	Conservatives (by topic)
E37	Scottish nationalism
E38	electoral strategy
E39	Scottish nationalism (Conservative)
E40	Europe (whole debate)
E41	English v Scottish nationalism
E42	cost (Conservative)
E43	Europe (Conservative)
E44	EVEL (Conservative)
E45	UK-wide franchise (Conservative)
E46	parliamentary supremacy (Conservative)
E47	previous referendums (Conservative)
E48	Scotland only (Conservative)
E49	threshold (Conservative)
E50	Scottish independence (Conservative)
E51	service personnel (Conservative)
E52	whole debate
E53	Kilbrandon
E54	Maude
E55	Howard
E56	Luff
E57	Heathcoat-Amory
E58	Jenkin
E59	Fallon
E60	Gamier
E61	Grieve

Table 18: 2013 evidence codes

E62	whole debate
E63	debating points
E64	consultative referendums
E65	governing competence
E66	turnout
E67	ECHR
E68	Scottish/UK co-ordination
E69	argument hegemony
E70	Scotland v. UK wide vote
E71	young person voting rights
E72	safeguarding
E73	prisoner voting rights
E74	electoral administration
E75	SEN
E76	service personnel/ families
E77	bending the rules
E78	young person political awareness
E79	Scottish society
E80	electoral strategy
E81	civic Scotland
E82	education
E83	previous elections
E84	finance
E85	Scottish society v. civic Scotland
E86	Scottish society (Scottish government)
E87	Edinburgh Agreement
E88	political entrepreneurs
E89	hard to reach voters v. Scottish society
E90	hard to reach voters v. civic Scotland
E91	third sector
E92	civic Scotland (components)
E93	Scottish independence v. SIRFA
E94	Sturgeon (hard to reach voters)
E95	Scottish society (components)

Table 19: newspapers

	1978	1997	2013
Guardian	F1	G1	H1
Telegraph	F2	G2	H2
The Times	F3	G3	H3
The Mirror	F4	G4	H4
The Sun	F5	G5	H5
Glasgow Herald	F6	G6	H6
The Scotsman	F7	G7	H7
Daily Record	F8	G8	H8
News of the World/ Sun on Sunday	F9	G9	H9
Sunday Mirror	F10	G10	H10
Sunday Telegraph	F11	G11	H11
Sunday Times	F12	G12	H12
The Observer	F13	G13	H13
Sunday Herald	F14	G14	H14
Sunday Post	F15	G15	H15
Sunday Mail	F16	G16	H16

(Black blocks denote inability to obtain the publication)

Strings

The overall effect is a concentration of codes that together, create a string. They are expressed as in-text, in line with the Harvard system. An example is provided below:

(A1; A2; B2; B6; B7; B9; E2; E3; E7; E10; E11; E15; F1; F2; F12; F15)

Figure 11 breaks down this example string. The ‘A’ codes account for the identified levers whereas the ‘B’ codes provide the context, the case in the example being the 1978 debate, and the discussion points. The ‘E’ codes represent the evidence for the analysis being undertaken at that point in the narrative. And the ‘F’ newspaper reportage, in the example case is a hypothetical matter from 1978 (the same approach to G (1997) and H (2013) newspapers).

Figure 11: example string

Newspapers were coded, with their reportage being subject to grid analysis. As is explained in the next section, this wholly separate exercise was intended to complement the insights from the debates.

Grid analysis

This section explains grid analysis and describes the scorecards used for this secondary investigation. The focus was the reporting in the newspapers of the three debates. The intention was simply to identify and calculate congruence to the process tracing undertaken in respect of the legislative debates.

Grid analysis is a foundation for a hybrid research system that combines repertory and conceptual modelling that has been used in a number of scenarios - political, strategic, business, psychology (Kelly, 1955; Pugh, 1981; Delugach, 2000). Its main usage is deemed to help gain greater understandings of decision-making and the processes involved (Kelly, 1955; Pugh, 1981). Grids are also known as decision matrices, weighted scorecards, repertory grids, and the Pugh matrix (Kelly, 1955; Pugh, 1981; Delugach, 2000; Bell, Fransella, and Bannister, 2004). They are also case specific and are a use-once tool, meaning that each and every grid is unique in one way or other. It is also necessary to develop an “unambiguous” design that can be replicated where a family of grids are in use in a single piece of research (Pugh, 1981: 497). The basic premise is to assess the numerical relations between two sets of data (horizontal and vertical), and do so in a way that allows for a fairly straightforward assessment of the data. Pugh also argues that every monitored criterion hold equal weight, regardless of the importance of one over another in relation to the research (Pugh, 1981). The eventuality is a grid that is populated by data sets that allow for meaning between the horizontal and vertical axes (Bell et al, 2004). Bell et al add that these data interpretations act as the basis for any subsequent analysis (Bell et al, 2004: 1). However, Pugh also warns about the potential for “conceptual vulnerability” where, there, grids are susceptible to weak design and lack attention to detail (1981: 502). The grids, or scorecards, used in this thesis operate from a very simple position. Newspapers populate the horizontal axis and the report content, the vertical. NVivo12 was again used to interrogate and code the newspaper articles and it is the results of these exercises that are mapped out on the scorecards. Unlike the process tracing stage of the investigations, the data here was not labelled and their code frequencies were logged in the scorecard. Complete cards were ordered numerically from highest to lowest, and from four starting positions, as per Table 20.

Table 20: grid content

Coded content	correlation to the debate codes and labels
Other content	off-topic reportage
External statecraft	interpretation via a statecraft lens and expressed as levers
Posture	newspaper perspective on the legislation

The scorecard design also allows for a number of cross-comparisons - reporting the day after versus the Sunday editions; Scotland-only publications versus UK/England; and on broadsheet versus tabloid comparison, all in line with the four interpretations mentioned above. In all, thirty-six newspapers were analysed and their completed scorecards can be found in appendices 3.3 (1978), 4.3 (1997), and 5.3 (2013).

Chapter summary

This thesis investigated how Scottish secessionism has been influenced by internal and external statecraft. It premised on a piece of inductive research that, in part, interpreted qualitative data numerically. This approach lent on grounded theory as a way for developing new explanations and theories on UK statecraft, as applied to Scotland's secessionist impulse, and from an evidence-based standpoint (Glaser, 1978; Charmaz and Thornberg, 2020). The transcripts from three legislative debates were process traced (Collier, 2010; Collier, 2011; Beach and Pedersen, 2013). The transcripts were also subjected to hoop tests with the Holmes variant being applied until a causal inference emerged. As such, individually and collectively, the words of MPs and MSPs were analysed for meaning in relation to the five levers, in line with seeking objective reality and the identification for the causation of an event or other, beyond reasonable doubt. The process traced investigations were accompanied by grid analyses of the newspaper reportage of the debates. The inclusion of this secondary investigation added a real-world context that had been hitherto missing from the somewhat insular and parochial debates taking place in the respective Chambers.

The results of these investigations are explained over the next five chapters, starting initially with Labour MP George Cunningham and his Amendment to the Scotland Bill (1977) that a forty percent threshold be added to the referendum on Scottish devolution, held in 1979 (See chapter two, Table 4).

NB: Appendix 5 accompanies this chapter. There, further information on process tracing, including the practical process tracing steps taken for the investigative stages of this thesis are

provided. Added, the data sets that support the hoop tests and the complete newspaper grid analyses for each of the three investigations are also to be found in appendices 7 (1978), 8 (1997), and 9, (2013).

Chapter six: the Burns Night plot

This chapter tests the competence of the first stage in the conceptual framework by looking for insights into the legislative preparations for the first referendum on Scottish devolution. The focus is an Amendment to the Scotland Bill (1977) that had been tabled by Labour MP George Cunningham (hereafter, CA1). CA1 called for forty percent of the Scottish electorate needed to have voted for devolution before a parliament was established. Cunningham was responding to the Scottish preconditions where, in times such as these, it is expected that a romanticised idea of independence will dominate the social discourse (Wood, 1981; Heraclides, 2002; Pavkovic and Radan, 2011). According to the literature, the potential for a secessionist event in the preconditions stage is extremely low, but could have sufficient support to damage the governing party in elections (Wood, 1981; Sorens, 2012). The consequence is, in line with statecraft theory, politicians remain fixated on winning elections, potentially more so given the additional competition (Bulpitt, 1986a; Hopkins, 2011). Statecraft theory indicates the potential that elected political leaders are free to ignore an issue if it is politically expedient to do so (Bulpitt, 1983; Hopkins, 2011; James, 2016). To this end, the first step in the conceptual framework is outlined in Figure 5.

Figure 5: statecraft in the preconditions
(Repeated from pg. 87)

However, by the late 1970s the UK has experienced three decades of continual decline in both the international and domestic fronts (Abernethy, 2000; Kegley and Wittkopf, 2001; Hyam, 2008; Tomlinson, 2009; Reynolds, 2015). Empire had been rapidly dismantled with the impact being experienced domestically via a loss of economic competitiveness, regular mass industrial action, and shortages (Shanks, 1963; Abernethy, 2000; Hyam, 2008; Tomlinson, 2009; Coyle, 2017). Regular delves into low politics by successive governments had caused the dual polity to collapse (Bulpitt, 1983). At the same time, the UK space was experiencing secession from within (Nairn, 1968; 1977; Forman, 2002; Alder, 2010; Wilson,

2017). The simple point is that this real-world environment does not read like the preconditions, as outlined by Wood (1981). Whilst secession, and the potential for it, remains an important factor in this chapter, the core interest here is separatism.

By definition a response was required if fears over the perpetuation of the status quo were to be realised (Wood, 1981). And as such, the governmental offer to Scotland represented as a liberalist solution to a constructivist problem, and in a way that maintained the integrity of the state (Wood, 1981; Buchanan, 1997; Evans, 1998; Baylis and Smith, 2001; Kegley and Wittkopf, 2001; Brecher and Harvey, 2002; Pugh 2005; Kalkman, 2011). To this end, this chapter is focused entirely on the domestic realm and relevance in terms of external statecraft consequent to which, this chapter intends gaining insight into the emergent opposition craft, particularly in terms of how statecraft was employed by an in-party oppositional cohort, and within its traditional setting.

This chapter begins with an overview of the debate on CA1 and the background to it. The accrued insights are central to the creating of a causal framework. From there an interim causal inference is offered and it is this interim model that was subjected to process tracing. To assist in this endeavour, three statements were posed, one for each step of the causal framework:

- 1:** CA1 precipitated a failure of all five statecraft levers.
- 2:** CA1 acted as a check on the creeping influence of referendums on the Commons and on Scottish devolution.
- 3:** CA1 presents as an indicator of an inward-looking political class.

Consequentially, this chapter offers insights into how elites sought to preserve the status quo in the preconditions era. There are two simple expectations for this chapter. First, that the debate was dominated by party in-fighting, particularly within Labour and second, that anti-devolutionary positions were in the majority.

A concluding causal inference can be found in the chapter summary.

The art of losing control

Consequent to Kilbrandon, Labour was elected in 1974 on a manifesto pledge to establish a Scottish parliament³⁶, and in 1976 the legislation was introduced. However a lack of support in the Commons caused it to be pulled from the Commons timetable (Callaghan 1987). Jim Callaghan took over as Prime Minister in this same year. A mid-term appointee, he inherited a minority government and had to rely on the smaller parties - Liberals, SNP, Scottish Labour Party (SLP)³⁷, and Plaid Cymru - to help pass legislation (Callaghan, 1987). In 1977 Labour again tabled legislation dedicated to Scottish devolution, this time including within it arrangements for holding a referendum, for which there was no electoral mandate (Hansard, 1978; Callaghan, 1987).

The decision to hold a referendum on devolution was a capitulation to MPs in the hope that the Bill would pass onto statute (Hansard, 1978a; Callaghan, 1987). However, this was not to be and the legislation continued to have a difficult journey (Callaghan 1987). A number of Amendments to the Bill (1977) had been tabled and these were debated on 25th of January 1978, a date more commonly known for Burns Night, a celebration of Scotland's Bard. One motion sought to provide that in the event that Scotland voted 'Yes' to devolution, Orkney and Shetland could have a veto thereby allowing it to continue to be directly ruled from London (F1; F2; F3; F4; F6; F7; F8; F10; F12; F15). Another two called for an additional referendum threshold over and above the simple majority practice. The first being levied at thirty-three percent of the Scottish electorate voting in favour of devolution before a parliament was established. The second was CA1, which called for a higher threshold of forty percent. Despite devolution being a liberalist tool for enhancing local autonomy (Wood, 1981; Baylis and Smith, 2001), it was already being labelled as a "threat to all representative government, especially Parliament itself" (Bulpitt, 1983: 220).

The Labour government went on to lose all three Amendment votes which meant that, in order to establish a Scottish parliament, Scottish voters needed not just vote in the majority but also to surpass forty percent of the electorate. It was an event that the Scottish Sunday Mail labelled as the 'Burns Night Plot' (H15) and it was symptomatic of a chaotic political environment, through which an in-party opposition craft played out. The events led to

³⁶ The UK government legislated separately for Welsh devolution.

³⁷ The Scottish Labour Party was a short-lived off-shoot from the Labour Party (Sillars, 2021).

newspaper speculation over the potential for an early general election, although there was little evidence to suggest that one was being planned (F10; F15).

CA1

CA1 was tabled by George Cunningham. He was a Scottish backbench Labour MP who represented an English seat. Cunningham argued in favour of a referendum because, he believed, neither the party system nor the institutional demands of the Commons were best placed to decide on constitutional issues (A1; A4; B2; B5). Adding that “the only way in which we can tell what the electorate wants on this issue ... is to test it directly” (A1; A4; B2; B5), and this meant holding a consultative referendum so the Commons could have the final say on interpreting the result (A1; A2; B1; B5). Cunningham also argued that a Scottish parliament would be an “irrevocable step” and it would not be practical politics to return the state to its previous incarnation (A1; A2; A4; A5; B3; B5; B8; F1; F3; F7; F12). Cunningham furthered that devolution was also a steppingstone to Scottish independence. As such, rather than employ the simple majority tests that elections had traditionally adhered to, the referendum needed to have “a minimum test” that equated to a “minimum majority of those who vote “Yes” over those who vote “No” (A4; B1; B4). For Cunningham, it was fair that this majority should be forty percent of the electorate and as a position, it had support in the chamber (A1; A2; A4; A5; B3; B4; B5; B7; B8; F1; F3; F7; F10; F12; F15; F16).

The debate itself was loaded with backbench MPs favourable to CA1 and the status quo. Indeed, and as an indicator of the difficulty facing the government, both Labour’s Robin Cook and Conservative Francis Pym posited that no one from the Labour party present at the debate was willing to support the Bill, as drafted (A1; A2; A3; B1; B4; B5; B9). That assertion, however, was not strictly true because Labour’s Dennis Canavan was a participant to the debate. He has also been a lifelong supporter of devolution and latterly campaigned in favour of Scottish independence (Canavan, 2009), and who voted against CA1³⁸. Another dissenter from the party line was Conservative David Knox. Knox, like Cunningham, was a Scotsman who represented an English constituency. Like Canavan, Knox also supported devolution contrary to Conservative policy (A1; A4; A5; B4; B9). The early indication here is party management as a pre-requisite for in-party opposition craft (Bulpitt, 1983; James, 2016; 2018). However, argument hegemony was also in play. Whilst Cunningham was in

³⁸ Canavan voted against CA1 and a month later he tabled his own Amendment to have it removed and the Bill (1977) returned to its original state (Hansard, 1978a; Canavan, 2009). His Amendment was voted down.

favour of a referendum in this instance, he sought to alleviate fears amongst his fellow MPs regards their more general creeping influence. Consequently, he assured his fellow MPs that nothing in either the legislation or CA1 was “mandatory” or would be “legally binding” upon them (A1; A4; B1; B5)³⁹. The suggestion here is that there existed an ulterior motive for CA1 that extended beyond simply seeking a stronger mandate from the people but related instead to interpreting referendum results, with the strong hint that the Commons will have the final say.

In the end, MPs voted by 168 votes to 142 in favour of CA1. The result forced government to add a forty percent threshold as an additional electoral test for the then upcoming referendum (Hansard, 1978; Mitchell, 1996: 321). Failure to pass it meant that Scotland, even if a majority voted in favour of devolution, would be denied a parliament.

‘The delayed action-bomb’

Naughtie argues that Cunningham made a “powerful” speech that “held a crowded House silent and attentive” (1980: 31). His speech mentioned a number of other subjects, including the perceived impact that both referendums and a Scottish parliament would have upon the primacy of the Commons (A1; A2; A3; A4; A5; B1; B3; B4; B5; B8; F1; F2; F3; F4; F6; F7; F8; F10; F12; F16). By tabling CA1 and arguing for a threshold, Cunningham was encouraging his peers to ditch the longstanding principle of the simple majority, the effect of which Mitchell said was akin to a “delayed-action bomb” (1996: 46). It is here where the attempt at rule bending is deemed to have occurred. In practice and through CA1, Cunningham was calling for an electoral precedent which smacked of rule bending, as argued by the SNPs Gordon Wilson (A1; A5; B3).

Bulpitt argues that it is not unusual to attempt to alter or manipulate electoral administration for politically expedient purposes (1986a: 184). To do this, all that is needed is a receptive audience, and in the case of CA1, that audience was found in the Commons. As stated, the debate on CA1 was dominated by MPs who either supported the imposition of a threshold and/or who were adverse to a devolved Scottish parliament. For James (2016), the need to win elections is a central factor in actions of this type with the result being that it should be expected that politicians will change electoral rules and procedures to help satisfy their needs,

³⁹ Cunningham added that “whatever comes before the House in the way of an order from the Government will be passed or not passed according to the discretion of the House” (A1; A4; B1; B5).

which may not be the same as those of the wider population (Bulpitt, 1983; James 2016; 2018). Indeed, this practice plays directly into the idea that statecraft as “the art of winning elections” (1986: 21), and was one that was supported by Robin Cook added his belief that the electoral test in place for the EEC referendum of 1974 was insufficient as a “minimum qualification” for altering the constitution (A1; A5; B1; B2; B5; B6). Nonetheless, what CA1 also did was turn an abstention into a ‘No’ vote (A1; A4; B4; B9). For Conservative MP George Gardiner, CA1 represented an opportunity to create rules for referendums (A1; A3; B1; B4; B5; B6; F1; F2; F3; F6; F7). By challenging the lack of rules for undertaking referendums and their anticipated influence on the Commons, CA1 was in effect, a rallying call.

Bulpitt (1983) believes that politicians also need to create a programme that unites and stimulates party members or peripheral supporters to win elections. At the same time however, this same system had been recognised for encouraging elective dictatorships that reinforce the idea that elections are for the governing party to lose (Bogdanor, 2009). The effect of CA1 was that political power was found on the backbenches, on this issue at least. And as it appears, MPs acted in their own collective interest and did so in full view of a weakened government. This is what appears to have occurred here and, in effect, CA1 was a realist-fuelled act of necessity, undertaken via opposition craft.

The CA1 casual framework is outlined in Figure 12. It is a three-step framework that premises on Cunningham and his allies first arguing the need for the forty-percent threshold. Second was an assessment of the impact of the threshold. Third was an attempt at justifying the threshold. Interpreted as acts of statecraft, step one has been deemed to lean on rule bending whereas step-two is considered indicative of electoral strategy, whereas the last step in the causal framework sees Cunningham and his allies justify the change to the franchise, which is considered to be a form of argument hegemony.

Figure 12: 1978 casual framework

Results

To reiterate from the chapter introduction, three statements were made - one for each of the three steps.

- 1: CA1 precipitated a failure of all five statecraft levers
- 2: CA1 acted as a check on the creeping influence of referendums on the Commons and on Scottish devolution
- 3: CA1 presents as an indicator of an inward-looking political class

Insights into each of the three statements are gained through asking a further set of four hoop tests (Collier, 2010; Beach and Pedersen, 2013), one set per question and specific to each of the three steps. To this end, this section is in three parts, with each sub-section offering an in-depth review of the three steps - (1) argue the need; (2) assess the impact; and (3), justify the change. The result is an interim causal inference, as indicated in Figure 13, which has been latterly tested using process tracing.

Figure 13: 1978 interim causal inferences

The observation is that CA1 acted as a driver for redefining the meaning of victory for the then upcoming devolution referendum. However, it should also be noted that consequent to the inferred lever usage, Figure 13 brings into question the competence offered by the first stage in the conceptual framework, as outlined in the introduction to this chapter.

Argue the need

The statement for this first step in the interim causal inference implies that CA1 had precipitated a failure of all five levers, and that rule bending acted as the predominant lever. This approach allowed for a systematic review of the relevance to each statecraft lever and

did so by posing four statements. These, and the evidence that support them, are found in Table 21. From there, this sub-section explains the narrative behind the evidence base.

Table 21: 1978 evidence 1

	hoop question	yes/no	evidence
1	CA1 required MPs to work together	yes	E1; E4; E8; E9; E10; E11; E15; E16; E18; E21; E26; E27; E28; E29
2	CA1 was a response to weakened Government	yes	E2; E3; E4; E5; E6; E7; E8; E25
3	MPs did not consider a Scottish parliament to be in the interests of the Commons	yes	E1; E4; E9; E10; E23; E27; E28; E29
4	MPs bent the rules	no	no evidence

(See Appendix 6 for the supporting data)

Argument hegemony: some MPs did not consider a Scottish parliament to be in the interests of the Commons. Premised on the potential for an irrevocable rival chamber, MPs viewed Scottish devolution as a constitutional matter which, consequentially, required additional scrutiny (E4; E9; E10; E23; E27; E28; E29). A Scottish parliament was also considered a stepping-stone to independence (E28). Labour’s Buchan, Cook, and Cunningham agreed the establishment of a Scottish parliament could be an electoral boon for the SNP. Having gained a majority of the MPs from Scotland at a future general election, the SNP would refuse to take up their seats in the Commons and instead decamp to Edinburgh and become a “government in residence” (E4; E28). Cook’s commentary was viewed sympathetically by Conservatives, who agreed, saying a Scottish parliament would lead to the breakup of the state. In this respect Conservative Julian Amery summed up for a number of speakers that CA1 was necessary because he argued, the unity of the Kingdom was potentially at risk⁴⁰ (E15; E28; E29).

The government minister, John Smith, disagreed. He argued that Scottish devolution did not represent a constitutional change (E8), Bulpitt (1983) says Smith was correct here - a retained Treasury, civil service, purse strings, and the intended continuance of the Scottish Office would see London continue its institutional and administrative control over Scotland (Bulpitt, 1983). For MPs, an irrevocable and rival chamber in Scotland was a threat to the primacy the

⁴⁰ The unity of the Kingdom would be at risk if the Bill went through ... it is often argued that if we do not pass the Bill, we shall endanger the unity of the United Kingdom. Many of us feel that the Bill will put that unity in danger (E15; E28; E29).

Commons had enjoyed since the placing on statute of the Parliament Act (1949). And in simple terms, Cunningham showed the Commons a way to reduce the likelihood of that eventuality. The Commons agreed and by consequence, argument hegemony remains in play as the predominate lever.

Governing competence: Table 21 above indicates a wealth of evidence suggesting MPs working together on the basis that a Scottish parliament was not in the interests of the Commons. Added, it hints at CA1 being a response to a weakened government. The combined effect overwhelmed the Labour government, the only response to which it could offer was to use the guillotine and bring the debate to a close at a predetermined time (Naughtie, 1980). This was an exercise in damage limitation and in fronting for the government, John Smith focused on four key areas - parliamentary sovereignty, basic rules of referendums, the influence of previous elections/referendums, and the merits of a threshold (E6; E8; E14; E15; E21; E25). Whilst these four points are considered to act as direct responses to issues raised in the house, it is also noted that he offered no response to the potential that Scottish devolution would lead to independence (E25). These aspects of the debate were left to the SNP, SLP, and the Conservative David Knox (E2; E3; E4; E5; E6; E7; E8; E9; E10; E11; E12; E13; E14; E15; E26; F1; F2; F3; F4; F6; F7; F8; F10; F12; F13; F15; F16). Indeed, it is also evident that whilst Smith spoke almost three times the average of all contributions to the debate, his and his allies' comments in the debate extended to a mere quarter of the totality of all speakers, as per Table 22. The clear indication again is of dominant support for CA1 amongst those who spoke in the debate.

Table 22: share of argument

Party	Words spoken	% share
Labour	14300	50.5
Conservative	7500	26
Government	2200	8
SLP	2700	9
SNP	1600	6
Knox*	1085	3.5
Average	1000	3.5
Total	29000	100

(Numbers do not include the Chair or Deputy Chair)

*Knox was pro-devolution and is differentiated from the rest of the Conservative party

Naughtie (1980) adds that the plan was that once the Bill (1977) had reached the House of Lords, Conservative Peers from the English shires would pick over it in ways not afforded in the Commons. For him, the Bill would have received a “mauling, safe from any government steamroller” (Naughtie, 1980: 23). Overall, and against an opposition craft comprised of in-party and official opposition elements, a weak government had lost control of its legislation. As such, governing competence remains in play as a potential predominate lever.

Party management: the success of CA1 relied on inter-party fraternisation which, for Naughtie (1981), was a central feature to what Leith and Soule argue was the effective staging of a “wrecking” Amendment (2012: 8). Conservatives were unwilling to front CA1 themselves and needed a Labour MP to do this for them, in the hope of picking up some extra support (Naughtie, 1980). In Cunningham they found a “formidable ally” who was prepared to front the Amendment (Naughtie, 1980: 28). At the same time, Labour backbenchers profiled and cherry-picked Conservatives to openly support CA1 (Dalyell, 2016). This fraternisation included the profiling by Labour of suitable Conservative allies who were “honourable” and who “knew how to keep their mouths shut” (Dalyell, 2016: 154). To be successful meant MPs working together to defeat the government and from here on in, opposition craft was in play. Conservative George Gardiner later stated that this collusion extended to co-ordinating anti-government tactics (1999: 122). Further fraternisation took place, albeit it to a lesser scale, and as observed in Table 23, and which served to benefit government. The overall effect is that party management had collapsed and, as such, this lever is redundant to this investigation.

Table 23: attendee position

For CA1	Country	Against CA1	Country
Abse (Lab)	Wales	Canavan (Lab)	Scotland
Amery (Con)	England	Crawford (SNP)	Scotland
Braine (Con)	England	Government (Lab)	England
Buchan (Lab)	Scotland	Knox (Con)	Scotland
Crouch (Lab)	England	Sillars (SLP)	Scotland
Cunningham (Lab)	England	Wilson (SNP)	Scotland
Cook (Lab)	Scotland		
Dalyell (Lab)	Scotland		
Douglas-Mann (Lab)	England		
Evans (Lab)	Wales		
Gardiner (Con)	England		
Hamilton (Lab)	Scotland		
Heffer (Lab)	England		
Higgins (Con)	England		
Hughes (Lab)	Scotland		
MacMillan (Con)	England		
Pym (Con)	England		
Raison (Con)	England		
Sproat (Con)	Scotland		
Taylor (Con)	Scotland		
Total	20		6

(Numbers do not include the Chair or Deputy Chair)

Electoral strategy: once backbenchers had captured the legislation, they used it as a tool for electioneering via redefining victory in the referendum. By definition, the hypothetical bomb that Mitchell (1996) spoke about was the arithmetical effects of an abstention counting as a ‘No’ vote (E15; E16; E17; E18; E19; E20; 21). Ultimately, an argument can be presented that CA1 *was* the anti-devolution electoral strategy and as such, this lever remains in play as the predominate lever for this first step.

Rule bending: there is no indication that CA1 broke any rules, either in terms of redefining victory in the referendum or breaching Parliamentary protocols. Similarly, as MPs themselves explained, there [are] were no rules for administering or holding, a referendum, and this position extended to the definition of an electoral victory, tradition aside. Simply put, rules cannot be broken if they do not exist in the first place, and there were none in respect of referendums. Added, with the Parliament Act (1949) shifting legislative primacy from the Lords to the Commons, it was the latter that had (and has) the final say on all legislation - not government and least of all, the Lords, and all that is required is a majority in the House (UK Government, 1949; Bulpitt, 1983; Dymond and Deadman, 2006). This is what Cunningham sought and this is what Cunningham got, the effect being that rule bending is redundant.

Summary: the assertion for this first step sees CA1 precipitating a failure of all five levers and it had been assumed that rule bending was predominating as an influencing lever. The basis for this posture lies with the idea that in redefining victory in the devolution referendum by way of adding in a forty percent threshold, CA1 represented as a case of blatant electioneering underpinned by rule bending. However, Cunningham can be ‘let off’ on a technicality, at least in procedural if not moral or ethical terms because, as the Parliament Act (1949) demonstrates, the Commons is a sovereign institution. A feature of this system, in tandem with the effects of an uncodified constitution, is that MPs are in the main unable to bind future Commons sessions (Allen and Thompson, 2002; Foster, 2006; Keating, 2018). What rules or arrangements that do exist can be undone latterly on a simple majority of supporting MPs. As such, in seeking to identify the lever predominate to step one in the casual framework the investigation found that both rule bending and party management are redundant to this investigation. Governing competence produced mixed results because whilst government had found itself in zugzwang, the causation was an opposition craft borne of fraternisation. Consequentially, the two levers that are deemed to have survived intact are electoral strategy and argument hegemony.

The rationale underpinning CA1 was expressed by Conservative Francis Pym who said that a Scottish parliament represented “a constitutional change of quite exceptional scope and importance”, and that the comparative practice for such arrangements in other states tended to revolve around needing a “two-thirds majority” as a “minimum provision” before change is undertaken (E4; E11; E15; E26). Regardless of the rhetoric, however, CA1 appears to be a standalone legislative tool because there was nothing of substance from the debate that suggested MPs having further interest in developing rules for referendum over the longer term. Instead, we can assert CA1 to be a one-off event of which the chief consideration was the redefining of victory in the 1979 Scottish devolution referendum.

Figure 14: 1978 hoop test probability-1

Through CA1, the Commons was using its sovereign powers to protect itself from a rival and irrevocable Scottish parliament, and they did this by undermining the potential for one existing in the first place. Ultimately, in what had appeared to be a cast iron case of rule bending is instead, an exercise in sovereignty, thereby resulting in argument hegemony as the predominate lever for this first step. This outcome is offered on a seventy-five percent probability, and premised on the data sets found in Table 21 (found at the outset of this subsection) and Figure 14.

Assess the impact

This first step in the interim causal inference implies that CA1 offered not just as a check on Scottish devolution but also on the creeping influence of referendums in binding the Commons, and that argument hegemony acted as the predominant lever. Four levers are in play here; argument hegemony, governing competence, party management, and electoral strategy - rule bending being redundant, consequent to the Parliament Act (1949). This approach allowed for a systematic review of the relevance to each statecraft lever and did so by asking four sub-questions. These, and the evidence that support them, are found in Table 24. From there, this sub-section explains the narrative behind the evidence base.

Table 24: 1978 evidence 2

	hoop question	yes/no	supporting graphs
5	MPs attempted to limit the impact of referendums on Commons supremacy	yes	E1; E4; E7; E9; E10; E11; E18; E20; E29
6	MPs tried to suppress turnout	yes	E12; E14; E15; E16; E17; E18; E19; E20; E21
7	MPs attempted to justify a change from simple majority	yes	E2; E11; E12; E14; E15; E21;
8	MPs cited previous practice in support of CA1	yes	E14; E26

(See Appendix 6 for the supporting data)

Argument hegemony: the first hoop test asked if MPs had attempted to limit the impact of referendums on Commons supremacy. In investigating, further evidence was found in respect of MPs attempting to justify a change from simple majority, and in respect of previous practice, MPs also justified the threshold via arguing the practices and experiences of other states.

George Cunningham was in favour of referendums, as long as they were consultative and non-binding on the Commons (E7; E11; E14; E29). In 1978, however, the UK had gained only limited experience of administering them (see chapter two, Table 4) and as explained earlier in this chapter, government had no intention of holding a referendum and only added one consequent to pacify its backbenches (Butler and Ranney, 1994; Torrance, 2017). Conservative George Gardiner argued that referendums are a tool of “unfavourable governments and regimes” which use referendums for their own gain (E2; E4; E9; E14; E21; E26). In reality, he was really talking about himself and the CA1 supporting cohort whose pressure on the central government caused it to capitulate on holding one in the first place. Even so, Gardiners’ comments gained support, including from his own Conservative colleagues, Francis Pym, Iain Sproat, Maurice MacMillan (son of the former Prime Minister, Harold), and Sir Bernard Braine (E22; E16; E26). Conservative Julian Amery also argued that it was beyond the remit of MPs to alter the constitution (E4). As a position, this is grossly incorrect - every piece of legislation is a change to the uncodified constitution (Allen and Thompson, 2002; Foster, 2006; Allen, 2015). The effect is the UK social contracts being in a constant state of flux, with the changes being catalysed in the Commons.

The SLP's Jim Sillars was also anti-referendum. For him, referendums were vulnerable to electoral abuse and "vested interests", and consequently he was not in favour of referendums (E3; E5). However, Sillars was pro-devolution so any settlement short of direct establishment of a Scottish parliament represented a threat to his political aspirations. Even so, the vested interests in this case were those backbenchers who thought referendums represented a challenge to the supremacy of the Commons. The irony here is that threshold been met, MPs would have bound themselves (E7; E12; E14; E16; E18). As such, argument hegemony remains in play as the predominate lever for this second step.

Governing competence: MPs cited examples of how other states make changes to their constitutions (E26). However, a problem with this line however, was that all the other states that were mentioned operate within a codified constitution, contrary to the UK practice. As such, these discussions contained information largely irrelevant to CA1. The effect was further debate on the rules for referendums and the lack of them (E4; E5; E8; E9; E11; E14; E15; E21; E26). Even though their arguments were misguided, it was backbenchers and not government that was pushing this issue. The effect is that these insights are deemed insufficient to pass judgement on governing competence as a predominate lever. As such, it is redundant to this investigation.

Party management: given step one had established that party management had collapsed on this issue party management is redundant to this investigation. All subsequent action comes consequent to the destabilising effect of opposition craft on government.

Electoral strategy: for Cunningham, the "strength of the majority" was a critical point in terms of the credibility of the result (E12; E15). He said that given the potential that Commons supremacy could be challenged by a Scottish parliament; the referendum required a higher test than a simple numerical victory (E12; E15). Francis Pym agreed but argued that although the EEC referendum represented a valid test of opinion, it was insufficient when applied to Scottish devolution. As such, he argued, the Commons needed a "tougher" test before MPs took action (E2; E4; E16; E20). For the government John Smith responded that the EEC referendum result had been viewed as "decisive, almost overwhelming" (E14). Smith added that had a threshold been an "obvious" requirement of referendums then it would have been raised in earlier debates (E11; E14; E15; E25). He also noted that had

Cunningham's "test" been applied to the EEC referendum the result would be viewed alternately as having "just scraped by" (E8; E14; E15).

This insight brings this section to a final point on the administration of the referendum and the redefinition of victory to include a forty percent threshold, particularly in respect of turnout. Whilst Jim Sillars argued that it was "possible to depress turnout" (E12; E17; E20; F1; F2; F3; F6; F7; F8; F10; F16), Labour's Norman Buchan disagreed. Buchan, an anti-devolutionist argued that there was no skulduggery involved in CA1. "Each side tries to stimulate its own supporters ... that is not manipulation, it is part of normal political campaigning, and it balances out" (E12). However, an effect of the threshold was that the lower the turnout the higher the margin of victory required (Butler and Ranney, 1994: 44). This meant that a Scottish electoral turnout of nearly eighty percent would have been necessary just to meet the threshold. A lower seventy percent turnout needed a fourteen percent majority, and a sixty percent turnout needed a thirty percent majority (Butler and Ranney, 1994: 44)⁴¹. Sillars added his belief that the death rate on the electoral register is around "1 per cent a month" (E12; E15). He then raised the prospect that given the electoral register being used for the referendum had been compiled in late 1977, by the time the referendum was to take place the register would be out of date by around twelve percent (E12; E15; F1; F2; F3; F6; F7; F8; F10; F16). The effect was that the dead would be counted as 'No' voters, caused by their obvious abstentions (Drucker and Drucker, 1980; Callaghan, 1987). Sillars furthered that "it is possible for us to get 40 per cent of the people eligible to vote given the death of the register, and yet register only 35 percent of the vote as Yes" (E12; E15).

Overall, this inquiry offers examples of the effects of CA1 including attempting to suppressing turnout and locking the electoral register months prior to the referendum date. It meant an artificially inflated electorate, the benefit of which tilted towards the status quo. To this end, electoral strategy remains in play as the predominate lever for this step.

Rule bending: redundant consequence to the Parliament Act (1949).

⁴¹ The turnout in 1979 was in the low sixty percent meaning that a 75/25% margin would have been needed to pass the threshold (Butler and Ranney, 1994).

Summary: the interim causal inference suggested electoral strategy as the predominate lever for this second step. With rule bending ruled out consequent to the Parliament Act (1949), party management having already been undermined following the step one investigation, and governing competence redundant here, this second inquiry focused in the main on argument hegemony and electoral strategy. The purpose was to assess the impact of CA1 via assessing attempts by MPs to justify the change from the simple majority, as way for mitigating the potential of that referendums could one day be binding on the Commons. Ultimately, the threshold was precedent-setting, the culmination if which strongly infers that whilst CA1 was a tool for checking Scottish devolution, as observed in step one, it also served to limit the aforementioned potential of referendums being binding on the Commons (E11; E15; E21). That said, the Commons would have bound itself had the test been surpassed (Qvortrup, 2018). In this light; CA1 was really a tool for ensuring MPs continue having the final, symbolic, say. The threshold artificially inflated the electorate by around ten percent, caused by the deceased remaining on the electoral register. The consequence for ‘Yes’ supporters meant they had to motivate and mobilise its support sufficient to vote because, by comparison, to vote ‘No’, the electorate needed only to sit at home (E12; E14; E15). This effect is deemed as a tactic for artificially suppressing turnout in an election (E12; E14; E15). To this end, electoral strategy is deemed the predominate lever for this second step.

Figure 15: 1978 hoop test probability-2

This outcome reports a one hundred percent probability - results like these are a rarity in the social and political sciences (Beach and Pedersen, 2013). Added, and given Q8’s weak evidence base, as per Table 24 at the outset of this subsection, caution is advised.

Justify the change

This first step premises that CA1 was as an example of institutional insularity, meaning that argument hegemony acted as the predominant lever. Again, four levers are in play here;

argument hegemony, governing competence, party management, and electoral strategy - rule bending being redundant, consequent to the Parliament Act (1949). This approach allowed for a systematic review of the relevance to each statecraft lever and did so by asking four sub-questions. These, and the evidence that support them, are found in Table 25. From there, this sub-section explains the narrative behind the evidence base.

Table 25: 1978 evidence 3

	hoop question	yes/no/contestable	supporting graphs
9	CA1 was designed to help perpetuate the legislative status quo	yes	E1; E2; E4; E7; E9; E11; E16; E21; E22; E24
10	CA1 attempted to undermine the concept of a Scotland-only referendum	yes	E3; E5; E6; E8; E13
11	MPs attempted to sell the threshold to the Scottish electorate	no	no evidence
12	Cunningham acted in the national interest	contestable	E8; E9; E11; E12; E14; E15; E25; E28; E29

(See Appendix 6 for the supporting data)

Argument hegemony: Bulpitt says that political elites have made a habit of being “prepared to engage in all sorts of tinkering with the territorial constitution to maintain or gain power” (1983: 186). That CA1 was designed to help perpetuate the legislative status quo is a tip to both Bulpitt’s perspective and to our earlier assessment that the entire exercise was intended simply to perpetuate Commons supremacy. Indeed, the preceding commentary on the irrevocability of a Scottish parliament, the push for Scottish independence, and the then creeping influence of referendums, on Commons supremacy is central to this same legislative status quo. By definition, as a tool for undermining devolution CA1 was also a tool for protecting the Parliament Act (1949) and, therefore, the legislative status quo.

A part of this process was MPs in English seats having the final say in creating a devolved Scottish chamber (E79; E13; E29). The SNP’s Gordon Wilson argued to this effect that CA1 was precedent for allowing non-Scottish MPs “engage in Scottish affairs” (E5; E27; E28; E29). This was a point that Cunningham denied but who went on to say of devolution that it “affects the whole of the United Kingdom; if it is a half-and-half thing which messes up our system we are entitled to have a say in it” (E9; E29). Conservative Julian Amery furthered that Scottish public opinion had forced government into legislating on devolution (E4; E7; E9). His argument was that the government had considered devolution as necessary to help

maintain the integrity of the state and that to do otherwise would put “the unity of the Kingdom would be at risk” (E15; E28; E29). Indeed, on the subject of Scottish independence, Cunningham had already argued that “only the Scottish people, as defined by the SNP, are entitled to take that decision, and not English Members or English Members with Scottish accents” (E7; E9; E13; E28).

It is difficult to understand Cunningham’s perspective here - devolution would have an impact so all MPs should have a say, but independence is not an issue that should concern non-Scotland MPs. If anything, his comments could also be interpreted that a majority of independence supporting MPs from Scotland is sufficient to unilaterally declare independence (E2; E27; E28). As a perspective, it echoes the fears of Robin Cook that SNP MPs could decamp to Edinburgh and set up an alternate Scottish government (E27; E28). In terms of a Scotland-only referendum whilst CA1 may not have completely undermined the concept, it did set in motion a vehicle for controlling one by testing the result against a pre-set English standard (E11; E12; E14; E21). Indeed, at no point was it noted that MPs considered the effects of their actions on the Scottish electorate, either in terms of the electoral ramifications or public perception. CA1 can be viewed as an institutional backstop, the overall effect of which is that argument hegemony remains in play as the predominate lever for this third step.

Governing competence: MPs argued that government had capitulated to the secessionist impulse that had emanated out of Scotland over the previous decade (E1; E2; E4; E7; E9). CA1 was the product and in tabling his Amendment Cunningham was seeking to preserve the Parliament Act (1949). CA1 helped perpetuate the sovereign, legislative, and electoral status quo. Gordon Wilson complained that MPs were placing “the rights of the House of Commons over the rights of the Scottish people” (E5), and contrary to government policy. Frankel argues the national interest not just being in the interests of government but also the elites (1970: 39), and by definition, this included Cunningham and his sovereign cohort in the Commons. The upshot is that the elites also have a primary interest in achieving statecraft and perpetuating the status quo, and there are times when interested parties will be in conflict - as was the case here. The effect is that having been overwhelmed by an opposition craft that was superior in strategy, tactics, and argument, governing competence is redundant to this investigation.

Party management: given its collapse, this lever is redundant.

Electoral strategy: Julian Amery said that he thought that a Scotland-only vote was wrong in both principle and practice, and that Scotland cannot be separated from England (E4; E13). Cunningham echoed something similar when he stated as justification for the threshold that “devolution does not affect only Scotland” (E7; E9; E13; E15; E29). But whilst English voters were not to have a say in the upcoming referendum, their influence on proceedings cannot be understated. A key justification for the forty percent threshold was its equivalence to the turnout and margin of victory in the earlier referendum on EEC membership (E7; E9; E12; E13; E15). The effect was that the referendum on Scottish devolution was not a test of Scottish opinion, but a test of Scottish opinion set against a pre-set English standard. Indeed, Cunningham admitted that at that EEC referendum Scotland would not have passed “the test” he was now proposing via the threshold (E11; E12; E14; E21). It is through this route that in redefining the franchise, CA1 was designed to help perpetuate the legislative status quo, itself allowing MPs in English seats had a say in that outcome. As such, and consequent to the English participation test CA1 undermined the concept of a Scotland-only referendum. And again, it is reinforced that at no point did MPs attempt to sell the threshold to the Scottish electorate. As such, electoral strategy remains in play as the predominate lever for this third step.

Bending the rules: consequent to the Parliament Act (1949) this lever is redundant.

Summary: this third step has found that consequent to the English test, Scottish sentiment was being tested against a preset, consultative, English standard and where English MPs would have a final say on proceedings. Add in discussion on the benefits of a UK-wide referendum and a number of avenues are opened that allow for the undermining of a Scotland-only referendum. The overall effect is that, having helped preserve the sovereign and electoral status quo, CA1 was, by definition, also helping preserve the legislative status quo. In this respect, Gordon Wilson was correct, all actions discussed point towards the placing personal and institutional needs over and above anything else, including the Scottish people - and in itself is the action of an inward-looking political class (E5; E29; E28; E29). Overall, and in line with the causal framework, argument hegemony acts as the predominant lever for this third step. This inference comes consequent to the data in Table 25, above, and offers a probability rating of fifty percent, as per Figure 16.

Figure 16: 1978 hoop test probability-3

The investigation could not be drawn on an enquiry on whether or not Cunningham acted in the national interest. The national interest was only defined in law in the 1980s, and equates to the interests of the government of the day (Ponting, 1987). Cunningham presents himself as being contrary to government policy and, therefore, also to the UK national interest. In doing so, this scenario offers not a composite response to the fourth hoop test but instead offers provides us with a definition of opposition craft which appears simply to be, an act of statecraft that runs contrary to the national interest.

Chapter conclusions

In the 1950s MPs discussed investing in infrastructural builds across Africa so to extract mineral wealth that had been lost to the UK economy consequent to the independence of India (Abernethy, 2000; Hyam, 2008; Rapoport, 2004; Reynolds, 2015). However, by 1978 the UK's colonial space had been dismantled to the point of non-existence and the secessionist impulses that helped cause this diminution were now present in the domestic space, and on multiple fronts (Nairn, 1968; 1977; Bulpitt, 1983; 1986; Forman, 2002; Alder, 2010; Wilson, 2017). This chapter has looked at the Scottish preconditions, and in respect of CA1 which, this investigation found, did not precipitate a failure of all five statecraft levers. It found further that CA1 acted as a check on the creeping influence of referendums on the Commons and on Scottish devolution, and that CA1 is an indicator of an inward-looking political class. The important combination of a faltering economy, a minority government, and unpopular legislation are important elements for creating the conditions for rebellions to fester and take hold (Bulpitt, 1983; James 2016). This is fertile territory for in-party rebellions, and given the circumstances leading to the tabling of CA1 these are also ripe conditions for opposition craft. The cohort behind CA1 had mobilised to preserve the integrity of the Parliament Act (1949). To do this, they needed to defend the Commons against the establishment of a Scottish parliament and the creeping influence of referendums.

Philpott (2016) said that sovereignty is practiced via a supreme and absolute authority not unlike the divine rights of Kings and having acquired sovereignty, the purpose is to keep it. Here, all actions in support of CA1 point towards the same, and it resulted in MPs placing personal and institutional needs over and above anything else, including the Scottish people. In this respect, Gordon Wilson was correct but, for Cunningham and his supporters, however, to do otherwise would be to take instruction direct from the electorate whilst also creating a rival and irrevocable Scottish chamber. The full outcome from the hoop tests is outlined in Table 26 where, and accumulative probability of seventy-five percent is offered.

Table 26: 1978 hoop tests

Step	Statement	Casual framework	Hoop test	Causal inference
1: argue the need	CA1 precipitated a failure of all five levers	bending the rules		argument hegemony
2: access the impact	CA1 was a check on the creeping influence of referendums on the Commons, as well as a check on Scottish devolution	electoral strategy		electoral strategy
3: justify the change	CA1 presented as an indicator of an inward-looking political class	argument hegemony		argument hegemony

How the Scottish preconditions were influenced by internal and external statecraft is outlined in Figure 17. The chapter finds two-thirds congruence to the conceptual framework, with governing competence replaced by argument hegemony. This one-third divergence can be explained in terms of emphasis on Cunningham, CA1, and opposition craft. CA1 was, in effect, a realist response to a liberalist solution for a constructivist problem.

Figure 17: 1978 casual inferences

When compared with Wood (1981) the events, as described and investigated for this first preconditions stage, is quite unlike that portrayed in his comparative framework. There, a limitation lies in his viewing both government and the state in holistic terms, with little attention paid to the prospects for splits in the party of government. Indeed, that aspect of his (1981) work lies in his second stage, what he called the rise of the secessionist movement. It is at this stage in proceedings when a secessionist movement emerges, a public-facing leadership included whose job it is to persuade the people that their interests are based served under an independent state (Wood, 1981). And it is to there where the next chapter turns its attention.

Chapter seven: rise of the secessionist countermovement

Labour lost the 1979 general election. When in opposition the party continued to offer devolution to the Scottish electorate, and the party boasted high support for the policy (Labour party, 1997; Duclos, 2006). Consequent to a number of performative actions Labour although the campaign for Scottish independence continued. At the same time, the 1980s proved to be fallow years for the SNP, with their only headline victory being a by-election victory in Govan (Mitchell and Hassan, 2016). Only in the 1990s did the party start to record modest improvements in its electoral results. This scenario is problematic given that this chapter should be focusing on the rise of the secessionist movement because ultimately, there wasn't a secessionist movement to investigate. The overall effect is that the second stage in the conceptual framework is at the outset, redundant to this chapter.

Figure 6: statecraft and the rise/movement
(Repeated from pg. 88)

The Thatcher era left a lasting imprint on the UK socially, economically, and politically (see chapters two and three) (Smith, 1991; Minikin, 1993; Alcock, 1997; Williamson, 2000; Baylis and Smith, 2001; Mavroudeas and Papadatos, 2007; Frazer, 2009; Conaghan, 2012). The culmination of her work occurred two years after she had left office when her mid-term successor, John Major oversaw UK membership of the EU single market (see chapter two). This was in 1992, a year in which Major also won a general election, albeit on a thin majority. However, Major had also inherited a party that had within it a growing unrest over EU membership, consequent to which he fought off two separate Eurosceptic-led votes of no confidence as party leader (1993 and 1995) (Curtis, 1999; Gardiner, 1999; Hayton, 2012). The Conservatives lost power in 1997 with Labour returning to power. The parliamentary Conservative party was reduced to a rump smaller than the overall Labour majority. Within a month of coming to power the new Labour government had tabled the Referendums

(Scotland and Wales) Bill (1997) (hereafter, the Bill (1997)) to test for a second time, electoral opinion on Scottish devolution. Over two hundred Amendments were tabled but only a handful of them were chosen for debate. One of them had been tabled by Conservative MP Bill Cash (hereafter, CA2) which called for a UK-wide referendum rather than the proposed Scotland-only vote. What this means for this chapter is that again and as with chapter six, discussions here centre on separatism and not secession and again, is a domestic matter. As such, events in this chapter are based primarily on the Conservative opposition benches. The effect is that the investigations also pertain to external statecraft, this time focusing an opposition craft found on the opposition bench rather than on the government side as was the case with CA1.

This chapter begins with an overview of CA2, its debate, the background to it, the insights of which are central to the creating of a causal framework that are based on observations from the debate. From there an interim causal inference was subjected to process tracing exercises. To assist in this endeavour, three statements were posed, one for each step of the interim inference:

- 4: CA2 was directed at the Commons and not the Conservative party.
- 5: CA2 was the consequence of problems within the Conservative party.
- 6: CA2 was an attempt to preserve the status quo.

A concluding causal inference can be found in the chapter summary.

Policy renewals as statecraft

The decision to hold a second referendum had taken place a year earlier. Duclos claims that Labour politicians had been left red-faced after having assured the electorate and media that there were no plans to hold referendums on Scottish devolution. Indeed, John McAllion, the Shadow Minister for devolution, resigned his position claiming that he had not been consulted on the new policy (Duclos, 2006). Cynicism and scepticism also grew over the proposed two-question referendum - one on the establishment of a parliament and the other on its having tax-raising responsibilities (Labour party, 1997). Duclos (2006) noted disquiet in the Yes campaign over the use of a referendum rather than direct installation, as had been originally planned in 1976. The result was a belief that the Labour leadership was intending undermining devolution, as had occurred in the late 1970s (Duclos, 2006). However, the Bill

(1997) was tabled within a month of Labour returning to power and with the referendum being held only four months after the general election, and in the presence of a rainbow coalition of pro-devolutionist supporters, it was clear that the campaign for a 'Yes' vote had already begun (G6; G7). It took longer for the Conservative dominated 'No' campaign to organise itself, with the Confederation of British Industry (CBI) being a potential ally to this 'new' cause (G15). The CBI claimed that it had no political interest in Scottish devolution and instead, was concerned only with the effect on the economic and business environment of a Scottish parliament with limited responsibilities over taxation (G15). That news aside, the Conservatives were in no fit state to develop and deploy a coherent response to the Bill (1997) (Duclos, 2006). At the 1997 general election the party remained clear in its "opposition to any political reform leading to devolution (let alone independence)" (2006: 141).

The Conservatives had earlier stood on a Scottish manifesto that provided equal footing to both the Leader of the Conservatives in Scotland with the party leader, John Major (Leith, 2006). The intention was to "project a strong sense of Scotland and Scottish national identity" in the manifesto and provide equal merit to Scottishness and 'Britishness' (Leith, 2006: 141). As a policy platform it was little more than a form of window dressing because in practical terms, the only 'constitutional' alteration the Conservatives were offering Scotland at the 1997 general election was a beefed up Scottish Grand Committee (Conservative Party, 1997; Leith, 2006). At the election the Conservatives were wiped out in Scotland and as one of John Major's last acts as Conservative leader, he convened a shadow cabinet sub-committee to coordinate opposition to devolution (G1; G6; G8; G15). Part of the plan was to "adopt" seats that had been lost in Scotland as an attempt to "keep the unionist flag flying" (G15). However, a limitation of this committee became obvious given it was not mandated to discuss party strategy or policy on devolution (G6). Nonetheless, the Conservatives were in turmoil and what was left of it, was in the process of opposing both the Bill (1997) and the stark potential of having to fight a second Scottish devolution referendum.

Whatever the problems the Conservatives were experiencing, the assumption is that the party is more adept at achieving argument hegemony than its political opposition in the Labour party (Gamble, 1993). For Blake (2012), the Conservatives act as the party-political wing of the UK establishment. The picture is of a manoeuvrable broad church of high-end supporters, meaning that the Conservative party will always have friends, regardless of its competencies

or electoral capabilities on display at any one time. Blake furthers that this model provides the roots of unionism and British nationalism are to be found. The effect is that, for Nairn, the UK has never completed the move from absolutism to modern constitutionalism, and remains stuck between two end locations (1977: 75). When there is a pull towards absolutism, it is normally under the direction of the Conservative party (Blake, 2012). Buller and James (2012a) say that these same conditions create space for cartels and sub-groups, sufficiently influential to impact the directions of both party and policy. Indeed, it is this same position that the Conservatives found themselves after the 1997 general election when several wings of the party were attempting to bolster the chances of their favoured candidates winning in the ensuing leadership election (Gardiner, 1999). Whilst this may be a part-reason for their two-to-one electoral successes since Salisbury, the actual product is an argument hegemony that revolves around the aristocracy and rest of the elite ruling classes (Blake, 2012). It is also through this route, Rhodes (1996) argues, where shared purposes emerge and help political parties evolve, and from where a recovery from the natural rate of governance can begin (Bulpitt, 1996; Hopkins, 2011).

The debate on the Bill (1997)

The Bill (1997) represented a departure from the previous referendum legislation from the 1970s in that this one was pre-legislative (Winetrobe, 1997). The ‘pre-legislative’ element meant that essentially, the Commons was being asked to vote on an abstract idea, with the Scottish electorate being placed in the same position (Winetrobe, 1997; Bochel et al, 2013). Labour’s strategy drew criticism from Conservatives and Labour’s Tam Dalyell who took a dim view on the pre-legislative approach. Dalyell was also critical of his party via its seeming pressurising a largely inexperienced Labour intake into supporting the Bill (1997) (Bochel et al, 2013: 46). John Major also claimed the new government was also “inexperienced” government (G6), whereas Conservative leadership candidate, Michael Howard, called the strategy a “silencing debate” (G6). Former Conservative Minister Sir Norman Fowler also attacked the government over its approach to the legislation, saying “their triumphalism and arrogance is already sowing the seeds of their destruction” (G6). Labour Scottish Secretary Donald Dewar denied that a “bullying executive” was “bulldozing” the legislation through parliament in an “unprecedented manner” (G6). The Bill (1997), he argued, was merely a “paving measure” (G6). Added, the referendum had been timetabled for September and the government wanted to keep its schedule on time (G6). A guillotine motion was tabled in response to Conservatives tabling around two hundred Amendments (G1; G2; G3; G4; G6;

G7; G8; G15). Indeed, the Glasgow Herald determined that this Conservative activity was borne out of “paucity and feebleness” (G6). The party also pinned its hopes on the House of Lords blocking the legislation (G1; G3; G7). It was a plan that led Dewar to warn the Lords not to “obstruct” the legislation (G7). Regardless, the Bill (1997) was a manifesto pledge meaning that the Parliament Act (1949) took precedence. Even so, Conservatives were deluding themselves if they thought they could undermine the legislation.

Nonetheless, CA2 was one of the Amendments chosen for debate. Tabled by Bill Cash, who said of the guillotine that it was akin to a “Stalinist dictatorship” (G7). Cash added that the Bill (1997) was a “cruel fraud” that meant the Commons debating in “an unprecedented manner ... not so much a guillotine motion as a lethal injection” (A1; A2; A4; C14), and he said of the Bill (1997) that it promoted a politics that was “inside out and upside down, with principles on the outside and precedents on the downside” (A2; C7).

Cash Amendment (CA2)

CA2 called for a UK-wide referendum rather than the intended Scotland-only vote. For Cash, the Bill (1997) was “a successor to the 1979 devolution legislation⁴²” that comprised a “first-class but a third-rate constitutional Bill” and ultimately, was “riddled with inconsistencies, injustice and contradictions” (A1; A2; A3; A4; C7; C14). For him, the primary point of principle and rationale for tabling CA2 was that “referendums should not be confined to Scotland and Wales - they should encompass the United Kingdom as a whole” (A1; A4; C14). And in a tilt to the pre-legislative nature of the Bill (1997), he furthered that “the Government promised that any tax-varying powers would be defined and limited, but that is not what the Bill or, indeed, the question on the ballot paper says” (A1; C5). “Given the Bill’s tax-varying proposals” he argued, “electors of my constituency and all those of the United Kingdom, including those of England and Northern Ireland, are involved” (A1; A4; C14). This outcome, he called “logic and commons sense” (A1; A2; A4; C14). Consequently, he argued, “any referendum involving the dismembering of the United Kingdom should be referred to the United Kingdom as a whole” (A1; A2; A4; C14). As such, the entire UK electorate should have a vote on the establishment of a devolved Scottish parliament.

⁴² It is also noted that Cash failed to acknowledge that the first devolution referendum had also been held to the exclusivity of the Scottish electorate.

Cash also talked about first-class constitutional Bills, however in the UK no such thing exists - all UK Parliamentary legislation has equal status and it can be assumed that either all legislation is constitutional and therefore 'first-class', or none of it is (Allen, 2015). Either way, Cash did not define what he meant by first-class, but it can be assumed that he was referring to the impact of the legislation as a challenge to the supremacy of the Commons. When the leader of the House sought to correct him, Cash responded by calling for her to be disqualified from office for disagreeing with him (A1; A2; C7). Ultimately, for Cash, CA2 was of sufficient importance to the UK that it should be called the "United Kingdom question" (A1; A2; A4; C3; C7; C14). However, Labour's Tam Dalyell hijacked this attempt at giving CA2 a name and called it the Gary McAllister question⁴³, much to the delight of the newspapers which appeared to credit CA2 to Dalyell and not Cash (A1; A2; A4; C9; C14; F1; F3; F6; F7; G1; G2; G3; G4; G6; G7; G8; G15).

A debate about a debate

There are two points of note in respect of the events following a general election loss. First, it is the optimum time to attempt party reform and second, such times create space for sub-groups and cartels to campaign for enhanced influence (Ostrom, 2005; Poteete, Janssen, and Ostrom, 2010). Either way, the expectation is the emergence of a broad church of ideas and these cannot be understated as drivers of, or responder to, policy change (Bulpitt, 1986a: 21 Ostrom, 2005; Poteete et al, 2010; Weible et al, 2011).

Conditions such as these are fertile ground for gaining insights into how opposition craft is practiced by a cartel. Interest in seemingly fringe or minority political interest's ebb and flow over time and a group or cartel that has a controlling policy or party interest today cannot be guaranteed the same tomorrow (James, 2016; 2018). The consequence is that argument hegemony is always in play, and the idea of a "winning rhetoric in variety of locations" invariably includes the internal party discourse (Bulpitt, 1986a: 21; Ostrom, 2005; Poteete et al, 2010; Weible et al, 2011). As such, the importance of argument hegemony as a vehicle for policy renewal cannot be understated (Bulpitt, 1983; James, 2016; 2018). The upshot here is that when a party does not have an effective policy platform, party discipline will ultimately become problematic and a party that does not maintain broad congruence with the prevailing socio-political wind is likely to find itself selling yesterday's fashion to the electorate. Where

⁴³ Gary McAllister was a Scottish footballer who at the time played in England (Macpherson, 2018).

such occasions occur, it becomes harder for the affected party to adopt new policies and enhance the potential for a return to government (James, 2012). However, a failed argument hegemony will also undermine an electoral strategy, the effect of which could easily lead to the forming of more cartels and more in-party fragmentation (Bulpitt, 1983; 1976; James, 2012; 2016). This insight adds fuel to Harris' (1998) idea that the return of Labour to government helped catalyse the Conservative right into action, given the government's mandate for reform. In all, the Bill (1997) acted as a window of opportunity for Cash to express a hard-right policy on Scottish devolution. Yet, given that CA2 did not stand a chance of being successful its being tabled and debated offered the opportunity for the Conservatives to debate party policy in the open. In the end, CA2 gained the support of half (eighty MPs) of the 1997 Conservative intake into the Commons (Hansard, 1997), and in itself, offers an insight into the attitudes and political positioning within the Parliamentary Conservative party at the time. As such, CA2 offers the potential for offering further descriptors of cartel opposition craft using, in this case, via sequestering the legislative system being for party political purposes.

CA2 acts as the basis for a second three-step causal framework. Step one sees Cash taking a position on Scottish devolution. Argument hegemony is deemed to act as the predominate lever. Step two concerns his attempts to mobilise support on the Conservative benches, which is considered as presenting as a case of party management. Step three, an attempt at changing policy is considered to be an act of governing competence.

Figure 18: 1997 causal framework

Results

This section is in three parts, with each sub-section offering an in-depth review of the three steps - (1) take a position; (2) mobilise the support; and (3), change the policy. The purpose is to test the integrity of the causal framework and to reiterate from the chapter introduction, three statements were made - one for each of the three steps.

- 4: CA2 was more directed at the Commons than the Conservative party
- 5: CA2 was the consequence of the leadership problems within the Conservative party
- 6: CA2 was an attempt at preserving the status quo

Insights into each of the three statements are gained through asking a further set of four hoop tests (Collier, 2010; Beach and Pedersen, 2013), one set per question and specific to each of the three steps. The purpose is to identify predominate statecraft levers for each of the three steps by empirically testing the evidence for congruence to the interim causal inference, with the results being found in the conclusion to this chapter. The observation is that CA2 acted as a driver for redefining the franchise for the then upcoming devolution referendum. The result is an interim causal inference, as indicated in Figure 19, which has been latterly tested using process tracing.

Figure 19: 1997 interim causal inferences

Take a position

The statement for this first step in the interim causal inference implies that CA2 was directed at the Commons and not the Conservative party, and that argument hegemony acted as the predominant lever. Four levers are in play here; argument hegemony, governing competence, party management, and electoral strategy - rule bending being redundant, consequent to the Parliament Act (1949). This approach allowed for a systematic review of the relevance to each statecraft lever and did so by posing four statements. These, and the evidence that support them, are found in Table 27. From there, this sub-section explains the narrative behind the evidence base.

Table 27: 1997 evidence 4

	hoop question	yes/no/unknown	supporting data
13	there was a consensus amongst Conservatives that devolution should come at a cost	yes	E42; E44; E53; E56; E57; E58; E61
14	Cash attempted to find consensus across the Commons	no	E33; E34; E35; E37; E41; E46
15	Cash was focused on promoting a UK-wide vote	no	E34; E35; E41; E43; E44; E46; E49; E53
16	Conservatives were focused on promoting a UK-wide vote	no	E33; E40; E42; E43; E44; E36; E47; E49; E51; E53; E54; E55; E56; E57; E58; E59; E60; E61

(See Appendix 7 for the supporting data)

Argument hegemony: neither Cash nor the Conservatives were focused on promoting a UK-wide vote. Francis Maude aside, Cash spoke the least on the topic of all Conservatives (E35; E54; E55; E56; E57; E58; E59; E60; E61). Instead, he talked about a wide range of other issues, none of which MPs were voting on, including Scottish representation in the Commons, Europe, EVEL, and a Cunningham-style threshold of sixty percent (E34; E35; E41; E43; E44; E46; E49; E53; G1; G6; G8; G15). Where Conservatives did talk in favour of a UK-wide referendum, the base argument leaned on primordialism (E34; E36; E41; E43; E46; G2; G3; G6; G7). Peter Luff argued that that it was an “outrage” that “Scots men and women, born in Scotland ... are being denied ... their birth right” (E34; E41; E45; E48; E56). Mark Garnier criticised the “illogical” disenfranchising of the Scottish Diaspora whilst giving a vote to EU citizens that were resident in Scotland (E34; E40; E43; E46; E48; E60). Cash cited non-Scots residents from Europe or elsewhere in the world who were temporarily located in Scotland having a vote in the absence of reciprocal arrangements with third countries (E34; E35; E43; E48). Another Conservative, Michael Fallon, remained largely on point; particularly given his argument coalesced around the abstract idea of a “continuing connection” with Scotland being sufficient to vote in the planned 1997 devolution referendum (E45; E47; E59). The approach did little to attempt finding consensus across the Commons and, indeed, it didn’t help that Cash had begun his promotion of CA2 by arguing that the Bill (1997) had been:

Conceived in a cuckoo's nest of a Cabinet that is controlled by a Scots cabal of Ministers of the Crown, representing the biggest takeover of the United Kingdom since the Union, in 1603, of the Crowns of Scotland and England. A quarter of all Ministers are Scots - 19 of the 89 Ministers are Scots. I mentioned a Scots cabal, and I

should explain that I define “cabal” as something representing conceit, arrogance, bombast, aggression and lies.

He continued by arguing that:

The plain fact is that the Bill represents the views that were expressed by the Prime Minister in the general election campaign and in the Labour party manifesto. However, his euphoria will be dashed - as was that of the Stuarts, in 1649, when Charles I lost his head because of his folly and his arrogance (E33; E35; E41; E46).

As an approach his style was somewhat dubious and, indeed, it did not go unnoticed. Labour’s John McAllion considered Cash and other Conservative speakers to be promoting the politics of English nationalism (E34). To this end, he called Cash and the cartel “a bunch of dinosaurs” (E37)⁴⁴. Nonetheless, where CA2 was relatively successful was in encouraging a consensus amongst Conservatives that devolution should come at a political cost. Cash said that “after the creation of a Scottish Parliament, it would be reasonable for us to propose changing our Standing Orders so that MPs from Scottish constituencies would be entitled to speak and not vote in the circumstances that I have described” (E35; E44; E46). EVEL was offered as a solution, as was the recommended reduction in MPs from Scotland. There, Cash is further noted to have argued:

There are at present 72 Scottish Members of Parliament. Some 30 years ago, the Kilbrandon commission on the constitution recommended that the number should be reduced and, indeed, one of my amendments proposes that it should be reduced to 45, which is, appropriately, the same number as when the Act of Union 1706 was passed (E34; E35; E53).

For Cash, this action was needed if the Commons was to maintain its supremacy post-Scottish devolution, and in a tip towards the Parliament Act (1949) he also posited of the Bill (1997) that it:

Left in limbo the role of the Secretary of State for Scotland, which, given his remarks today, is no doubt what he deserves. It is essential that it is clearly reaffirmed, just as the sovereignty of the United Kingdom should also be reaffirmed in the Bill (E46; E53).

Cash was not alone in believing that devolution should come at a cost to Scottish representation in the Commons (E44; E53; E57). That he was not operating alone indicates the presence of a cabal operating opposition craft. Nonetheless, the debate on CA2 allowed

⁴⁴ McAllion argued further that “It is [was] difficult not to come to the conclusion that the speeches we are hearing from Conservative Members are basically anti-Scottish. All the talk of Scotland being over-represented, of fiscal transfers and of the English taxpayer paying for the services provided for the people of Scotland is, frankly, racist. The hon. Member for Stone (Mr. Cash) introduced the debate in an offensive manner. It is offensive to have the ability of Cabinet members questioned on the basis of their ethnic origin (E34; E37).

Conservatives to verbalise a policy platform that was largely contrary to the official party line (E34; E35; E38; E40; E43; E45; E48; E54; E55; E56; E57; E58; E59; E60; E61), and to this end, argument hegemony remains in play as the predominate lever for this first step.

Governing competence: having been reduced to a rump grouping smaller than the Labour majority, it was evident that neither Cash nor the wider Conservative cohort could outmanoeuvre a government that had executed a to-the-book monopolisation of the Commons timetable (Bulpitt, 1983; James, 2016). The consequence is that the opposition's failure to focus fully on CA2 was a consequence of the guillotine, leading to a proxy-debate comprising of those other two hundred Amendments denied debating time (G1; G2; G3; G4; G6; G7; G8 G11; G13; G15). If it was intentional, as a strategy it was not effective because ultimately, Cash was asking MPs to vote on a UK-wide franchise and nothing else, whilst at the same time promoting a policy platform much further to the right of the official party position (Gardiner, 1999). Indeed, Labour's Henry McLeish commented that Conservatives had "ranged wide" in their support of CA2 (E46). To this end, in a debate where neither Cash nor Conservatives attempted to promote the merits of a UK-wide vote, where he failed to find consensus across the Commons, and where the only agreement offered to him was in respect of devolution coming at a cost, governing competence is redundant as the predominate lever for this first step.

Party management: it is important to note that via CA2, Cash promoted a fundamentally different policy platform to that promoted by the Conservative leadership (E34; E35; E41; E43; E44; E46; E49; E53; G1; G6; G8; G15). The platform was concerned with the relationship between the state and Scotland, with the cabal consensus being that devolution should come at a cost (E34; E35; E44; E46; E53). That there was no attempt to garner support from across the Commons further hints that Cash was more interested in changing minds in the party rather than the wider House (E34; E35; E53). Ostensibly, Cash was exerting pressure on the leadership and despite his blunderbuss approach he was achieving this outcome. The upshot was, however, that the Conservative party was in a post-electoral mess and CA2 was a product of a hard right cartel that had a recent history of in-party rivalry (Gardiner, 1999). Whilst this insight hints at argument hegemony taking place, it is itself an issue of party management consequent to the ongoing leadership election. As such, party management remains active as a candidate for the predominate lever for this step.

Electoral strategy: as was noted earlier, Cash was not focused on promoting a UK-wide referendum (E34; E35; E41; E43; E44; E46; E49; E50; E53). But neither were his party colleagues, given that not one Conservative speaker spent more than half of their contributions to the debate discussing the merits of a UK-wide referendum (E34; E36; E39; E40; E42; E43; E44; E46; E47; E49; E51; E53; E54; E55; E56; E57; E58; E59; E60; E61). Indeed, given that a number of issues raised in the debate centring on peripheral or ideological perspectives, Conservative Michael Fallon was fairly unique in questioning the administrative arrangements for the referendum which, he argued, could cause Scots serving in the military and located outside the country to be disenfranchised (E51; E59). His comments were supported by Michael Howard and Bernard Jenkin (E55; E58). However, the UK government had also made provisions for proxy and postal votes (BBC, 1997). Nonetheless, given the likelihood for victory and given that Cash didn't overly promote a UK-wide vote in his speech; it is fair to say that in terms of electoral strategy, CA2 was performative. The meaning here is that in terms of the predominant lever for this first step, electoral strategy is redundant.

Rule bending: consequent to the Parliament Act (1949), this lever is redundant.

Summary: this step tested the potential that CA2 was directed at the Commons and not the Conservative party. Following examination this assertion is incorrect and instead, the opposite is true (E33; E35; E37; E41; E46). Cash' audience was the Conservative rump and not the wider Commons and it is a position reinforced by evidence confirming that neither Cash nor the Conservatives were focused on promoting a UK-wide vote. Through CA2, Cash was calling for something more extreme than what was on offer by the party and the outgoing leader. The investigation noted an emergent consensus between Conservatives that there should be a political cost to Scottish devolution. In general terms however, the topics Conservatives spoke on can be categorised in terms of militarism, primordialism, and Commons supremacy, and were typical of a blood and soil politic that has traditionally been found in the hard right of the Conservative party (Shils, 1957; Curtis, 1999; Gardiner, 1999; Hayton, 2012). Added, it cannot be helpful to criticise or belittle the very people needed for CA2 to be successful, but this is what Cash and some of his cohort did, hence John McAllion calling them "a bunch of dinosaurs" (E37). The appearance is that CA2 was an act underpinned by a hard right cartel intent on forcing a change in Conservative policy on Scotland, all the while sequestering the Commons to advance its cause.

Overall, the main justification for holding a UK-wide vote appears not to be the furthering of an electoral strategy but this lever is redundant, as was governing competence. Put simply, the Conservatives were in a mess and were arguing amongst themselves and in public about the direction of party policy on Scotland. The party was demoralised and existed in political terms as name only, and a cartel was looking to shift policy to the right. Cash took a position on Scotland. Through CA2, Cash sequestered the Commons and when on his feet he spoke of a number of issues that offer insight into his general stance on Scotland and its place under UK governance. At the vote, half the Conservative MPs opted to agree with him. This may read like party management territory but it is not. Instead, the investigation finds CA2 as ideological and, as such, argument hegemony acts as the predominate lever for this first step.

Figure 20: 1997 hoop test probability-4

Whilst it should be noted that this insight comes with only a twenty-five percent probability, as per Figure 20, above, a number of arguments that inform on argument hegemony come consequent to the insights gleaned from the failing hoop tests.

Mobilise the support

The statement for this second step in the interim causal inference implies that CA2 was a consequence of the problems within the Conservative party, and that party management acted as the predominant lever. Four levers are in play here; argument hegemony, governing competence, party management, and electoral strategy - rule bending being redundant, consequent to the Parliament Act (1949). This approach allowed for a systematic review of the relevance to each statecraft lever and did so by asking four sub-questions. These, and the evidence that support them, are found in Table 28. From there, this sub-section explains the narrative behind the evidence base.

Table 28: 1997 evidence 5

	hoop question	yes/no	supporting data
17	the Conservative leadership supported CA2	yes	E35; E55
18	Conservative speakers offered alternatives to CA2	no	E30; E31; E32; E45; E49; E51
19	Conservatives MPs were critical of CA2	no	insufficient evidence
20	the Conservative leadership offered an alternative to CA2	no	insufficient evidence

(See Appendix 7 for the supporting data)

Argument hegemony: Michael Howard led for the Conservative front bench (E55). Like Cash, he was a Eurosceptic and was to be found on the right of the party (Curtis, 1999; Gardiner, 1999). Howard was also a candidate in the party leadership election, so it is arguable that CA2 provided him a soapbox from which he could advertise his policies as leader. He noted that Conservative policy was not supportive of CA2 before going on to disregard this same policy. He then spoke at length about a number that had been previously raised by Cash and other Conservatives - EVEL, the “over-representation” of Scottish constituencies, and the financial servicing of Scotland by Westminster (E46; E53; E55). He also offered his “sympathy” for CA2 and commented similarly to the English primordial and militaristic postures detected in the investigation for step one, above (E34; E41; E43; E55). These elements were summed up by him when talking of the effects of a Scotland-only referendum:

Behind it lies the real difficulty encountered by those who happen temporarily to be resident elsewhere in the United Kingdom, who are to be given no voice on a matter that touches not only on the government of Scotland and Wales but on the administration of the whole of the United Kingdom ... I cannot begin to see any genuine patriotism in disfranchising those Scottish and Welsh soldiers who form some of the finest regiments in the British army ... The Bill denies a say to many natives of Wales and Scotland, while giving a say to citizens of the European Union who happen to be residing temporarily in those countries. So, in some cases there will be a vote for people born in Athens but not in Arbroath, a vote for people born in Samos but not in Stornoway (E34; E41; E43; E55).

Howard did not offer an alternative to CA2 and, indeed, neither did any other Conservatives who spoke in the debate. They did, however seek to build on it by adding more components, as per the discussions outlined above in step one. This included raising concerns for the need for constitutional reform, specifically EVEL, as a response to Scottish devolution (E44). By

definition, if there was any criticism of CA2 it is that it did not go far enough. The causal problems may have been party-related but the consequence was the emergence of the battle of ideas which had implications elsewhere. In effect, Conservative backbenchers were calling for a more robust response from the leadership. The culmination was Howard supporting CA2 contrary to party policy and to this end, argument hegemony remains in play as the predominate lever for this step.

Governing competence: whilst the leadership had expressed sympathies for a number of backbench concerns, it offered little in the way of a challenge to the Bill (1977) or even an alternative to CA2. The leadership had planned to submit a Cunningham-style threshold Amendment, but this did not happen (Winetrobe, 1997). John Redwood, another leadership candidate and again, an ally of Cash, did table an Amendment calling for a fifty percent threshold, but consequent to the guillotine it was not debated (G7). Given these insights the indication here is that the observable problems within the Conservative party were systemic, resulting in paralysis in the leadership and wider party machine. The product was a comment by Howard - a statement on behalf of the leadership. He said, “If the Government's proposals are to acquire real legitimacy - which must be their objective and *we do not seek to challenge it* - they must provide convincing answers” (E55). In effect, it was a capitulation and, as such, governing competence is redundant to this investigation.

Party management: Cash had complained that the shadow Cabinet did not formally whip CA2 (E35; E55). He believed that had the leadership acted otherwise they would have been continuing to reinforce the manifesto that the Conservatives had stood on a month earlier at the general election. The decision not to whip effectively gave Conservative MPs a free vote on CA2, and in doing so adds further congruence to the indication in the evidence base that the Conservative leadership failed to support Cash (see Table 28, above). However, and as has already been noted, Michael Howard was more vocal in this respect resulting in his failing to adhere to the basic principle of a united front by the wider leadership collective (E55). And between them, Cash and Howard took up around a quarter of the entire debate, as per Tables 29 and 30, with both saying roughly the same thing, the bulk of which was contrary to party policy (E35; E55).

Table 29: word share by party

	% Share
Conservatives	58
Labour	30
LibDems	10
SNP	1
Total	99

Table 30: Conservative contributors

	% Share
Cash	16
Fallon	7
Garnier	3
Grieve	1
Heathcoat-Amory	7
Howard	10
Jenkin	5
Luff	9
Maude	0
Total	58

(Percentages and numbers do not include the Speaker)

Aided by an ineffective and weak whip system, Howard's failure to toe the party line was an internal matter and indicates an evident failure of party management (Bulpitt, 1983; Hopkins 2011). But in line with other Conservative MPs, he was not critical of CA2 and also called for further reform as a response the establishment of a Scottish parliament (E44; E53; E55). Howard, however, was in-step with the leadership insofar that despite his criticisms, he also failed to offer any alternatives to CA2. The overall indication here is that again, CA2 was the consequence of the problems within the Conservative party and, in this case, allowed Howard to soapbox his leadership credentials. To this end, party management remains in play as the predominate lever for this second step.

Electoral strategy: this investigation has already accrued insights in respect of the failure of the leadership or other Conservative speakers to offer alternatives to CA2, or in the case of the leadership offer support to it (E55). That CA2 was the consequence of the problems within the Conservative party only forms a part of the picture. As such, investigating this lever is not as straightforward as could be first thought. The Bulpittian perspective that sees statecraft centring on winning the next election, Conservatives were facing three - the devolution referendum, the leadership election, and the inevitable long term matter of the next general election. And, whilst there is little doubt that CA2 came consequent to the problems within the Conservative party, it is not clear from the debate which of the three elections took priority. This lack of clarity leads this investigation to assess that electoral strategy is redundant as the predominate lever for this second step.

Rule bending: consequent to the Parliament Act (1949), this lever is redundant.

Summary: As for step one, this second investigation also boils down to an almost fifty-fifty choice outcome in respect of argument hegemony or party management acting as predominate lever for this step. The inference is that CA2 had come consequent to a failure of party leadership, particularly given the party failure to take a supporting stance on Cash' Amendment. Yet at the same time, the Conservative leadership was sufficiently shrewd in opting to not whip Conservative MPs. Not whipping offered the leadership a quick test of opinion whereas whipping them could have caused a rebellion and led to further fragmentation (Cowley, 2012). By definition, this scenario presents as an exercise in the battle of ideas - specifically, a new policy platform as response to Scottish devolution (E42; E43; E44; E45; E46; E49). That Howard and Cash, both from the same wing of the party, were able to utilise the legislative process to soapbox a hard-right policy was essential here, particularly given that it took place during the party leadership election.

Whilst it is important to note that Howard was a candidate for leader, the observation is also coincidental. It is also entirely possible that the failure of the Conservative leadership to develop a coherent counterstrategy was the opportunity Howard needed to soapbox. To this end, and whilst the importance of argument hegemony cannot be understated, this investigation finds party management as the predominate lever for this second step. As with step one, this finding also comes with a lowly twenty-five percent probability.

Figure 21: 1997 hoop test probability-5

The statement for this first step in the interim causal inference implies that CA2 was an attempt to preserve the status quo, and that governing competence acted as the predominant lever. Four levers are in play here; argument hegemony, governing competence, party management, and electoral strategy - rule bending being redundant, consequent to the Parliament Act (1949). This approach allowed for a systematic review of the relevance to

each statecraft lever and did so by asking four sub-questions. These, and the evidence that support them, are found in Table 31. From there, this sub-section explains the narrative behind the evidence base.

Table 31: 1997 evidence 6

	hoop question	yes/no	supporting data
21	CA2 challenged Conservative policy	Yes	E34; E35; E36; E39; E40; E41; E42; E43; E44; E45; E47; E48; E49; E50; E51; E52; E53; E54; E55; E56; E57; E58; E59; E60; E61
22	Conservatives were concerned with the irrevocability of a Scottish parliament	Yes	E50; E53
23	Cash attempted to undermine referendums as electoral events	No	no evidence
24	CA2 was an act of necessity	Unknown	insufficient evidence

(See Appendix 7 for the supporting data)

Argument hegemony: it was observed earlier that Cash had not reached out across the Commons. Whilst the tone of his argument and the response had been a considerable influence in coming to that particular outcome, not everything he said was spurned by those outwith the hard right of the Conservative party or indeed, MPs from other parties. One issue where a consensus of sorts emerged was in relation to Kilbrandon, particularly regards reducing Scottish representation in the Commons post devolution. Michael Howard said that the Labour government had yet to “address the over-representation of constituencies in Scotland” (E42; E44; E45; E53; E55). Consequentially, MPs found themselves proactively debating the merits of an English parliament (E44), including David Heathcoat-Amory who said of MPs from Scotland that, following devolution, Scottish MPs will, in effect, be idle⁴⁵ (E34; E36; E44; E46; E53; E57). The idea resonated with LibDem MP Robert MacLennan, formerly of the Labour party, who argued that “Scots would have not only the right to speak, but to vote not only on United Kingdom matters but on matters affecting parts of England for which they do not have direct responsibility or responsibilities which are discharged” (E31; E44; E46; E53). More moderate Conservatives spoke, including Dominic Grieve who asked “at what point will the anxieties of, or the knock-on effects on, the people in England be

⁴⁵ They will have nothing to do in their own constituencies ... They will, however, apparently continue to come to this Parliament in the same numbers in order to interfere in matters that apply to England, and to my constituents in particular (E34; E36; E44; E46; E53; E57).

addressed” (E44; E45). Grieve added that “those of us who believe in the Union and want it to survive are concerned that devolution will lead to an explosive situation, we want to prevent that” (E46; E50; E61).

Grieve was talking about the prospect of Scottish independence and in doing so provides this thesis a certain irony in his advocating for the establishment of one devolved parliament whilst also complaining about the effects of creating another. Nonetheless, for Grieve there was inevitability to a Scottish parliament and as an unspoken issue, the irrevocability of a Scottish parliament was the vehicle that would push Scotland to the precipitancy. It was a point that Cash had also recognised. He said that “we [MPs] shall face not only the dismembering of the United Kingdom ... but a Trojan horse for reducing the component parts of the United Kingdom to provinces”⁴⁶ (E35; E50). And with that, Cash noted the potential of a rival chamber, just as had been argued in 1978 during the debate on CA1. This enduring concern was, for Cash, an “unreal” situation but “is [was] real because it has arisen” (E35; E50). Overall, the assessment is that CA2 did challenge Conservative policy, with a justification being a concern over the irrevocability of a Scottish parliament. However, whilst Conservatives called to protect the Parliament Act (1949), there was no evidence of concern that the Commons could be dictated to via binding referendums. As such, and regardless that it is unknown that CA2 was an act of necessity borne of opposition craft, there is sufficient evidence to keep argument hegemony in play as the predominate lever for this third step.

Governing competence: policy development and its selection are a necessary component of governing competence, but it does not comprise all of it. A shared or communal political purpose is particularly importance, especially if a party is to present even a semblance of competence (Rhodes, 1996; Hopkins, 2011; James, 2016). It is through this lens that this investigation views Cash’s blunderbuss approach to the debate in respect of his verbalising of a swathe of policies in respect of Scotland, all of them contrary to official party policy (E34; E35; E42; E43; E44 E45; E47; E53). In fairness, he was speaking in a vacuum and he could have said anything to attempt to fill it. As such, this action is less a matter of governing

⁴⁶ Cash further added that “anyone who thinks that the Bill does not go to the heart of the future of the United Kingdom should not be sitting in this House as a Minister. We should repudiate any possibility of the Bill being a trojan horse for reducing the component parts of the United Kingdom to provinces within the European Union and reaffirm the direct accountability, [whether] in Scotland [or Wales], of Ministers of the Crown exclusively to the United Kingdom Parliament” (E35; E40; E46).

competence and more to do with the source and cause of the vacuum, and this implies party management. To this end, governing competence is redundant to this third step.

Party management: Cash had spoken about CA2 being congruent to the election manifesto that the Conservatives stood on a month beforehand, however, the leadership decided not to Whip Conservatives into supporting CA2 (E35). Michael Howard said as much when he said the Conservatives did not intend challenging the legitimacy of the Bill (1997) (E55). But as a point of reference his position centred on the policy being up for negotiation. The problem here is that as said earlier, other than an anti-independence stance, there wasn't really a policy in place. As such, none of what Cash was calling for adhered to Conservative policy, and the same applies to his party colleagues who spoke in the debate (E34; E42; E43; E44; E45; E49). By proxy, CA2 challenged Conservative policy, and whilst Conservatives were concerned with the irrevocability of a Scottish parliament, they did so in response to the policy vacuum at the heart of the party.

It has also been noted that Cash made no attempt to undermine referendums as electoral events. One reason for this posture lay in the reality that Cash was anti-EU and supported a referendum on that issue (Gardiner, 1999). Despite being a Conservative MP, Cash had links to Sir James Goldsmith and had undertaken research work on his behalf as preparation for the establishment of the Referendum Party (Curtis, 1999; Gardiner, 1999). Goldsmith's party had at the 1997 general election unsuccessfully campaigned on the single issue of holding a referendum on UK membership of the EU (Curtis, 1999; Gardiner, 1999). For Cash, if his contribution to the debate on CA2 was anything to go by, he had not given up on his anti-EU posture and a referendum remained an important tactic in achieving his longer-term political aims. But whilst it made sense for him not to mention referendums, the circumstances behind the decision are entirely an issue of party management and, as such, this lever remains in play as the predominate lever for this step.

Electoral strategy: as outlined above, a wealth of evidence exists sufficient to suggest that CA2 was directly challenging Conservative policy (E34; E35; E42; E43; E44 E45; E47; E53). However, whilst CA2 may present as some form of electoral strategy, the rationale behind it lies in the belief that others should have a say on Scottish devolution (E30; E45), and this is argument hegemony. As such, electoral strategy is redundant to this third step.

Summary: consistent with the investigations for the first and second steps, this third step also boils down to a predominate either-or in respect of argument hegemony and party management. This investigation sought to find the potential that CA2 was an attempt at preserving the status quo. In reality, the integrity of the state and pre-existing institutions aside, there was nothing to preserve - Scotland was having a referendum on devolution whether it wanted one or not and the Conservatives were mere bystanders to this eventuality. The reality of the situation is that the next time the Conservatives formed a government the structure of the state would be fundamentally different and the party needed to develop a policy to reflect this new reality (Rhodes, 1996; Hopkins, 2011; James, 2012). For Cash, the answer lay with seeking to protect Commons supremacy (E35; E46). His hard-right colleague Bernard Jenkin, pretty much said so himself. “It is fine for Scotland to have its own Parliament” he said, “but it is quite another matter for Scotland to have its own Parliament while remaining a member of the United Kingdom” (E46; E48; E58). Through CA2, Cash challenged Conservative policy on an irrevocable Scottish parliament and for them, Michael Howard, and the other backbenchers who spoke in support, the cost should be a reduction in the number of Scottish constituencies, ideally to forty-five MPs (E35; E46; E53). However, CA2 was performative and spoke more to the parliamentary Conservative party than the rest of the House. In doing so, the action provided Michael Howard the ability to soapbox his leadership campaign and he used his time to appeal to the right of the parliamentary party.

Ultimately, the indication is that CA2 was an exercise in cartel-led opposition craft that sequestered the legislative system for political gain. Nonetheless, and regardless of its weak posture, CA2 was an attempt to preserve the status quo. Credit to Cash, however, comes via his being in the unusual position of being a Conservative MP not just with a vision, but of a type that offered clarity on what he did and did not want. The problem is, however, the debate was playing out in public and whilst it is possible to construct an abstract argument as to why CA2 could be construed as an act of necessity. However, in reality his position was founded from a very lowly position. To this end, this investigation finds in favour of party management as predominate lever for this third and final stage. This finding comes with a fifty percent probability.

Figure 22: 1997 hoop test probability-6

Chapter conclusions

This chapter could not investigate the rise of Scotland's secessionist movement because one did not emerge. The effect is that Scotland does not fit the model as set out by Wood (1981) and, as such, the competence of the conceptual framework is vulnerable to criticism. Instead, this chapter reviewed the rise of a secessionist countermovement led by a hard-right cabal that deployed opposition craft to catalyse reform of Conservative policy towards Scotland. Founded on a combination of primordialism, militarism, and an overtly Eurosceptic posture, the countermovement had as its base goal, the perpetuation of Commons supremacy. In reality however, CA2 was nothing more than a front-loading ruse. It had little or no chance of the Commons voting for it, and as such its tabling was a performative gesture that did little to offer even a short term challenge to the Bill (1997). Instead, the assessment is that CA2 was intended to catalyse debate in the parliamentary Conservative party and not the Commons. The position was that if Scotland must have devolution, it should come at the cost of reduced representation in the Commons, all the while the centre retained indirect but full control, as per Bulpitt (1983) and as first postured by Salisbury via his Home-Rule trade off (Marsh, 1978). The cabal also called for the establishment of an English parliament to cater for EVEL. This thesis doesn't place much importance on this policy because it appears more an attempt to muddy the waters around Scottish devolution rather than its being a long-held political aspiration because to act accordingly could potentially undermine the sanctity of the Parliament Act (1949).

However, CA2 was not a complete attempt at preserving the status quo, particularly given the cabal's strategic interest in using a referendum to test opinion on EU membership (Gardiner, 1999). The state border notwithstanding, this chapter assesses that there was nothing to preserve in terms of either state or party structure, or indeed, the influence of referendums on the Commons. This insight is slightly problematic for this study given that with this thesis

defining statecraft in terms of how the elites respond to real world events as they seek to perpetuate the status quo. Here, the cabal were never in a position to satisfy this need, in the short to middling term at least. Longer term, the accumulative intention was to lift the bar to independence, and from within a system where a Scottish parliament would be exposed to interference and erosion. In practice this means either a UK-wide vote in line with CA2, or potentially a threshold of sixty percent threshold in the event of a Scotland-only vote.

Table 32: 1997 hoop tests

Step	Statement	Causal framework	Hoop test	Causal inference
4: take a position	CA2 was directed at the Commons and not the Conservative party	argument hegemony		argument hegemony
5: mobilise the support	CA2 was the consequence of problems within the Conservative party	party management		party management
6: change the policy	CA2 was an attempt to preserve the status quo	governing competence		party management

To this end, the investigations undertaken for this chapter found that although CA2 called for a UK-wide vote on Scottish devolution, as a lever for advancing an electoral strategy, it did nothing. Governing competence was redundant to this investigation meaning that the overriding inference is a combination of party management and argument hegemony, with the results favouring the former over the latter by a two thirds ratio. The overall result is a causal inference, with an accumulative probability of thirty-three percent, as visualised in Figure 23.

Figure 23: 1997 causal inferences

The outcome is that it is fair to say that even before Scotland had voted on a devolved parliament, a hard-right countermovement was plotting to respond with the political equivalent of a tiger cage. The overall effect is that as had been the case with Cunningham and CA1, CA2 could also be viewed as a realist response to a liberalist solution for a constructivist problem.

In September 1997 the Scottish electorate voted ‘Yes’ to a Scottish parliament and ‘Yes’ to its having tax-raising powers (Devine, 2012; Dalyell, 2016; Leith and Sim, 2020). The devolved Scottish parliament was founded twenty months later, in May 1999. Any fears of its being a rival to the Commons appear misplaced. Indeed, Keating (2021) says that the knock-on effects of devolution settlements have been nugatory and in terms of the functions of the state, nothing has really changed. In reality, devolution is a mere bolt-on to the existing state system, through which the UK retains the ability to overrule Scotland’s government and parliament, just as Bulpitt (1983) had predicted. However, Keating has since argued that the UK has also found it difficult in adjusting to devolution (2021: VI), and a pessimism has set in within the central government. The causation is in part offered by Leith in that the UK was “no longer alone in her state” (2006: 11). However, devolution has done little to depressurise Scotland’s secessionist impulse, as warned by numerous MPs in both the debates on CA1 and CA2.

Tam Dalyell said that devolution was the stone from where “creepy crawly creatures emerge” (2016: 70), by which he means as a platform for a push for independence. That time came in 2011 when the SNP won a majority in the Scottish parliament and entered into negotiations with the UK government on holding an independence referendum.

Chapter eight: the dual polity in the precipitancy

Labour had been in power for thirteen years. Tony Blair was in office for a decade and his early years in office oversaw the completion of the two decade long reform programme identified in this thesis (see chapter two, Table 2), brought through the liberalisation of interest rates, tax reform to include credits, and through reforming public expenditure to adhere to a new practice definition of poverty (Alcock, 1997). As had been noted in the previous chapter, Blair's government introduced legislation on a referendum on Scottish devolution in his first month in office. In 2007, and a month before he resigned as Prime Minister, the SNP gained control of the Scottish government and in doing Blair oversaw the near-end of a trajectory that the academics and politicians had previously warned about (Sorens, 2012; Griffiths (a), 2016). Gordon Brown was his replacement and he had a torrid time in office. He was regularly criticised by the press for a less slick political and personal presentation than his predecessor. However, his real problems began when the US sub-prime market collapsed and had a knock-on effect across the West (Greenspan, 2008; Bini Smaghi, 2008; US Securities and Exchange Commission, 2008; Jickling, 2012). The crisis spread across the globe with some banks being over-exposed and at levels that exceeded the domestic state GDP (Bini Smaghi, 2008). This is what happened in Iceland where an over-exposed UK felt a direct knock-on effect through a run on the banks, with the UK government having to nationalise parts of the banking system. To pay for this endeavour, the UK entered into a period of austerity (Financial Services Authority, 2011; Blyth, 2015), which as a policy, arguably, remains in place. The event brought to an end the longest period of stability in the UK in its post-1945 history and help cause Labour to lose the 2010 general election, to be replaced by a Conservative/LibDem coalition, with David Cameron as Prime Minister.

This chapter is concerned with the Scottish precipitancy. The indication from the literature on statecraft and secession is that it is at this point in time where the state is likely to fight than watch its power and influence ebb away (Kaplan, 1957; Easton, 1965; Morgenthau, 1978; Wood, 1981; James, 2016; 2018). Hence, this thesis' assumption that the closer a secessionist movement progresses towards the precipitancy, the more likely the state will respond with hard-line realist tactics (Easton, 1965; Morgenthau, 1978; James, 2016; 2018). This same eventuality bears out in the third stage of the conceptual framework, which is repeated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: statecraft in the precipitancy
(Repeated from pg. 89)

This chapter also introduces the Scottish parliament in 2013, specifically in respect of the first debate on the Scottish Independence Referendum (Franchise) Act (2013) (SIRFA). That said, the initial focus for this chapter relates to David Cameron, his brand of statecraft, and the product, in respect of the Scottish precipitancy. As such, this chapter notes the centrality of the dual polity as a weapon for shaping UK governmental responses during this era.

Cameronian statecraft

This section reviews the statecraft strategy that Cameron employed in the lead up to and following his elevation to Prime Minister. The focus is his image and his involvement in both high and low politics. This section is divided into three sub-sections. This section notes a continuance of pressure from the hard right of the Conservative part, as outlined in chapter seven, and in relation to CA2. Also reviewed is Cameron’s approach to the dual polity and in specific reference to the emergent Scottish precipitancy. This section begins, however, with a brief overview of his public profile.

The Cameron brand

Cameron’s elevation to Conservative leader was based on a “carefully cultivated image of a family man” who believed that marriage should be rewarded through the tax system (Hayton, 2010: 492). The Conservative general election campaign in 2010 lent on a similar polished, stage managed approach, similar to that practiced by Tony Blair (Buller and James, 2012a; 2012b).

In a break from the then recent tradition, Cameron was the first Conservative leader not to receive an “explicit endorsement” from Margaret Thatcher (Hayton, 2014: 3). Following her

death Cameron said that “I’m certainly a big Thatcher fan, but I don’t know whether that makes me a Thatcherite” (Alexandre-Collier, 2015: 116). Although Crampton noted his saying at the time, “we are all Thatcherites now,” the suggestion was that Cameron had failed to include himself in this cohort whilst also suggesting he had some issues with her legacy (2013: n.p.). That said, it also remains unknown as to whether Cameron had brought Thatcherism to an end or whether he had adopted a form of neo-Thatcherism (Hayton, 2012; 2012b). The suggestion is that his style of leadership centred on a series of “slippery” non-answers that did little to inform the wider populous (Heppell, 2008; Crampton, 2013; Hayton, 2014; Kettle, 2016: n.p.). A similar stance is to be found in respect of whether or not he was supportive of UK membership of the EU. Here, it is noted that he attained his first job in politics in the early 1990s when he worked for the then Chancellor, Normal Lamont. Lamont had asked Cameron his position on Europe, to which he replied “Euro sceptic - but not as Euro sceptic as you are” (Kettle, 2016: n.p.). A similar non-answer is noted to Labour’s Dennis McShane, that he was “much more Euro sceptic than you imagine ... [but] was no Euro obsessive” having had “too much time spent alone with Bill Cash” (Kettle, 2016: n.p.). The effect was that questions remain whether his politics reflected pragmatism or not (Hayton, 2014). For Hayton, the consequence was Cameron’s political ideology being less than solid that left Cameron being accused of being a “lily-livered liberal lacking the necessary Thatcherite fibre” (2014: 1).

From being photographed with huskies in front of melting glaciers to hosting video blogs in his kitchen (Hern, 2013; Vaughan, 2016), this was the “heir to Blair” who had been offered as a fresh face in UK politics (Buller and James, 2012a: 31). Given Barak Obama had called him a “lightweight” (Owen, 2008: n.p.), it may be fair to suggest that Cameron was viewed in some circles as a politician of little substance. Indeed, the former journalist and Director of Communications to Tony Blair, Alistair Campbell said of Cameron that if we scratched away at the veneer there would just be more of the same (2010: n.p.). Even so, for Hayton, Cameron had been the “most effective [statecraft] practitioner the party had produced since Thatcher” (2021: 414). And for Buller and James (2012a), the result was a party portrayed as a modern, liberal, collective. The knock-on effect was Cameron benefitting from decent approval ratings, which in turn contributed to a revival of Conservative electoral fortunes (Buller and James, 2012a). However, Buller and James (2012a) add that although fiscal conservatism had gained approval in the right-wing newspapers, it had left the party open to criticism that it was not interested in the poor and the vulnerable. Hayton also points out that

Cameron hadn't been as successful as suggested because polling indicated that the Conservatives were still not to be trusted with public services (2018; 2021). This weakness was made most obvious when during the televised debates during the 2010 UK general election, which should have played to Cameron's strong points, "the mantle of change" that he had sought to project was seized by the LibDems (Seldon and Lodge, 2010: 115032).

Nonetheless, the Conservatives won the 2010 general election, albeit in a minority. Via a Coalition with the LibDems, Cameron, in becoming Prime Minister, inherited a UK that was veering towards both deglobalisation and the Scottish precipitancy (Tomlinson, 1996; 2009; Bello, 2013; Bordo, 2017; van Bergeijk, 2019; Witt, 2019; Kornprobst and Paul, 2021).

High politics

The literature on statecraft states that institutional constraints make the job of party leader easier (Foster, 2006; Shapiro, Skowronek, and Galvin, 2006; James, 2016). It remains a duty of the party leader to maintain good relations between the layers and sections of the party, and the individuals within it (Bulpitt, 1986a). However, and as with previous Conservative leaders going back to the 1970s, Cameron had also been dogged by party in-fighting over Europe (Buller and James, 2012a). Buller and James argue that his approach to party management impacted his ability to achieve argument hegemony. This weakness, they say, had a profound effect on the internal politics of the Conservative party (Buller and James, 2012a). It didn't help that his presidential style overlapped Bulpitt's "locus of actual political power" (1983: 61), with Foley's "status, role and meaning of a prime minister's position" (2004: 292) - in layman terms, conflating government with the Office of Prime Minister. Nonetheless, this type of presidentialism was reinforced by Cameron's remaining focused on high politics. However, that arena was a quagmire and by 2013 he was talking about the possibility of a referendum on EU membership, and although the indication was his caving into pressure, in reality he did little about it.

Regardless, the result was a rift between his office and his backbenchers. This situation was further compounded by a subsequent Conservative Amendment to the 2013 Queens speech expressing "regret" that Cameron had not included a referendum on EU membership in his government's programme (H12). This position caused the newspapers to question whether or not Cameron was "losing control" (H12). The Conservatives were portrayed as split and Cameron was "running scared of its own backbenchers" (H12). The overall effect, for

Observer columnist Andrew Rawnsley, was the potential that the Conservatives could split (H13), with the United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP) being a potential home for some Conservative MPs⁴⁷. To compound matters further, and in what was hardly a triumph of party management, Cameron reportedly called this Eurosceptic bloc “mad swivel-eyed loons” (H12). And by virtue of his leadership style, Cameron was front and centre to the party in-fighting and also central to the posturing over the potential of a referendum on EU membership. However, his *modus operandi* did not extend to the very real independence referendum campaign being rolled out in Scotland at the time where, there, Cameron was conspicuous by a lack of direct involvement (Faulconbridge and Osborn, 2014; Pike, 2015).

Low politics

Chapter two discussed Bulpitt’s (1983; 1986a; 1986b) perspective that everything outside of high politics comprises low politics. Cameron, employed an operational mobilisation system of territorial management and again, as per Bulpitt (1983), peripheral bodies and organisations undertook governmental activity and at an arm-length from the centre (Bulpitt, 1983; Ayres et al, 2018). Devolution assisted in this endeavour and provided the central government with the opportunity for Cameron to act in accordance with Bulpitt’s analogy of the “absentee landlord” (1983: 61). Rather than enact legislation to hold a referendum and then table it in the Commons, as had been the case in 1978 and 1997, Cameron instead entered into negotiations with the Scottish government and in doing so, avoided a potentially damaging legislative journey. Torrance (2013) claims that the Scottish government had gone into the negotiations determined only to get an agreement, the actual substance being a secondary consideration. However, what is clear that the Scottish government came out of the negotiations having prevailed on a number of key points - including having autonomy over the definition of the franchise and its administration; the timing of the referendum; the extent of the franchise and the lowering of voting rights to sixteen years of age; informing the Scottish society on the referendum and its issues; and, reducing barriers to voting (UK Government, (2012). In all, the resultant Edinburgh Agreement provided the legal framework for the referendum, in line with Section 30 of the Scotland Act (1998). In effect, with all the important cards being transferred to the Scottish government, Cameron had little or no involvement in day-to-day or administrative oversight of the referendum.

⁴⁷ UKIP was a descendent of Jimmy Goldsmith’s Referendum party and within the Conservative ranks were potential defectors, with a number of them being sitting MPs (Alexandre-Collier, 2015).

The agreed two-year run-in all but guaranteed that the independence debate would not only dominate the Scottish social discourse but intensify as the referendum date grew closer. The dual polity may have been protected, albeit for reasons of governing competence (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; James, 2016; 2018), but the elongated campaign was not helpful to Cameron in winning the battle of ideas (James, 2016; 2018). Nonetheless, the upshot is that whilst Cameron may have been a superficial politician, he was also one canny enough to know his limitations as an electoral asset. In practice, this meant deploying avoidance techniques for when his presence was not electorally beneficial. Ultimately, Cameron had little involvement with the ‘No’ campaign - ‘Better Together’. The result was high-profile Scottish Labour politicians, including Alistair Darling, dominating the front-facing team, with Conservatives and LibDems in support (Simpkins, 2015; Pike, 2015). And with Cameron refusing to debate Scottish First Minister, Alex Salmond, the No campaign more resembled a Labour offshoot (Trichton, 2015; Gourtsoyannis, 2020).

The No campaign was itself, headquartered in Downing Street. The Devolution Unit was overseen by media strategist Rob Shorthouse, who oversaw the production, co-ordination, and dissemination of the Better Together media message (Atikcan, Nadeau, & Belanger, 2020; Pike, 2015). Aside from the day-to-day management of hustings, the Devolution Unit was noted for requesting moral support from international third parties, including peer states - Russia, USA, China, France, Australia, Canada, and international organisations including NATO (WikiLeaks, 2014; Pike, 2015; McHarg et al, 2016). Other activities included asking Sony not to release the first series of *Outlander* in case it energised support for Scottish independence (WikiLeaks, 2014). In addition, the UK civil service was vulnerable to claims that it had become politicised and was no longer impartial, on this issue at least (Pike, 2015; McHarg et al, 2016; Keating, 2020). Arguably, one of the Devolution Unit’s successes in the referendum was its capability in claiming the Scots lacked competence in state formation, primarily through being financially inept. That argument arose out of the UK’s tactic to deny a currency union with an independent Scotland (McWhirter, 2014; Pike, 2015). It meant an independent Scotland being tied to the Bank of England. As a part of this strategy, the state-owned RBS announced it would register outside of Scotland following a Yes vote (McWhirter, 2014; Pike, 2015). Actions of this type are in line with Boyer’s (2000) argument that when faced with a crisis, states will operate from a finance-first position. Boyer adds that institutional change is an inevitable consequence of crisis, and one of their first considerations is reform of financial systems and their regulation. This is what was seen with

both the RBS and currency union tactics. A problem is, however, that the cyclical nature of economics means that stability can never be assured long-term. And in any case, structural changes to the economic or financial system need to take into consideration the socio-political context (Boyer, 2000). The upshot was the UK government, in the lead up to referendum day, making financial decisions for reasons of political expedient purposes.

Running parallel to this strategy was the SAP programme, which convened over an eighteen month period (UK Government, 2013). One of its publications gave an international legal perspective on Scottish independence. It says that “a successor state, in contrast with a continuing state, does not automatically assume the rights, obligations and powers of the predecessor” (UK Government, 2013: 33-34). And, as a newly independent state, Scotland would start with no infrastructure to assist in international relations (UK Government, 2013: 33; 75-76). This publication had been co-authored by former ICJ Judge James Crawford. Crawford asserted that following Scottish independence the UK would acquire ‘continuator status’ with Scotland being a ‘successor state’ (UK Government, 2013: 33-34). In coming to this decision, Crawford had lent heavily on the Vienna Convention on Succession of States in respect of Treaties (UN, 1978). He uses the Treaty to argue the UK’s right to all assets, memberships, and treaties in use at the time. However, the UK is not a signatory to the Treaty nor appears to recognise it (UN, 1978). As for the ‘continuator’ status that Crawford refers to, it exists nowhere in the Treaty and instead is an interpretation of his own (2006) works. As such, it is disingenuous for him to argue the application of an unrecognised Treaty as being applicable to the Scottish precipitancy, all the while conflating the Articles of Treaty with his own work (UN, 1978; Crawford, 2006). As for Crawford himself, he argues that sovereignty is acquired only as a spoil of war and a referendum is not a sufficient mandate for enacting a secessionist event (Crawford, 2006: 417). Added, he has argued that the threshold for achieving secession should be higher (2006).

Regardless, however, of the measures and countermeasures that were put in place by the UK government as part of the campaign for the status quo, the reality was that the responsibility for the legislation on holding an independence referendum resided with the Scottish government. In terms of responsibility, that this outcome came about in the first place is a consequence of Cameronian statecraft.

The product of Cameronian statecraft

This section provides an overview of the debate on SIRFA. There are three subsections. The first provides a brief overview of the Scottish parliament, or Holyrood. The second considers the debate itself. This section concludes with a testable causal framework.

Holyrood

Holyrood employs a participative approach to democracy that centres on the relationship between the Scottish government and civic Scotland (Crowther et al, 1999; Cairney, 2011; Leith and Soule, 2012). Holyrood uses a participatory system, itself a legacy of the Scottish Constitutional Convention (Cairney, 2011). As a practice it is far removed from that encountered in the House of Commons, is deemed to be less remote, and actively encourages external input to legislative preparations (Crowther et al, 1999; Cairney, 2011; Leith and Soule, 2012). Crowther et al (1999) argue that this style of governance is in itself a legacy of the Act of Union (1707). There, it is suggested that certain Scottish sectors have benefitted from retaining relative post-1707 autonomy - law, religion, and education (Crowther et al, 1999), and via the participatory model, each (and others) have a prominent role in helping shape legislation at Holyrood. The participatory model is further developed via having a parliament in the round and with MSPs being elected via proportional representation. The normal effect is that the party of government needs to develop a cross-party consensus if it is to get its policies through parliament. That changed in 2011 when the SNP won its outright majority (Pike, 2015; Leith and Sim, 2020).

SIRFA

The Scottish government raised two separate referendum Bills. The first centred on the legislation for holding the referendum, and the second being SIRFA which intended lowering the age of franchise for the referendum from eighteen to sixteen. Reducing the vote to sixteen in Scotland had been a long-held SNP policy and SIRFA had also been viewed as a trial for a permanent reduction in the age of franchise votes for sixteen-year-olds in Scotland-only elections (Carrell, 2014). The effect was an inflation of the Scottish electorate of one hundred thousand (BBC, 2014), and as with CA1 and CA2, SIRFA also presents as another piece of legislation that sought to redefine the franchise for politically expedient purposes.

The debate was opened by the Deputy First Minister Nicola Sturgeon who stated that:

Everyone in the chamber knows that the Government was elected in 2011 with a mandate to hold a referendum on our constitutional future, the date for which has been confirmed as 18 September 2014. The proposals that we are debating are the result of extensive consultation with the Scottish people ... followed by negotiations between the Scottish Government and the United Kingdom Government. As members are aware, those discussions culminated in the Edinburgh agreement, which paved the way for the referendum on Scottish independence (A1; A2; D3; D7).

However, Members of the Scottish Parliament (MSPs) were concerned with the remit of the legislation. Labour's Patricia Ferguson questioned the legislative provisions that offered Ministers the ability to arbitrarily alter the legislation if necessary. She argued against the "wide ranging" nature of the legislation and called it "unusual" (A1; A2; D24). Conservative Annabel Goldie was also critical of these provisions saying that they were "wider than might normally be expected" (A1; A2; D5; D24). However, the authority being asked for in SIRFA was in principle no different to the system of statutory instruments used by the House of Commons⁴⁸. Sturgeon's response was that the Scottish government did not have any "specific intention" for using this delegated instrument but that its inclusion in the legislation was necessary to allow Ministers to "swiftly" make changes to SIRFA if and when it was needed (A1; A2; D24). To this end, she reminded the chamber that SIRFA was one of two related Bills that needed to be legislated in "sync"⁴⁹ (A1; A2; D24).

MSPs used the debate to argue for even more change than SIRFA had originally intended. An inclusive referendum was encouraged, one in which barriers to electoral engagement were systematically removed. For example, Labour's Patricia Ferguson was hopeful that "those who face barriers in their everyday lives can be informed participants" (A4; D3; D10; D14). However, the limitations of this inclusivity soon became apparent when a number of MSPs wanted the franchise extended to convicted prisoners (A1; A2; A3; A4; D2; D3; D4; D5; D7; D8; D9; D11). It was a policy that Sturgeon disagreed with. She said those in prison had committed crimes against society and their penance should include losing their right to vote (A1; D2; D5). The Chamber was reminded, however, that a large number of those convicted in Scotland served their sentence in the community and, as consequence, retained their entitlement to vote (A1; A5; D2; D7; H7). The effect caused Margo McDonald to accuse

⁴⁸ An example was the retrospective altering of the Scotland Act (1998) to return to direct UK control, territory in Antarctica that had been erroneously devolved to Scotland (see chapter three) (Hansard, 2012; Gray, 2014).

⁴⁹ The other point that it is worth bearing in mind is that [SIRFA] is closely connected to the main referendum Bill - the Scottish Independence Referendum Bill ... the two Bills are being progressed separately, and the main Bill will still be subject to amendment once the Bill that we are debating has been passed. Therefore, we need the flexibility that the power in section 11 gives to bring the two Bills into sync, should that turn out to be necessary in the light of any amendments that are made to the main Bill (A1; A2; D24).

Sturgeon of making “exceptions” to the franchise. “I think that we are going down a very dangerous road” she argued “when we start to make exceptions of prisoners - the ones who might vote and the ones who might not” (A2; A4; A5; D1). Differentiating crimes and the punishments, she furthered, is a matter for a Sheriff and not a politician.

Discussions on prisoner voting rights were a rare example of where MSPs disagreed and Holyrood was split. By contrast, turnout was a discussion point that, typical for this debate, led MSPs to express concerns that voter engagement could be detrimentally impacted by a negative campaign. This point was raised by all parties and contributors also used their time to offer hope for a high turnout, particularly amongst the newly franchised younger generation (A1; A2; A3; A4; D1; D4; D6; D13). The effect was MSPs committing to a positive referendum campaign, catalysed by a desire to see young people being ‘inspired’ into becoming active in politics (A1; A2; A3; A4; D4; D2; D4; D5; D6; D8; D13). The culmination, for Labour’s John Pentland, was that a low turnout of the newly franchised would indicate that this “once-in-a-lifetime” event was poorly run (A1; A4; D4; D6). Another point that MSPs largely agreed on was the need to educate the newly franchised cohort so they could make an informed decision in the referendum (A1; A4; D1; D4; D5). The upshot was MSPs agreeing to the creation of an awareness programme that included youth agencies, education services, and a host of external, third-party, and third-sector organisations as agents in the referendum campaign (A1; A2; A3; A4; D1; D3; D4; D6).

Table 33: 2013 contributor data

Party	Contributors	Constituency	List	% share
Conservative	2	-	2	9
Green	1	-	1	5
Independent	1	-	1	5
Labour	7	5	2	26
LibDems	2	1	1	5
SNP	13	8	5	49
Total	26	14	12	99

(Numbers do not include the Presiding Officer or the SNPs’ Dennis Robertson)

As outlined in Table 33, the SNP were responsible for half the contributions in the debate. As a tactic, this was not necessary given the overall SNP majority in the Chamber because the cohort could have sat and said nothing and achieved the same outcome. Nonetheless, SIRFA received widespread support in the Chamber - from Labour, LibDems, Greens, and the independent Margo McDonald, leaving the Conservatives isolated in a counter-position that

premised on their not agreeing with the general principles of the legislation⁵⁰ (A1; A4; A5; D1; D4). SIRFA passed the first reading and successfully completed the legislative journey and the age of franchise was reduced to sixteen for the 2014 independence referendum.

Chapter conclusions

This chapter has reviewed the dual polity during Scotland's secessionist precipitancy. The intention had been to assess Cameronian statecraft as a comparator in respect of his involvement in high politics through which insights could be offered on his approach to the Scottish precipitancy and how it played out. In handing over a number of the key controls of the referendum and the result aside, Cameron had managed to insulate himself and his government from the effects of the campaign and in doing so, helped preserve the dual polity. If this is an accurate assessment then it may be fair to say that as was the case with CA1 and CA2, it was the dual polity, and not Scotland, that was an uppermost consideration for UK politicians.

The decision to devolve control of the referendum to the Scottish government presents as a problem for this thesis because this third interim causal inference is premised on Holyrood and not the Commons. There are several issues here - first, that the action in itself remains unexplained in the literature, and second, that the generic Bulpittian perspective offers little insight into a host of observations from SIRFA and the events leading up to it or, indeed, activity in Holyrood. There, however, and as had been the case with CA1 and CA2, MSPs also argued over a number of issues that on the surface were not directly relevant to the matter being voted on. The result was a debate that included additional considerations regards the administration of the referendum, its promotion within Scottish society, and the involvement of a number of third parties as agents in the same (A1; A4; D3; D5; D17; D18; D20; D21). Ultimately, the observed true outcome of Cameronian statecraft was the emergence of a movement that centred on newly appointed secessionist entrepreneurs, as per Wood (1981). The process leading to this outcome is visualised in the three-step causal framework outlined in Figure 24. Central to the framework is the necessary redefinition of the franchise, and to use the participatory model to bolster the referendum administration (A1; A4; D3; D5; D17; D18; D20; D21). Lastly, SIRFA is viewed as being a catalyst for

⁵⁰ Annabel Goldie argued that "My party is not supportive of the principle of using the referendum as an experiment for extending votes to 16 and 17-year-olds. That is not to say that we do not consider that there is a debate to be had. There is and it would be welcome, but my party feels that the step in the Bill is precipitate and premature" (A1; A2; A3; A4; D1).

movement building - a wider movement to mobilise sixteen-year-olds as political actors and build a support network around them. For MSPs this was the necessary approach if they were to ensure a positive campaign and a high turnout.

Figure 24: 2013 casual framework

Overall, and similar to the previous debates on CA1 and CA2, SIRFA is also considered to be a case of using the legislative process for politically expedient purposes, the twin potential of electioneering notwithstanding. It should be noted that this assumed outcome was not just the SNP’s doing because as was noted earlier, the wider parliament was united, Conservatives aside (A1; A4; D3; D5; D17; D18; D20; D21; H7). Based on observations in respect of the association of argument hegemony, governing competence, and electoral strategy, the interim casual inference looks as such:

Figure 25 2013 interim causal inference

In reality, this chapter has concerned itself with an exercise in external statecraft and which had been catalysed by David Cameron. The result was opposition craft at play in Holyrood rather than in the Commons. In this, as with CA1 and CA2, the indication is that the legislative system had been used for politically expedient purposes. Added is the inherent involvement of third party agents and actors, including in international relations, in serving to influence opinion in Scotland. Given these additional dynamics, it is fair to suggest that there isn’t much that has been discussed in this chapter that can be classed as low politics, and again, it’s a matter that the literatures are yet to explain. Nonetheless, the appearance is that

by 2013, Cameron's government had adopted a strategy akin to organisation mobilisation, as per Bulpitt's (1983) ideas on territorial management. Primarily, this task had been outsourced to the Labour party, which was not in power and had no influence over enacting promises made in the event of a 'No' vote. As an insight, it hints that Cameron had served only to insulate his government further. That said, the next chapter explains the results on the investigation to test the causal framework and focuses on SIRFAs utility in encouraging mobilisation in the precipitancy.

Chapter nine: mobilisation in the precipitancy

This chapter explains the results of the investigation related to the debate on SIRFA.

Chapter six noted that Scotland had not experienced the rise of the secessionist movement in the way as predicted in the literature or visualised in the conceptual framework. This chapter suggests the mobilisation took place during the precipitancy. In reality, there were two campaigns - the very real campaign playing out on the streets of Scotland, and another seeking out newly franchised voters and encouraging them to partake in the campaign. The resultant causal framework indicates the potential that through SIRFA, the Scottish government and parliament agreed to redefine the franchise then commit to creating a positive campaign. The addition of a campaign designed to produce a high turnout was, as a final step, intended to encourage the mobilisation of Scottish society.

Figure 24: 2013 casual framework
(Repeated from pg. 173)

The result was an interim causal inference that relied on a combination of argument hegemony, governing competence, and electoral strategy, which also is repeated below.

Figure 25: 2013 interim causal inferences
(Repeated from pg. 173)

An immediate point to note here is another departure of the causal framework from the conceptual framework. Even so, and for the final time, this chapter offers a set of three statements, one for each step in the causal framework. These are:

7: the Scottish government fully exploited the autonomy provided via Cameronian statecraft

8: SIRFA was premised towards citizen mobilisation

9: SIRFA encouraged the mobilisation of Scottish society

This chapter is in three sections. The first tests the presumed predominance of argument hegemony in defining the franchise. The second questions the potential that governing competence was most important when administering the referendum and the vote. And the third concerns mobilisation, which has been deemed to be an act akin to electoral strategy. The expectation is that the Scottish government and wider SNP would use the SIRFA debate to first, soapbox on independence; and second, tilt the legislation so to be favourable to the secessionist cause.

Define the franchise

The statement for this first step in the interim causal inference considers the potential that the Scottish government fully exploited the autonomy provided via Cameronian statecraft and that argument hegemony acted as the predominant lever. The Parliament Act (1949) does not extend to Holyrood. As such, all five levers are in play here. This approach allowed for a systematic review of the relevance to each statecraft lever and did so by asking four sub-questions. These, and the evidence that support them, as per Table 34. From there, this section explains the narrative behind the evidence base.

Table 34: 2013 evidence 7

	hoop question	yes/no/ unknown	supporting graphs
25	redefining the franchise meant more responsibilities for the Scottish government	yes	E68; E71; E72; E74; E75; E76; E78; E84; E79
26	the Edinburgh Agreement bound the Scottish government	yes	E64; E87
27	redefining the franchise meant the Scottish government breaking the rules	no	E87
28	the Scottish government maximised the potential offered by redefinition	no	E63; E66; E67; E69; E73; E87

(See Appendix 8 for the supporting data)

Argument hegemony: chapter eight noted that via the Edinburgh Agreement a number of the important cards had been handed over to the Scottish government. These include control of the date of the referendum; the definition of the franchise; the wording of the question

(Electoral Commission oversight aside); the rules on campaign financing; and other rules regards the conduct of the referendum (UK Government, 2012: 3). However, the Scottish government did not acquire complete autonomy of action over the referendum because the Parliament Act (1949) retained primacy (UK Government, 2012). In practice, it meant that the referendum was consultative and that the Commons retained the final say on any vote for independence. As a tool of control, this approach served two purposes - not only did it reinforce the idea of Commons supremacy; it also served to undermine the legitimacy of any post-referendum unilateral declaration of independence and again, because the Commons would have been denied a 'final' say.

The debate exposed another UK-control impact, this time in relation to votes for prisoners. In arguing against extending SIRFA Sturgeon deferred to the Representation of the People Act (1983) (E68), that votes for prisoners was "not a change that is within the power of this Parliament" (E68; E69; E73; E87; H7). But that was not an accurate reflection of the Edinburgh Agreement, which said nothing about continuing the denial of the vote to prisoners. Indeed, reference to this Act in the Agreement extends solely to the provision of free of charge postal campaign services (UK government, 2012). Article 11 of the Agreement confirmed that:

The Scottish Government's decision on what to propose to the Scottish Parliament will be informed by the analysis of responses to its consultation exercise and by practical considerations. The Order does not restrict the extension of the franchise in the case of this referendum (UK Government, 2012: 6).

Article 11 says, in effect, that if the Scottish government had been receptive to extending the franchise to prisoners, then a political will to achieve this outcome could have materialised. Indeed, it is not as if the consultation was devoid of evidence on the subject because MSPs took submissions from academic and legal experts who had called for prisoners to attain the franchise in the independence referendum (E73). Contrary to this position were Professor Stephen Tierney and the Law Society of Scotland. Both had submitted to the parliament that the legal argument for extending the franchise to prisoners was weak (E67; E73). Tierney suggested that any challenge to the current ban on human rights grounds was likely to fail, the reason being that the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) does not differentiate between elections and referendums (E67; E73)^{51 52}.

⁵¹ Bates (2014) notes the ECHR position that the UK's ban on prisoners having the right to vote is incompatible with the Treaty. The central component there lies in Article 3.1 which commits the UK to "hold free elections at reasonable intervals by secret ballot, under conditions

Overall, the assessment for this first lever, as such, is that whilst the evidence indicates that in redefining the franchise the Scottish government acquired more responsibilities, the effect was limited by its unwillingness to extend the franchise to the prison population. Indeed, as stated by Sturgeon, the Representation of the People Act (1983) took precedence even though there was no obligation to fully comply, albeit under certain circumstances. To this end, the indication is that the Scottish government did not maximise the potential offered by redefinition. In all, and despite its offering considerable room for manoeuvre, the Edinburgh Agreement bound the Scottish government, testament to the consultative nature of the referendum and adherence by the Scottish government to the even when there was scope to do otherwise. As such, it is safe to suggest that SIRFA was enacted in Westminster's image, the meaning being that argument hegemony is redundant to this first investigation.

Governing competence: the investigation notes that whilst redefining the franchise meant more responsibilities for the Scottish government, the resultant activity was not “straightforward” (E71; E72; E74; E79). Labour's John Pentland argued that reducing the age of franchise created an “issue of how to compile the list of eligible voters without compromising the personal data of those who are not yet old enough to vote” (E71; E72; E74; E79). Sturgeon agreed saying “it is essential to treat sensitively the information that will be collected” but also recognised the need to “replicate, as far as possible, existing electoral practice, while recognising the need to treat data on young people responsibly and appropriately” (E71; E72; E74; E79). She was suggesting creating a secondary set of protections which, she argued, would further secure the data held on a small number of fourteen-year-olds who would be franchised by the time the referendum was held (E71; E72; E74; E79).

In reality, however, this data protection problem affected only a tiny minority of the electoral register and it was criticised by Former SNP Depute Leader, MP and MSP, Margo McDonald. McDonald was now an Independent MSP and she had little truck with these

which will ensure the free expression of the opinion of the people in the choice of the legislature” (European Court of Human Rights, 2022: 5). Bates (2014) also notes animosity between the UK government and the European Court of Human Rights in Strasbourg. Central to this situation was the 2005 case of *Hirst v. United Kingdom* that concluded that contravening Article 3 of the ECHR “the UK's blanket ban on prisoner voting was indiscriminate and disproportionate” (Johnston, 2020: n.p.).

⁵² It is worth noting that the Blair government had previously looked at potential alternatives to a blanket ban on prisoner voting and more recently (post 2014) the Scottish government undertook a similar review (Johnston, 2020). The result there led to a limited extension of the franchise to specific categories of prisoner. This move occurred without there being a need for changes in the framing of the ECHR (Johnston, 2020).

arguments. “If they [fourteen–sixteen-year-olds] are equally able to take the sort of informed decision that we more adult electors will take, why should they be protected” (E71; E72; E74; E79). The consequence was that whilst the Scottish government was in the process of redefining the franchise, the effect on its acquiring more responsibilities was somewhat limited. Nor was there any suggestion that in advancing the administration of SIRFA that the Scottish government was breaking any rules. This stance applies also to the financial costs of the independence referendum, which was being met by the Scottish government (UK Government, 2012). Included in the debate on SIRFA was a two-way discussion between the Deputy First Minister and Labour’s Michael McMahon (E84). The two haggled over minor discrepancies in the proposed cost of increasing awareness of the referendum. McMahon was arguing that there was “a technical problem with the financial memorandum” that related to the proposed cost of the referendum, its administration, and promotion (E84). The appearance here is the Scottish government held to a higher level of accountability than that similarly afforded to the UK government by MPs in the House of Commons, and by arguing over minutia (E84). On the whole, however, the Scottish government was vulnerable to scrutiny, the overall effect being that as governing competence remains in play as the predominate lever for this first step.

Party management: it was noted earlier that the chamber was split on whether or not prisoners should get the vote. LibDems with the Greens and the Independent Margo McDonald aligned in favour, with the SNP and Conservatives against (E63; E73). With only the Labour party showed signs of disunity, and on that same subject (E63; E73), overall, the indication is that party management is redundant to the investigation for this first step.

Electoral strategy: James’ (2012) asserts that electoral administration is vulnerable to statecraft manipulation. He furthers that electoral administration is a “partisan” issue that can be used to enfranchise, disenfranchise, and suppress the electorate so to attain the desired effect (James, 2012). However, that argument premises on the Westminster-centric Bulpittian perspective and doesn’t fully extend to Scotland in administrative terms. In Scotland, electoral administration is outsourced to local authorities (James, 2014). There, the task is overseen by Valuation Joint Boards and specifically, Electoral Registration Officers (EROs) (James, 2014). ERO activities, however, are not aligned to local authority boundaries and not the Commons constituency map. As such, cross-working and co-ordination of ERO activities was/is an essential task (James, 2014). The overall consequence is that EROs already benefits

from substantial autonomy and operates independent to the Scottish government. Sturgeon had already acknowledged that SIRFA had caused EROs additional “joint working” duties (E68; E74; E76). In reality, redefining the franchise to include sixteen-year-olds meant cross-working not just between EROs, but also their inter-working with the UK Ministry of Defence (in respect of registering service personnel and their families) and the Electoral Commission (E71; E72; E74; E76; E78; E87). And whilst this insight implies that in redefining the franchise, the Scottish government did acquire more responsibilities, these were merely delegated to sub-agencies.

However, if the Scottish government had avoided direct involvement in the reformation of the electoral register, it wasn't the end of the matter. The general mood amongst MSPs was that there needed to be high turnout in the referendum and that voters needed to make an informed decision (E66; E78; E79). With this, MSPs discussed all voters having access to referendum material, including Labour's Patricia Ferguson calling for government pamphlets to be published in a number of languages, whilst the SNP's Stuart McMillan called for coloured ballot papers so to avoid the visually impaired and voters with dyslexia being disenfranchised (E75; E79). The scenario, as described, hints that via the Edinburgh Agreement, there was indeed scope to maximise the potential offered by redefinition, primarily through widening access to the franchise and helping make an informed decision in the referendum. To this end, the importance of a high turnout to both the Scottish government and MSPs means overall, that electoral strategy remains in play as the predominate lever for this step.

Rule bending: with the Edinburgh Agreement offering substantial room for manoeuvre it is fair to suggest that it would have been difficult for the Scottish government to bend any rules. Insofar as this first step is concerned, there is no evidence of any such attempt. The consequence is that rule bending is redundant to this first investigation.

Summary: this first investigation considered the potential that the Scottish government fully exploited the autonomy provided via Cameronian statecraft, with argument hegemony being presumed to be the predominate lever for this first step. However that was found not to be the case given the independence referendum being run under Westminster 'rules' (E64; E87). With party management and rule bending being deemed redundant, only electoral strategy and governing competence remained in play. The primacy afforded to governing competence

revolves around the responsibilities the Scottish government placed upon itself as it prepared for the referendum. The upshot is though, of the Scottish government operating its own dual polity, a process made easier by delegating the bulk of work to local authorities (E70; E74; E75; E81). This investigation also notes the micromanagement of the Scottish government by MSPs over electoral cost and associated work required for improving data protection of fourteen to sixteen-year-olds (E68; E71; E72; E74; E76; E78; E81; E84; E87). These additional tasks, however important to the administration of the referendum, were side-effects effects of SIRFA as opposed to being a core pillar in redefining the franchise. As an insight, these observations tip the balance of probability away from governing competence, in favour of electoral strategy as the predominate lever for this first step.

Ultimately, inflating the electorate for politically expedient purposes presents as an out-and-out case of electoral strategy, as per the Bulpittian perspective (Bulpitt, 1983; James, 2012; 2016; 2018). Indeed, as an approach it is also in line with the pro-hegemonic approach to referendums (Lijphart, 1984). However, if referendums are pro-hegemonic, as Lijphart (1984) says they are, it is questionable as to why the attempts to maximise the potential offered by redefinition came from the backbenches and not the Scottish government, particularly given the potential outcomes in electoral terms.

Figure 26: 2013 hoop test probability-7

The overall assessment is that the Scottish government had not fully exploited the autonomy provided via Cameronian statecraft. Administrative autonomy was not exploited, nor was the redefinition of the franchise. And as such, electoral strategy acts as the predominate lever for this first step. As per Figure 26, above, this finding comes replete with a probability of fifty percent. The evidence base can be found in the earlier Table 34.

Promote the vote

The statement for this second step in the interim causal inference considers the potential SIRFA was premised towards citizen mobilisation and that governing competence acted as the predominant lever. As with step one, all five levers are in play here. This approach allowed for a systematic review of the relevance to each statecraft lever and did so by posing four statements. These, and the evidence that support them, are found in Table 35. From there, this section explains the narrative behind the evidence base.

Table 35: 2013 evidence 8

	hoop question	yes/no/ unknown	supporting graphs
29	SIRFA facilitated the involvement of third parties in preparations for the referendum	yes	E62; E66; E71; E75; E76; E78; E79; E81; E82; E85; E88; E91; E92
30	SIRFA facilitated a new class of political entrepreneur	yes	E81; E82; E88; E91
31	the involvement of third parties was entirely related to votes for sixteen-year-olds	no	E75; E79; E81; E82; E85; E88; E92; E91; E95
32	the Scottish government controlled the activities of third parties	no	E66; E69; E71; E78; E80; E81; E82; E87; E88; E91; E92

(See Appendix 8 for the supporting data)

Argument hegemony: as preparation for the referendum the Scottish government issued an earlier consultation document, *Your Scotland, Your Referendum*, in line with the Edinburgh Agreement (Scottish government, 2012; UK Government, 2012). It produced over forty thousand submissions, mostly from members of the public (E71; E78). However, MSPs were mostly interested in promoting the input from a plethora of external organisations from the public, private, third, and voluntary sectors. They included the Association of Directors of Education in Scotland; Children in Scotland; Chairs of Scottish child protection committees; the Church of Scotland; the Educational Institute of Scotland; the Electoral Reform Society; Howard League for Penal Reform; the Law Society of Scotland; the National Deaf Children’s Society; the National Union of Students (NUS) Scotland; Quakers Scotland; Scotland’s Commissioner for Children and Young People; Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations; Scottish Human Rights Commission; Young Scot; and the Scottish Youth Parliament (E69; E71; E78; E80; E81; E82; E87; E88; E91; E92; H6; H7).

The people who work or volunteer in these politico-employment roles are, for Tarrow, “entrepreneurs” (2011: 11), most of whom are sourced from the middle-classes and for whom career-activism is not uncommon. The result, it is argued, is professionally organised movement-led organisations populated largely by professional activists (Klandermans, Kriesi, and Tarrow, 1988), each of whom, in this case, had their points to put forward regards the extension of the franchise and to a lesser extent, votes for convicted prisoners. To this extent a decent body of evidence exists to infer that whilst not all involvements by third parties were entirely related to votes for sixteen-year-olds, SIRFA did facilitate the involvement of third parties in preparations for the referendum. Wood (1981) argues that the job that these entrepreneurs are expected to undertake involves education and mobilisation.

One of them was Robin Parker of NUS Scotland was noted to be “extremely positive” on reducing age of franchise to sixteen (E78; E81; E88; E91; H6). His mentioning was consistent with an observed practice by MSPs of name-dropping specific individuals, predominately those found in the Scottish Youth Parliament (E81; E88), and who formed part of an aspirant and up-and-coming political class. Tarrow calls this cohort ‘early risers’ and it is their job to organise early can cause “diffusion, extension, imitation, and reaction” amongst the wider collective (2011: 205). For Patrick Harvie of the Scottish Greens, their role was to do encourage a high turnout and for the SNP’s George Adam, to “inspire young people to vote” (E66; E71; E78; E80). What is missing from this narrative, however, is intent to sway voters, regardless of their being newly franchised or not. The overall effect is that there is a wealth of evidence that caters for argument hegemony remaining in play as predominate lever for this second step.

Governing competence: the previous investigation observed that whilst the Scottish government retained for itself the power to amend the legislation should the issue arise (E74), it also outsourced much of the additional work and responsibility regards the referendum to co-opted third parties, including EROs (E74). The effect indicated the Scottish government operating its own brand of dual polity. However, having investigated this aspect of the debate, it is also evident that the inclusion of the early risers and other entrepreneurs was primarily advanced by backbench MSPs, including from other parties, and not just the SNP. Theses insights aside, governing competence offers little to suggest predominance in this second step and, as such, is redundant to this investigation.

Party management: as was noted earlier, only the Labour party showed any sign of a split in the party and this was in specific relation to extending the franchise to convicted prisoners (E73). That issue aside, all parties were united and used SIRFA to encourage external bodies to become involved in the referendum campaign, Conservatives and Margo McDonald aside. As such, this lever is redundant to the investigation.

Electoral strategy: Tilly (1977) argues that mobilisation is best suited to institutions rather than through individual action, with resource mobilisation being the vehicle for political advancement. Tarrow (2011) adds further that these activities aid mutual support between separate groups and organisations and encourage solidarity between them through overlaps in ideology or outlook. These networks, in conjunction with activist early risers, represented an important step in the establishment of a wider movement. And whilst these third parties were not operating under the direct control of the Scottish government, their co-opting by MSPs is indicative of the early formations of a movement, albeit one intended merely to “inspire young people to vote” (E66; E78). With MSPs also calling for administrative changes to take account of dyslexia and English as a second language (E74; E75), the drift towards encouraging increased political awareness of the referendum drew in other professions, including teachers (E78; E81; E88; E92). Schools were identified as being central to educating and increasing awareness of the referendum within the newly franchised cohort, and it was a task that predominately was encouraged by SNP MSPs (E71; E78; E80; E81; E82; E91; E92; H6). The SNP’s Bob Doris went as far to suggest that raising awareness of the referendum should be a core facet of teaching whereas his colleague, Rob Gibson, called for “quality” materials to be produced in time to inform young people in deciding which way to vote (E71; E78; E80; E81; E82; E91; E92; H6). Gibson also called for “collaboration across the thirty-two education authorities and with School Leaders Scotland, the association of secondary head teachers” so to encourage and enable a greater understanding of “what is happening” (E71; E78; E80; E81; E82; E91; E92; H6). Labour’s Patricia Ferguson went further and encouraged similar informational projects in vocational education, including apprenticeship centres (E82; E91; E92; H6). As an approach it bucks a trend detected by Armstrong (2015) that politicians are increasingly content with and un-informed and unmotivated electorate.

To this end, the creeping co-opting of schools and other educational establishments as referendum agents offered further opportunity for George Adam to say that young people

should become involved in politics. Clare Adamson, a party colleague, agreed saying that she trusted young people to “take a full part” in the campaign (E66; E71; E78). She added that she could “think of no better reinforcement for our young responsible citizens than extending the voting franchise to them” (E66; E71; E78). However, Conservatives argued that placing political resources in schools and other educational institutions amounted to propaganda (E74; E78; E82). Nevertheless, Conservatives aside, the general consensus was that lowering the vote would “enthuse” the younger generation and they were needed to play a party in the campaign (E66; E71; E78). Overall, from the base perspective of this second investigation, the hint is that the tone of this debate is reminiscent of electoral strategy and to this end this lever remains in play.

Rule bending: there is no evidence that either the Scottish government or the wider Holyrood sitting made any attempt at bending the rules. As such, this lever is redundant to this investigation.

Summary: this second investigation founded on the idea that SIRFA premised on citizen mobilisation as a foundation for a Scottish dual polity. Citizen mobilisation is driven to encourage the citizenry to become active in support of governmental policy objectives (Ayres et al, 2018). However, this second investigation suggests a narrative more akin to organisational mobilisation, a process that Bulpitt argues, is intended to “establish, control, and deploy in its own interests the resources of local political organisations” (1983: 62). Bulpitt furthered that “real power holders do not have a significant territorial connection” (1983: 60), and that to become involved in low politics is a sign of weakness. It is for this same reason that the UK powerbase was deemed by Bulpitt to be disconnected from the rest of society (Bulpitt, 1983)⁵³. It is this simple, concentrated structure that is at the core of the attempt to maintain the dual polity, particularly given its preservation is deemed to help preserve the status quo (Bulpitt, 1983). For Bulpitt, the close proximity of headquartered bureaucratic departments of state and the politicians who oversee them helps create an administrative centre, the effect of which is more commonly known as ‘the Westminster bubble’. This bubble is a direct consequence of the dual polity and the same system appears to be present at Holyrood. A main difference, however, is that via the participatory model, entrepreneurs are able to play a part in the forming of legislation, consequent to the

⁵³ The headquartered bureaucratic departments of state and the politicians who oversee them are located at the ‘centre’ (Bulpitt, 1983: 3), and is more commonly known as ‘the Westminster bubble’.

participatory model. The effect is proximity between the politicians at Holyrood, entrepreneurs, early risers, and other organisations. They are, in effect, secondary agents in the political process. In respect of SIRFA, these agents also had a role to play following SIRFA's ratification (E78; E88; E91; E92).

It does not appear to be a coincidence that these people and organisations are largely drawn from the same local elites and professionals that remain amongst the beneficiaries of relative local autonomy post-1707. They comprise what this thesis calls 'civic Scotland' (E81; E92), and for Searle-Chatterjee (2017), employment in those types of organisations tend to be generative and indicative of some form of pre-determined radicalism, and of a type not dissimilar to that described by Tarrow (2011) in respect of mutual reinforcement of ideals and opinions. The centrality of this Edinburgh bubble to this debate also reinforces the existence of a distinct employment sector that is wholly reliant on the participatory model for the continuity of its business model (Crowther et al, 1999; Cleveland, 2003; Searle-Chatterjee, 2017). The important point, however, is that the bubble was being mobilised by MSPs and not the Scottish government and amongst the co-opted were schools and other educational establishments; student unions and organisations; and, a plethora of quasi-public bodies and third-sector organisations, as promoters of the independence referendum (E74; E75; E78; E81; E88; E91; E92). And in what resembles a virtuous circle, the actions sit more comfortably within organisational mobilisation than its citizenry counterpart. Overall, the assessment is that the idea that the participatory model counters a Westminster-style bubble effect is somewhat dubious (Crowther et al, 1999; Cairney, 2011; Leith and Soule, 2012).

Figure 27: 2013 hoop test probability-8

The investigation for this second step also premised on the idea that governing competence acted as predominate lever for this second step. However, governing competence, as well as party management and rule bending, were deemed redundant to this investigation. The result leaves argument hegemony and electoral strategy competing as the predominate lever for this

second step. The primacy of argument hegemony relies on the roles of civic Scotland and its proximity to, involvement with, and influence over, MSPs. The overall effect is that SIRFA did not necessarily facilitate a new class of political entrepreneur but it did give an old class a new job (E71; E78; E81; E88; E91; H6). Nonetheless, the inference is that MSPs were asking civic Scotland to promote a positive referendum campaign, and to encourage a high turnout and to this end, this investigation sways towards electoral strategy as the predominate lever for this second step. As per Figure 27, this finding comes replete with an accumulative probability of fifty percent.

Mobilise Scottish society

The statement for this third step in the interim causal inference considers the potential SIRFA encouraged the mobilisation of Scottish society and that electoral strategy acted as the predominant lever. Again, all five levers are in play here. This approach allowed for a systematic review of the relevance to each statecraft lever and did so by posing four statements. These, and the evidence that support them, are found in Table 36. From there, this section explains the narrative behind the evidence base.

Table 36: 2013 evidence 9

	hoop question	yes/no/ unknown	supporting graphs
33	MSPs considered raising the awareness of the referendum within Scottish society	yes	E66; E79; E81; E85; E88; E91; E92
34	the Scottish government offered specific arrangements to involve hard-to-reach voters	no	E89; E90; E91; E92; E93; E94; E95
35	civic Scotland was fully representative of the Scottish electorate	no	E79; E81; E82; E85; E88; E91; E92; E95
36	the Scottish government maximised the opportunities for movement building	no	E66; E73; E79; E81; E82; E85; E86; E88; E88; E89; E91; E92; E94; E95

(See Appendix 8 for the supporting data)

Argument hegemony: argument hegemony is an inherently realist statecraft lever that requires the effective projection of political ideas on to the people if it is to be successful (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986; Kissinger, 2014; James, 2016). For Leys, argument hegemony does not need to be loved, “it is merely necessary that it have no serious rival” (1990: 127). In short, and regardless of the method or medium used, argument hegemony is concerned with

winning people over to a particular cause. The relevance here relates to Margo McDonald who spoke about accessing hard-to-reach voters by suggesting a leafleting campaign similarly to that which had taken place in the lead up to the 1979 devolution referendum (E74; E78; E79; E80; E89; E90). But, similar to her response on convicted prisoners, Sturgeon refused and took no action (E85; E94). Indeed, Sturgeon made no specific arrangements to involve hard-to-reach voters. The indication is that, in terms of argument hegemony, and even though MSPs had considered several ways of raising the awareness of the referendum within Scottish society, the Scottish government did not take these offers. This is an awkward observation regards Sturgeon, and is not helped by her seeming reluctance to use the occasion to soapbox on independence. But this was not the case. She alone contributed to around a quarter of the debate but mentioned ‘independence’ only twice (E93)⁵⁴. The point is it is extremely difficult to win at argument hegemony when a case is not presented. Ultimately, and other than her failure to grasp a series of opportunities that could help advance her political *raison d’être*, Sturgeon offered nothing of significance to the debate. However, she was also not the only one offering nothing in this respect. George Adam said of SIRFA and the wider referendum that:

The whole idea is that we are showing the public how they can make a difference ... this is about having a vision and a passion for the future of the country. That is what will make a difference for many people (E66; E79).

The problem for Adam is that ‘passion’ offers nothing without action, and short of agreeing the reduction in the age of franchise, he was offering little else, particularly that which could be assumed to fall in line with a realist perspective, either in furthering a political agenda via opposition craft or in terms of being pro-hegemonic towards the arrangements for the referendum. Another SNP MSP who offered nothing was the SNP’s Clare Adamson who said of the Scottish electorate that if they didn’t partake in the referendum the consequences were theirs to live with, saying that “if they [the Scottish electorate] decide to turn their back on the fire and burn their behinds, then they will just have to sit on their blisters” (E66; E69; E79; E89; E90; E95). The point being made here is that the ideological vacuum identified via Sturgeon’s non-committal non-actions was also present in the wider party.

Smith argues that “cultures and politics are forged by small minorities, usually by one kind of elite or other” (2008: 6). Regards Scotland, Leith and Soule argue that those that make up

⁵⁴ Sturgeon actually mentioned ‘independence’ nine times but seven of them were in her directly referencing the legislation under debate (E93).

civic Scotland act as the “custodians of nationalist ideas” (2012: 6; 81). A problem, however, is that these same elites have very different ideas on national identity to those of Scottish society (Leith and Soule, 2012). The suggestion is disconnect between civic Scotland and Scottish society, reinforced by a lack of awareness by MSPs as to what motivates the rest of the Scottish population. This disconnect is not undermined by arguments that Scottish independence could “end that dependency culture by making Scotland and individual Scots stand on their own two feet” (Cochrane and Kerevan, 2014: 57). This perspective is also relevant to MSPs who, by definition, are a cohort of the wider civic Scotland and as a collective, also showed to have very different expectations of Scottish society than those that comprise it. And to this end, this investigation noted that it was a rarity when MSPs Scottish society was viewed in a positive light. Instead, they talked about criminality, sectarianism, and of a growing disengagement with politics which, as far as this thesis is concerned, is a practice that serves to reinforce this disengagement - but along class lines (E66; E69; E79; E81; E85; E86; E88; E91; E92; E95). The culmination is that whilst the appearance is that civic Scotland was not representative of the Scottish electorate and that the Scottish government failed to maximise the opportunities for movement building, either in logistical, organisational, or ideological terms. To this end, this investigation offers insights symptomatic of an Edinburgh bubble, meaning that overall, argument hegemony remains in play as the predominate lever for this third step.

Governing competence: Bulpitt (1983) argued that the dual polity needed to be maintained if statecraft was to be achieved. It is important to know when and how to intervene in low politics without experiencing rebound. Mitigating factors can include, but are not limited to, party ideology, difficulty in implementation, the reputation of the governing party, the competence of the politician making the final, actionable, decisions notwithstanding (Morgenthau, 1978; Bulpitt, 1986; James, 2018). It is also beneficial to structure an intervention into low politics and to assist, Bulpitt offers his models of territorial management (see chapter two). The upshot is that how problems are managed are in themselves, an important component for achieving statecraft (Morgenthau, 1978; Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; Stevens, 2002; Buller and James, 2012a; 2012b; James, 2016; 2018). And to this end, and as had been noted earlier investigations, the Scottish government continued to delegate work, this time to civic Scotland and the Edinburgh bubble (E62; E63; E66; E71; E74; E75; E78; E81; E85; E86; E88; E89; E90; E91; E92). This cohort represented the vanguard of a growing collective tasked with promoting the referendum and a high turnout (E66; E74; E78)

- a task arguably undermined by Sturgeon's failure to accept arrangements to involve hard-to-reach voters, despite MSPs suggesting remedies (E74; E79; E86; E89; E90). This failure of opposition craft was further compounded when it is remembered that via their majority in Holyrood, the Scottish government was largely free to act, limited Edinburgh Agreement constraints aside. Yet, Sturgeon maintained a neutral hand throughout, contrary to the literature on statecraft and realism (Morgenthau, 1978; Bulpitt, 1983; Kissinger, 2014; James, 2016; 2018). The consequence is that whilst governing competence presents as a failure, the scenario warrants more discussion and, as such, this lever remains in play.

Party management: there is no evidence to suggest this lever has relevance to this investigation. As such, it is redundant.

Electoral strategy: the accumulative investigative results already indicate the Scottish government's failure to make arrangements to involve hard-to-reach voters (E86; E94; E95). This posture persisted despite a submission to Holyrood by the Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations (SCVO). THE SCVO had called for specific measures to encourage participation the poor, vulnerable, and black and ethnic minorities in the referendum campaign, most of who could be found in "areas of social deprivation" (E66; E74; E80; E81; E85; E88; E89; E90; E91; E92; E95). These were the hard-to-reach voters, of whom John Pentland said represented roughly ten percent of the electorate and who had fallen off the electoral register (E66; E79; E83; E89). Quoting the SCVO, Pentland said, "In areas of high levels of deprivation it can be more than thirty per cent. In particular social groups in those areas, more than half of those who are eligible remain unregistered" (E66). However, Sturgeon offered no solutions or remedies and ignored this cohort in her final summary (E86; E94). It is also evident that it was MSPs and not the Scottish government that considered raising the awareness of the referendum within Scottish society. Lijphart said referendums are "controlled" and designed to be "pro-hegemonic" (1984: 203), but that does not appear to be the case here. The consequence is further evidence to suggest that the Scottish government did not offer specific arrangements to involve hard-to-reach voters and with this, it failed to maximise the opportunities for movement building. Here, it is important to note that in a time when, for Armstrong (2015), politicians appear content with a lack of voters or an ill-informed electorate, and whilst the investigations found that MSPs were operating contrary to that trend, the same cannot be said for Sturgeon (E94).

The point being made here is that the investigations undertaken for CA1 and CA2 indicate the franchise being manipulated for politically expedient purposes, and this same premise applies also to SIRFA. However, extending the franchise to this cohort represented a modest two percent inflation of the electorate (BBC, 2014), but ignored a missing ten percent. The clear inference is of a failed electoral strategy which, by routine, would make the lever redundant to this investigation. This abnormal result, however, requires more discussion and to this end, electoral strategy remains in play as the predominate lever for this third step.

Rule bending: there is no evidence to suggest this lever has relevance to this investigation. As such, it is redundant.

Summary: this investigation premised on the potential SIRFA encouraged the mobilisation of Scottish society, with electoral strategy acting as the predominant lever. This final summary sees three surviving statecraft levers acting potentially as the predominate lever - argument hegemony, governing competence, and electoral strategy.

This final investigation had begun in the knowledge that SIRFA mobilised the Edinburgh bubble and who, laterally, were to be provided pre-defined campaign roles (E72; E74; E75; E78; E81; E82; E88; E92). To this end, it is arguable that SIRFA did indeed build the necessary infrastructure to inform and educate a newly franchised one hundred thousand voters. However, the failure to connect with the hard-to-reach ten percent of the electorate potentially wiped out any electoral benefit offered by SIRFA, potentially by up to eight percent. This feat involved operating a dual polity that centred on organisational mobilisation. It involved the Edinburgh bubble, civic Scotland, and the wider middle classes, as agents for promoting both a positive campaign and a high turnout. Within this situation, overwhelming evidence that the Scottish government did not maximise the opportunities for movement building (E66; E73; E79; E81; E82; E85; E86; E88; E88; E89; E91; E92; E94; E95). The argument is that the Scottish government took as neutral as position a possible on the preparations, promotion, and raising awareness of the independence referendum, a position that is further compounded by Sturgeon's further failure to use the debate to promote Scottish independence. As a position, this is contrary to the established lines in the literatures on secession, statecraft, realism, and referendums (Morgenthau, 1978; Wood, 1981; Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; Lijphart, 1984; Qvortrup, 2000; 2020; James, 2012; 2016; 2018).

Figure 28: 2013 hoop test probability-9

As such, and given the development of support systems that correlate to governing competence and argument hegemony, the overall effect was to mobilise - administratively, promotionally, and informatively - and in a way that encouraged a positive campaign and a high turnout, and this in itself presents as an out and out case of electoral strategy (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; James, 2012; 2016). To this end, electoral strategy is deemed to be the predominate lever for this third and final investigation. This insight, however, requires caution given that it comes with a lowly probability of twenty-five percent, as indicated in Figure 28, above. The supporting evidence base can be found in Table 36.

Chapter conclusions

The absence of rule bending in the precipitancy runs contrary to the literatures on necessity, realism, secession, and statecraft. These insights present a problem for these final comments to this chapter because we are using blunt instruments to aid our interpretation of events as investigated and found. Chapter eight had already outlined noted gaps in the Bulpittian perspective, particularly in respect of how statecraft is achieved in a parliament elected by proportional representation, and of the effects of the participatory model on achieving statecraft. These limitations are further enhanced when it is remembered that given the downward trend in secessionist cases since the turn of the century, explanations as to how a devolved government or parliament behaves in the precipitancy are a bit thin on the ground. Nonetheless, a first point to note is from Wood (1981) that in the precipitancy both state and secessionist force will use 'security' as justification for action. However, there is no evidence that this eventuality occurred in the Scottish precipitancy. The same can be said regards rule bending which at this stage in proceedings is deemed a pre-requisite across the literatures on secession, statecraft, and realism (Morgenthau, 1978; Wood, 1981; Mearsheimer, 2001; Sorens, 2012; Kissinger, 2014; Griffiths (b), 2016; James, 2016; 2018). The result is that contrary to doctrine, rule bending is absent here. So too is party management which had little relevance to the investigations undertaken for this chapter.

In effect, the prevailing insights relate only to argument hegemony, governing competence, and electoral strategy. With governing competence being shaped by a dual polity that leaned on organisation mobilisation, the Scottish government effectively outsourced all aspects of electoral administration, awareness, and promotion of the independence referendum to third parties, many of which had pre-existing relationships with Holyrood. As an action, it fed into an opposition craft that completely lacked in any form of argument hegemony. Indeed, there were no indicators that Sturgeon had sought to act in a pro-hegemonic manner and instead, a wealth of evidence exists to suggest that instead, she took a neutral position to the independence referendum. This posture also fed into the failed potential that Sturgeon and wider SNP would use the SIRFA debate to tilt the legislation so to be favourable to the secessionist cause. In fairness, inflating the electoral register by around two percent does present as another case of politicians making politically expedient changes to electoral administration (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986; James, 2012; 2016; 2018). Collectively, and as collated in Table 37, these insights come with an accumulative forty-one percent probability rating.

Table 37: 2013 hoop tests

Step	Statement	Causal framework	Hoop test	Causal inference
7: redefine the vote	The Scottish government fully exploited the autonomy provided via Cameronian statecraft	argument hegemony		electoral strategy
8: promote the vote	SIRFA was premised towards citizen mobilisation	governing competence		electoral strategy
9: mobilise Scottish society	CA2 was an attempt to preserve the status quo	electoral strategy		electoral strategy

It is difficult to see how Sturgeon or the wider Scottish government could achieve statecraft by committing to a series of policies that did little to help it prevail in the referendum. SIRFA offered only limited impact, was under-exploited, what benefit it did offer to the Scottish

government and wider SNP was vulnerable to being completely wiped out. Her refusal to agree informational mail shots; her objection to re-enfranchising the missing ten percent (four hundred thousand voters); and her failure to extend the franchise to convicted prisoners, presents as a posture completely contrary to the accepted doctrinal approaches outlined in the literature. The importance of argument hegemony cannot be understated here because insofar as opposition craft is concerned, the Scottish national interest had been deemed to be best advanced through neutrality. Yet, as per Figure 29, the investigations found that SIRFA was an out-and-out case of electoral strategy, albeit a flawed one. In all, SIRFA was a liberalist response to a realist solution for a constructivist problem.

Figure 29: 2013 causal inferences

Overall, the investigations for this chapter found that the Scottish government failed to fully exploit the autonomy provided via Cameronian statecraft. Sturgeon spurned emergent opportunities to engage directly with the poorest ten percent of the electorate. Whilst MSPs claimed that the newly franchised were beneficiaries of SIRFA, the immediate benefactors were the political entrepreneurs and professional activists, whose proximity to Holyrood had been concretised via the participatory model. The product heavily associated with Wood's (1981) concept of the secessionist entrepreneur whose job it was to mobilise both the newly franchised sixteen-year-olds and the rest of Scottish society positively, and in a way that encouraged a high turnout. To this end, organisational, not citizen, mobilisation was used to complete this task and enabled by MSPs with their own pet causes to promote, and consequent to which an Edinburgh Bubble emerged.

SIRFA was a piece of legislation from the Scottish government that sought to propagandize the independence referendum by giving sixteen-year-olds the vote. The Scottish government said the policy would be a success and the vast majority of MSPs agreed. To ensure it was successful, associates and entrepreneurs from within the Edinburgh Bubble were tasked with

promoting a positive campaign and a high turnout. Their base message said nothing about winning and ignored the missing, and poorest, ten percent of the overall electorate. In all, SIRFA was intended to mobilise Scottish society but served only to mobilise the middle classes. In the referendum Scotland voted by a ten percent margin for the status quo. A week after the referendum, research for the House of Commons Library indicated that voters in receipt of state benefits were more likely to have voted 'Yes' for independence (Ayres, 2014). As for the referendum itself, it is remembered for its high turn and is remembered in the public conscience for being a joyous political experience. In fairness, the middle classes did as they were asked.

Chapter ten: the fourth estate

The media is not a monolithic bloc and is instead, made up of an array of sectors across TV, radio, newspapers, and online platforms, with each working in competition and at times, in conjunction. Newspapers offer longevity in that they precede these other formats (see chapter five). Recent convergence with the online setting aside, newspapers have relied on roughly the same business model since inception. The analyses undertaken for this chapter comes on the back of complaints that the media were, and are, biased against Scottish independence (Robertson, 2014; Blain et al, 2016; Schlesinger, 2020). Robertson (2014) had said that broadcasters tended to push a party political line that resulted in a three-to-one bias against any representatives from the SNP or Yes campaign, whilst Monbiot (2014) says that apart from the sole exception of the Sunday Herald, all newspapers, local and national, were against Scottish independence. Building on these insights, this chapter builds upon these insights by making further inquiries, this time by analysing press reportage of the debates on CA1, CA2, and SIRFA, and do so through a statecraft lens so to improve our understanding of newspapers, as a foundation for future inquiries into newspapers and the wider media as agents of statecraft. Park et al's (2009) model on media influence is used for this exercise, meaning that bias in newspapers is considered in terms of business - owners, advertisers, and target audience; and politics - government, political view, and ideology (Park et al, 2009). Given the timeframe involved in these analyses (1978-2013) the expectation is to see fluctuations in newspaper postures towards Scottish devolution and/or independence.

Newspapers across the impulse

The investigations into newspaper reportage of the debates have already informed aspects of chapters six, seven, and eight. That effort culminates in this section, which offers further insights into the debates on CA1, CA2, and SIRFA, as well as wider contextual insights regards in the preconditions, rise/movement eras, as well as in the precipitancy. This section outlines the results of the grid analyses undertaken in respect of the reporting on the three debates. For reference, the newspaper codes are repeated below. See chapter five for an explanation of the coding arrangements and in respect of grid analysis, and its application.

Table 19: newspapers
(Repeated from pg. 111)

	1978	1997	2013
Guardian	F1	G1	H1
Telegraph	F2	G2	H2
The Times	F3	G3	H3
The Mirror	F4	G4	H4
The Sun	F5	G5	H5
Glasgow Herald	F6	G6	H6
The Scotsman	F7	G7	H7
Daily Record	F8	G8	H8
News of the World/ Sun on Sunday	F9	G9	H9
Sunday Mirror	F10	G10	H10
Sunday Telegraph	F11	G11	H11
Sunday Times	F12	G12	H12
The Observer	F13	G13	H13
Sunday Herald	F14	G14	H14
Sunday Post	F15	G15	H15
Sunday Mail	F16	G16	H16

(Black blocks denote inability to obtain the publication)

1978 - CA1

The lead-in reportage focused not on CA1 but instead on the Amendment tabled by the Liberal MP Jo Grimond calling for an opt-out for Orkney and Shetland in the event that Scotland voted in favour of devolution (F1; F2; F3; F4; F6; F7; F8; F10; F12; F15). However, Grimond's Amendment was given so much coverage largely because it was directly impacted by the guillotine motion put in place by the Labour government. As such, it was government that dictated the time allocated to debate on the legislation, Amendments included. MPs were not happy with the use of the guillotine and the newspapers reported a disorderly and belligerent Commons. There, unnamed pro-devolution MPs were reported to have attempted to disrupt and delay the Grimond Amendment by hanging around in the lobbies as a way to run down the clock to guillotine time. The Commons became rowdy. Conservatives chanted 'cheat, cheat' at the Labour front benches, and to cheers, the Speaker of the Commons ordered that the delayed vote be announced as it then stood, regardless of whether completed or not. His action allowed Grimond to successfully table his Amendment with minutes to spare. The main journalistic stance premised on accusations that the Labour government had not played fairly in the Commons, which it had (Bulpitt, 1983; James, 2016; 2018).

Table 38: 1978 article contents

	F 1	F 2	F 3	F 4	F 6	F 7	F 8	F 10	F 12	F 15	Total
guillotine	16	17	6	6	10	13	2	1	-	-	71
Orkney & Shetland	13	5	7	4	11	8	1	2	2	1	44

In reality, the press was largely in favour of the backbench action and over-whelming in its opposition to Scottish devolution. The newspapers accessed for this investigation made little attempt to criticise CA1 on its merits as a standalone electoral act. In all, the reportage on CA1 was superficial and relied on a dominant argument hegemony that revolved around the promotion of parliamentary sovereignty, as per Table 39, whilst further promoting the idea that the Labour government had bent the rules by breaking parliamentary protocols. At the same time, journalists made no attempt to criticise CA1 on its merits as a standalone electoral act. Indeed, the principle of entrusting the House of Commons with preserving Scottish territorial integrity was a criticism too far for a press corps that was collectively in favour of the entire plot to undermine the Bill (1977) and Scottish devolution. As for George Cunningham, this research found one solitary criticism. Found in a column in the Sunday Post, the article contained zero political insight and offered only an eighty-seven-word long ad hominem diatribe (F15)⁵⁵.

Table 39: 1978 articles coverage

	F 1	F 2	F 3	F 4	F 6	F 7	F 8	F 10	F 12	F 15	F 16	Total
parliamentary supremacy	21	21	24	7	29	50	9	1	2	1	1	166
merits of a threshold	11	16	17	1	9	26	3	3	4	-	1	91
turnout	8	5	14	-	1	17	2	3	-	-	2	52
Scotland v. UK-wide vote	4	-	15	-	8	5	-	-	-	-	-	32

Instead, and as is indicated in Table 40, newspapers appear to have presented a narrative that was overwhelmingly in favour of the backbench action and were overwhelming in their editorial opposition to Scottish devolution. Overall, the newspapers largely took an anti-devolutionary position that failed to offer a thorough analysis of the implications of CA1 on the then upcoming referendum. The same can be said for the earlier Table 38 in relation to the Grimond Amendment.

⁵⁵ Titled “He’s another Enoch!” it was an article aimed at George Cunningham who it was claimed was a “loner” with a “self-righteous attitude” who had abandoned Fife and who had “spent most of his life south of the Border” (F15).

Table 40: 1978 newspaper postures

	F 1	F 2	F 3	F 4	F 6	F 7	F 8	F 10	F 12	F 15	F 16		Total
anti-devolution	31	31	45	4	37	48	11	5	5	9	4		230
pro-devolution	16	14	8	1	13	15	7	2	2	-	2		80

Here it should be noted that government had found it difficult to achieve statecraft in the 1970s (Bulpitt, 1983; Tomlinson, 1996). Government had become “overwhelmed”, was increasingly boxed in, and was constantly fire-fighting (Bulpitt, 1983; Tomlinson, 1996; Buller 1999: 698). Theory also says that when situations such as CA1 occur, blame should lie with the Prime Minister (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986; Stevens, 2002; Griffiths (b), 2016; James, 2016; 2018). However, Callaghan largely escaped direct blame in the newspapers and direct reference to him in the press was limited. Instead, blame was apportioned to Michael Foot who as Leader of the House had the job of ensuring the safe passage of the Bill (1977) to Royal Assent. But it had been captured by an in-party opposition craft then altered, so to redefine victory in the then upcoming referendum (F1; F2; F3; F4; F6; F7; F8; F10; F12) (see chapter six). However, Callaghan had his own issues with newspapers to address.

He had been in the job for two years and the newspapers were already speculating on his future, including the potential of an imminent general election (F10; F15). Indeed, the press had already lined up potential candidates to replace him following an expected electoral loss, including Michael Foot and the Energy Secretary, Tony Benn. Indeed, political memoirs from the time indicate a similar scenario (Callaghan, 1987; Dalyell, 2016; Sillars, 2021). All three were depicted in cartoons, some of which was highly personalised⁵⁶. And whilst they helped reinforce an anti-devolution position, primarily in respect of parliamentary supremacy, newspapers were feeding into an analysis that promoted overwhelming argument hegemony as the main driver behind the reporting, as per Table 41.

⁵⁶ The Telegraph portraying Callaghan as bloated and puffed out, losing a race against a relatively lean Tony Benn (F2). This image of Benn was at odds with real life given that the newspapers had deemed him to be a procrastinator who had sat on a report on a much-needed reform of the UK’s energy infrastructure for a year and a half (F1; F6; F7). As for Foot, his likeness was captured by the Sunday Times cartoonist Gerald Scarfe who linked another story at the time, that of an out-of-control Soviet satellite, to Foot’s experience over CA1 (F12), the caption underneath simply saying: “devolution satellite burns out over Scotland” (F12).

Table 41: 1978 newspaper levers

	F 1	F 2	F 3	F 4	F 6	F 7	F 8	F 10	F 12	F 15	F 16	Total
argument hegemony	39	17	44	6	41	73	10	2	4	8	6	250
governing competence	32	35	20	9	19	18	7	3	5	4	2	154
electoral strategy	12	17	16	-	16	35	6	5	14	-	3	124
party management	12	16	14	1	14	7	2	-	6	4	-	76
bending the rules	10	4	4	2	11	11	1	1	1	-	2	47

The evident splits in the Labour party that led to CA1 were rarely mentioned and whilst rule bending was a further minority interest, its usage largely related to the use of the guillotine, and in doing so served to reinforce both the message of governmental wrongdoing and of parliamentary sovereignty.

The full dataset can be found in at Appendix 6.

1997

Conservatives responded to the Bill (1997) by tabling around two hundred Amendments (see chapter seven). The newly elected Labour government retaliated by imposing a guillotine on the debate, just as Callaghan had done in 1978. Again, the action caused anger amongst MPs and in the papers, headlines again reported “angry scenes” in the Commons “as the Government sought to force through its proposals for devolution referendums in Scotland [and Wales]” (G6). The Guardian took a more principled view. The editorial there argued that “the use of the guillotine was an action of an arrogant government which holds Parliament in contempt” (G1). It also reported on backbench Conservatives complaining that the Church of England could be disestablished “in weeks using a guillotine motion” (G1). A similar line was taken in the Times where the editorial argued that “victory in the referendum will only give the Government the authority to introduce a Bill, not smuggle it past scrutiny (G3). By deploying the guillotine now, the case for quick passage of the Devolution Bill has become a casualty” (G3). In effect, and similar to 1978, the focus of the press had been the actions of a Labour government perceived to have disrespected the rules of the UK Parliament by applying the guillotine (G1; G2; G3; G4; G6; G7; G8; G10). Indeed, Conservative accusations of ‘tyranny’ were also given a reasonable airing in the papers (G1; G2; G3; G6; G7).

However, only minority coverage was offered to the actual merits of either the Bill (1997) or indeed, CA2 and completely ignored a number of the more complex issues, i.e., the legacy of Kilbrandon, or EVEL, as well as debate on the potential that devolution could aid progress towards Scottish independence. Instead, the papers focused on a number of secondary issues as content topics - votes for service personnel, the cost of setting up a Scottish parliament, and the potential for another CA1-style threshold (G1; G2; G3; G6; G7; G8; G15). As had been the case with CA1 in 1978, the attempt by the newspapers to inform their readerships on events was, collectively speaking, a relatively poor effort.

Table 42: 1997 article contents

	G 1	G 2	G 3	G 4	G 6	G 7	G 8	G 15	Total
guillotine	17	3	10	1	19	12	2	1	65
Parliamentary supremacy	8	4	8	-	11	15	1	-	47
performative politics	7	1	2	1	17	6	-	-	34
tyranny	9	1	4	-	5	9	-	-	27
Scotland-only vote	1	-	-	-	-	-	10	-	11
UK-wide vote	1	-	1	1	5	1	3	2	14
Scottish nationalism	1	2	-	-	3	-	4	-	10
English nationalism	-	2	1	-	3	1	-	-	7
threshold	-	-	1	-	2	1	-	1	5
service personnel	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	2
cost	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
other states	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1

The Herald, which publishes out of Glasgow, reserved judgement on Labour’s use of the guillotine. In a warning to the fledgling Labour government, it argued that “we are not too fazed about the use of the guillotine in this instance, but it will be different if the Government tries the same tactic when the full legislation comes before Parliament after the referendum” (G6). Inherent in this response was the prospect that Scotland would vote for devolution, a genuine likelihood given that the Herald also reported on polling showing three-one for ‘Yes’ (G6). In respect of CA2, this was addressed directly in the Times, and offered editorial support for a UK-wide vote (G3)⁵⁷.

⁵⁷ “It is legitimate to debate why only those resident [sic] in Scotland and Wales should vote when the entire kingdom will be affected by the result. It is not self-evident why Scotland and Wales should have different questions or why Scots should be asked to vote simultaneously on the principle of a parliament and then whether that parliament should have tax-varying powers. Finally, Parliament might ask why even the meanest golf club requires more than a mere majority to change its constitution, the United Kingdom can be recast by a simple majority of a tiny minority” (G3).

Table 43: 1997 newspaper postures

	G 1	G 2	G 3	G 4	G 6	G 7	G 8	G 15	Total
anti-devolution	8	2	1	-	17	13	4	11	56
pro-devolution	2	4	2	1	10	3	9	1	32

As noted in Table 43, the indication is that, as had also been the case in 1978, newspapers remained unconvinced of the merits of Scottish devolution, this time at a narrower rate of nearly two to one. As indicated in Table 44, journalists premised their reporting on Commons supremacy and the status quo, another parallel with 1978 that fed into a dominant argument hegemonic stance.

Table 44: 1997 newspaper levers

	G 1	G 2	G 3	G 4	G 6	G 7	G 8	G 15	Total
argument hegemony	27	9	9	-	32	27	16	9	129
governing competence	10	2	10	1	14	9	7	2	55
party management	8	-	2	-	6	3	4	2	25
electoral strategy	1	-	-	-	2	2	16	2	23

Unlike in 1978 however, the newspapers were also critical of the Conservatives. Only a month earlier the party had received a drubbing in Scotland and polling in Scotland put the party support in single figures (G6). The Herald asked was it not time to “ask if it is not the Tory MPs who are being arrogant, high handed, and showing blatant disdain for the electorate” (G6). The Conservative position on the guillotine premised on the argument that the guillotine had never been applied to constitutional debates (G1; G6). This was not true, as had been noted the earlier discussion on the Grimond Amendment. The Guardian said that the guillotine motion was “the cause of much fake outrage from the Tories”, particularly given the tactic had been used sixty-one times since 1979 (G1). The Herald concluded that “one of the most disappointing things about a guillotine debate is the lack of a guillotine” (G6). A cartoon in the same paper centred on a pompous but fictional Conservative MP displaying false horror at the use of the guillotine to cut short the debate. “Sir Bufton Tufton” represented as a shift along from the personalised attacks that formed the backbone of broadsheet political cartoons in 1978 involving Callaghan, Foot, and Benn. By 1997, this ‘promotion of the personal’ had acquired a life of its own (Bulpitt, 1986b; Foley, 2004; Buller and James, 2012a; James, 2016; 2018). Fuelled by the Blair brand, resulting practice was one far removed from that observed in 1978 (see chapters three, five, and, seven).

Personal frailties and other quirks of the human condition were weaponised by newspapers in an attempt to caricature politicians, this time not by cartoons but by words, and politicians appear to have had little choice in their partaking in this new style of political practice.

An example relates to the reportage of the Conservative leadership battle. Andrew Rawnsley in the Observer argued the next leader of the Conservatives would be either “Cavalier Ken or Hague the Vague” (G13). William Hague was ruled out, having been described as “John Major, but with O-levels” (G13). Clarke was also the favourite for a young Boris Johnson who was urging his readers in the Telegraph to support Clarke because he was less likely to be a “nationalist xenophobe” (G2). The irony of this statement being amplified by the same paper’s editorial warning that Clarke possessed an “unusual moral status, that of the ‘good German’ during the war” (G2). Aside Clarke, another front runner was Michael Howard who the Observer said of his strengths and weaknesses of becoming leader that they revolved around his being a “shameless opportunist” (G13). The Guardian had said of him in respect of his performance in the Commons, that “either he has taken speech lessons or else someone has removed the ceremonial truncheon of state from up his backside” (G1). As for the Mirror, it reminisced about when as an aspirant MP, Howard stood for election for a constituency in Liverpool. Apparently, he was an “oily” character who “stood out like a black face at a Boer’s wedding” (G4). This caustic form of political reporting was not exclusive to the Conservatives. Scottish Secretary Donald Dewar, who was fronting the Bill (1997), also came to the attention of the newspapers and which portrayed him as miserable and perplexed.

The Scotsman said Dewar had the same facial expression people express when they are “not quite sure whether or not they have left the gas on” (G7). Whereas the Sunday Post said, “Nobody would award Donald first place in a happy faces competition ... [he] looks like a funeral director on the verge of bankruptcy” (G15). The drift towards personalised and ad hominem-led political discourse occurred in a similar timeframe that saw Alistair Campbell move from the Daily Mirror to Downing Street to act as Tony Blair’s Director of Communication (see chapter three). And in what represents as an out and out case of argument hegemony, the political narrative shifted towards the promotion and destruction of public personas whilst also leaning heavily on a manufactured politic that equated competence with charisma (Buller and James, 2012a; 2012b; James, 2018). This latter brand of political communication and analysis also fed into the newspapers reporting on the Bill (1997) and CA2, the reason being it was Tony Blair and not Donald Dewar who gained

political credit in the newspapers. “Blair crushes opposition to referendum” was the headline in the next day’s Scotsman (G7) - even though he’d played no part in the debate. Instead, and a month after he had won a landslide at the general election, Blair was preparing to go on tour (G12). ‘Talk to Tony’ intended travelling the UK so the new Prime Minister could repeat what he did a few weeks earlier during the general election, namely attend superficially stage-managed events and be photographed meeting and interacting with a hand-picked audience (G12).

CA2 and the wider debate on the Bill (1997) was a next day story which had been mostly forgotten by the time the Sunday papers were being printed. Only the Sunday Post reported on it, saying that George Cunningham had been watching the debate and was reported to have said that whilst he “wouldn’t get away with his threshold in 1997 he intended campaigning “for Scots in England to vote in the referendum” (G15). This was contrary to the position he took in 1978 when he intimated support for a Scotland-only vote (see chapter six), and by implication, removes any doubt if there were any, that Cunningham was not anti-devolutionist, assuming his position hadn’t changed. As for this research, the indication is that the press position also had not changed because, in congruence with the reporting in 1978, they continued to lean heavily on an argument hegemony that firmly supported the status quo. Added, and gauged from the reporting on CA2 and its related matters, the indication is of a newspaper corps that was less likely to report on the actual events and instead offer journalistic takes on what they had deemed as newsworthy.

The full dataset can be found in Appendix 7.

2013

For the third time, newspapers failed to inform their readerships of political events. Only two next-day Scottish newspapers - the Herald and the Scotsman - covered the debate (H6; H7), so in reality, this is really a case of ignoring events rather than reporting on them inaccurately. The Scotsman offered the more extensive reportage but the focus was predominantly on prisoner voting rights (H7), as per Table 45. The Scotsman’s report included a comment by Nicola Sturgeon that convicted prisoners should not be entitled to vote because they had broken their “contract with society” (H7). Her comment was published

without rebuttal, even though it was misleading⁵⁸. At the same time, discussion on turnout, electoral administration, and indeed, any mention of Scottish independence are notable by their absence. Whilst these insights are extremely limited in their scope, it is observed that once again that argument hegemony was predominate in shaping the reports, as per Table 47, caused primarily by the top-heavy reporting on the prisoner franchise. Table 48 notes that this tiny sub-sample also recorded a newspaper reportage that, consistent with the findings in respect of CA1 and CA2, was again pro-status quo.

Table 45: 2013 newspaper reporting

	H 6	H 7	Total
prisoner voting rights	2	19	21
16-18 voting rights	6	4	10
civic Scotland	5	2	7
third sector	4	2	6
contract with society	-	5	5
political entrepreneurs	3	2	5
Scottish society	-	4	4
education	2	1	3
Franchise Bill	1	2	3
16-18 electoral awareness	-	1	1

Table 46: 2013 newspaper levers

	H 6	H 7	Total
argument hegemony	7	23	30
electoral strategy	5	1	6
party management	1	1	2

Table 47: 2013 newspaper posture

	H 6	H 7	Total
anti-SIRFA	3	13	16
pro-SIRFA	4	8	12

The debate on SIRFA took place some sixteen months prior to the date of the referendum and the campaign was already heating up and the SIRFA debate formed only a part of a busy week in Scottish politics. The Sunday Times reported on a trip to Edinburgh by the UKIP

⁵⁸ There is no such thing as a ‘contract with society’. Individuals do not have obligations to one another. What obligations we do have are placed on us by the state. i.e., it is not society that determines what acts are criminal and of those that are not - it is the state. And the nuance of criminal legislation means that what is illegal today may be legal tomorrow, and vice versa (Allen and Thompson, 2002; Foster, 2006; Elliott and Thomas, 2020).

Leader, Nigel Farage, who intended campaigning for a ‘No’ vote. However, his intentions were thwarted when members of the Radical Independence Campaign (RIC) organised a counter-protest causing Farage to take shelter in a pub on Canon’s Gait and wait until the Police came to the rescue (H12). The papers also reported on the creation of two more pro-independence groups - ‘Business for Scotland’, which intended putting forward a business case for independence; and, ‘Christians for Yes’ which announced an intention to hand out leaflets at the then upcoming General Assembly of the Church of Scotland (H6; H15). These groups formed part of the wider Yes movement, an organisational mobilisation occurring in tandem with the precipitancy. And as was being recorded in the newspapers, this eventuality was taking place in real time. Accompanying the rise was the emergence of secessionist entrepreneurs, many of whom were heavily associated with the emergent Edinburgh Bubble. Natalie McGarry is one example - she had worked as an advisor in the third sector and her aunt happened to be at the time the Presiding Officer at the Scottish parliament (BBC, 2022; Women for Independence, 2023). In a textbook example of secessionist entrepreneurialism, her public persona had been boosted when by the time of the SIRFA debate, she was writing articles in the Scotsman (H7).

By acquiring a public persona, the task that McGarry and the like had effectively set themselves included countering the SAPs that were emerging out of the Downing Street Devolution Unit (see chapter eight). The most recent had argued that Scottish independence would cause financial services to relocate out of Scotland and lead to a 2008/09 Iceland-style “meltdown” (H15). Added, whilst an independent Scotland would be in need of an IMF-style bail-out but would be unable to secure one because it wouldn’t be able to afford to pay it back (H14). The results would cause individual Scots £65,000 each (H15). Indeed, the same paper, the Sunday Post, also reported that at the time banking assets held in Scotland had been valued at over a thousand percent of the projected GDP of an independent Scotland (H15), itself a contradiction of the SAP data. Reportage of this nature is entirely in line with Robertson’s argument that the arguable economic consequences of independence, i.e., trade, taxes, cost of living, unemployment, were prominent news features in the lead-up to the referendum (2014: n.p.). In the same issue, the Post also published details on the Callaghan government covering up the 1975 McCrone Report that assessed the true wealth of North Sea oil, the vast majority of which was, and is, resident on Scottish maritime waters (H15)⁵⁹. Yet,

⁵⁹ The McCrone report concluded that “large revenues and balance of payments gains would indeed accrue to a Scottish Government in the event of independence provided that steps were taken either by carried interest or by taxation to secure the Government ‘take’. Undoubtedly

the SAP data was never rebutted nor was there any evidence of further investigation. The effect was that readers were left to draw their own conclusions over the state-sponsored argument that an independent Scotland would face an inevitable financial cataclysm. The only counter-resource available was the ‘Wee Blue Book’ published and distributed in large numbers by the blog, Wings over Scotland (WoS). WoS was positioned similarly to RIC with both falling into a campaign category that, for Berger (1979), is frowned upon by the political elites because their strategies involve anti-politics, a position arguably reinforced consequent to the Farage incident. Yet, it was RIC, and not the Scottish government, that strategized and rolled out a campaign to encourage mass voter registration in hard-to-reach communities (Carrell, 2014), an essential task if the much-anticipated high-turnout was to be realised. As for the Wee Blue Book, the former First Minister of Scotland, Alex Salmond, latterly attributed a fifteen percent rise in support for independence directly to it and WoS (Alba Party, 2021).

A newspaper not informing its readership is not a new observation for this chapter, nor is the consistency in promoting the status quo via a dominant practice of argument hegemony. What was new however, and observed in this investigation, was the overlap between newspapers output and content published online, particularly social media. The product is shortened, superficial, news articles presented in bite-size chunks similar to what Ritzer called “the McPaper” (2004: 7). The optimum example is the Daily Record, published in Scotland and sister-paper to the Sunday Mail (see chapter six), where, there, a news feature included tweets received by the paper the previous day⁶⁰. In reality, this was mere gossip masquerading as news or current affairs and typifies that although journalistic practice had altered somewhat between 1978, 1997, and 2013, the prevalence for not informing on Scottish politics in any meaningful way continued, as did tacit support for the status quo.

The full dataset can be found in Appendix 8.

this would banish any anxieties the Government might have had about its budgetary position or its balance of payments. The country would tend to be in chronic surplus to a quite embarrassing degree and its currency would become the hardest in Europe, with the exception perhaps of the Norwegian kroner. Just as deposed monarchs and African leaders have in the past used the Swiss franc as a haven of security, so now would the Scottish pound be seen as a good hedge against inflation and devaluation and the Scottish banks could expect to find themselves inundated with a speculative inflow of foreign funds” (Scottish Economic Planning Department, 1975: 8).

⁶⁰ Former Prime Minister Gordon Brown took lead place in the article (H8). Having helped set up Unite with Labour, a pro-status quo campaign group, the Record published tweets claiming he talks “more sense than many” and that he did “amazing work for charity” (H8).

Sources of journalistic bias

The previous section noted different approaches to journalistic practice between 1978, 1997, and, 2013. These changed practices affected not just the style and content of reporting, but also the end product. And, whilst newspapers and individual journalists will levitate towards a particular party-political agenda, or that of an individual politician, they have been consistent in offering antipathy towards any change in the status quo in respect of Scotland. Underpinning that stance was a dominant argument hegemony that promoted parliamentary supremacy. This insight hints that as agents of external statecraft newspapers are limited in how willing they are to practice opposition craft to its full potential. Indeed, the expectation for this chapter premised on a potential that, in line with the thesis hypothesis, that the closer Scotland progressed towards independence, the more likely newspapers would employ a hardened realist stance. However, there is no indication from the grid analyses that was the case, particularly given that the SIRFA debate was mostly ignored by journalists. In all, these insights act as the basis for this section which looks at the sources of journalistic bias, as a way for helping explain the results of the grid analyses.

Park et al (2009) say that bias is an inherent feature of the news production processes, with the eventual outcome being political polarisation. If this insight is accurate then it may be fair to suggest the same can be found here in the UK context, particularly given the outcome of the grid analyses. Identifying bias is important if we are to better understand if newspapers adopted a hard line realist stance the closer Scotland got to the precipitancy. However, some newspapers might support government policy and others may not, meaning potentially that that statecraft and opposition craft are opposing components in occupying the same marketplace. Even so, and the BBC aside, newspapers are private businesses and by definition, a starting assumption is that they are also agents of external statecraft.

Figure 8: sources of media bias
(Repeated from pg. 100)

Park et al (2009) offer up six areas from where, in this case newspapers, inherit bias. They have been group into two areas - business and politics

Business

Park et al (2009) cite three business interests that influence and cause bias in news reporting. They are advertisers, and target audience, and the owners, and it is to these interests that this sub-section looks at first.

In terms of an analysis of their content, newspapers are offered scant regard in the literatures on statecraft. A rare example comes from Bulpitt who makes a passing reference that when it emerged in the 1970s the campaign for Scottish independence provoked an “overreaction” from the media (1983: 166). That aside, mention of newspapers or the wider media via a statecraft lens tends to focus on how the media is, or can be, used to advance party-political and/or electoral opportunities, and as a way for testing the reception of policy announcements (Hopkins, 2011). This insight aside, if newspapers are largely ignored by the Bulpittian perspective, the interest afforded to the political power and influence attained by proprietors is non-existent. Proprietors are a small clique that has been described as having power without responsibility (Curran and Seaton, 2002), and it is not a label offered without just cause. Here, cases can be presented that more than imply the dangers to democracy of powerful newspaper proprietors. Indeed, the post-Salisbury era is replete with examples of political stand-offs between the old newspaper barons and the government of the day - in 1915 the tabloid pioneer Lord Northcliffe helped oust Asquith to the benefit of Lloyd George (Jackson and de Castella, 2011). In the 1930s Lords Rothermere and Beaverbrook ran

campaigns against Stanley Baldwin (Jackson and de Castella, 2011), and in the 1960s Cecil King attempted to bring down the Wilson government (see chapter three). The suggestion is that press barons and owners have a track record in wielding their power for politically expedient purposes, and of those mentioned above the hint is was of acts that were contrary to the national interest. As such, it is arguable that along with in-party rebellions, cabals, and devolved chambers, newspapers also offer themselves up as agents of external statecraft.

The apparent concentration of power in a few hands has been a matter of concern for politicians in recent decades and has led to calls for a media ownership that contains more diverse opinions and voices. The Blair government argued that a “healthy democracy was dependent on a culture of dissent and argument and this culture would inevitably be diminished if there were only a limited number of providers of the news. And to this end, the Communications Act (2003) was intended to address some of the blockages to that aspiration. However, the legislation had little effect because five years later a House of Lords Select Committee on Communications report again argued the necessity of “a free and diverse media” to a quality democracy (HM Parliament, 2008: 6). “If one voice becomes too powerful” the report said, the “process is placed in jeopardy and democracy is damaged” (2008: 6). Again, calls like this one fell on deaf ears because in 2021 the Media Reform Coalition (MRC) reported that three companies controlled ninety percent of the national UK newspaper sector, and that six companies controlled over eighty percent of local papers (2021: 4). The result, according to the MRC (2021), sees over half of all newspapers sold in the UK being controlled by two billionaires. The effect is in line with the idea news production premises on a very narrow and limited interpretation of events and reflects a wider global trend where control of the news resides in even fewer hands (see chapter three).

Nonetheless, whilst newspapers appear to present as sought after commodities, but given the sector has never achieved a state of financial independence their viability as a commercial venture is illusory (Curran and Seaton, 2002). Newspapers, Curran and Seaton argue, are sustained by advertising revenue. It is a predicament that leaves editors vulnerable to censorship via client advertisers having degrees of editorial control, on threat of a withdrawal of business (Osborne, 2015). In 2015, for example, the Telegraph avoided publishing stories damaging to HSBC, a major advertising client at the time (Osborne, 2015). This practice is not reflective of all newspapers, however. In 2016 the Financial Times (FT) came under pressure to drop a story about one of its clients, Hewlett Packard Enterprise (HPE) (Griggs, 2016). The

FT responded by publishing an open letter that explained the back story and then went on to proclaim the paper's commitment to editorial freedom (Griggs, 2016). In the end, HPE merely drew attention to a story that it had sought to suppress. Nonetheless, editorial independence is pressured from a number of sources, and can be further complicated by the close proximity of celebrity publicists to editors (Levin and Clifford, 2005). The job of a publicist is to manipulate in one way or other, a public profile, usually for longer term financial gain, and results in the drafting of salacious and at times completely manufactured stories⁶¹ (Levin and Clifford, 2005). The end product is little more than a highly sophisticated set of celebrity-centred adverts that are then presented to the readership as news. A less sophisticated example was identified via the investigations undertaken for this thesis when a report in the Sunday Mail in 1978 speculated on the potential for Scotland sliding towards a Northern Irish style civil war (F16).

A group calling itself the 'Scottish Republican Army' was reported to have mobilised and was threatening terrorist activity and rioting (F16). The effect would cause Scotland to experience violence on a scale so serious that the British Army and UN Peacekeepers would need to be deployed⁶² (F16). It is only towards the end of the article where it is stated that the entire story is based on "political fiction" (F16). In reality, the report was a book plug disguised as a news article - same font, layout, and sandwiched between stories from the real world (F16). Authored by a journalist on the Mail's sister paper, the Daily Record, it was "the book which every Scot - and every Englishman - will want to read" (F16), even though the report was, as Frankfurt (2005) would argue, bullshit. Nonetheless, adverts, regardless of their sourcing, form a part of a narrative that considers newspapers as tools of persuasion - what to think about, and on the matters the newspapers deem important (Cohen, 1963; Anderson, 1983; McCombs, 2004). Until recently, political parties were also paid advert customers of newspapers, particularly at election time (Mayhew and Kakar, 2018). More recently, however, political parties have shifted their spending online - the 2017 general election, for example, resulted in political parties spending newly twenty times more on online advertising than it did on adverts in newspapers (Mayhew and Kakar, 2018). In reality, political parties are merely partaking in a wider trend in which newspaper revenues are losing

⁶¹ Numerous publicists have been, and are, in operation. Max Clifford was one of the more well-known. His company was responsible for a series of stories that helped cultivate a manufactured public image for his celebrity clientele (Levin and Clifford, 2005). Added, he was responsible for numerous 'kiss-and-tell' stories that implicated politicians and others in public office (Levin and Clifford, 2005). In all, Clifford's work came from the same school of propaganda practiced by the likes of Edward Bernays and Walter Lippmann (see chapter three).

⁶² The title of the article has been appropriated by this thesis as the title for chapter six - the Burns Night Plot. Fair dealing applied.

out to an increasingly dominant online market. Short of financial independence and in the absence of advertising revenue Curran and Seaton (2002) argue the only other option for newspapers is financial reliance on the state, as per the BBC. And that is what happened in 2020. Newspaper advertising revenues were in “free-fall” during the recent Covid-19 emergency (Cathart, 2022: n.p.), the UK government responded by taking out a three month advertising campaign the cost of which is rumoured to be around £35m. However, in what reads more like a bail-out, and where large sums appear unaccounted for, the true figure may be several times higher (Cathcart, 2022).

For an advert to be successful, it needs a target audience (McQuail, 1997; Tatham, 2015). Access to the audience is important, as is the position of an advert in a newspaper so to have maximum impact. As a strategy, the practice did not go unnoticed during the grid analyses, and it relates to a column in the Sunday Mirror written by former Labour MP Woodrow Wyatt. In *In life*, Wyatt (2012) had what can be called a cavalier approach to monogamy and as such, it is of no coincidence that his column was surrounded by adverts that at the time were stereotypically associated with women⁶³ (F10). In effect, women were Wyatt’s target audience, which opens the door to the potential that the Sunday Mirror and its advertisers had been trading on Wyatt’s reputation. The Wyatt example hints at an underlying practice in which both newspaper and the stories that are contained within them are targeted at a specific audience. Target Audience Analysis (TAA) is a model used by newspapers so to identify and target their own audiences (McQuail, 1997; Tatham, 2015). It is a layered project that involves the monitoring of demographics including but not limited to, social class, political opinions and voting preferences, so to know the audience and tailor content accordingly. As a strategy, it is not dissimilar in the preparatory process to the propaganda works of Bernays and Lippmann (see chapter three). The main difference is that TAA is used not merely as a tool for targeted stories but is a major contributor to the positioning of individual newspapers in the sector and wider market (McQuail, 1997; Tatham, 2015). Political, or underlying, messages are follow-ons.

The final product is a message tailored to suit a prevailing political message useful in both the short and longer term, and as an insight it brings us to a politico-journalistic habit of explaining Scottish politics through footballing analogies. The practice was detected in the

⁶³ Included were adverts for corsets (and other undergarments), wigs, slippers, and, vacuum cleaners (F10).

grid analyses and was found in both UK and Scottish papers, and in both daily and Sunday editions⁶⁴. As a practice, it is similar to that explained by Cohen (1963) and McCombs (2004), where newspapers are tools for persuading certain perspectives on particular topics or issues. This type of agenda setting represents a practice employed by politicians which is then regurgitated by journalists. Table 48 outlines its usage in 1978 in respect of former Scotland footballer, Kenny Dalglish (F7). Table 49 concerns the more widespread reporting of the Gary McAllister question during the debates in 1997.

Table 48: 1978 football analogies

	F 1	F 2	F 3	F 4	F 5	F 6	F 7	F 8	F 9	F 10	F 11	F 12	F 13	F 14	F 15	F 16	Total
World Cup	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	3
Kenny Dalglish	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1

Table 49: 1997 football analogies

	G 1	G 2	G 3	G 4	G 5	G 6	G 7	G 8	G 9	G 10	G 11	G 12	G 13	G 14	G 15	G 16	Total
Scottish Diaspora	2	1	-	-	-	5	2	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	15
Gary McAllister	1	-	-	-	-	3	1	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	12

Tables 48 and 49 offer a glimpse of how journalistic agenda setting plays out in the end product. TAA is useful in this respect because through differentiating audiences stereotypically via social class, age, religion, political allegiance et al, agendas can be set for specific audiences, and for the collective, and within the same publication (Cohen, 1963). If this is an accurate interpretation of TAA then it implies a sophisticated practice, and one that is layered both in substance and context, and in audience(s).

As an insight, the observations also indicate the potential that TAA is a tool for advancing particular argument hegemonies, the final product of which appears to be a journalistic practice that combines business, politics, and entertainment. Here, Cohen (1963) said that newspapers and other media sources tell us not just what to think, but instead, what to think about. As such, it is fair to suggest that the commentaries in respect of footballing analogies, Woodrow Wyatt (F10), and the deceit of Scotland sliding towards insurgency (F16) are all cut from the cloth, albeit with different underlying corporate and political rationales. The

⁶⁴ An isolated example concerns a cartoon in the Sunday Mirror. There, two Scottish football fans are chatting with one is saying to the other, “aye, there’d be one hell of a row on devolution if we weren’t concentrating our minds on Argentina”⁶⁴ (F10).

effect is distraction by context, or whitabootery, the scale of usage of which in respect on the reporting in and around the debate on CA1 is outlined in Table 50.

Table 50: 1978 whitabootery

	F 1	F 2	F 3	F 4	F 5	F 6	F 7	F 8	F 9	F 10	F 11	F 12	F 13	F 14	F 15	F 16	Total
book plug	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	8
terrorism	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	5
UK constitution	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4
cost	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	3
civil unrest	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	3
oil	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	3
anti-Scottish sentiment	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
criticism of Cunningham	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1
electoral administration	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
minority government	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
military deployment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
threshold reversal	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
two-question ballot	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
UN peacekeepers	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
West Lothian question	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1

TAA, by definition, leads to a form of reportage that intertwines fact and fiction. The appearance is that this posture is inherent in the business model. To this end, this chapter finds congruence to Park et al (2009) and their assertion that ownership, advertisers, and target audiences as major influences in the final journalistic output. Another important influence is the journalists themselves and no clearer is this additional influence than during the reporting on events in and around the 1997 Conservative party leadership contest. In context terms, the distraction types outlined in Table 50 are absent here. By contrast, Table 51 presents a style of reportage that on the surface is more professional than that on display in 1978, in this case offering informed insights into matters relating to CA2 and the second Scottish devolution referendum, albeit from a particular perspective. This was the era when Presidentialism and personalised politics was in vogue and the door between politics and the media had started to revolve (Osborne, 2004; Foley, 2004; Buller and James, 2012a; Griffiths (b), 2016; James, 2018) (see chapter three). The appearance is of this new operating environment impacting journalistic practice, particularly given the potential that individual journalists could, through their wares, offer themselves up as spin doctors, intent on moving closer to power. The end product, however, was a style of reporting that relied on individualised and derogatory commentary to get a message across. The effect is, however, that we can never truly know in whose interest a journalist is writing an article, the extent of

their bias, and whether or not they are trying to advance their careers by currying favour with specific politicians or parties.

Table 51: 1997 whitabootery

	G 1	G 2	G 3	G 4	G 6	G 7	G 8	G 15	Total
constitutional change	-	1	7	-	3	1	-	-	12
Gary McAllister	1	-	-	-	3	1	4	3	12
Parliamentary protocols	4	-	1	-	1	2	2	-	10
two question referendum	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	4	6
Conservative think-tank	1	-	-	-	2	-	1	1	5
mass Amendments	-	-	2	1	-	2	-	-	5
pre-legislative referendums	-	-	3	-	2	-	-	-	5
West Lothian question	2	-	-	-	2	-	1	-	5
Donald Dewar	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	3	4
mandate	-	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	4
Scotland Bill (1978)	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	3
Anglo-Scots MPs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
taxation	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	4
opinion polling	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	2
House of Lords	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
Michael Howard	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Bill Cash	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1
poll tax	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
referendums	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1

Football as an explanatory for politics in Scotland presents as a distraction type that Philo (2012) argues is typical of a press that merely amplifies public discontent, all the while nudging readers onto another topic. With this, it is important point to note the role that spin played in creating some of the articles that helped populate Table 49. These articles point to the primacy of the Gary McAllister question to the newspapers, some of whom opted to include pictures of footballers in either Scotland or England strips. The Daily Record offered its own spin on the Gary McAllister question. With a report titled ‘Poll Gascoigne’, it asked why Glasgow-based English footballer Paul Gascoigne would have a vote in the 1997 devolution referendum but McAllister would not (G8). This approach is indicative of Cohen’s (1963) idea that newspapers and other media sources tell us not just what to think, but also what to think about. By definition, we do not think about other things because we are not informed about them in the first place (Cohen, 1963). And with this perspective in mind, this subsection presents Table 52 and the whitabootery in regards 2013’s SIRFA debate.

Table 52: 2013 whitabootery

	H 1	H 2	H 3	H 4	H 5	H 6	H 7	H 8	H 9	H 10	H 11	H 12	H 13	H 14	H 15	H 16	Total
Scotland v. UK wide vote	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16-18 political awareness turnout	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scotland/UK coordination	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ECHR consultative referendums safeguarding	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
experience of other states	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
service personnel	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SEN	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
finance	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
previous elections	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Edinburgh Agreement	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
hard to reach voters	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scottish independence	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

The empty content in Table 52 represents the reality that only two of the newspapers accessed for this investigation covered the SIRFA debate, albeit limitedly. However, the failure to report more comprehensively on the SIRFA debate is another unexpected outcome that helps skew the results of the grid analyses. This insight is particularly relevant given the comparative saturation coverage of the debates on CA1 and CA2. Nonetheless, Table 52 points to a journalistic practice that rather than offer whitabootery, editors opted for ignorance, which is intriguing because this chapter had assumed that as agents of external statecraft, the newspapers would practice opposition craft and this would also mean influencing the readership, as per the previous sub-section.

Bias is inherent and exists across the personal, practice, corporate, and institutional levels (Curran and Seaton, 2002; Park et al, 2009). The effect should be a myriad of stories, content, angles, et al, with some presenting as opposition craft. That was indeed the case but only up to a point because the one constant identified in the grid analyses has been the primacy to the reporting of status quo-led argument hegemony. This observation raises the potential that newspapers, via the owners and the journalists, acted as one and did so in a way commensurate with this thesis’ definition of statecraft, i.e., they were responding to real world events so to perpetuate the status quo. If this is an accurate interpretation of events then it also implies an agenda, and a uniform one at that. This outcome also offers insight into the newspaper business model and how it is employed but, in fairness, it does little to satisfy the potential that the closer Scotland progressed towards independence, the more likely newspapers would employ a hardened realist stance. Regardless, the final journalistic output

resembles a fusing of business, entertainment, and politics, the latter of which, for Park et al (2009), sees further bias via governmental, ideological, and political influences. These points are considered in the next sub-section.

Politics

In the pre-WW2 years four English Lords controlled the majority of the UK's media output (Curran and Seaton, 2002). Today, and despite protests from within political circles, the sector remains controlled by a small clique of influential businessmen. Of them, Rupert Murdoch has arguably been the primary media mogul of the past few decades. He was the 'go-to' baron who "struck fear" into the same political leaders who also courted the support of his newspapers (Casalicchio and Bloom, 2023: n.p.). Murdoch's political power was encapsulated by the failure of the Labour party to acquire the backing of the Sun during the 1992 general election. The morning after the Conservatives were narrowly re-elected, the Sun's headline rubbed salt in the Labour wound - 'It's the Sun wot won it' was not a mere gloat but also a warning of the power of the press and specifically, Murdoch (Thomas, 2007). By the 1997 general election, presidentialist and highly personalised politics had crept into the political landscape and to this day the practice of media-friendly politics continues, supported by allied journalists (Negrine and Stanyer, 2007). Whilst much has already been discussed in this thesis, the trend that began with employing journalists as spin doctors or special advisors, and/or journalists getting elected to office, continues. Today, it is not uncommon for politicians becoming pundits once out of office and, as has been the case, when still in office⁶⁵. The result is a revolving door between Westminster and 'the lobby', and is typical of what Swanson calls the politico-media complex (2007: 37). At its heart is an interdependent and mutually beneficial arrangement involving journalists, politicians, columnists, and more commonly, and political entrepreneurs - each of them competing for exposure (Swanson, 2007). Yet, it is from within this same environment where political oversight and regulation of the press originates. The result is a series of mostly voluntary codes of conduct, behaviour, and practice.

Journalistic practices were reported on via the Leveson Inquiry into the culture, practices, and ethics of the press (2012), and as a response to the phone hacking scandal involving Rupert

⁶⁵ TV coverage of the vote count for the UK's 2024 general election included elected politicians as pundits on extended news broadcasts. They included Nicola Sturgeon (ITV) and Mayor of Greater Manchester, Labour's Andy Burnham (SKY). The slots included Sturgeon part-interviewing and analysing fellow SNP member and former MP, Joanna Cherry. A similar conversation occurred between Burnham and fellow Labour Mayor of London, Sadiq Khan.

Murdoch's now defunct News of the World - sister paper to the Sun. The Inquiry exposed a culture of corruption that embroiled proprietors, editors, journalists, politicians, spin doctors, policemen, and other public servants (Leveson, 2012). It also exposed powerful people working in cahoots and contrary to criminal and civil law, and highlighted a distinct lack of sector regulation. At the time, newspapers had been regulated via the industry-controlled Press Complaints Commission (PCC), which operated between the 1950s and 2014 when, following Leveson, it was closed down (PCC, 2014). By definition, the PCC regulated newspapers reporting on CA1, CA2, and SIRFA and it oversaw a practice that said independence would cause Scotland to slide to insurgency; where readers were told to think about football; and in regards SIRFA, where journalists simply ignored the political event of the day. Nonetheless, Leveson recommended the PCC to be replaced by a new organisation, one supported via statute law, a recommendation that had been refused by the Cameron government (Leveson, 2012). Cameron's successor, Theresa May later shelved the anticipated Inquiry Pt 2 which had intended focusing on unlawful and improper conduct in the press (Walker, 2018).

Today, there are two regulators - the Independent Press Standards Organisation (IPSO) (2024) and Impress (2024). Maher reports that "both were intended to better hold journalism to account, with sharper teeth, than the PCC" (2022: n.p.). He adds that IPSO can fine newspapers up to one million pounds, whilst Impress can table indictments for hate speech (2022: n.p.), which, had it existed in 1997 could have offered Michael Howard and others a route to a redress of grievance. However, both schemes remain voluntary and whilst a number of papers, including the Guardian, have declined signing up to IPSO, the FT has blanket-refused all forms regulation (Maher, 2022).

The Advertising Standards Authority (ASA) is another body with regulatory oversight of newspapers. It is similar to the redundant PCC in that it is also a self-regulatory industry body, and one that is also wholly financed by the advertising sector via levies on the cost of adverts (ASA, 2024). The Committee of Advertising Practice (CAP) is a sister organisation to the ASA and is its regulator (CAP, 2024). Conway (2019) argues that in 1997, CAP had been concerned about impact of the Human Rights Act (1998) on the ASA, particularly the potential that the ASA could restrain political speech during election campaigns. The solution was to remove political adverts from ASA oversight (Conway, 2019). In 2004 the Electoral Commission argued that there should be a voluntary code for regulating political advertising,

and beyond the reach of the ASA (2019: n.p.), but this did not happen. The upshot is that electoral law governs advertising by political parties (Conway, 2019), the culmination of which means that there is no requirement political parties to publish adverts in newspapers that are either truthful or factually accurate.

Yet, it is from within this environment that the politicians regulate the press with the result being voluntary codes, degrees of impotence included. This same arrangement applies also to reportage on official secrets where, there too, a voluntary code is in existence and is overseen by the Defence and Security Media Advisory Committee (DSMA) (DSMA, 2024a). The origins of the DSMA can be traced back to the years immediately prior to WW1 and the placing on statute of the Official Secrets Act (1911)⁶⁶. In 1912, the UK government developed a system intended to encourage media self-censorship (Wilkinson, 2009). The ‘D-Notice’ (D - Defence) was intended to beef up UK national security and as Greenslade reports, it acted as a “collaboration between state and media has offered a compromise between national security and press freedom” (2015; n.p.). This system remains in place but has since evolved but continues to be premised on “a voluntary code which operates between the Government departments which have responsibilities for national security and the media” (DSMA, 2024a). Greenslade (2015) also notes that the D-Notice system only became public knowledge when in 1967 Harold Wilson criticised the Daily Express for publishing details on the ultra vires monitoring of domestic telegrams and cables by the security services. The scandal led to the D-Notice being replaced the DA-Notice (DA - Defence Advisory).

Newspapers have on occasion, ignored the DSMA or its predecessor systems. For example, in the lead up to the 2003 invasion of Iraq, the Observer reported that the UK’s security services had been spying on diplomats at the UNSC (Greenslade, 2015). Greenslade also reports that the Guardian initially published data on the Snowden revelations but subsequently referred stories to the DA committee rather than go straight to print. The effect caused the Cameron government to update the DA system, with the DSMA being the present incarnation. Today, the Committee includes, but is not limited to the Society of Editors; The Times and Sunday Times; Daily Telegraph; Press Association; Mail on Sunday; Trinity Mirror; Scottish Newspaper Society (DSMA, 2024b). Also included are representatives from the BBC, ITV, Sky, and book publisher associations. The DSMA say that the “system is

⁶⁶ for Bartlett and Everett, offers up as “the main legal protection in the UK against espionage and the unauthorised disclosure of information” (2017: 7), with criminal prosecutions being a remedy for breaching the legislation.

voluntary” and “has no legal authority and the final responsibility for deciding whether or not to publish rests solely with the editor or publisher concerned” (2024c: n.p.). That said, the DSMA is not without referent or coercive power because it also proactively monitors media content and requests content removal (Curtis, 2022). This happened to the website Declassified UK which had been pre-emptively contacted by the DSMA which requested content be removed from its website. Declassified UK refused and published anyway (Curtis, 2022). Declassified UK, WikiLeaks, Craig Murray, and the like are more likely to be found online than in print format. They do not benefit from voluntary relationships with the state, and instead are subject to surveillance - the simple reason that investigative journalists are deemed a threat to UK national security (HM Government, 2001).

The Society of Editors, which is also a DSMA participant, says that the system is a tool for “self-restraint rather than self-censorship” (Greenslade, 2015: n.p.). Here, practicing self-restraint rather than self-censorship offers up an interesting insight into journalistic psyche, particularly in respect of there being a willingness on the part of journalists to conform to the whim of government rather than through coercion. For Greenslade (2015) this same attitude was present in 1912 when the original D-Notice system was set up. He adds that press owners and editors were “fiercely anti-German” and that they “were only too happy to prevent the enemy from accessing useful intelligence” (2015: n.p.). The inference is that journalism in the UK is underpinned by an engrained ideology that, for Curran and Seaton (2002), more closely resembles Whiggism (see chapter two). Whiggism evolved out of the Glorious revolution and William of Orange’s accession to the Crown in 1688. The underpinning ideology included the promotion of Protestantism over Catholicism and premised on the concept of Parliamentary supremacy (Womersley, Bullard, and Williams, 2005). By extension, Whiggism provided a system for limited constitutional monarchy rather than the absolutism of the Divine Right of Kings (Curran and Seaton, 2002)⁶⁷. Ultimately, it was this constitutional halfway house that was founded in England in 1688 but which, latterly, extended to Scotland post-1707 (Nairn, 1977). The ideological influence of the Whigs continued into the eighteen hundreds when at the time, the radical press, which was to be found on the left of the political spectrum, had catalysed social and democratic change, their endeavours doing little to endear themselves to the wider establishment and elites (Curran and Seaton, 2002; Womersley et al, 2005). Added, the establishment was concerned because

⁶⁷ Indeed, this is a point that Nairn had touched upon when “the Anglo-British state remains a product of the general transition from absolutism to modern constitutionalism: it led the way out of the former but never genuinely arrived at the latter” (1977: 75).

the radicals had achieved financial independence and in business terms were free of both advertiser and government interference and bias (Curran and Seaton, 2002: 7). Curran and Seaton say that a number of “indirect ways” were used to bring “power to bear on unsympathetic journalism” (2002: 7). The solution, they argue, lay with taxes, duties, and financial bonds that forced up costs and prices sufficient to push the radicals out of business (Curran and Seaton, 2002: 7). With the radicals priced out of the market, newspaper ownership became dominated by societal stakeholders - aristocrats, landowners, and other wealthy elites (Curran and Seaton, 2002). It was then when politicians started arguing that “person[s] exercising the power of the press should be men of respectability and property” (Curran and Seaton, 2002: 8). Curran and Seaton also argue that the late Victorian period has been considered to be the “golden age of journalism” (2002: 4). It was in this era that the earliest newspaper barons emerged, who then claimed responsibility for the socio-democratic changes that the radicals had fought for and won. The barons also appropriated another radical legacy, namely the abolition of newspaper taxes through which the idea of a ‘free press’ was founded (Curran and Seaton, 2002).

News management is not a recent occurrence and has been formally practiced in the UK for over a century. Its basis is an ideological and mutually beneficial alignment between the elites in the state and newspaper barons. The findings of the grid analyses help support that argument and, indeed, offer an explanation for the consistency in the postures taken by newspapers, as recorded in the grid analyses. This consistency and congruence to the status quo are observed in Tables 53 and 54. There is also the potential that newspapers practiced self-restraint when reporting or not on the SIRFA debate. Overall, however, and as was noted in the previous sub-section, there exist limitations in the ability or willingness of newspapers to practice opposition craft. Given the context, it is now unclear whether or not newspapers are agents of external statecraft, as had been premised in this chapter and in chapter three.

Table 53: Whig influence 1

Lever	Grid count	percentage
argument hegemony	409	45
governing competence	209	22
electoral strategy	153	17
party management	103	11
bending the rules	47	5

Table 54: Whig influence 2

	1978	1997	2013
parliamentary supremacy	166	47	-
guillotine	71	65	-

Chapter conclusions

This chapter sought out to review the press reportage of the debates on CA1, CA2, and SIRFA, and do so through a statecraft lens so to improve our understanding of newspapers as agents of external statecraft. The expectation had been that the analyses would see fluctuations in newspaper postures across the time span, but this was not the case. Cohen (1983) said by not informing or telling us of relevant events, newspapers have a seeming arbitrary control over not just what we know, what we understand, and what we think about, but also what we don't. The analyses found newspapers willing to tilt and slant articles and confuse opinion and fact. Armstrong argued of governments that they seem content with voters that are "ill-informed" (2015: 4) but, it seems, newspapers appear happy too, particularly in this case. This chapter asserts that newspaper coverage of the debates on CA1 and CA2 are littered with misinformation and disinformation. They come in many guises - reportage, columns, opinion pieces, letters, and even, cartoons - and are central to a form of misdirection, intended to nudge us in another direction, mentally or otherwise. The analyses also found two consistencies in the reportage (1) an overwhelming argument hegemony, and (2) hostility to any pro-Scotland deviation to the status quo. In the case of CA1 and CA2, dominant support for parliamentary sovereignty was also evidenced. To this end, the grid analyses found congruence with Bulpitt's (1983) suggestion that the press would had been/were willing participants in the reinforcement of the status quo. It is a behaviour that this chapter finds to be ideological.

In the eighteen hundreds, politicians created the newspaper baron as a way for suppressing a radical press intent on encouraging social change (Curran and Seaton, 2002). For the duration these barons have employed editors that practice self-restraint in their reportage (Greenslade, 2015). This practice is since been formalised via editorial participation in state-run news-suppression committees (DSMA, 2024a). Newspapers had also previously been subject to an industry wide system of self-regulation but whilst the system has since changed, regulation remains voluntary (Leveson, 2012; Maher, 2022; 2024; Impress; 2024). Newspaper

advertising is also regulated, this time by an industry body (ASA, 2024; CAP, 2024). Oversight, however, does not extend to political parties which are free to lie and deceive in their placed adverts, and without consequence (Conway, 2019). Newspapers are positioned across the political spectrum and offer allegiance to particular parties. However, they appear united in their alignment to Whiggism (Curran and Seaton, 2002; Womersley et al, 2005). This is an ideology that believes in the concept of parliamentary supremacy with its influence perpetuated by William of Orange's Mace, resident in the House of Commons (Womersley et al, 2005; UK Parliament, 2021). To this end, the press and its barons remain invested to a status quo that views investigative journalists as a threat to UK national security (HM Government, 2001). The final product is a journalism that does not tell us what has happened and instead, offers a version of the same, itself being littered with biases and at times, falsehoods (Herman and Chomsky, 1988; Park et al, 2009). The end-product is a narrow interpretation of news from a profession resident inside a political system, itself operating from a narrow interpretation of democracy (Marsh et al, 2003; James, 2016). Ultimately, it may be fair to say that, with a few exceptions aside, in the UK the concept of a free press is a myth and instead, the term refers solely to relations between the press barons and the taxman (Curran and Seaton, 2002).

Chapter eleven: findings and concluding comments

This thesis initially set out to investigate how Scottish secessionism has been influenced by internal and external statecraft and premised on the potential that the closer that Scotland progressed towards independence, the more likely the state will respond with hard line realist tactics. This was not to be the case. The literatures on statecraft and secession leaned heavily towards rule bending in the Scottish precipitancy, the investigations for this these found few clear examples on offer, either by the UK government or the devolved government in Scotland. What the investigations did find was further evidence to support the claims that the state and media are ideologically aligned through Whiggism, the effect being that newspapers have an inherent interest in preserving the status quo and are likely to act almost in unison when it is challenged (Curran and Seaton, 2002; Womersley et al, 2005).

This final chapter contains three sections. The first passes comment on the literature, concerning particularly the evident gaps in the literatures on statecraft and secession in explaining Scotland's secessionist impulse and the UK's response to it. The second section provides an overview of the impulse, as analysed by this thesis. The third and final section looks at a brief look at the UK and Scotland in the ten years since the independence referendum.

The literature

This thesis has highlighted a number of the limitations in the literatures on statecraft and secession, particularly regards their application to and explanation of, Scotland's secessionist impulse.

The Bulpittian perspective

States claim to exist in perpetuity and they always have (Foster, 2015; van de Mieroop, 2016; Chase-Dunn and Lerro, 2016). States also actively seek power and they use what power they do have to acquire more (Morgenthau, 1978; Mearsheimer, 2001; Kissinger, 2014. For the domestic population, the absolutism that underpinned the Divine Rights of Kings remains in play, albeit in a different guise and of a type that, via the democratic process, renews itself regularly. States still demand obedience from their populations and expect a suitable capitulation (Morgenthau, 1978; Wolff, 1990; Boitani and Torti, 1999; Baylis and Smith, 2001; Mearsheimer, 2001; Lake, 2003; Philpott, 2016). This realist agenda premises on what

Schmitt called equilibrium, a term he defined to mean “compulsion” (1996: 36), as though little has changed. And in some ways little has changed, societies continue to be governed by political hierarchies that place perpetuating the status quo as their primary objective. Indeed, recent decades have seen states undertake direct interventions in its own space so to preserve their integrity from secessionist or revolutionary actions, using violence where deemed necessary. Such tactics have previously been employed in a number of secessionist precipitancies, including Northern Ireland, Bougainville, and in the entirely peaceful Catalan event in 2017 (Taylor, 2014; Regan, 2019; Ponasti, 2020). Interventions of these types remain a default position where the perpetuation of the state is threatened not just by secession, but also civil war, revolution, and widespread social unrest (Bookman, 1994; Rapoport, 2004; Hall, 2016). In the most extreme, it can be expected that the state will exist for no other reason than to ensure its own survival.

These types of hard line tactics are more commonly known as necessity and in the UK this doctrine is more commonly known as acting in the national interest. The basic premise is that a particular scenario effects government in a way that it cannot operate effectively without redefining the parameters that it sets itself in more ‘normal’ circumstances (Ponting, 1987). The resulting actions can be relatively benign and can lead to worse case scenarios, as outlined above. Nonetheless, when it redefines its operating parameters in this way, government will be acting in the national interest, with the action explained in theoretical terms via statecraft theory. To this end, it is fair to suggest that statecraft is a realist tool. The day-to-day effect for the politicians is that every decision is taken with one eye on the next election (Bulpitt, 1983). With the Bulpittian perspective focusing on the party political system, it does so at the expense of offering genuine insights, from an external statecraft perspective. Practicing realism is not an end game in itself. There needs to be an underlying philosophy or ideology to protect and believe in - Soviet communism being one example (Baylis and Smith, 2001; Reynolds, 2015). This thesis observes the UK’s Whiggish ideology, comprising of legacies of the Glorious Revolution that include a Constitutional Monarchy, and the expunging of Catholicism from the higher echelons of the state (Curran and Seaton, 2002; Womersley et al, 2005). These are insights that we would not know about if we took Bulpitt’s (1983) works at face value. Bulpitt downplays the legacies of the Glorious Revolution and at one point states “how can anything serious or interesting be said about a project in which ... William of Orange ... played a part” (1983: 71). Via this very limited perspective, Bulpitt also pays scant regard to Whiggism, saying it no longer presents as the

dominant view of the UK, and that is not the case - not while William's Mace remains hiding in plain sight. In all, and in what points this thesis to a hint that Bulpitt works are also of a Whiggish influence, is his pointing towards an Anglicised rewriting or reinterpreting of history that does little to reflect reality. For example, he says that union between Scotland and England was inevitable (Bulpitt, 1983: 72). This is untrue and as a standpoint serves only to paint the campaign for Scottish secessionism as an abnormality when compared to the contrived natural order of the status quo. Bulpitt also claims that one reason for union between Scotland and England was the encouraging of addressing "pressing need to integrate the Catholic Irish into a wider and less divisive community" (1983: 72). The question to be asked here is how integrating a mostly-Catholic Irish population into a sectarian state is 'less divisive'.

Bulpitt's dismissal of Whiggism helped make space for his advancing the dual polity as an explanation for territorial management in the UK. The problem here is that by focusing on winning elections, Bulpitt added short-termism into his work, the effect of which is to see a time when his works are no longer relevant and represent as an explanation of a past era. The overall effect is that whilst the concepts of high and low politics remains relevant, it may be fair to suggest that the dual polity is out of date and has been for some time. At the turn of the century devolved parliaments and assemblies were established in Scotland, Northern Ireland, Wales, and London. Since then, devolution has been applied piecemeal across England, creating a patchwork of devolved institutions, each with varying degrees of responsibility. The result, for Bevir, is the UK now being dominated by "a complex matrix of diverse and negotiated patterns of rule" (2010: 12). Ayres et al (2019) made a similar observation in that devolution has created space for another territorial model. It is via this route that an emergent opposition craft is now in play. The traditional place for opposition craft was the Commons where party rebels and cabals play out their agendas. By definition, each rebel or cabal has the capability to operate contrary to the national interest. The Bulpittian perspective classifies these matters as issues of party management, and whilst that view remains relevant insofar as explaining the House of Commons, it has also identified opposition craft playing out in Holyrood. The assessment is that if opposition craft plays out in one devolved chamber then by definition, it plays out in the other assemblies and Mayoral offices that have acquired devolution. For the dual polity, with each transfer of authority from the centre to the periphery, it offers offer less explanatory relevance. To this end, we may be better served

discussing a multi-polity and one that centres on the interplay between competing intra-state forces.

A Scottish perspective

A first point concerns Wood (1981) and his comparative framework which, having offered utility in helping demystifying the evolution and trajectory of the Scottish impulse, his work is largely redundant beyond that point - the expected argument hegemony and rule bending simply did not materialise as predicted; Scotland experienced the rise/movement and precipitancy simultaneously; and, the preconditions appearing more like the precipitancy, and vice versa. These insights expose potential limitations to both Wood's (1981) generic comparative framework and of macro-led historical institutionalism, in identifying and analysing specific case studies. Buchanan (1997) said that the literature on secession would find difficulty in evolving into a more coherent body of work and, as it appears, the same remains today. The literatures on secession still lack any obvious schools of thought. As such, it is difficult to assess the underlying posture of a relevant publication without interacting directly with the content and assessing latterly whether an article or publication offers relevance to works being undertaken. The recent trend for niche meso research has not helped in this endeavour. Nonetheless, the preparatory work for this thesis included a mapping exercise intended to track respective positions and scholarly research foci so to develop some form of rudimentary structure of the literature. An example is outlined in Table 55 and helped to locate author proximity to one another and in terms of their complimenting and competing ideas.

Table 55: literature map - secession

	colonialism	ethics	war/ conflict	revolution	rational choice	parent state	devolution
Buchheit	X	X		X			
Buchanan	X	X					
Sustein						X	
Hetcher	X				X		
Sorens							X
Griffiths							X
Heraclides	X						X
Crawford			X				
Altman/Wellman						X	
Pavkovic/Radan	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wood	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Through this route, Wood (1981) and Pavkovic and Radan (2011) were deemed as being central to this thesis in that they both took a generic view of secession all the while premising on a neutral position on the merits of the event itself. Table 55, it should be noted, is not an exhaustive list on secession and merely represents some of the publications accessed for this thesis. The same applies also to the literature on statecraft where, there too, a similar mapping exercise was undertaken and an example is outlined in Table 56.

Table 56: literature map - statecraft

	Neo-statecraft	Westminster-centric	Bulpittian perspective	Central autonomy	Natural rate of governance	Presidentialism	devolution
James	X	X				X	
Bradbury	X	X		X	X	X	X
John	X	X	X	X		X	
Ayres		X					X
Buller	X	X	X		X	X	X
Hopkins		X	X		X	X	
Convery			X				X

James’ narrative on rule bending was important to this thesis. Not only did it allow for equal weight to be applied to the five levers, but also allowed for a more intrusive interaction with the literatures on realism, necessity, and the national interest. In effect, incorporating rule bending allowed for a full statecraft spectrum response as intended by Wood (1981), all the while maintaining proximity to Bulpitt. A major problem, however, was the literatures on statecraft paying scant regards to Scotland or Scottish independence. This reality meant that as the focus of this research shifted from Westminster to Holyrood, statecraft theory offered less explanatory relevance, and what gaps in the research existed became more pronounced as the investigations progressed. Indeed, Scottish government policies were so ‘off the scale’ that in the end even realism could not account for the electoral policy employed by the Scottish government policy towards the independence referendum. To this end, this thesis proposes that to understand politics in Scotland via statecraft, a Scottish perspective is required. These works do exist but collectively they are yet to be viewed through a statecraft lens, particularly a Scottish one. Some have been referenced across this thesis and they each cross into a number of areas associated with statecraft - independence, governance in Scotland, devolution, referendums, Scottish foreign policy, the workings of the Scottish parliament, and Scottish politics, relations with the UK, and social attitudes, to name a few - all without explicitly working from a statecraft perspective. Table 57 highlights these works and explains their usage and interpretation in this thesis, in line with the five Bulpittian levers.

Table 57: literature map - Scottish statecraft

Argument hegemony	Naim, 1968; 1977; Ferguson, 1998; Cairney, 2011; Devine, 2012; McHarg et al, 2016; Tierney, 2017; Keating, 2018; Leith and Sim, 2020; Keating, 2021.
Governing competence	Connolly, 2009; Ker-Lindsay, 2012; Leith and Soule, 2012; Keating and Harvey, 2014; Keating and Wilson, 2014; Blyth, 2015; Gibbs, 2016. Keating, 2020.
Party management	Lynch, 2002; Bochel et al, 2013; Mitchell and Hassan, 2016; Finlay, 2016; Torrance, 2017; Kippen, 2019.
Electoral strategy	Crowther, Martin, and Shaw, 1999; Lynch, 2002; Murkens et al, 2002; Leith, 2006; McAngus, 2013; Torrance, 2013; McWhirter, 2014; Robertson, 2014; Pike, 2015; Blain et al, 2016; McEwen, 2018.
Bending the rules	---

This Scottish perspective will have to be multi-angled, sufficient to explain both politics in Scotland and politics between Scotland and the wider UK and it would also have to consider a wealth of practices not considered in the Bulpittian perspective. It may even be that the five levers are insufficient for the task, that more are required or that some of the existing levers are redundant. That said, a most obvious feature of Table 57 is the distinct lack of literature on rule bending, as viewed through a Scottish lens. That’s not to say such works do not exist, it’s just that they were not encountered during the preparation of this thesis. Indeed, it is entirely possible that the neutral stance on SIRFA, as adopted by the Scottish government, skewed the investigations away from such works.

The impulse

This thesis had sought to investigate how Scottish secessionism has been influenced by internal and external statecraft. It had assumed that the closer a secessionist movement progressed towards independent statehood, the more likely the state would respond with hard line realist tactics and as was stated at the outset, that assumption proved to be inaccurate. The overall result, based on lever predominance at each of the three stages and in terms of how statecraft played out across the impulse is outlined below.

Figure 30: the three stages of Scottish secessionism

This thesis opted to investigate the three legislative debates consequent to their being perceived as altering the franchise for politically expedient purposes. These investigations brought to the fore a number of niche insights into how statecraft was employed across the lifespan of the ongoing Scottish impulse. To this end the assumption, as per the Scottish case, is incorrect meaning that Figure 30 in no way offers as a coherent explanation for the UK response to the Scottish impulse over the long term. There are a number of reasons as to why this is the case and they all relate to the choice of investigative tools and research foci and our subsequent understanding of how the three stages - preconditions, rise/movements, and precipitancy - played out.

Preconditions: rule bending was a central feature of the events in the Commons on Burns Night in 1978, particularly given the underlying intentions and effects of the Grimond Amendment on Orkney and Shetland combined with the two threshold Amendments, including CA1. The investigations found that the underlying rationale for tabling CA1 was the preservation of Commons supremacy. This was achieved avoiding a rival and irrevocable chamber, and one that could lead to Scottish independence. Here, it is important to recall the environment in which both government and Commons were operating at the time. Post 1945 and up until CA1, the UK has struggled to find a place in the post WW2 world (Kissinger, 2014; Tomlinson, 1996; 2009). Its post-1945 geopolitical performance told a story of drift, decline, and diminution and it went on to record regular and ongoing economic crises, borne through structural deficiencies and a lack of competitiveness (Tomlinson, 1996; 2009). By 1978, the UK had endured three decades of regular secessionist impulses consequent to decolonisation. Similar impulses had emerging in Wales and Scotland, and in Northern Ireland where, there, PIRA were engaging the British Army in their efforts to advance Irish irredentism (English 2008; Taylor, 2014). The point being made is that when MPs talked of the SNP reconvening in Edinburgh and forming a government in residence, it may not be

hyperbole and they actually meant it, particularly given that there is nothing in the UK constitution to prevent it (HM Government, 2009; Tierney, 2017; Murray, 2009). To avoid this eventuality, MPs went to extreme measures. But whilst rule bending was a central feature, the reality was that there weren't any rules to break, consequent to the Parliament Act (1949). This insight tells us that rule bending has no relevance where opposition craft plays out in the Commons. Nonetheless, and insofar as this thesis is concerned, the Scottish preconditions appear more like how the precipitancy is expected to play out and to this end, these insights offer up a limitation of Wood (1981) in that his framework, when tested against a real-world case, might not stand up.

Rise/movement: Wood's (1981) framework again fails to explain - this thesis notes that the 1980s were fallow years for the SNP meaning that Scotland did not experience the rise of a secessionist movement, as expected. The push for independence, inadvertent or otherwise, was maintained by the Scottish branch of the Labour party. In reality, it was a performative gesture purposed only to reinforce a party policy in favour of devolution and the opportunity came in 1997 when the party returned to power. A second devolution referendum was held and Scotland voted 'Yes' to both a parliament and one with tax-raising responsibilities. As predicted by Bulpitt, however, the emergent parliament was a "hived-off territorial administration" and was (and is) fully reliant on "collaborators" to ensure the success of the resultant constitutional arrangement, of which Bulpitt called a "straitjacket" (1983: 190). The rival chamber was contained via the Scotland Act (1998) and its irrevocability being gradually eroded through incremental reduction in MPs from Scotland to the House of Commons. On side was a hard-right countermovement that was found on the depleted Conservative opposition benches which outlined that Scotland was free to have a parliament, just not whilst it remained in the UK. These policy objectives included an impossibly-high Cunningham-style threshold of sixty percent. The upshot here is that if the Scotland Act (1998) is a straitjacket and Kilbrandon a tiger cage, the sixty-percent threshold is the wider prison.

Precipitancy: Scotland reached the precipitancy in the absence of a secessionist movement. The effect was the country experiencing the rise/movement and the precipitancy simultaneously. The devolving of all authority for holding a referendum to the Scottish government remains unexplained in the literature. To this end, this thesis suggests the Edinburgh Agreement was a vehicle for help preserve the dual polity and similarly to events

in 1978 and 1997, Scotland was not the uppermost consideration for the London-based politicians. The result left the Scottish government holding a host of important cards and it did not deploy them to full effect. Reducing the age of franchise to sixteen offered nugatory electoral impact and was a propagandizing tactic deemed more important than direct engagement an estimated ten percent that were least likely to vote and who were mostly likely to have voted ‘Yes’ to Scottish independence (Ayres, 2014). To this end, the Scottish precipitancy presented more like the preconditions. One reason could be the neutral posture adopted by the Scottish government. As a practice, it actively defied realist, referendum, statecraft, and secessionist logic. The result was predominance for an unexplainable electoral strategy for the 2014 independence referendum that actively undermined the Scottish national interest.

A note on referendums

There was no need to hold a referendum in 1997. Labour could have been to have pledged to directly set up a Scottish chamber, as had been the expectation even a year earlier where, up until then it had been assumed that a Labour government would legislate for the direct establishment of a Scottish parliament as had been the original intention in 1974 (Duclos, 2006). It could also have legislated to retrospectively amend the Scotland Act (1978) by removing the threshold and allow the 1979 result to stand. Instead, the 1997 devolution established the idea in the UK that referendums are consultative tools, thereby undermining the potential of the Commons taking instruction from the people. It also addressed at the outset the predominance of the Parliament Act (1949) and, as was noted, not one member of the hard-right cabal criticised referendums, quite possibly out of political expedience given their aspirations for a referendum on UK membership of the EU. Another effect of the 1997 referendum helped solidify the idea that Scottish political sentiment should be tested through government-sanctioned referendums rather than via, e.g., UDI. The resultant talk in the Scottish political classes was not of independence but instead, talk of an independence referendum. Overall, neither referendum in 1979 and 1997, nor indeed the primacy of the dual polity to the 2014 referendum, were actually about Scotland. If there was a ‘winner’ from Scotland’s three referendums, it was Westminster.

These insights bring us to one last point, this time concerning comments made during the SIRFA debate by Scottish Green Patrick Harvie who mentioned the “non-binding nature of referendums” which “makes them different from elections” (Hansard, 2013: n.p.). He

appeared not to know that the non-binding element he referred to is borne of Parliamentary sovereignty, itself being an entirely English feature that does not extend to Scotland (1953 SC 396). There, the tradition has been determined by the Claim of Right through which the people are sovereign (1953 SC 396; Priddy, 2016; Torrance, 2018: n.p.). The totality of this insight is that should a time come when Scotland acquires its independence and its people continue to claim sovereign status over and above its parliament, referendums results will have to be mandatory on government. To do otherwise, as Harvie implies, suggests parliamentary supremacy and in an independent Scotland either the people will be sovereign or it will be their parliament - it cannot be both.

A decade later

Since 1945 the UK had experienced drift, decline and diminution in both the international and domestic fronts. After a brief period of relative stability the state is now in the early years of an era of deglobalisation which, in effect, presents as a re-enactment of Salisbury's splendid isolation, and it began in 2016 when the UK voted as a whole to leave the EU.

A general election took place in 2015. It was won by David Cameron's Conservatives, this time with a working majority. The Conservative manifesto included a commitment on holding an 'In/Out' referendum on EU membership, which was held a year later in 2016 with the result being 'Out'. Cameron resigned immediately and was replaced by Theresa May who called another general election in 2017. She scraped through on a small working majority, albeit with a party split along pro- and anti-EU lines (BBC, 2018). The consequence was her experiencing a torrid time in government and resulted in her deal with the EU being voted down in the Commons and in 2019, and in what was an act of gross governing incompetence, MPs voted to take control of the Commons timetable (Bulpitt, 1983; BBC, 2019). Such was the crisis at the heart of government it was not uncommon for May to declare action being undertaken in the national interest (Price, 2019). She resigned as Prime Minister later in the year and was replaced by former Telegraph columnist Boris Johnson who illegally prorogued the UK Parliament before going on to call a third general election in five years, which the Conservatives won again. In 2020 the UK left the EU and the effects, combined with pandemic, have left the state further diminished internationally. Domestically, it has recorded a poor economic and fiscal performance and indicators of a creaking national infrastructure (Giles, 2020; Szalay, 2020; Corlett and Try, 2022; Springford and Portes, 2023; Islam, 2024). The overall extent is that over the past few years peacetime UK has never been weaker, and

presents as a case of a state in the early stages of failure. For supporters of Scottish independence, the potential to push towards another precipitancy was real and they looked to Nicola Sturgeon to advance the cause.

Sturgeon became SNP leader and First Minister in late 2014. Buoyed by a two year long national discussion on independence and with membership quickly soaring to over a hundred thousand (Bennie, Mitchell, and Johns, 2018), the SNP was also cash rich. And the effect was immediate - at the 2015 general election, the party won all but three Scottish seats in the 2015 general election (BBC, 2015). The result was more than sufficient to meet the Cunningham/Cook UDI test under which the SNP would have been expected to decamp to Edinburgh and set up a government in residence. However, that there was no movement towards a second precipitancy. However, the SNP remained hooked on a second independence referendum. The 2016 EU referendum, with Scotland voting overwhelmingly to remain, handed Sturgeon another mandate to advance the cause of independence. The golden opportunity came during the 2017 general election campaign but it was spurned. The SNP campaigned not on Scottish independence but, instead, to ensure Scotland has a say in EU departure negotiations (SNP, 2017). This policy had hardened by 2019 when the headline policies included reversing the 2016 referendum result and holding an independence referendum in 2020 (BBC, 2019). In both elections, 2017 and 2019, the SNP again passed the Cunningham/Cook test and again, there was stagnation and no movement towards the precipitancy. By the time of the Scottish parliament in 2021, Sturgeon again committed her party to holding an independence referendum (SNP, 2021). The UK had already left the EU and to date, Scotland remains the only constituent country to get the settlement it voted for in the EU referendum. Even so, Sturgeon spurned an opportunity to flood Holyrood with pro-independence MSPs (BBC, 2021), and despite a slim pro-independence majority in Holyrood, no referendum has taken place. To be fair, her government did draft a Bill for one to take place but it was a performative act that ended up being heard in the UK Supreme Court on whether Holyrood has the competence to legislate on a referendum on Scottish independence (Torrance, 2022). The Court decided the answer was 'no' meaning that the Scottish government lost the case.

Sturgeon resigned in 2023 and leaves behind a legacy that includes her fronting an electoral strategy for the 2014 referendum that was flawed from the outset and who, as First Minister, spurned every opportunity to advance independence. Added, such is the strategic ineptitude

that through her actions, she served only to limit Scotland's routes to independence. In all, it is difficult to understand how she managed to remain at the helm of Scottish politics for so long given her consistent failures at numerous critical junctures. As for the SNP, it is left facing numerous crises - legal, financial, political, and the Scottish government is showing signs of the natural rate of governance (Hopkins, 2011; BBC, 2024; Curtice, 2024). These problems have since been further compounded by a sharp fall in party membership and a collapse of the SNP vote at the recent 2024 UK general election. That's not to say, however, that support for independence has also waned because it hasn't (Wade, 2023). Instead, support for independence has merely decoupled from the SNP and is a legacy of an observation made by McAngus (2013) when he said that before the referendum the campaign for independence had centred in the main around the electoral fortunes of the SNP but afterwards, the party is now merely a part of something bigger.

In all, the political wing of the Yes movement can no longer be relied upon to advance the cause of independence. In addition, and in line with Tilly (1977) and Tarrow (2011), the entrepreneurs that populated and networked the Edinburgh bubble in the lead-up to 2014 have reverted to type and are now focused on other contentious issues. What remains of the standing movement is suffering from low morale, is apathetic, and is splintered (Hinde, 2017; BBC, 2023). But whilst returning to the precipitancy is further undermined by the lack of an effective political vehicle, an opportunity exists for the movement it to create its own. Table 57 (pg. 229) tells us that whilst scholars remain fixated on the party political system, research into rule bending in the Scottish context is underexploited. As such, we do not know the potential offered by rule bending in the push towards another precipitancy. To this end, and in the absence of an effective party-political vehicle, the movement could be better served by investigating the potential benefits of practicing its politics by other means.

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Appendix 1: glossary

Agreed settlement: this involves a government and a secessionist movement agree on a course of action for testing or settling the depth of an impulse. This can occur via an electoral event, more commonly a referendum, or in some cases their agreement to cause a secessionist event. Thereafter a new state is created with the recognition of the parent state.

Argument hegemony: winning the battle of ideas (James, 2016; 2018). It is defined as “the party achieving an easy predominance in elite debate regarding political problems, policies and the general stance of government”, and it can be won and lost, at any time, in a number of arenas - governmental, oppositional, and/or social (Bulpitt, 1986: 21; Hopkins, 2011).

Bending the rules: the normal rules of government and its interaction with society are changed by the centre to suit, so to respond to real-world events and circumstances so that statecraft is achieved (Bulpitt, 1983; Buller & James, 2012; James, 2016). Bending the rules and as a practice, it is entirely in line with the best of practice offered by realism. Bending the rules is required by necessity.

Constructivism: constructivist explanations are, in the main, focussed on the idea that society, historical memory, ethnicity, felt nationality, and a host of other, essentially non-political factors impact the international arena (Onuf, 1989; Chandra, 2001a; 2001b; Checkel, 2008).

Devolution: an administrative change to the internal structures of state to facilitate a separate and distinct politico-legal jurisdiction within the state’s existing territorial space. The result is partial local control over a territory.

Dual polity: Bulpitt (1983: 61) argued that the central government is where “the locus of actual political power” is found. Ostensibly, the concern here relates to the nucleus of the state. Its main interest is high politics. Outside that zone, in the periphery, is low politics. The intention in the literature is that government should be separating the affairs of both and staying aloof by concentrating on international affairs and the like.

Early risers: predominately populated by entrepreneurs, these are pace setters and who define early on the nature and style of a campaign. For them, there is a benefit to having political connections in times of political opportunity. Those that can organise early can help shape the direction of a campaign (Tarrow, 2011: 205).

Elites: land-owning aristocratic elites who absorbed then directed political power and influence sufficient that they supplanted themselves at the helm of the state (Peters, 1967; Roberts, 2012). Today, this cohort includes the political classes, industrial and media barons (Sampson, 1962-2004; Marsh, 1978; Hennessey, 1986; Roberts, 2012).

Entrepreneurs: political activists whose public persona and, at times, employment incomes, are directly related to specific political issues, including secession. The indicator is that primarily, these roles are filled by the middle classes and their function is to compete for the political upper hand (Tilly, 1977; Wood, 1981; Tarrow, 2011).

External statecraft: the levers of statecraft outwith the direct control of central government and the elites and can include devolved institutions, media, banking, and finance.

Electoral strategy: statecraft is about winning again and again. To this end, party politicians place winning general elections their uppermost consideration. The effect is the perpetuation of the status quo, this time to include the party-political status quo (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; Hopkins, 2011; James, 2012; 2016; 2018).

Glorious Revolution: a revolution that occurred between 1688 and 1689 and which resulted in James VII being deposed and replaced by William and Mary of Orange (Miller, 1997). The event was a cornerstone of Whiggism, the symbols of which remain in situ to this day.

Governing competence: competent government is not just about policy or its implementation but also how it is perceived but that can mean deciding to do nothing, to deal with problems directly, or devolving responsibility to other areas of the state, as per the dual polity (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; Buller and James, 2012). Effective policy rejection when in government is as necessary a requirement as policy adoption (Bulpitt, 1986: 21; Hopkins, 2011).

Independence: following a secessionist event, the newly formed state acquires independent statehood, premised on being the sovereign power in the given territory (Crawford, 2006; Pavkovic & Radan, 2011).

Internal statecraft: the levers of statecraft within the direct control of central government and the elites.

International system: those political and legal organisations and frameworks that support and regulate relations between states, and the geopolitical geography demarcate the territory of states, their sovereignty, and the geographic limits of their legal jurisdictions (Baylis and Smith, 2001).

Liberalism: liberalists encourage a peaceful co-existence across the international system (Evans, 1998; Baylis and Smith, 2001; Kegley and Wittkopf, 2001; Brecher and Harvey, 2002; Pugh 2005; Kalkman, 2011). The ideas, it is argued, helped elevate self-determination as a political ideal and has create and maintain the social contract through offering a direct link between society, state, and the international arena.

National interest: defined in UK law as being in the interests of the government of the day (Ponting, 1987).

Natural rate of governance: an ill-defined concept that links economic performance to governing competence (Bulpitt, 1996; Hopkins, 2011). But, in essence the interpretation is that the longer a party is in government, the more likely it is to become exhausted by events, causing it to struggle to achieve governing competence, sufficient to have a negative impact at a subsequent election.

Opposition craft: an act of statecraft contrary to the national interest.

Partition: the result of interference or intervention in the administration of a state that result in the creation of two or more states in the same space (Heraclides, 2002). A commonality sees partition being used to settle wars and conflict.

Party management: intended to gear the party-political machinery to create, preserve, and/or portray a unified party, regardless of the rank or purpose of any official or member (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986a; Buller and James, 2012; James, 2016; 2018).

Pre-conditions of secession: cleavages in a territory that shape a different agenda and opinions that are contrary to the status quo and in favour of territorial independence. These cleavages can be found across a wealth of areas, including geography; social and psychological attitudes; and in alternative economic and political policy and practices (Wood, 1981).

Realism: Westphalia formed the basis for relations between states. Realism centres on territory and premises on the exercise of political authority in four areas - territory, autonomy, control, and mutual recognition (Elrod, 1976; Kegley and Wittkopf, 1981; Krasner, 1999; 2001; Kissinger, 2014). Realism applied in the domestic space leads to “compulsion” (Schmitt, 1996: 36).

Referendum: a standalone single issue electoral event and can commonly result in a binary choice, i.e., yes, or no, in, or out.

Response of central government: when faced with calls for secession, central government has three choices in front of it - suppress or accommodate, or equilibrium - a combination of both (Wood, 1981). States may also be reluctant to adopt autonomy or devolution and, instead, stick to a centralised system of governance (Heraclides, 2002). Similarly, it is a rare event for a state to welcome a secessionist impulse in its space.

Rise of secessionist movements: a key requirement of secessionists is to mobilise the population, creating a public face to the movement (Wood, 1981). It is the job of an emerging leadership to convince the affected population that their futures are best served as an independent state. The leadership acts as the vehicle that brings to life the social aspirations that underpin a secessionist impulse, and which create further cleavages between the affected population and the wider masses (Wood, 1981).

Salisbury’s codes for government: devised in the late 1800s, these were an early form of statecraft intended to respond to numerous party and policy issues that had the potential to impact the status quo. These codes were a response to the UK’s diminution internationally and from within its own space and were responsible for the concept of the dual polity, splendid isolation, and a system for party management (Marsh, 1978; Pollard, 1989; Tomlinson, 2009).

Secession: the process that sees a part of an existing state territory break away to either form its own state or join with another existing state (Pavkovic & Radan, 2011). Successful secessionist events result in geopolitical geographic change.

Secessionist accommodation: where a state recognises the existence of secessionist impulse and responds by developing strategies that include offering primacy to minority rights, creating devolved institutions, as well as developing a consensus that secessionist event is inevitable (Wood, 1981).

Secessionist impulse: beginning in the hearts and minds of individuals, a secessionist impulse emerges when a population asks itself abstract questions of the self - identity,

nationality, with the product being a social discourse on how best a territory is to be governed (Buchheit, 1978; Wood, 1981).

Secessionist precipitancy: the direct precipitants of secession are those events that drive secessionism towards the tipping point, and where there is a distinct possibility that the state will fracture. At this point conflicting parties arrive at the zero sum and where events could lead to the creation of an independent state or the use of force by the state to maintain its integrity. It is anticipated that both sides will use security as both a cause and a goal, particularly where force or violence is present (Wood, 1981), leading to a claim of secession via remedial rights (Buchanan, 1997).

Secessionist suppression: Suppression is multi-faceted and can include passive resistance and actual violence (Buchheit, 1978; Wood, 1981; Buchanan, 1997). One example offered by Wood (1981) involves the mobilisation of the 'home' focussed population within the affected territory who can be utilised to advocate for the status quo. This suppressor approach can also be called counter-secessionism (Ker-Lindsay, 2012). The state, its core intent is to re-legitimise the political status quo and, for Wood it is only through such actions that the state is able to compete and maintain its integrity (1981).

Self-determination: the aspirant state of independence and caused through a secessionist event. Ultimately, a secessionist impulse, its entrepreneurs, and the wider movement campaign to experience self-determination.

Separatism: a process that aids state reform to accommodate a secessionist impulse via devolution or other form of autonomy. All reform is internal and there is no change to the geopolitical geography.

Social movement: where ordinary people combine their efforts in an organised way to exert influence or power over political or social issues contrary to the status quo (Tarrow, 2011). These groups can be dominated by entrepreneurial early risers.

Sovereignty: the idea that strength, power, and legitimacy are sufficient for one to rule over another (Kissinger, 2014). Sovereignty has been practiced for several millennia and has seen sovereignty being invested in people. More recently the trend has been for sovereignty to be invested in an institution, i.e., a parliament.

Statecraft: those machineries of state employed to combat challenges to the governing party, the state and/or the status quo. These challenges directly affect the executive and can be policy, party, and crisis led (Bulpitt, 1983; 1986). The purpose of statecraft is to maximise political outcomes in the favour of the governing party, the state and/or the status quo.

Unilateral declaration of independence: where a secessionist movement declares independence contrary to the demands of the parent state, including their withholding recognition (Wood, 1981; Crawford, 2006; Ker-Lindsay, 2012).

Whiggism: this ideology evolved out of the Glorious revolution and William of Orange's accession to the Crown in 1688. The underpinning ideas include the promotion of Protestantism over Catholicism and premised on the concept of Parliamentary supremacy and limited constitutional monarchy (Curran and Seaton, 2002; Womersley, Bullard, and Williams, 2005).

Appendix 2: early secessionist examples

Ancient history is replete with a number of social conditions and relational qualities which today, we would equate to a range of terms - nationalism, identity, difference, control, power, freedom, class, elites, coercion, interference, and the social contract. To illustrate this, this section briefly examines three distinct ancient events. The first concerns the rise and fall of the first acknowledged political community and Empire, Akkad. Second, the attempted independence revolt in Ionia; and lastly, the Conflict of the Orders in the Roman Republic. This section outlines a key insight that in those earlier times the events leading up to an act of secession were politically driven, as were the after-event era. But the events themselves possessed legal characteristics. This section begins by looking at the region which spans from Egypt, up through Israel and Lebanon, and across into modern day Syria and Iraq.

Thousands of years ago these territories boasted rich pastoral lands where the first complex farming systems would be established. Known as the Fertile Crescent, the region is also recognised as the ‘Cradle of Civilisation’ from which the first organised political communities emerged (van de Mieroop, 2016; Foster, 2015; Chase-Dunn and Lerro, 2016). This same territory would soon boast urban spaces complete with ornate and plumbed buildings (Podany, 2018a). Homes boasted domesticated pets; communities traded with one another, and food was communally ‘managed’ to ensure that the society benefitted from any surplus (Grayson, 2000; Podany, 2018b). These advancements may now be read as rudimentary, but they represented a type of superpower of the era. After all, the peoples inhabiting Europe four and a half thousand years ago were still hunter-gatherers (Fagan, 2016). It is from the Cradle where the first Empire emerged. Akkad existed between roughly c.2300-2100 BC and is considered to be the first political system that governed over a society that possessed competing cultural identities (Foster, 2015; Chase-Dunn and Lerro, 2016). These included the Sumerian and Mesopotamians and their existence meant that Akkad lacked stability. Indeed, history records that the Akkad leadership faced numerous rebellions, each are thought to have been ruthlessly suppressed (Foster, 2015; van de Mieroop, 2016). Over time, new territorial elites began to emerge and power would gravitate to suit the prevailing wind.

The result was a territory that lacked any clear or obvious centre of administrative power, leading to an outcome that will be familiar to scholars of nationalism, namely that the language and culture of Akkad became hegemonic devices in the contest for political control (Foster, 2015; van de Mieroop, 2016; Chase-Dunn and Lerro, 2016). It is this era that Foster calls the “invention of Empire” (2015: n.p.), a system of governance that bore the hallmarks of Engels’ (1884) idea of the state as a coercive force dominated by a repressive ruling class intent on maintaining its rule over the masses. Even so, by the 2100s BC Akkad had collapsed and the ensuing regional power vacuum was filled by a succession of Dynasties (van de Mieroop, 2016; Foster, 2015; Chase-Dunn and Lerro, 2016). A further evolution resulted in the emergence of more rival Empires, Old Assyria and Old Babylonia (Grayson, 2000; Lipschits, 2005; Podany, 2018a). Latterly, in 891 BC, the Neo-Assyrian Empire expanded down between the Tigris and Euphrates Rivers and into Babylonia. By 500 BC, however, the Neo-Assyrian eastern territory was being squeezed. The Persian Empire had swept westwards through Babylonia and Assyria and on into what is now Turkey (Lipschits, 2005; Podany, 2018a). Located to the Persian far west was an area called Ionia. Its people had more of an affinity to Greece and in 499 BC they began to revolt against their rulers so to secure their independence (Holland, 2006). The campaign lasted six years and was bolstered by Greek military assistance (Abbott, 1900; Fink, 2014). The campaign was a disaster and the

Persians prevailed. Holland (2006) notes that the Ionian Revolt was a factor in the ensuing Greco-Persian Wars, during which time salt was rubbed in Ionian wounds via the region being used by Persia as a staging post for assaults on Greece.

The annals of history can help us better understand the development of forms of relations between the governing and the governed. The selective history here covers a time span that ranges over a period of roughly two millennia. Examining what we now regard as secessionist movements in these contexts reinforces the idea offered by Coggins (2016) that what is now called self-determination has been a perpetual factor of political life. They all have in common the demand of a people to be ruled in a way not offered by their then-status quo. The suggestion here is that public administration is synonymous with exclusionary politics, to an extent that bureaucracy is used to isolate the elites from the masses through limiting accountability. It is a process that Jessop (2018) labelled as form determinacy, in that the administration of political communities is always institutionally mediated. What is particularly striking is the reliance of the elites to use force to maintain their authority. These ancient struggles for power and sustainability present what can be collectively termed the antecedents of state formation as we know it today (Brooke, Strauss, and Anderson, 2018). Added, in the Ionian case, the Greek presence in the shape of its being an interested third-party allows for parallels in the contemporary practice where states interfere in the affairs of another political domain (Baylis and Smith, 2001; Kissinger, 2014). For scholars such as Wohlander (2001), such interventions lead to intensification and an inevitable lengthening of any conflict theatre and, indeed, the same eventuality is found with the Greco-Persian Wars. Rome was different from its predecessors because it had a constitution, albeit focused more on the continuity of the power base through a pre-determined system of succession (Schiller, 1978). This was little use to the common man, the pleb, those who basically existed solely to satisfy debt bondage - a system that trapped them into a cycle of perpetual poverty and forced labour (Abbott, 1901; Schiller, 1978). Compulsory mobilisation as unpaid foot soldiers was also a commonality (Abbott, 1901; Schiller, 1978; Raaflaub, 2005; Drake, 2013). In 494 BC the plebs started to revolt. It was the start of a series of actions called the *secessio plebis*. These formed the basis for an era in Roman history called the Conflict of the Orders, which went on for roughly two hundred years (Phillipson, 1968; Schiller, 1978).

The acts, of which there were at least five, were a direct challenge to the established order. Plebs started to adopt disruptive tactics including for example, developing a system of collective identity during debt bondage roll calls. Their most potent tactic bore some striking similarities with modern industrial action. The plebs would in effect, go in strike. They would depart the city en-masse and set up camp on the hills outside the city. It was a place where they could exercise liberties normally denied to them (Abbott, 1901; Schiller, 1978). They called the space, *Res Publica* and would send negotiation teams to meet with the city's patricians. One early success was the Twelve Tables which comprised as a set of rights, as per a rudimentary social contract, that outlined the limits of the Republic in the private, public, and financial spheres (Phillipson, 1968; Schiller, 1978). History records five acts of the *secessio plebis* with each resulting in further tilts in power relations away from the established order and to the benefit of the people. The Conflict came to an end in 287 BC with the ratification of the Hortensian Law. This is the law that gave the plebs their legal independence from Rome and it was during this same era when the linguistic formation of the key terminology surrounding secession originated - 'Se' translates into English as "apart" whilst 'cedere' means "to go" (Abbott, 1901; Pavkovic and Radan, 2011: 3).

At no point, however, did the plebs seek to overthrow the patrician elites in what current terminology would term as a revolution. This final insight builds on a number of historical phenomena that centred in and around what today would be labelled as secessionist activity. The cases mentioned above involve aspects of nationalism and the associated politicisation of language and culture. Added is the potential for third-party interests to attempts at secessionist, as is the realisation that the events leading up to a secessionist event are political, as are the events afterwards. The event itself is a legal matter. In all cases is the presence of a repressive ruling class.

Empire existed for a further two and a half thousand years and its dismantling as a form of governance began less than a hundred years ago. The overall effect is that of all the states in the world at present, the vast majority have existed for less than seventy five years.

Appendix 3: secessionism and separatism in the domestic space

Notwithstanding the protracted fallout of the collapse of the USSR, global geopolitical geography is more stable now than at any time since, arguably, Westphalia, at least in terms of the recent downturn in secessionist events. Consequentially, secessionist scholars have no live case studies that reflect the modern context, which in itself presents as an inherent weakness when attempting to advance knowledge in this area. A consequence is that scholars are largely reduced to questioning the merits and dynamics of secession (Buchanan, 1997). However, and as was noted in chapter one, secessionist impulses comprise innumerate socio-political influences and other elements that need be taken into account. The meaning here is that every case of secession has its own unique historical trajectory (Farley, 1986; Onuf, 1989; Smith; 1991; Chandra, 2001a; 2001b; Checkel, 2008; McEwan, 2018). Factors such as these lead us to assert a potential that our knowledge on secession is complicated consequence of the inherent crossovers into other subject matters, i.e., ethnicity and nationalism (Haverland, 2000; Pavkovic and Radan (2011). This is also the case when discussing state formation where reference to works on nationalism via the likes of Gellner (1983), Hobsbawm (1990), Ozkirimli (1990), and in the case of the UK, Nairn (1977). This path is well trodden within the literature on nationalism and forms the basis of Anderson's (1983) modernist argument that national identity is a political construct and a by-product of the industrial revolution. Similarly, Miller argues that nationalism tends to be based upon a common sense of belonging between peoples who are bound by a sense of identity (1995: 22). Such communities exist because of "mutual recognition" and in the contemporary sphere this same sense of belonging also correlates to a claim over the territory in which this same community resides (Miller, 1995: 24).

As such, it is fair to say that secession as area of academic or political interest is a highly contestable one. Yet as has already been outlined in chapter one, it is possible to construct a consensus based on generalised assertions in respect of how secession causes through state fracture, a newly created independent state. How that occurs, what forces and energies are used, and what rights permit remain contingent to various factors. For example, Wood argues that "the ideological content of virtually every secessionist movement's appeal is some form of nationalism" (1981: 122). For Nairn, the UK space possesses a novelty factor in that the nationalisms that exist there compete against the "hopelessness and corruption of the post-imperial political scene" (1968: 1). He cited the Irish secessionism of the 1920s as an influence and for him the inevitable outcome was the political fragmentation of the UK. For him the catalyst was a set of small but significant Parliamentary victories for secessionists in Scotland and separatists in Wales. The response from the state was to convene its 1969 Royal Commission on its Constitution (Kilbrandon), the terms of reference for which comprised "to examine the present functions of the central legislature and government in relation to the several countries, nations and regions of the UK" (Alden, 2001: 119). Nairn added further that by the 1970s nationalist sentiment in the UK had replaced class struggle as "the principal factor" for altering the political status quo and social contract (1977: 79). He argued that eventuality would be of benefit to England:

Fringe nationalisms [Scottish, Welsh, and Irish] will be good for the English, by forcing upon them a more painful reassessment of themselves than any they have yet undergone. The smug 'deep sleep' Orwell spoke of - the fruit of the oldest and most successful of modern imperialisms - would be more disturbed by the loss of Wales or Scotland than ever it was by the loss of India or Africa (1968: 1)

Nonetheless, the rationale of Kilbrandon was the continuance of the state as a unitary model but to do it in such a way that accommodated local and regional governance (HM Government, 1973). This proposed system is what Alder labelled as a “regionalised unitary state” through which elected parliaments and Assemblies for Scotland and Wales would be created, each incorporated within the structure of the state (2010, 117). A further proposal was the creation of additional bodies dedicated to enhancing the powers of the English regions (Forman, 2002; Wilson, 2017). However, Kilbrandon spurned making recommendations for either Northern Ireland or Overseas Territories and, indeed, not all went to plan (HM Government, 1978). Forman (2002) notes that the Commission was divided over its findings hence the publication of a dissenter annex when the final report was published (HM Government, 1973). It also took a further six years before concrete attempts at altering the UK system emerged though in the end, these efforts came to nothing, and the state was not altered and, indeed, took a further two decades before real change took effect. To this end, this chapter now consider the recent journeys of each of the countries that make up the UK space, beginning first with Wales.

3.1: England

Formed in the 1100s (see chapter two’s discussion on rule bending) England is unique in that it is the only constituent country of the UK to have not experienced an obvious and sustained secessionist impulse. Added, England it does not boast its own devolved administration, nor has its electorate been asked whether it should have one or not. Today, England is littered with regional and locally devolved systems of varying degrees of autonomy, in line with a piecemeal approach to political reform (Tomaney, 2010; Sandford, 2013). Much of what is described here is in line with Nairn (1977) who asserted the possibility that English regionalism could motivate political change.

Kilbrandon recommended a set of regional bodies that could enhance the English regional voice (HM Government, 1973). Nine bodies were suggested, with London benefitting from region-city status (HM Government, 1973). For Morrison (2013) progress towards devolved legislatures across England was slow, to the point of being nugatory. In 1998 voters in the English North-East voted against its own dedicated assembly whereas in London, a referendum there led to the creation of the London assembly and a separately elected Mayor (Morrison, 2013; Tomaney, 2010; Sandford, 2013). By the 2010s a new policy was adopted that heralded an era of elected Mayors for English cities, with large local councils also being mandated to hold local referendums on the establishing of a Mayoral office (Sandford, 2013). More recently UK Parliamentary reform made space for a new England-only system of legislation. English Votes for English Laws (EVEL) had been intended to address a political paradox at the UK Parliament in which elected members from the three other constituent countries had been able to vote on matters that pertained only to England (UK Parliament, 2021). EVEL has since been repealed but, nonetheless, the effect was England temporarily having its own de-facto parliament, albeit one that sat on a part-time basis (Elliott and Thomas, 2020). Indeed, by default of devolution being installed elsewhere in the UK space, there are times when the UK Prime Minister and Cabinet have overseen England-only policies. Only recently have opinion pollsters began to ask questions on English independence. The results have reported near 50/50 returns (Business for Scotland, 2020).

3.2: Northern Ireland

Following the Irish secession from the British Empire and resultant partition of the Island in 1921, Northern Irish affairs had been overseen by a Governor, of a type found elsewhere in the colonial space up until 1973 (Bell, 2008). Then, the Irish Catholic communities had experienced ongoing structural discrimination across the social, political, and economic, spheres (Lipset, 1959; Galtung, 1969; Honderich, 1973; Nairn, 1977; Derrida, 2002; Bell, 2008; Della Porta, 2008; Mansfield, 2011; Taylor, 2014). For example, the rules for standing for election required candidates to be property owners (Bell, 2008). Systemic gerrymandering of electoral constituency boundaries provided further limitations. The result was a political system that aided and supported the enhanced representation of the British Protestant communities while at the same time the Irish Catholic communities continued to experience higher than average unemployment and poverty levels (Derrida, 2002; Bell, 2008; Della Porta, 2008). The overall result meant that relatively few of their number could afford to meet the thresholds to stand for office, and attempt political change (Bell, 2008; Taylor, 2014).

To this end, it is fair to suggest that Northern Ireland contained the ingredients necessary for political exclusivity to flourish, and where this is the case, it is impossible for communities to co-exist peacefully (Angell, 1910; Lipset, 1959; Galtung, 1969; Honderich, 1973; Derrida, 2002; Duggan, 2004; Bell, 2008; Della Porta, 2008; Gilady, 2017), and indeed this proved to be the case. Ongoing civil unrest resulted in the UK deploying its military to the country in 1969 as an attempt to maintain law and order. It was an event that coincided with the initiation of Kilbrandon and which, ultimately, offered nothing of substance for addressing the situation in the country (HM Government, 1973; Wilson, 2017). For Taylor, the reason lay with the parallel bilateral - UK/Irish - Sunningdale Agreement which mandated a number of cross-border initiatives and a referendum on irredentist secessionism (Taylor 2014).

The referendum took place in 1973 but was boycotted by the Catholic communities, leading to a result heavily in favour of the status quo. By this time Northern Ireland was in the early years of the 'Troubles' which saw the proscribed Provisional Irish Republican Army (PIRA) emerge as a paramilitary force. PIRA boasted sufficient numbers to sustain an almost three decade long paramilitary campaign in support of Irish irredentism (Townshend, 1984; CGS, 2007; English, 2008; Taylor 2014). In addition, the organisation was capable of operating on a number of fronts - not only in Northern Ireland or wider UK but also as far afield as Germany and Gibraltar (English, 2008; Taylor, 2014). Its 'England Department' was created to take their war direct to the heart of the UK government (Taylor, 2014). The premise there was that operations in England garnered much more media coverage than those launched in Northern Ireland. A wide-ranging target list was devised to inflict economic damage and make the UK presence in Northern Ireland unaffordable (Taylor, 2014; English, 2008). A consequence for the UK government was that it became the insurance underwriter of damage caused by PIRA attacks (English, 2008; Taylor, 2014). High value target areas included England's provincial shopping centres, essential infrastructure, London's West End, and the City of London.

By the 1990s the UK insurance costs were spiralling (McLeod, 1993; English, 2008; Taylor, 2014; Poolre, 2021a; Poolre, 2021b; Poolre, 2021c) The 1993 Bishopsgate bombing, for example, is on record as being the most expensive terrorist attack in the world, being usurped

only by the 2001 al Qaeda attacks on the USA⁶⁸ (McLeod, 1993; English, 2008; Taylor, 2014; Poolre, 2021a). At this time and in the background, the UK and Irish governments had been again in negotiation and had agreed the wording of a Downing Street Declaration which committed both states to peaceful irredentist secessionism should popular democratic support demand it (Taylor, 2014). In response PIRA suspended its operations so further negotiations could take place. However, after two years of stagnation, in 1996, the organisation returned to its military operations (English, 2008; Taylor, 2014). A second ceasefire was brokered in 1998; this time aided via EU and US support (English, 2008; Taylor, 2014). The result was the Good Friday Agreement which helped reform the Northern Irish political system, as well as lever the disarmament, demobilisation, and reintegration of all proscribed combatants back into society (Review Panel in Northern Ireland, 2022).

In 1998 the electorate in Northern Ireland voted via referendums in favour of a devolved Assembly with equal representation between communities. In 2007, and after some thirty-eight years of ongoing operations, UK military deployment to Northern Ireland came to an end (CGS, 2006). As it stands the UK government is now committed to Irish reunification should it be supported by a majority of its electorate (HM Government, 2008). Recent opinion polls, particularly following the UK departure from the EU, have recorded an upswing in support for holding a referendum on reunification with opinion polls also indicating the country being split almost 50/50 on irredentism (Coniam, 2021).

3.3: overseas territories

The UK retains remnants of its Imperial past. Fourteen overseas territories including three Crown dependencies and territory on Antarctica are represented by the UK in international relations, and also acts on behalf of the City of London (Monbiot, 2011). Each individual territory offers the potential to become micro-states. Many are tax havens and are hard-wired into the international financial system, and act as subsidiary bases to the UK whilst simultaneously benefitting from a level of autonomy and self-governance historically denied to the countries of the UK (Commonwealth Parliamentary Association UK, 2021). In 2013, the Falkland Islands held a sovereignty referendum and more recently there have been calls for independence referendums in Bermuda and the Cayman Islands (Watts, 2013; McWhirter, 2019; CNS, 2020)⁶⁹.

3.4: Scotland

Formed in the 900s, it took until the 1200s to agree a formal border agreement between Scotland and the newly emergent England (BBC, 2014). However, less than a century later both countries were at war (Penman, 2014). The Wars of Independence lasted for around a century and were what we would call in today's parlance a manifest conflict, a prolonged time of warfare interspersed with periods of latency (Pfetsch and Rohloff, 2000). The 1320 Treaty of Arbroath is considered the first example in history of a formal unilateral declaration of independence (Penman, 2014; National Records of Scotland, 2021). Its focus is not so much directed at the English to the south but also the Papacy which, at the time, practiced, universal sovereignty (Cowan, 2000). In 1603 King James VI of Scotland inherited the

⁶⁸ The cost of four large scale 'spectacular' attacks alone cost the UK exchequer over £7.5Bn at 2020 levels - the Baltic Exchange (1992), Bishopsgate (1993), Canary Wharf (1996), and Manchester city centre (1996) (McLeod, 1993; Poolre, 2021a; Poolre, 2021b; Poolre, 2021c).

⁶⁹ One territory that we can assume will not be acquiring its independence any day soon is the Chagos Islands of which UK continues to claim sovereignty in spite of a recent International Courts of Justice judgement calling for its de-colonisation (Landmark Chambers, 2020). To date, the UK continues to act in violation of the judgement.

English crown and the House of Stuart, which had primacy in Scotland dating back to the years immediately following the Wars of Independence, moved to London where it would rule for a century or so. In that time, the Wars of the Three Kingdoms and the overspill of the English Civil War meant that a peaceful co-existence on the Island was beyond reach (Merriman, 2000; Royle, 2005; Reid, 2012).

In 1707 the Act of Union between the English and Scottish parliaments created a new political community which, would see sovereignty over Scotland being transferred from Edinburgh to London, a settlement that persists to this day. Political union failed to deliver a pacific neighbourhood. The Jacobite Rebellions of 1715 and 1745 resulted in a reinforcement of the status quo, the dismantling of the Clan system and heralded in the Clearances (2012). At the time Scotland hosted nearly four hundred British army bases (Stennis Historical Society, 2020), and by the 1800s sentiment towards Scottish independence was subdued. The clear emphasis here is that by the turn of the century the union was stable. That changed in 1819 when Sir Walter Scott located the Honours of Scotland - Crown, Sceptre, and Sword - and had them were put on display at Edinburgh Castle (Burnett and Tabraham, 1993; Devine, 2012). The effect was almost instant in that a series of protests that took place in 1820, known as the Radical War and which, in reality, as little more than industrial action and social unrest (Devine, 2012), the 'War' was unusual for the time in that alongside a demand to widen the franchise protesters also called for a repeal the Act of Union (1707). The aristocracy mobilised militias, the ringleaders were arrested and sentenced to death (Berresford Ellis and Mac A' Ghobhainn, 2016). Little had changed by the end of the 1800s by which time Lord Salisbury feared a Scottish reckoning. He re-established the Scotland Office as part of a reform package that intended side-stepping a growing grievance in Scotland that had the potential to grow into a secessionist impulse, as was the case in Ireland at the time (Hanham, 1969; Bulpitt, 1983; Kidd, 2005; James, 2016). Numerous reforms had already been undertaken, most of which revolved around creating bodies and institutions that were specifically mandated to administer Scottish affairs (Kidd, 2005). The intended job of the Scotland Office was to co-ordinate them (Kidd, 2005). The result, however, was a de-centralised state system, one that would further distinguish Scotland politically, culturally, and administratively from the rest of the UK (Torrance, 2017). As an evasive policy, it did not work because by 1912 the UK Parliament had debated the second reading of the Government of Scotland Bill which had intended legislating for a devolved Scottish parliament (Hansard, 1912). The Bill was successful but WW1 got in the way and Scottish Home Rule on the backburner (BBC, 2014).

Scots were laterally energised by the 1917 Russian revolution and by 1919 a number were convinced that the class system could be overthrown (Bell, 2018; Craig, 2018; MacAskill, 2019). Radicalised by the Red Clydesiders, a general strike had begun that called for a reduced working week so to accommodate thousands of unemployed veterans. The action spread quickly from the west of Scotland across the central belt, causing a number of their towns to become hot beds of radical leftist politics⁷⁰ (MacAskill, 2019). In Glasgow, strikers numbering in their thousands met in George Square and were met by large numbers of police officers. Rioting broke out and the military was deployed (Bell, 2018; Craig, 2018; MacAskill, 2019). The decision to deploy armed troops into peacetime Glasgow had been taken by a 'War Cabinet' chaired by Andrew Bonar Law, a senior Conservative, politician

⁷⁰ Leading Red Clydeside activists included Manny Shinwell who, five years later, became an MP and latterly, a Minister in the Atlee government of 1945-1950 (Devine, 2012); John MacLean, who was the Bolshevik Consul for Scotland (Bell, 2018; MacAskill, 2019); and, Willie Gallacher who later became the Communist MP for West Fife (Devine, 2012; MacAskill, 2019).

(National Archives, 2021). To get round declaring martial law he placed military units at the disposal of the civil authorities. His was an act of necessity and one that would set precedent and have implications years later in Northern Ireland (CGS, 2006). In 1934 the SNP was formed out of the merger of a number of independence supporter groups (Lynch, 2002). The party's *raison d'être* was "self-government for Scotland ... and the enablement of a Scottish parliament which will be the final authority on all Scottish affairs" (Keating 2020: 636).

3.5: Wales

Having been annexed by England in the 1200s and fully assimilated into it in the 1500s, Wales traditionally has lacked a differentiated legal system (Forman, 2002). Kilbrandon had recommended a distinct Welsh Assembly even though at the time there was little appetite across the country for self-governance (HM Government, 1973; Forman, 2002), and indeed in 1979, the Welsh voted against having their own Assembly. For Forman (2002), Wales has the potential to be simply more than a cultural antiquity and for Nairn (1977) the country has presented itself as an emerging country. Indeed, by the time Kilbrandon had been published the state had already enacted reforms intended to promote limited Welsh local decision making, and further legislation intended to protect and promote the Welsh language (Forman, 2002). For this reason, Forman (2002) argues, Welsh political manoeuvres tended to coalesce around socio-cultural autonomy rather than full blown political independence or, indeed, self-governance (Forman, 2002).

That position was reversed in 1997 when Wales voted narrowly in favour of an Assembly which was created a year later. In a third referendum in 2011 Wales voted in numbers not previously recorded for their Assembly, increasing its responsibilities, including additional rights to change the law in Wales (BBC, 2011). This practice has been in line with the traditional policy of Plaid Cymru which, as was indicated in chapter one, has traditionally been the main driver for Welsh separatism; and it is only recently that the party has shifted its policy to advocate a more proactive policy on Welsh secessionism (Elias, 2009). However, Welsh support for independence lags behind the rest of the domestic UK population. Current estimates indicate although backing for Welsh independence is growing, support still resides at around the thirty percent level (Paun and Hall, 2021).

Appendix 4: secession in international relations theory

Jeremy Bentham first coined the phrase ‘international’ as a way of explaining early dynamics of international politics (Ozkirimli, 2000: 58). His then works had been largely influenced by an era which experienced the emergence of states as sovereign international actors. Notwithstanding the protracted fallout of the collapse of the USSR, global geopolitical geography is more stable now than at any time since, arguably, Westphalia, at least in terms of secessionist events. Consequentially, whilst secessionist scholars have no live case studies that reflect the modern context, international relations theory continues to offer a perspective on secession, its influences, and its undermining as an event.

4.1: constructivism

Constructivist explanations are, in the main, focussed on the idea that society, historical memory, ethnicity, felt nationality, and a host of other, essentially non-political factors impact the international arena (Onuf, 1989; Chandra, 2001a; 2001b; Checkel, 2008). Onuf (1989) contends that whilst states continue to operate out of self-interest they do so not because they are of an inherently realist hue but, instead, they seek out other states that possess similar ideologies and seek to form alliances with them. This approach to geopolitics serves to support, and sustain partnerships between states (Checkel, 2008). Checkel (2008) also notes, however, that these same decision processes help fuel inter-state rivalry. This outcome, Onuf (1989) suggests, is in stark contrast to the partnership system which is deemed to be more proactive and productive. This perspective is reminiscent of Waltz’s (1959) premise that inter-state rivalries are influenced by history and culture to an extent that they play a part in the form of anarchy that persists in the international system. Checkel (2008) asserts Waltz’s (1959) position is a contradictory one because it ignores the sociology of the international system as an influence on global dynamics.

Yet, for Adler (1997), there is a middle ground within which it is possible for alternate explanations of international relations to co-exist within the same school of thought. Nevertheless, what is becoming clearer here is a splintering of the constructivist school along geographic and philosophic lines. Weber (2010) continued this theme through his support for the idea that history and culture are factors that are intrinsic to the evolution and dynamics of the international arena. Weber (2010) offers an analysis of inter-state interactions in terms of its actual impact on state activity. This perspective acts as a direct challenge to Waltz (1959) given that he advanced a neo-realist agenda, which is contrary to Weber’s (2010) constructivist ideals. At this juncture it is worth recalling that the core thrust of constructivist theory is the advancement of ethnic or nationalist identities through geographic or local associations (Bookman, 1994). Situations such as these are particularly relevant where these same identities act as competition to that which is promoted by the state. Disgruntled peoples also frequently question whether they are likely to become more prosperous or not as an independent state than under the status quo (Bookman, 1994). This issue has already been highlighted in respect of Catalonia, but the same could also have been said for Yugoslavia which had adopted a more centralised economic system where the impact of reform was felt on its richer territories, namely, Croatia and Slovenia (Bookman, 1994). Recently, there has been discussion of the idea that secession is borne of greed or grievance (Collier and Hoeffler, 2002). The implication here is that the public discourse can be supported through popular culture and what results is secession being “presented as the solution to the challenge of peaceful coexistence between distinct peoples” (Collier and Hoeffler, 2002: 37). These debates are often underpinned by considerations of structure and agency, given that they are

recurring themes that run through society which can be seen to hinder or promote opportunity, free will, and autonomy (Barker, 2005). Overall, it is insights such as these that reinforce Chandra's (2001b: 337) position that constructivism forms part of "conventional wisdom". Regarding structure and agency, for secessionist movements and states alike the competition for meaning to peoples' lives is the embodiment of Stanton Rowe's (1897) need for national unity. For it is through this that people can achieve a sense of belonging (O'Donnell, 1997: 11; Barker, 2005).

4.2: liberalism

Moravcsik (1997) asserts that liberalism has helped to create and maintain the social contract through offering a direct link between society, state, and the international arena. Approaches such as these are considered by Liberalists to encourage a peaceful co-existence across the international system (Evans, 1998; Baylis and Smith, 2001; Kegley and Wittkopf, 2001; Brecher and Harvey, 2002; Pugh 2005; Kalkman, 2011). These understandings owe much to the politics of US President Woodrow Wilson and the work of Norman Angell. Angell's (1910) paper on war as a false economy argues that there is little benefit of conquering new territories, as was the business of Empire. Victorious states did not really benefit from the spoils of war because a conquered society that remains less than obliging reinforces the idea that any economic benefit to war would be nugatory (Angell, 1910; Miller, 1995).

Angell's work is reminiscent of the three conditions of the Kantian Triangle - consolidated democracy; liberal practices and policies; and peaceful co-existence (Gilady, 2017). In real-world terms, these are the outcomes of the shift away from a force-based order to one set around rules and laws. The upshot is that liberalism encourages interdependence between states. Indeed, frameworks such as the Montevideo Convention (1934) allow states to enter proactive diplomatic relations with other one another based on their adherence to a seeming level playing field. For example, Article 1 of Montevideo frames that to be a state, there is a need to be "(a) a permanent population; (b) a defined territory; (c) government; and (d) capacity to enter into relations with other states" (Montevideo Convention, 1934). These conditions represent as the fundamentals of the state, as prescribed by the declaratory school of statehood (Grant, 1999). These are the four targets that secessionist movements must hit for a secessionist event to take place, at least in terms of politico-legal de facto status (Kreijen, 2004; UN, 2006; Michalowski, 2016).

The liberalist frameworks reviewed here grew out of the elevation of self-determination as a political ideal, particularly those of Woodrow Wilson that placed human rights at the forefront of an international commitment to reform the social contract. There is little doubt that the mass exterminations during WW2 consolidated human rights thinking which act as a cornerstone of the UN Charter (Hopkins, 2000; Zimmerman, 2006; Blatman, 2014). The belief is that the imperial mindset was a factor in industrial-scale murder combined with the idea that international regulation could have prevented such gross excesses. This was an issue that was not lost on Buchanan (1997) who had rightly asserted that the reformation of the international legal system gave strength to the idea of self-determination as a right. For Buchanan (1997) the upshot was that this was how territorial transitions from Imperial governance to independence could be justified. What we are talking about here is his idea of remedial rights which, we should note, is Buchanan's only justification for secession. He was largely anti-secession and railed against a primary right to secede. Buccheit (1978) had also referred to remedial rights. His argument was that any remedial right to secede rested solely on the nature of the social contract between state and society.

However, the evolution of the post 1945 international legal system has not been perfect. Starkey (1965) noted early on the potential for loopholes being built into the system that allowed states to usurp or bend international law to their favour. The basis for that claim is one that Buchanan (1997) had also touched upon. He stated that Article 1 of the UN Charter (1945) had been written as a narrow interpretation of international practice. This was problematic he argued, because what it meant was that international law had arbitrarily limited self-determination to the colonial context. He continued that “international law does not recognise a right to secede in other circumstances, but that it does not unequivocally prohibit it either” (Buchanan, 1997: 33). Yet at the same time the real world sees calls to secede tending “to have international consequences that call for international responses” (Buchanan, 1997: 33).

The years following 1945 have seen the international system expand in structural terms. Bodies such as the International Courts of Justice (ICJ) and the UNSC have emerged to boast unrivalled international clout in terms of the regulation of inter-state relations (Greig, 1970; Wolfrum, 2007; Beeson, 2010). What this tells us is that international practices no longer revolve exclusively around what states are able to accomplish by power alone. Wolfrum (2007) argues that the presence of organisations and bodies such as these are a factor in this regulation. However, we are minded that given the loopholes, any limitations placed on states by the international community can only really go so far because international law is made by states, for states. Realism remains a powerful explanatory theory for many of the larger dynamics in international relations.

4.3: realism

In the medieval era man was viewed as being “asocial” and was willing to “trample on reason and logic in order to secure for himself immediate, momentary advantage” (Schmitt, 1996: 36). Schmitt continues that “the more dangerously this asocial individualism asserts itself, the stronger becomes the rational necessity for reaching a general peace” (1996: 36). This Hobbesian perspective on humanity views each and every one of us to be primal, regardless of wealth or strength (Wolff, 1990; Boitani and Torti, 1999; Mearsheimer, 2001). It’s a view straight out of the Machiavellian playbook where equilibrium is achieved through “compulsion” and an impression of the masses being pressured from above by a higher force (Schmitt, 1996: 36). In *The Prince*, Machiavelli argued that the possession of power is characterised through its wielding. “Since there cannot be good laws without good arms”, he argued “I will not consider laws but speak of arms” (2017: CW 47). Machiavelli asserted that state coercion is the basis for legality. Having acquired sovereignty, the purpose of the political actor is to ensure the perpetual retention of power. Sovereignty is practiced through supreme and absolute authority of a kind not unlike the olden Divine Rights of Kings (Philpott, 2016) (see chapter four), and as evidenced in the earlier discussion on Akkad, Ionia, and in Rome. Machiavelli was led to conclude that fear is always preferable to affection in subjects, just as violence and deception are superior to legality in effectively controlling them (2017: CW 47). What results is a socio-political hierarchy with the sovereign at the helm (Wolff, 1990; Boitani and Torti, 1999). Perspectives and practices of this type lead to the idea that states have a right to command and expect obedience (Wolff, 1990: 20; Boitani and Torti, 1999; Baylis and Smith, 2001; Mearsheimer, 2001; Lake, 2003). The success of government, from this perspective, is dependent upon how power is applied over society in order to encourage obedience and once this condition is achieved, it is possible for the state to retain its position of primacy. And in a hat-tip to Machiavelli,

Morgenthau summed realism up in a very simple way; “power positions do not yield to arguments, however rationally and morally valid, but only to superior power” (1978: 7).

Realists would argue that state sovereignty holds the international system together (Baylis and Smith, 2001; Walt, 1998; Krishna-Hensel, 2013). The presence of anarchy in the international system means there is no higher authority than the state and there is nothing to stop states simultaneously holding or advancing policies that are completely contradictory to one another. For example, the UK holds different positions on the secessionist events in both Kosovo and Crimea (HM Government, 2009; UK Government, 2018). The associating issue is Russia and the intention of the UK to act out of self-interest through seeking to undermine the international standing of the Russians. At the same time, Russia’s refusal to recognise an independent Kosovo means that UN and, consequentially, EU membership remain out of reach. Kosovar independence is unique in that it has been adjudged legal under international law, as per a recent ICJ ruling (HM Government, 2009). This is the effect of the state acting in its own interests. This is realism, and it is perfectly legal. Whether the (parent) state survives or not should be irrelevant. The overall assessment that can be made here is that the international system is a configuration of self-interested and highly competitive actors (Baylis and Smith, 2001; Mearsheimer, 2001; Lake, 2003; Kissinger, 2014). Realist theorists further argue that states are the authors of their own destiny. They can never rely on no-one but themselves for their existence (Baylis and Smith, 2001; Mearsheimer, 2001). However, the effect of the secessionist precipitancy is that the state becomes wholly reliant on its peers for its existence, as per constitutive recognition, and this is an occasion where realism is yet to account for any meaningful way. Clearly, as an explanatory framework for international relations, realism has its limits.

Appendix 5: process tracing

5.1: ten rules of process tracing

This section draws largely from the works of Bennett and Checkel (2012) which sets out ten rules that need to be adhered to in order to undertake an efficient process traced investigation.

The first step is the need to cast widely in seeking out any alternate explanations for how X became Y. Failure to do so will leave the research findings open to arguments that they are unconvincing. Step two is the need to be equally tough in assessing alternative inferences and explanations. In reference to this present research, the alternative explanations for each casual step were identified in chapter one and built into the conceptual framework found in chapter three. In practical terms what this means is that where the investigation indicates, argument hegemony as the dominant statecraft lever, due diligence requires further assessments of the evidence relating to the other four alternatives so to rule them out or as has already been indicated, acknowledge primacy for an alternate lever contrary to the original estimation. The same goes with the third step of a good standard for process tracing: it requires the researcher to indicate that an alternative explanation for an inference can be just as valid as the one opted for in the research. The investigations for this thesis relied on hoop tests to assess against this eventuality (these have been explained in more detail in chapter four). Bennett and Checkel also call for consideration that evidence gather will contain biases (2012: 28). They point out that social psychologists have noted that individuals who argue contrary to their own ideology or political perspective are viewed favourably. This insight is important given that the subjects in this research were elected politicians for whom statecraft, whether borne of the national, party, or personal interest, presents as an important shaper in the means, motives, and opportunities for action. As such, this research has already recognised that we can never truly know the rationale behind political action or rhetoric.

Table 58: ten rules

1	Cast the net widely for alternative explanations
2	Be equally tough on the alternative explanations
3	Consider the potential biases of evidentiary sources
4	Take into account whether the case is most or least likely for alternative explanations
5	Make a justifiable decision on when to start
6	Be relentless in gathering diverse and relevant evidence, but make a justifiable decision on when to stop
7	Combine process tracing with case comparisons when useful for the research goal and feasible
8	Be open to inductive insights
9	Use deduction to ask, “if my explanation is true, what will be the specific process leading to the outcome?”
10	Remember that conclusive process tracing is good, but not all good process tracing is conclusive

A further indicator of good practice is to be clear about choosing and justifying a starting point for the investigation. Bennett and Checkel (2012: 30) use the Cuban missile crisis as an example. Would an investigation there be timed to start when it was learned of the Soviet deployment, or should it begin further back in time to the Russian Revolution (Bennett and Checkel, 2012). The same applies when a decision is made about where the research stops. In

the case of this research, the investigations begin on the 25th of January 1978 and end on the 14th of May 2013. As is indicated in the next section, these dates mark the timing of events that were deemed to have moved Scotland's secessionist impulse in the comparative framework of secession (Wood, 1981). A beneficial consequence this approach has upon the investigations is that it can help identify pertinent and worthwhile supporting evidence (Bennett and Checkel, 2012). The substance of this research is the investigations revolving around three legislative debates supported by additional insights found in political diaries and other first-hand accounts of the events at the time. Although this research lacks triangulation, it does contain two investigations. The first, as explained, concerns the application of statecraft levers and their usage within legislative debates in the UK and Scottish parliaments. A second investigation sought to consider how these same debates were narrated and portrayed in the print media. Again, this aspect of the thesis is explained in the next section. A further limitation in undertaking an effective process tracing practice was the inability of this research to combine process tracing with case comparisons, as per Bennett and Checkel's guide. Certainly, that was the case with the investigative explanations found in chapters five, six, and seven. Chapter eight, however, analyses the results of the investigations and it is there where case comparisons are found. Bennett and Checkel's (2012) last two points on operating process tracing to a good standard lies in the need to combine both inductive and deductive reasoning - inductive in terms of the insights offered by the evidence and deductive when affirming a causal inference. A last point of note lies in the caveat that "conclusive process tracing is good, but not all good process tracing is conclusive" (Bennett and Checkel, 2012: 35) - applying these ten points for good process tracing helps address this issue.

Bennett and Checkel's (2012) caveat to their good practice model is a reminder to research practitioners that process tracing is only a tool for building theory or testing it. Success in offering causal inference does not mean accuracy in how or why an event occurred, or why X became Y. As such, process tracing only offers one of a number of possible reasons for change. As such, process tracing does not equate to absolutism and does little to address the failure of the social sciences in creating cumulative theories. The points for good practice aside, Bennett and Checkel (2012) argue that more work is needed to expand upon the usage of process tracing into other research models for gathering evidence. Included in this low uptake is discourse analysis of which George and Bennett (2004: 6) suggest are archival documents and interview transcripts which have been largely ignored by process tracers. In this study, process tracing was used to interrogate multi-person transcripts; but unlike discourse analysis, this research limited its investigative analysis the underlying intent of politicians based on the topics of conversation. There was no attempt to infer meaning from the quirks of the spoken work. In its simplest terms this research was investigating what a group of people said to one another during a discussion, as a way for making inference with regard the underlying meanings.

5.2: ten steps for process tracing multi-person transcripts

Deconstruct: break down the multi-person transcript into a series of individual files, one for each speaker and which contains all their contributions. The result should be a series of individual files, one for each speaker.

Code: in isolation of the others, each separate file undergoes a line-by-line coding exercise. undertake as many coding runs as necessary so to achieve the required data sets or depths.

Reconstruct: once all the files have been coded, the transcript can be rebuilt. The intention is to highlight an alternative narrative, not immediately identifiable from the original structure.

Refine: due diligence requires that the codes are reviewed. This step acts involves the active interaction with the codes, in line with an evolving observable manifestation.

Reconstruct: rebuild the transcript in line with the observable manifestations.

Identify the human terrain: look for patterns in human behaviour, i.e., grouping, associations, collaborations et al. This step can also include the numbers in the data - i.e., the numerical advantage of one group over another. Log this data.

Gather evidence: the data is interrogated for its utility as observable evidence for a causal framework. A cohesive and coherent data set is the intended outcome. It is beneficial to use software for this task.

Create causal framework: the causal framework is the crux of the research. It is made up of the observable manifestations and involves further interaction with the literature as a way for explaining and justifying the causal framework.

Create tests: the tests determines whether or not the evidence as presented, is sufficient or necessary for confirming the causal framework. Four tests are available - straw-in-the-wind; smoking gun; doubly decisive. This thesis the fourth, hoop tests, given their inherent ability for building an evidence-based narrative.

Analyse: each step of the causal framework is subject to four closed questions. It is against these questions the evidence is tested and can culminate in four answers - Yes/No/insufficient evidence/unknown. These answers confirm either the causal framework or lead to a new causal inference.

Figure 31: interrogating multi-person transcripts

5.3: process tracing in figures

Figure 32: identify X and Y

Figure 33: locate the black box

Figure 34: theory building map

(Source: Beach, 2012: 21)

Appendix 6: CA1

6.1: 1978 human terrain

Table 59: 1978 debate attendees

(Numbers do not include the Chair or Deputy Chair)

Party	No.	Country	No.	Party	England	Scotland	Wales
Conservative	11	England	12	Conservative	9	2	
Government	1	Scotland	12	Government		1	
Labour	11	Wales	2	Labour	3	6	2
SLP	1			SLP		1	
SNP	2			SNP		2	
Total	26		26		12	12	2

Table 60: 1978 MPs supporting the Amendment

For	No.	Party	England	Scotland	Wales
Conservative	3	Conservative	3		
Labour	6	Labour	1	4	1
Total	9		4	4	1

Table 61: 1978 MPs opposed to the Amendment

Against	No.	Country	No.	Party	England	Scotland
Conservative	1	Scotland	2	Conservative	1	
SLP	1	England	1	SLP		1
SNP	1			SNP		1
Total	3		3		1	2

Table 62: 1978 top contributors

(Numbers do not include the Chair or Deputy Chair)

Ringleaders	Country	Share of the debate
Amery (Con)	England	3.5%
Buchan (Lab)	Scotland	8%
Cook (Lab)	Scotland	10%
Cunningham (Lab)	England	12%
Evans (Lab)	Wales	3%
Hamilton (Lab)	Scotland	11.5%
Hughes (Lab)	Scotland	12.5%
Macmillan (Con)	England	3.5%
Pym (Con)	England	5.5%
Total		69.5%

6.2: 1978 scorecard

Coded content	F 1	F 2	F 3	F 4	F 5	F 6	F 7	F 8	F 9	F 10	F 11	F 12	F 13	F 14	F 15	F 16	Total
parliamentary supremacy	21	21	24	7	-	29	50	9	-	1	-	2	-	-	1	1	166
merits of a threshold	11	16	17	1	-	9	26	3	-	3	-	4	-	-	-	1	91
turnout	8	5	14	-	-	1	17	2	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	2	52
Scotland v. UK-wide vote	4	-	15	-	-	8	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	32
rules for referendums	6	4	6	-	-	2	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	25
Scottish independence	1	-	3	-	-	-	5	-	-	1	-	10	-	-	2	1	23
previous elections	-	2	-	-	-	-	14	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	18
irrevocability	2	-	1	-	-	-	4	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	9
experience of other states	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other content																	
guillotine	16	17	6	6	-	10	13	2	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	71
Orkney & Shetland	13	5	7	4	-	11	8	1	-	2	-	2	-	-	1	-	44
referendums	-	2	4	-	-	-	6	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	13
Michael Foot	1	3	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	10
lack of interest	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	5	1	9
primordialism	-	-	-	-	-	1	6	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9
book plug	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	8
terrorism	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	5
UK constitution	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4
cost	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	3
civil unrest	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	3
oil	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	3
World Cup	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	3
anti-Scottish sentiment	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
criticism of Cunningham	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1
electoral administration	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Kenny Dalglish	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
minority government	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
military deployment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
threshold reversal	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
two-question ballot	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
UN peacekeepers	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
West Lothian question	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
Levers																	
argument hegemony	39	17	44	6	-	41	73	10	-	2	-	4	-	-	8	6	250
governing competence	32	35	20	9	-	19	18	7	-	3	-	5	-	-	4	2	154
electoral strategy	12	17	16	-	-	16	35	6	-	5	-	14	-	-	-	3	124
party management	12	16	14	1	-	14	7	2	-	-	-	6	-	-	4	-	76
bending the rules	10	4	4	2	-	11	11	1	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	2	47
Posture																	
anti-devolution	31	31	45	4	-	37	48	11	-	5	-	5	-	-	9	4	230
pro-devolution	16	14	8	1	-	13	15	7	-	2	-	2	-	-	-	2	80

6.3: 1978 NVivo results

6.3.1: MP results

⊕ Name	↔ Codes	References
📄 Cunningham	14	106
📄 Government	11	95
📄 Cook	12	94
📄 Sillars	12	89
📄 Pym	14	78
📄 Wilson	12	75
📄 Hughes	12	51
📄 Buchan	14	50
📄 Amery	13	49
📄 Knox	13	44
📄 Hamilton	13	44
📄 Evans	14	40
📄 Macmillan	10	40
📄 Gardiner	11	32
📄 Canavan	11	29
📄 Sproat	10	20
📄 Dalyell	8	12
📄 Raison	7	11
📄 Braine	5	7
📄 Couch	6	6
📄 Taylor	5	5
📄 Mr. Douglas-Mann	4	4
📄 Heffer	3	3
📄 Crawford	3	3
📄 Higgins	3	3
📄 abse	2	2

6.3.2: coding results

<input checked="" type="radio"/> Name	Files	References
<input type="radio"/> AH	22	189
<input type="radio"/> ES	22	131
<input type="radio"/> parliamentary supremacy	17	108
<input type="radio"/> merits of threshold	21	98
<input type="radio"/> BtR	17	83
<input type="radio"/> Basic rules	17	80
<input type="radio"/> GC	18	65
<input type="radio"/> Influence from previous ref.	15	59
<input type="radio"/> turnout predictions	16	50
<input type="radio"/> Scottish independence	12	31
<input type="radio"/> PM	11	26
<input type="radio"/> Irrevocability	10	21
<input type="radio"/> Scotand v UK vote	8	13
<input type="radio"/> Other states	10	12

6.3.3: 1978 evidence

E1: backbench contributors

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Cunningham	105	13
Files\Cook	93	11
Files\Sillars	88	11
Files\Pym	77	13
Files\Wilson	74	11
Files\Hughes	50	11
Files\Buchan	49	13
Files\Amery	48	12
Files\Hamilton	43	12
Files\Knox	43	12
Files\Evans	39	13
Files\Macmillan	39	9
Files\Gardiner	31	10
Files\Canavan	28	10
Files\Sproat	19	9
Files\Dalyell	11	7
Files\Raison	10	6
Files\Braine	6	4
Files\Couch	5	5
Files\Taylor	4	4
Files\Mr. Douglas-Mann	3	3
Files\Crawford	2	2
Files\Heffer	2	2
Files\Higgins	2	2
Files\abse	1	1

E2: backbench statecraft

Codes	Number of coding referenc	Aggregate number of coding reference	Number of items code	Aggregate number of items code
Codes\AH	167	167	21	21
Codes\ES	124	124	21	21
Codes\BtR	65	65	16	16
Codes\GC	60	60	17	17
Codes\PM	25	25	10	10

E3: pro-government statecraft

Codes	Number of coding referenc	Aggregate number of coding reference	Number of items code	Aggregate number of items code
Codes\AH	167	167	21	21
Codes\ES	124	124	21	21
Codes\BtR	65	65	16	16
Codes\GC	60	60	17	17
Codes\PM	25	25	10	10

E4: backbench debating points

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\parliamentary supremacy	99	99	16	16
Codes\merits of threshold	88	88	20	20
Codes\Basic rules	70	70	16	16
Codes\turnout predictions	49	49	15	15
Codes\Influence from previous ref.	48	48	14	14
Codes\Scottish independence	31	31	12	12
Codes\Irrevocability	21	21	10	10
Codes\Scotland v UK vote	13	13	8	8
Codes\Other states	12	12	10	10

E5: pro-government debating points

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Basic rules	31	31	5	5
Codes\parliamentary supremacy	31	31	5	5
Codes\Influence from previous ref.	24	24	5	5
Codes\merits of threshold	24	24	5	5
Codes\turnout predictions	16	16	5	5
Codes\Other states	3	3	2	2
Codes\Scottish independence	3	3	2	2
Codes\Irrevocability	2	2	1	1
Codes\Scotland v UK vote	1	1	1	1

E6: government statecraft

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\AH	22	22	1	1
Codes\BTR	18	18	1	1
Codes\ES	7	7	1	1
Codes\GC	5	5	1	1
Codes\PM	1	1	1	1

E7: ringleader statecraft

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\AH	103	103	9	9
Codes\ES	75	75	9	9
Codes\GC	42	42	9	9
Codes\BtR	22	22	6	6
Codes\PM	16	16	7	7

E8: government debating points

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Influence from previous ref.	11	11	1	1
Codes\Basic rules	10	10	1	1
Codes\merits of threshold	10	10	1	1
Codes\parliamentary supremacy	9	9	1	1
Codes\turnout predictions	1	1	1	1

E9: ringleader debating points

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\parliamentary supremacy	67	67	9	9
Codes\merits of threshold	61	61	9	9
Codes\Basic rules	42	42	7	7
Codes\Influence from previous ref.	30	30	7	7
Codes\turnout predictions	28	28	8	8
Codes\Scottish independence	23	23	8	8
Codes\Irrevocability	15	15	6	6
Codes\Scotand v UK vote	12	12	7	7
Codes\Other states	7	7	6	6

E10: statecraft (whole debate)

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\AH	189	189	22	22
Codes\ES	131	131	22	22
Codes\BtR	83	83	17	17
Codes\GC	65	65	18	18
Codes\PM	26	26	11	11

E11: basic rules

Files	Number of coding references	▼ Number of codes coding
Files\Cook	15	1
Files\Sillars	11	1
Files\Government	10	1
Files\Pym	10	1
Files\Cunningham	9	1
Files\Wilson	6	1
Files\Evans	4	1
Files\Canavan	3	1
Files\Gardiner	3	1
Files\Hamilton	2	1
Files\Amery	1	1
Files\Buchan	1	1
Files\Couch	1	1
Files\Dalyell	1	1
Files\Knox	1	1
Files\Raison	1	1
Files\Taylor	1	1

E12: turnout

Files	Number of coding references	▼ Number of codes coding
Files\Sillars	8	1
Files\Cook	6	1
Files\Cunningham	6	1
Files\Evans	4	1
Files\Hamilton	4	1
Files\Buchan	3	1
Files\Gardiner	3	1
Files\Hughes	3	1
Files\Knox	3	1
Files\Canavan	2	1
Files\Sproat	2	1
Files\Wilson	2	1
Files\Amery	1	1
Files\Dalyell	1	1
Files\Government	1	1
Files\Pym	1	1

E13: Scotland v. UK vote

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Cunningham	4	1
Files\Buchan	2	1
Files\Macmillan	2	1
Files\Amery	1	1
Files\Evans	1	1
Files\Hughes	1	1
Files\Pym	1	1
Files\Wilson	1	1

E14:influence of previous referendums

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Cunningham	11	1
Files\Government	11	1
Files\Sillars	9	1
Files\Cook	8	1
Files\Pym	4	1
Files\Evans	3	1
Files\Amery	2	1
Files\Braine	2	1
Files\Canavan	2	1
Files\Sproat	2	1
Files\Buchan	1	1
Files\Gardiner	1	1
Files\Knox	1	1
Files\Macmillan	1	1
Files\Wilson	1	1

E15: merits of threshold

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Cunningham	12	1
Files\Government	10	1
Files\Hughes	9	1
Files\Pym	9	1
Files\Cook	8	1
Files\Macmillan	8	1
Files\Amery	6	1
Files\Knox	6	1
Files\Gardiner	5	1
Files\Hamilton	5	1
Files\Sillars	4	1
Files\Buchan	3	1
Files\Canavan	3	1
Files\Sproat	3	1
Files\Couch	1	1
Files\Dalyell	1	1
Files\Evans	1	1
Files\Mr. Douglas-Mann	1	1
Files\Raison	1	1
Files\Taylor	1	1
Files\Wilson	1	1

E16: backbench electioneering

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\merits of threshold	88	88	20	20
Codes\Basic rules	70	70	16	16
Codes\turnout predictions	49	49	15	15
Codes\Influence from previous ref.	48	48	14	14
Codes\Scotland v UK vote	13	13	8	8

E17: pro-government electioneering

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Basic rules	31	31	5	5
Codes\Influence from previous ref.	24	24	5	5
Codes\merits of threshold	24	24	5	5
Codes\turnout predictions	16	16	5	5
Codes\Scotland v UK vote	1	1	1	1

E18: ringleader electioneering

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\merits of threshold	61	61	9	9
Codes\Basic rules	42	42	7	7
Codes\Influence from previous ref.	30	30	7	7
Codes\turnout predictions	28	28	8	8
Codes\Scotland v UK vote	12	12	7	7

E19: government electioneering

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Influence from previous ref.	11	11	1	1
Codes\Basic rules	10	10	1	1
Codes\merits of threshold	10	10	1	1
Codes\turnout predictions	1	1	1	1

E20: electioneering

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\merits of threshold	98	98	21	21
Codes\Basic rules	80	80	17	17
Codes\Influence from previous ref.	59	59	15	15
Codes\turnout predictions	50	50	16	16
Codes\Scotland v UK vote	13	13	8	8

E21: merits v. basic rules

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\merits of threshold	98	98	21	21
Codes\Basic rules	80	80	17	17

E22: backbenchers

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Irrevocability	21	21	10	10
Codes\Scottish independence	31	31	12	12

E23: pro-government

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\\Irrevocability	2	2	1	1
Codes\\Scottish independence	3	3	2	2

E24: ringleaders

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\\Scottish independence	23	23	8	8
Codes\\Irrevocability	15	15	6	6

E25: John Smith

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
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E26: experience of other states

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\\Amery	2	1
Files\\Sillars	2	1
Files\\Buchan	1	1
Files\\Cook	1	1
Files\\Dalyell	1	1
Files\\Evans	1	1
Files\\Gardiner	1	1
Files\\Hamilton	1	1
Files\\Knox	1	1
Files\\Pym	1	1

E27: Scottish independence/ irrevocability

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\\Scottish independence	31	31	12	12
Codes\\Irrevocability	21	21	10	10

E28: Scottish independence

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\\Amery	4	1
Files\\Braine	2	1
Files\\Buchan	5	1
Files\\Canavan	1	1
Files\\Cook	5	1
Files\\Cunningham	4	1
Files\\Evans	1	1
Files\\Hamilton	1	1
Files\\Hughes	2	1
Files\\Knox	2	1
Files\\Macmillan	1	1
Files\\Sproat	3	1

E29: irrevocability

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Macmillan	5	1
Files\Cunningham	3	1
Files\Pym	3	1
Files\Amery	2	1
Files\Knox	2	1
Files\Sproat	2	1
Files\Braine	1	1
Files\Dalyell	1	1
Files\Hamilton	1	1
Files\Hughes	1	1

Appendix 7: CA2

7.1: 1997 human terrain

Table 63: 1997 contributor by party and country
(Percentage share does not include the Speaker)

Party	Number	Country
Conservatives	9	England
Labour	6	Scotland
LibDems	3	Scotland
SNP	2	Scotland
Total	20	11/9 Scottish majority

Table 64: 1997 word share by party and country
(Percentage share does not include the Speaker)

	% Share
Conservatives	58
Labour	30
LibDems	10
SNP	1
Total	99
England	58
Scotland	41

7.2: 1997 scorecard

Coded content	G 1	G 2	G 3	G 4	G 5	G 6	G 7	G 8	G 9	G 10	G 11	G 12	G 13	G 14	G 15	G 16	Total
Parliamentary supremacy	8	4	8	-	-	11	15	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	47
Scotland-only vote	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11
UK-wide vote	1	-	1	1	-	5	1	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	14
Scottish exceptionalism	1	2	-	-	-	3	-	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10
English exceptionalism	-	2	1	-	-	3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7
threshold	-	-	1	-	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	5
service personnel	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
cost	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
other states	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Scottish independence	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
GERS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Kilbrandon	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
EVEL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
previous elections	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other content																	
guillotine	17	3	10	1	-	19	12	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	65
performative politics	7	1	2	1	-	17	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	34
tyranny	9	1	4	-	-	5	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	27
Scottish diaspora	2	1	-	-	-	5	2	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	15
constitutional change	-	1	7	-	-	3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12
Gary McAllister	1	-	-	-	-	3	1	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	12
Parliamentary protocols	4	-	1	-	-	1	2	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10
two question referendum	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	6
Conservative thinktank	1	-	-	-	-	2	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	5
mass Amendments	-	-	2	1	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5
pre-leg. referendum	-	-	3	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5
West Lothian question	2	-	-	-	-	2	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5
Donald Dewar	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	4
mandate	-	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4
Scotland Bill (1978)	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3
Anglo-Scots MPs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1
taxation	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	4
opinion polling	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
House of Lords	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Michael Howard	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Bill Cash	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
poll tax	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
referendums	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Levers																	
argument hegemony	27	9	9	-	-	32	27	16	-	-	-	-	-	-	9	-	129
governing competence	10	2	10	1	-	14	9	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	55
party management	8	-	2	-	-	6	3	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	25
electoral strategy	1	-	-	-	-	2	2	16	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	23
Posture																	

anti-devolution	8	2	1	-	-	17	13	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	11	-	56
pro-devolution	2	4	2	1	-	10	3	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	32

7.3: 1997 NVivo results

7.3.1: MP results

⊕ Name	↔ Codes	▼ References
📄 Cash	13	84
📄 MacLennan	13	43
📄 Howard	12	52
📄 McAllion	12	55
📄 Jenkin	11	31
📄 McLeish	11	78
📄 Heathcoat-Amory	10	31
📄 Dalyell	9	19
📄 Fallon	9	35
📄 Luff	9	45
📄 Garnier	6	18
📄 Salmond	6	8
📄 Grieve	5	5
📄 Smith	5	6
📄 Wallace	5	6
📄 Ewing	4	4
📄 Canavan	3	3
📄 Maxton	3	3
📄 Godman	2	2
📄 Maude	1	1

7.3.2: coding results

| References |
|--|---|--|
| <input type="radio"/> AH | 17 | 99 |
| <input type="radio"/> ES | 17 | 71 |
| <input type="radio"/> Parliamentary supremacy | 13 | 80 |
| <input type="radio"/> Scotland only | 13 | 41 |
| <input type="radio"/> Uk wide franchise | 12 | 54 |
| <input type="radio"/> GC | 12 | 51 |
| <input type="radio"/> PM | 9 | 20 |
| <input type="radio"/> EVEL | 7 | 11 |
| <input type="radio"/> English exceptionalism | 7 | 22 |
| <input type="radio"/> Kilbrandon | 7 | 12 |
| <input type="radio"/> Scottish independence | 7 | 8 |
| <input type="radio"/> Europe | 6 | 13 |
| <input type="radio"/> Service personnel | 5 | 15 |
| <input type="radio"/> Cost | 4 | 5 |
| <input type="radio"/> Scottish exceptionalism | 4 | 12 |
| <input type="radio"/> threshold | 3 | 5 |
| <input type="radio"/> GERS | 3 | 5 |
| <input type="radio"/> Previous referendums | 3 | 5 |

7.3.3: 1997 evidence

E30: whole debate (statecraft)

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\AH	99	99	17	17
Codes\ES	71	71	17	17
Codes\GC	51	51	12	12
Codes\PM	20	20	9	9

E31: whole debate (by topic)

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Parliamentary supremacy	80	80	13	13
Codes\Uk wide franchise	54	54	12	12
Codes\Scotland only	41	41	13	13
Codes\English exceptionalism	22	22	7	7
Codes\Service personnel	15	15	5	5
Codes\Europe	13	13	6	6
Codes\Kilbrandon	12	12	7	7
Codes\Scottish exceptionalism	12	12	4	4
Codes\EVEL	11	11	7	7
Codes\Scottish independence	8	8	7	7
Codes\Cost	5	5	4	4
Codes\GERS	5	5	3	3
Codes\Previous referendums	5	5	3	3
Codes\threshold	5	5	3	3

E32: Conservatives (share by Member)

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Cash	49	9
Files\Howard	29	8
Files\Luff	23	6
Files\Heathcoat-Amory	19	7
Files\Fallon	18	5
Files\Jenkin	18	7
Files\Garnier	11	4
Files\Grieve	4	4

E33: Conservative statecraft

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\AH	62	62	8	8
Codes\ES	37	37	7	7
Codes\GC	22	22	6	6
Codes\PM	10	10	5	5

E34: English exceptionalism

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Heathcoat-Amory	5	1
Files\Luff	5	1
Files\Cash	4	1
Files\McAllion	4	1
Files\Jenkin	2	1
Files\Dalyell	1	1
Files\Maclennan	1	1

E35: Cash

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Parliamentary supremacy	17	17	1	1
Codes\Uk wide franchise	10	10	1	1
Codes\Europe	5	5	1	1
Codes\EVEL	5	5	1	1
Codes\English exceptionalism	4	4	1	1
Codes\Kilbrandon	4	4	1	1
Codes\threshold	2	2	1	1
Codes\Cost	1	1	1	1
Codes\Scottish independence	1	1	1	1

E36: Conservatives (by topic)

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Parliamentary supremacy	51	51	8	8
Codes\Uk wide franchise	44	44	8	8
Codes\English exceptionalism	16	16	4	4
Codes\Europe	10	10	4	4
Codes\Scotland only	10	10	4	4
Codes\EVEL	9	9	5	5
Codes\Kilbrandon	8	8	4	4
Codes\Service personnel	8	8	3	3
Codes\GERS	3	3	2	2
Codes\Previous referendums	3	3	1	1
Codes\Scottish independence	3	3	3	3
Codes\Cost	2	2	2	2
Codes\Scottish exceptionalism	2	2	1	1
Codes\threshold	2	2	1	1

E37: Scottish exceptionalism

Files	Number of coding references	▼ Number of codes coding
Files\McAllion	6	1
Files\Jenkin	2	1
Files\Maclennan	2	1
Files\Salmond	2	1

38: electoral strategy

Files	Number of coding references	▼ Number of codes coding
Files\Luff	11	1
Files\Fallon	7	1
Files\Howard	7	1
Files\Cash	4	1
Files\Jenkin	4	1
Files\Garnier	3	1
Files\Heathcoat-Amory	1	1

39: Scottish exceptionalism (Conservative)

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Jenkin	2	1

E40: Europe (whole debate)

Files	Number of coding references	▼ Number of codes coding
Files\Cash	5	1
Files\Garnier	3	1
Files\McLeish	2	1
Files\Fallon	1	1
Files\Howard	1	1
Files\Salmond	1	1

E41: English v Scottish exceptionalism

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\English exceptionalism	22	22	7	7
Codes\Scottish exceptionalism	12	12	4	4

E42: cost (Conservative)

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Cash	1	1
Files\Heathcoat-Amory	1	1

E43: Europe (Conservative)

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Cash	5	1
Files\Garnier	3	1
Files\Fallon	1	1
Files\Howard	1	1

E44: EVEL (Conservative)

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Cash	5	1
Files\Grieve	1	1
Files\Heathcoat-Amory	1	1
Files\Howard	1	1
Files\Luff	1	1

E45: UK-wide franchise (Conservative)

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Cash	10	1
Files\Howard	10	1
Files\Luff	8	1
Files\Fallon	7	1
Files\Garnier	3	1
Files\Jenkin	3	1
Files\Heathcoat-Amory	2	1
Files\Grieve	1	1

E46: parliamentary supremacy (Conservative)

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Cash	17	1
Files\Howard	10	1
Files\Heathcoat-Amory	6	1
Files\Jenkin	6	1
Files\Luff	6	1
Files\Garnier	3	1
Files\Fallon	2	1
Files\Grieve	1	1

E47: previous referendums (Conservative)

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Fallon	3	1

E48: Scotland only (Conservative)

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Howard	4	1
Files\Garnier	2	1
Files\Jenkin	2	1
Files\Luff	2	1

E49: threshold (Conservative)

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Cash	2	1

E50: Scottish independence (Conservative)

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Cash	1	1
Files\Grieve	1	1
Files\Jenkin	1	1

E51: service personnel (Conservative)

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Fallon	5	1
Files\Jenkin	2	1
Files\Howard	1	1

E52: whole debate

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\AH	99	99	17	17
Codes\ES	71	71	17	17
Codes\GC	51	51	12	12
Codes\PM	20	20	9	9

E53: Kilbrandon

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Cash	4	1
Files\Heathcoat-Amory	2	1
Files\Howard	1	1
Files\Luff	1	1

E54: Maude

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
-------	-----------------------------	---------------------------------------	-----------------------	---------------------------------

E55: Howard

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Parliamentary supremacy	10	10	1	1
Codes\Uk wide franchise	10	10	1	1
Codes\Scotland only	4	4	1	1
Codes\Europe	1	1	1	1
Codes\EVEL	1	1	1	1
Codes\GERS	1	1	1	1
Codes\Kilbrandon	1	1	1	1
Codes\Service personnel	1	1	1	1

E56: Luff

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\\Uk wide franchi	8	8	1	1
Codes\\Parliamentary s	6	6	1	1
Codes\\English excepti	5	5	1	1
Codes\\Scotland only	2	2	1	1
Codes\\EVEL	1	1	1	1
Codes\\Kilbrandon	1	1	1	1

E57: Heathcoat-Amory

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\\Parliamentary supremacy	6	6	1	1
Codes\\English exceptionalism	5	5	1	1
Codes\\GERS	2	2	1	1
Codes\\Kilbrandon	2	2	1	1
Codes\\Uk wide franchise	2	2	1	1
Codes\\Cost	1	1	1	1
Codes\\EVEL	1	1	1	1

E58: Jenkin

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\\Parliamentary supremacy	6	6	1	1
Codes\\Uk wide franchise	3	3	1	1
Codes\\English exceptionalism	2	2	1	1
Codes\\Scotland only	2	2	1	1
Codes\\Scottish exceptionalism	2	2	1	1
Codes\\Service personnel	2	2	1	1
Codes\\Scottish independence	1	1	1	1

E60: Garnier

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\\Uk wide franchi	7	7	1	1
Codes\\Service person	5	5	1	1
Codes\\Previous refere	3	3	1	1
Codes\\Parliamentary s	2	2	1	1
Codes\\Europe	1	1	1	1

E59: Fallon

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\\Europe	3	3	1	1
Codes\\Parliamentary supremacy	3	3	1	1
Codes\\Scotland only	2	2	1	1
Codes\\Uk wide franchise	3	3	1	1

E61: Grieve

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\\EVEL	1	1	1	1
Codes\\Parliamentary supremacy	1	1	1	1
Codes\\Scottish independence	1	1	1	1
Codes\\Uk wide franchise	1	1	1	1

Appendix 8: SIRFA

8.1: 2013 human terrain

Table 65: 2013 debate population

SNP	Labour	Conservative	LibDems	Greens	Independent	Total
Adam	Eadie	Carlaw	McInnes	Harvie	MacDonald	
Adamson	Ferguson	Goldie	Scott			
Crawford	Findlay					
Doris	McMahon					
Ewing	Kelly					
Fabiani	Pearson					
Gibson	Pentland					
Hepburn						
Lyle						
Mason						
McMillan						
Robertson						
Stevenson						
Sturgeon						
14	7	2	2	1	1	27

(Numbers do not include the Presiding Officer or the SNPs' Dennis Robertson⁷¹)

⁷¹ Robertson had asked to intervene in a speech. This was refused and he did not follow up later on.

8.2: 2013 scorecard

Coded content	H 1	H 2	H 3	H 4	H 5	H 6	H 7	H 8	H 9	H 10	H 11	H 12	H 13	H 14	H 15	H 16	Total
prisoner voting rights	-	-	-	-	-	2	19	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	21
16-18 voting rights	-	-	-	-	-	6	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10
civic Scotland	-	-	-	-	-	5	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7
third sector	-	-	-	-	-	4	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6
political entrepreneurs	-	-	-	-	-	3	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5
Scottish society	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4
education	-	-	-	-	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3
Franchise Bill	-	-	-	-	-	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3
16-18 electoral awareness	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Scotland v. UK wide vote	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16-18 political awareness	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
turnout	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scotland/UK coordination	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ECHR	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
consultative referendums	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
safeguarding	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
experience of other states	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
service personnel	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SEN	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
finance	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
previous elections	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Edinburgh Agreement	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
hard to reach voters	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scottish independence	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other content																	
contract with society	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5
Nicola Sturgeon	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5
Scottish administered	-	-	-	-	-	2	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5
UK election rules	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5
LibDems	-	-	-	-	-	1	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4
Conservatives	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3
propaganda	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3
fundamentalist	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Labour	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
legitimacy	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Margo McDonald	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
political consensus	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Levers																	
argument hegemony	-	-	-	-	-	7	23	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	30
electoral strategy	-	-	-	-	-	5	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6
party management	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
governing competence	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
bending the rules	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Posture																	

anti-Bill	-	-	-	-	-	3	13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	16
pro-Bill	-	-	-	-	-	4	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12

8.3: 2013 NVivo results

8.3.1: MSP results

⊕ Name	⇄ Codes	References
📄 Scottish government	22	135
📄 Patricia Ferguson	20	75
📄 Patrick Harvie	14	59
📄 George Adam	20	57
📄 Jackson Carlaw	13	57
📄 Bruce Crawford	18	50
📄 Rob Gibson	15	43
📄 Annabel Goldie	16	41
📄 Tavish Scott	13	40
📄 Helen Eadie	19	39
📄 James Kelly	13	39
📄 John Pentland	17	38
📄 Linda Fabiani	16	38
📄 Annabelle Ewing	14	35
📄 Margo MacDonald	15	34
📄 Jamie Hepburn	11	33
📄 Richard Lyle	14	33
📄 Stuart McMillan	12	31
📄 Clare Adamson	12	26
📄 Graeme Pearson	13	24
📄 Michael McMahon	10	14
📄 Alison McInnes	6	13
📄 Bob Doris	5	5
📄 John Mason	5	5
📄 Neil Findlay	5	5
📄 Stewart Stevenson	4	4

8.3.2: coding results

⊕ Name	↔ Files	References
○ argument hegemony	24	139
○ Electoral strategy	26	127
○ bending the rules	23	106
○ governing competence	19	73
○ YP voting rights	21	70
○ Prisoner voting rights	19	67
○ Civic Scotland	18	43
○ YP political awareness	16	39
○ Electoral administration	13	28
○ third sector	14	28
○ Independence (bill)	10	28
○ Scottish society	17	27
○ political entrepreneurs	13	23
○ Turnout	10	21
○ Scot-UK co-ordination	10	20
○ ECHR	10	18
○ Consultative referendum	10	17
○ Safeguarding	9	14
○ independence	9	14
○ Service personnel & family	8	13
○ Education	11	13
○ party management	8	12
○ Other states	8	11
○ Finance	2	5
○ SEN access	3	4
○ Soctland v UK vote	3	4
○ Previous elections	4	4
○ hard to reach voters	3	3
○ Edinburgh Agreement	1	2

8.3.3: 2013 evidence

E62: whole debate

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\argument hegemony	139	139	24	24
Codes\Electoral strategy	127	127	26	26
Codes\bending the rules	106	106	23	23
Codes\governing competence	73	73	19	19
Codes\party management	12	12	8	8

E63: debating points

Codes	Number of coding references	▼ Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\YP voting rights	70	70	21	21
Codes\Prisoner voting rights	67	67	19	19
Codes\Civic Scotland	43	43	18	18
Codes\YP political awareness	39	39	16	16
Codes\Electoral administration	28	28	13	13
Codes\Independence (bill)	28	28	10	10
Codes\third sector	28	28	14	14
Codes\Scottish society	27	27	17	17
Codes\political entrepreneurs	23	23	13	13
Codes\Turnout	21	21	10	10
Codes\Scot-UK co-ordination	20	20	10	10
Codes\ECHR	18	18	10	10
Codes\Consultative referendum	17	17	10	10
Codes\independence	14	14	9	9
Codes\Safeguarding	14	14	9	9
Codes\Education	13	13	11	11
Codes\Service personnel & family	13	13	8	8
Codes\Other states	11	11	8	8
Codes\Finance	5	5	2	2
Codes\Previous elections	4	4	4	4
Codes\SEN access	4	4	3	3
Codes\Soctland v UK vote	4	4	3	3
Codes\hard to reach voters	3	3	3	3
Codes\Edinburgh Agreement	2	2	1	1

E64: consultative referendums

Files	Number of coding references	▼ Number of codes coding
Files\Jackson Carlaw	3	1
Files\Patrick Harvie	3	1
Files\Annabel Goldie	2	1
Files\Bruce Crawford	2	1
Files\Scottish government	2	1
Files\George Adam	1	1
Files\Helen Eadie	1	1
Files\John Pentland	1	1
Files\Patricia Ferguson	1	1
Files\Rob Gibson	1	1

E65: governing competence

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\\Scottish government	18	1
Files\\Linda Fabiani	6	1
Files\\Bruce Crawford	5	1
Files\\James Kelly	5	1
Files\\Patricia Ferguson	5	1
Files\\Rob Gibson	5	1
Files\\John Pentland	4	1
Files\\Annabel Goldie	3	1
Files\\Graeme Pearson	3	1
Files\\Margo MacDonald	3	1
Files\\Patrick Harvie	3	1
Files\\Stuart McMillan	3	1
Files\\Tavish Scott	3	1
Files\\George Adam	2	1
Files\\Annabelle Ewing	1	1
Files\\Helen Eadie	1	1
Files\\Michael McMahon	1	1
Files\\Neil Findlay	1	1
Files\\Richard Lyle	1	1

E66: turnout

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\\George Adam	4	1
Files\\Clare Adamson	3	1
Files\\James Kelly	3	1
Files\\John Pentland	3	1
Files\\Jackson Carlaw	2	1
Files\\Margo MacDonald	2	1
Files\\Annabel Goldie	1	1
Files\\Helen Eadie	1	1
Files\\Jamie Hepburn	1	1
Files\\Patrick Harvie	1	1

E67: ECHR

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\\Patrick Harvie	5	1
Files\\Scottish government	4	1
Files\\Annabel Goldie	2	1
Files\\Bruce Crawford	1	1
Files\\George Adam	1	1
Files\\Graeme Pearson	1	1
Files\\Helen Eadie	1	1
Files\\Jackson Carlaw	1	1
Files\\Patricia Ferguson	1	1
Files\\Stewart Stevenson	1	1

E68: Scottish/UK co-ordination

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\\Scottish government	7	1
Files\\Linda Fabiani	3	1
Files\\Annabel Goldie	2	1
Files\\Jamie Hepburn	2	1
Files\\Annabelle Ewing	1	1
Files\\George Adam	1	1
Files\\John Pentland	1	1
Files\\Patricia Ferguson	1	1
Files\\Patrick Harvie	1	1
Files\\Rob Gibson	1	1

E69: argument hegemony

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Scottish government	16	1
Files\Jackson Carlaw	14	1
Files\Patrick Harvie	8	1
Files\Richard Lyle	8	1
Files\Annabel Goldie	7	1
Files\George Adam	7	1
Files\Helen Eadie	7	1
Files\Jamie Hepburn	7	1
Files\John Pentland	7	1
Files\Tavish Scott	7	1
Files\Clare Adamson	6	1
Files\James Kelly	6	1
Files\Margo MacDonald	6	1
Files\Patricia Ferguson	6	1
Files\Annabelle Ewing	5	1
Files\Rob Gibson	4	1
Files\Stuart McMillan	4	1
Files\Alison McInnes	3	1
Files\Graeme Pearson	3	1
Files\Linda Fabiani	3	1
Files\Bruce Crawford	2	1
Files\Michael McMahon	1	1
Files\Neil Findlay	1	1
Files\Stewart Stevenson	1	1

E70: Scotland v UK wide vote

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Helen Eadie	2	1
Files\Jamie Hepburn	1	1
Files\Margo MacDonald	1	1

E71: young person voting rights

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Scottish government	9	1
Files\George Adam	7	1
Files\Jackson Carlaw	7	1
Files\Jamie Hepburn	6	1
Files\Patricia Ferguson	4	1
Files\Annabel Goldie	3	1
Files\Annabelle Ewing	3	1
Files\Clare Adamson	3	1
Files\John Pentland	3	1
Files\Linda Fabiani	3	1
Files\Patrick Harvie	3	1
Files\Richard Lyle	3	1
Files\Bruce Crawford	2	1
Files\Graeme Pearson	2	1
Files\Helen Eadie	2	1
Files\James Kelly	2	1
Files\Margo MacDonald	2	1
Files\Rob Gibson	2	1
Files\Stuart McMillan	2	1
Files\Alison McInnes	1	1
Files\Tavish Scott	1	1

E72: safeguarding

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Patricia Ferguson	3	1
Files\Scottish government	3	1
Files\Linda Fabiani	2	1
Files\George Adam	1	1
Files\Helen Eadie	1	1
Files\James Kelly	1	1
Files\John Pentland	1	1
Files\Margo MacDonald	1	1
Files\Richard Lyle	1	1

E73: prisoner voting rights

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Scottish government	12	1
Files\Patrick Harvie	10	1
Files\Tavish Scott	9	1
Files\James Kelly	5	1
Files\Annabel Goldie	4	1
Files\Patricia Ferguson	4	1
Files\Alison McInnes	3	1
Files\Bruce Crawford	3	1
Files\Jackson Carlaw	3	1
Files\Margo MacDonald	3	1
Files\George Adam	2	1
Files\Helen Eadie	2	1
Files\Annabelle Ewing	1	1
Files\Graeme Pearson	1	1
Files\John Pentland	1	1
Files\Linda Fabiani	1	1
Files\Richard Lyle	1	1
Files\Rob Gibson	1	1
Files\Stewart Stevenson	1	1

E74: electoral administration

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Scottish government	8	1
Files\Patricia Ferguson	4	1
Files\Rob Gibson	3	1
Files\Annabel Goldie	2	1
Files\Bruce Crawford	2	1
Files\John Pentland	2	1
Files\George Adam	1	1
Files\Helen Eadie	1	1
Files\Jackson Carlaw	1	1
Files\James Kelly	1	1
Files\Linda Fabiani	1	1
Files\Margo MacDonald	1	1
Files\Stuart McMillan	1	1

E75: SEN

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Stuart McMillan	2	1
Files\Patricia Ferguson	1	1
Files\Scottish government	1	1

E76: service personnel & families

Files	Number of coding references	^ Number of codes coding
Files\Bruce Crawford	1	1
Files\Helen Eadie	1	1
Files\Jamie Hepburn	1	1
Files\John Pentland	1	1
Files\Rob Gibson	1	1
Files\Annabelle Ewing	2	1
Files\Patricia Ferguson	3	1
Files\Scottish government	3	1

E77: bending the rules

Files	Number of coding references	▼ Number of codes coding
Files\Scottish government	13	1
Files\Patricia Ferguson	12	1
Files\Jackson Carlaw	10	1
Files\Patrick Harvie	9	1
Files\Helen Eadie	6	1
Files\Jamie Hepburn	6	1
Files\George Adam	5	1
Files\Annabelle Ewing	4	1
Files\James Kelly	4	1
Files\Linda Fabiani	4	1
Files\Rob Gibson	4	1
Files\Tavish Scott	4	1
Files\Alison McInnes	3	1
Files\Annabel Goldie	3	1
Files\Bruce Crawford	3	1
Files\Graeme Pearson	3	1
Files\Margo MacDonald	3	1
Files\Stuart McMillan	3	1
Files\John Pentland	2	1
Files\Richard Lyle	2	1
Files\Bob Doris	1	1
Files\Clare Adamson	1	1
Files\John Mason	1	1

E78: young person political awareness

Files	Number of coding references	▼ Number of codes coding
Files\George Adam	6	1
Files\Rob Gibson	6	1
Files\Jackson Carlaw	3	1
Files\Margo MacDonald	3	1
Files\Patrick Harvie	3	1
Files\Stuart McMillan	3	1
Files\Annabel Goldie	2	1
Files\Bruce Crawford	2	1
Files\Clare Adamson	2	1
Files\Graeme Pearson	2	1
Files\Patricia Ferguson	2	1
Files\Bob Doris	1	1
Files\James Kelly	1	1
Files\John Mason	1	1
Files\Richard Lyle	1	1
Files\Scottish government	1	1

E79: Scottish society

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Clare Adamson	3	1
Files\Tavish Scott	3	1
Files\George Adam	2	1
Files\Graeme Pearson	2	1
Files\James Kelly	2	1
Files\John Pentland	2	1
Files\Margo MacDonald	2	1
Files\Richard Lyle	2	1
Files\Alison McInnes	1	1
Files\Annabel Goldie	1	1
Files\Bob Doris	1	1
Files\Bruce Crawford	1	1
Files\Jackson Carlaw	1	1
Files\John Mason	1	1
Files\Michael McMahon	1	1
Files\Scottish government	1	1
Files\Stuart McMillan	1	1

E80: electoral strategy

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Scottish government	14	1
Files\Patricia Ferguson	9	1
Files\Patrick Harvie	9	1
Files\Jackson Carlaw	8	1
Files\George Adam	7	1
Files\Annabelle Ewing	6	1
Files\Bruce Crawford	6	1
Files\Helen Eadie	6	1
Files\Jamie Hepburn	6	1
Files\John Pentland	6	1
Files\Rob Gibson	6	1
Files\Tavish Scott	6	1
Files\Annabel Goldie	5	1
Files\James Kelly	5	1
Files\Richard Lyle	5	1
Files\Linda Fabiani	4	1
Files\Margo MacDonald	4	1
Files\Stuart McMillan	4	1
Files\Graeme Pearson	3	1
Files\Alison McInnes	2	1
Files\Bob Doris	1	1
Files\Clare Adamson	1	1
Files\John Mason	1	1
Files\Michael McMahon	1	1
Files\Neil Findlay	1	1
Files\Stewart Stevenson	1	1

E81: civic Scotland

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Patricia Ferguson	6	1
Files\Bruce Crawford	5	1
Files\George Adam	3	1
Files\James Kelly	3	1
Files\Linda Fabiani	3	1
Files\Rob Gibson	3	1
Files\Scottish government	3	1
Files\Stuart McMillan	3	1
Files\Annabel Goldie	2	1
Files\Annabelle Ewing	2	1
Files\Clare Adamson	2	1
Files\Patrick Harvie	2	1
Files\Helen Eadie	1	1
Files\Jamie Hepburn	1	1
Files\John Pentland	1	1
Files\Michael McMahon	1	1
Files\Richard Lyle	1	1
Files\Tavish Scott	1	1

E82: education

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Rob Gibson	3	1
Files\Bob Doris	1	1
Files\Bruce Crawford	1	1
Files\Clare Adamson	1	1
Files\George Adam	1	1
Files\Graeme Pearson	1	1
Files\Jackson Carlaw	1	1
Files\John Mason	1	1
Files\Linda Fabiani	1	1
Files\Patricia Ferguson	1	1
Files\Patrick Harvie	1	1

E83: previous elections

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Annabel Goldie	1	1
Files\Clare Adamson	1	1
Files\Helen Eadie	1	1
Files\Patrick Harvie	1	1

E84: finance

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Michael McMahon	4	1
Files\Scottish government	1	1

E85: Scottish society v. civic Scotland

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Civic Scotland	43	43	18	18
Codes\Scottish society	27	27	17	17

E86: Scottish society

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Clare Adamson	3	1
Files\Tavish Scott	3	1
Files\George Adam	2	1
Files\Graeme Pearson	2	1
Files\James Kelly	2	1
Files\John Pentland	2	1
Files\Margo MacDonald	2	1
Files\Richard Lyle	2	1
Files\Alison McInnes	1	1
Files\Annabel Goldie	1	1
Files\Bob Doris	1	1
Files\Bruce Crawford	1	1
Files\Jackson Carlaw	1	1
Files\John Mason	1	1
Files\Michael McMahon	1	1
Files\Scottish government	1	1
Files\Stuart McMillan	1	1

E87: Edinburgh Agreement

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Scottish government	2	1

E88: political entrepreneurs

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Bruce Crawford	6	1
Files\Patricia Ferguson	3	1
Files\George Adam	2	1
Files\Scottish government	2	1
Files\Stuart McMillan	2	1
Files\Annabelle Ewing	1	1
Files\Helen Eadie	1	1
Files\James Kelly	1	1
Files\John Pentland	1	1
Files\Linda Fabiani	1	1
Files\Michael McMahon	1	1
Files\Richard Lyle	1	1
Files\Tavish Scott	1	1

E89: hard to reach voters v. Scottish society

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Scottish society	27	27	17	17
Codes\hard to reach v	3	3	3	3

E90: hard to reach voters v. civic Scotland

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Civic Scotland	43	43	18	18
Codes\hard to reach voters	3	3	3	3

E91: third sector

Files	Number of coding references	Number of codes coding
Files\Bruce Crawford	5	1
Files\Patricia Ferguson	4	1
Files\Stuart McMillan	3	1
Files\Clare Adamson	2	1
Files\George Adam	2	1
Files\Linda Fabiani	2	1
Files\Rob Gibson	2	1
Files\Scottish government	2	1
Files\Annabelle Ewing	1	1
Files\Helen Eadie	1	1
Files\John Pentland	1	1
Files\Michael McMahon	1	1
Files\Richard Lyle	1	1
Files\Tavish Scott	1	1

E92: Civic Scotland (components)

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Electoral administration	28	28	13	13
Codes\third sector	28	28	14	14
Codes\political entrepreneurs	23	23	13	13
Codes\Education	13	13	11	11

E93: Independence v. SIRFA

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Bill 2013	28	28	10	10
Codes\independence	14	14	9	9

E94: Sturgeon (hard to reach voters)

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
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E95: Scottish society (components)

Codes	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding referen	Number of items code	Aggregate number of items coded
Codes\Prisoner voting rights	67	67	19	19
Codes\SEN access	4	4	3	3
Codes\hard to reach voters	3	3	3	3

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